

D1.11 Annual Work Plan for the fourth year

WP1 Coordination

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: all partners

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D1.11 Annual Work Plan Year 4
WP and task	WP1 / Task 1.2
Leader	ANSES
Other contributors	All partners
Due month of the deliverable	M33
Actual submission month	M34
Type R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER	R
Dissemination level PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).	PU See updated Grant Agreement
Dissemination Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s)</u>: REA Officers and EC Steering Group</p>

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1 Glossary

AH: Animal Health

ASM: Annual Scientific Meeting

AWP: Annual Work Plan

CaM: Communication workshop and Media training

CPD: Continuing Professional Development

CT: Coordination Team

ESAB: External Scientific Advisory Board

FOC: Free Of Charge

FS: Food Safety

JIP: Joint Integrative Projects

JRP: Joint Research Project

MS: Member State

OHEJP: One Health European Joint Programme

PH: Public Health

PMC: Programme Managers Committee

PMT: Project Management Team

POC: Programme Owners Committee

REA: Research Executive Agency

SPR: Summary Progress Report

SS: Summer School

SSB: Scientific Steering Board

ST: Support Team

STM: Short Term Mission

WS: Workshop

2 Coherence with annex 1

2.1 AWP objectives for month 37 to 48 (year 2021)

- The 16 JRPs and JIPs selected under the second call and the JRPs and JIPs selected under the first call having requested a 6 months extension (5 projects) will be supervised and monitored to ensure the implementation of the projects according to their objectives and work plan.
- The JIP COVRIN to be launched in September 2020 in order to address the One Health aspects of the SARS-CoV2 virus conforming to the topic “Development and harmonisation of detection and characterization methods for SARS-CoV2 in humans, animals, and food and feed specimens” will follow its implementation.
- The final evaluation of the first round JRPs and JIPs will be carried out

- The 16 PhD programmes will be supervised and monitored to ensure the implementation of the PhDs according to their objectives and work plan;
- The 2021 Training and Education Activities: STMs, Workshop satellite to the ASM, CPD, CaM, Summer School will be implemented;
- The 2022 Training and Education Activities will be selected.
- The second Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM) will be organised in Copenhagen during spring 2021;
- The One Health EJP website and social media accounts will be regularly updated. The annual report for stakeholders will be prepared and disseminated;
- A series of integrative missions will be launched to build relations between partner institutes and allow additional partners to liaise with ongoing Joint Integrative Projects;
- Two cogwheel workshops will be arranged to continue to pinpoint projects and initiatives of strategic interest to the OHEJP and provide opportunities for interaction;
- Update of the overarching OHEJP data management plan will be made to ensure its alignment with the OHEJP dissemination plan;
- Supervision and support will be provided to the JRP and JIP leaders in their task to update their data management plans;
- Dissemination of outcomes from the OHEJP to stakeholders to meet their needs and to support policy initiatives will be ensured as well as a broaden communication with stakeholders with a focus on international stakeholders and global visibility.

2.2 Expected impacts

The set of activities described in the Annual Work Plan (AWP) from month 37 to 48 will contribute towards the implementation of the fourth out of the five years of the OHEJP with the ongoing implementation of the scientific research and integrative projects and Training and Education activities.

2.2.1 WP1

In the fourth year, the Coordination Team (P01-Anses and P04-Sciensano) assisted by the Project Management Team will ensure that the AWP Y4 of the fourth year is correctly implemented. The CT will manage the both the technical and financial reporting, of the third year to the Research Executive Agency. The Support Team will support the organisation of PMT, PMC, SSB, POC and ESAB meetings. The website and social media will be regularly updated and the project results will be disseminated both within the consortium, the European and international scientific community and the wider public.

2.2.1.1 Enlargement of the consortium

The enlargement campaign started in 2021 will continue with inclusion of new organisations that have shown interest to join the OHEJP consortium when invited to do so in 2021.

A specific kick-off meeting dedicated to the newcomers will be organised in order to allow them meeting the Project Leaders and getting acquainted with the possibilities of participating to activities such as Education and Training, integration activities, and the Annual Scientific Meeting.

2.2.1.2 Expected Communication Impacts:

The continued development and implementation of the Communication Strategy in Year 4 will ensure that the progress and outcomes of the OHEJP are effectively disseminated both internally and externally to the consortium and stakeholders. The key impacts expected in Year 4 are as follows:

- Regularly updating of the OHEJP website with news, events and information will ensure that all of the up to date information is available for those internal and external to the consortium. This will subsequently encourage collaboration and involvement in the One Health EJP events and funding opportunities to aid sustainability.
- The OHEJP social media presence is increasing on a monthly basis, which will result in improved dissemination of our research and outcomes. This will have a significant positive impact on our dissemination as we can reach individuals across the globe by tailoring messages to suit audiences, in line with the Communication Strategy.
- The success of the OHEJP social media accounts, the traffic to the OHEJP website and the success of newsletters will continue to be monitored regularly, which allows the Communications Team to monitor the success of the Communication Strategy and amend accordingly.
- The dissemination of the Communication Strategy, Dissemination Procedure and Publication Policy will support the OHEJP consortium and aid in improving the dissemination of OHEJP outcomes. Creating documents that are manageable and contain clear, descriptive infographics will be important in supporting consortium members.
- Strengthening collaborations with EU-JAMRAI, the One Health Platform and the One Health Commission will aid in the dissemination of the OHEJP outcomes. The OHEJP and EU-JAMRAI Communications Teams work together and support each other's social media accounts. Furthermore, sharing information the One Health Platform and One Health Commission will reach audiences worldwide, thus increasing interest for the OHEJP.
- The internal and external newsletters will also improve the internal and external communication from the OHEJP and ensure that all of our stakeholders are aware of our progress and achievements on a regular basis.
- The Annual Report from 2020 will be published in Year 4 and will showcase all of the OHEJP achievements from Year 3. This document will be disseminated to stakeholders and both those internal and external to the OHEJP. This will help promote the OHEJP and our research.
- Effective communication of OHEJP progress, news, events, funding opportunities and Education and Training events and their subsequent alumni will create a European One Health community of scientists who are experts in the One Health field. The use of our social media platforms and increasing our followers and engagements will also contribute to developing this community of scientists, stakeholders and the general public that have a been interest and passion for implementation of the One Health concept.
- The Communication Team will work with all of the One Health EJP Work Packages to ensure that our research outcomes and activities are effectively communicated with policy makers across the EU. This will be a multifaceted approach and will require an internal network, including the CCPs, within the consortium to ensure that the impact of our work is resulting in translation of science to policy.

2.2.2 WP2

The public version of the strategic research agenda (SRA) will continue to be disseminated towards OHEJP partners, stakeholders and other EU projects. Strategic interactions with other EU projects and initiatives will be further explored and encouraged, with the aim to create synergies and avoid duplication (also through cogwheels workshops, WP4). Moreover, the web based database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives will be updated.

2.2.3 WP3

The main activities of WP3 in the fourth year will concentrate on the monitoring of the JRP reporting. All output will be disseminated to the right WP in the One Health EJP for further processing, i.e. to WP2 and WP7 for further updating and developing the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and to WP5 regarding science to policy, the information of our stakeholders of the scientific and innovative progress made. WP7 is further developing the sustainability process for the EJP. Although most project deliverables are purely scientific, integrative activities are also part of JRP. Therefore, JRP have a direct impact on, for instance, ongoing surveillance programmes in the MS, capacity building of the various members, building and extending biobanks and databases, strengthening collaboration with international stakeholders and national risk assessors, etc.

WP3 also brings together scientists in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats through the organisation of the Annual Scientific Meeting, thus supporting the creation of a One Health Community. The success of the online ASM2020 webinar showed that there is a broad international need for information on One Health, where the One Health EJP can contribute to.

2.2.4 WP4

Two JIPs, ORION and COHESIVE, will finish during year 4, and the results and outputs will be further disseminated. The projects are integrative and most of the work is done in close collaboration to EFSA and ECDC, but also OIE and FAO. Many outputs are already placed as resources to the “Tripartite Zoonoses Guide Surveillance and Information Sharing Operational Toolkit” (SISOT). There will be dissemination seminars arranged by the JIPs to share the output within the OHEJP and dissemination workshops are planned for the stakeholders. The One Health Output Inventory (OHOI) is an access point for open data. It functions as an entry point to the joint open resources and has links to the resources produced by JRPs and JIPs. The OHOI is continuously updated and can be accessed via the OHEJP website or by direct links.

All JIPs have stakeholder contact persons designated. These persons are updated and communicated with about the project progress on a regular basis. Many of the project activities also have direct impact, since the work is performed in close collaboration with e.g. national authorities or diagnostic laboratories. One JIP (CARE) has the aim to produce biobanks with reference material and make this available for the laboratories. The new JIP COVRIN will contribute with important One Health aspects concerning SARS-CoV2. This knowledge will, as for all JIPs, be made available during the lifespan of the project.

Upcoming cogwheel workshops will contribute to the exchange with relevant external One Health initiatives and projects across Europe. A thematic integrative meeting will be arranged to bring together scientists within the OHEJP consortium to work on issues of joint interest. If possible (depending on the COVID-19 situation) there will be possibilities for short term integrative missions during Y4. ORION has already initiated a similar kind of activity, called supra-national pilot, allowing people to spend a longer period with EFSA and ECDC. This initiative is very appreciated by the

stakeholders. COHESIVE will develop a website in collaboration with MedVetNet Association to display a decision tool produced. The activities contribute to the sustainability of the OHEJP.

2.2.5 WP5

During the fourth year, WP5 “Science to policy translation” will follow the established procedures for an efficient information flow to and from European and international stakeholders. It will ensure that output of research and integrative activities reaches national, EU and international stakeholders in a timely and targeted manner, focusing on closing the identified knowledge gaps as well as fulfilling needs for scientific support. In parallel, WP5 will be kept up to date with the EU key stakeholders’ needs mainly by direct communication, complemented indirectly via scanning of stakeholders’ published documents. Efficient dialogue and regular scanning of stakeholders’ documents will also contribute to avoid any duplication of work between OHEJP, key EU stakeholders and other EU funded initiatives.

Indeed, the engaged participation of both ECDC and EFSA in the OHEJP Stakeholders Committee and in workshops of some OHEJP projects ensures the continued liaison, avoiding data model overlaps and guaranteeing the access for risk assessment. Both organisations clearly support any OHEJP initiative that builds on existing features such as databases, models and procedures. There is also a close and direct communication set up between ECDC, EFSA and the projects of interest. WP5 will continue to work towards strengthening this dynamic of dialogue, with particular attention to the interaction between the second call JIPs and JRPs and the appointed contact officers at ECDC and EFSA.

One of the important elements for this will be targeted dissemination workshops to be organised in collaboration with WP4, WP3 and WP6. These workshops will focus on specific topics identified by the stakeholders of being of particular interest. Antimicrobial resistance as well as environmental aspects have already been identified as being of interest to several international stakeholders.

Moreover, tools like the Outcome Inventory will have an additional role in informing national and international stakeholders as well as fostering internal communication and interaction. Through the actions described in the AWP, WP5 will also depict complementarity between activities inside the consortium and outside, supporting potential collaborations and interactions.

2.2.6 WP6

In the fourth year, Work Package 6 will continue to support and monitor the 16 PhD studentship grants, which were selected to be funded in first and second year of the OHEJP. Each project has a dedicated webpage detailing the background to the project. PhD students will take part in the 3MT PhD competition at the Annual Scientific Meeting to showcase their projects and continue to build a cohort community of OHEJP PhD students. PhD students can also join other students and Early Career Researchers (ECRs) attending or participating in the remaining WP6 activities towards building the next generation of ‘One Health’ researchers.

Finally, each PhD student will submit a 9-month summary progress report in addition to a 12-month annual summary report.

WP6 will monitor the progress of the Short-Term Missions funded in the third year, and will work with the Communications Team to communicate this on the website through visually attractive, OHEJP-branded case studies.

In addition, WP6 will also oversee and support the organisation of the following events in the fourth year, which were selected in the third year:

- The third ASM Satellite Workshop

- The third Summer School
- The second CPD module (Note, an amendment was submitted for the deliverable report (D6.9) for the second CPD module in Y3. This CPD event will now take place in Y4)
- The third CPD module

Simultaneously, WP6 will coordinate the calls and selection procedures for the organisation of the fourth satellite workshop, summer school and CPD module in the fifth year. WP6 will also co-ordinate the call and selection procedure to fund up to a further ten STMs in the fifth year.

2.2.7 WP7

In the fourth year, Work Package 7 will continue to elaborate, in collaboration with WP2, a strategy for long-term sustainability of OHEJP, considering the framework of Horizon Europe and the demands by stakeholders; this will involve the implementation and development of SRIA. Moreover, the scientific social and policy constraints that might impair the development of OH will be investigated through a PHD project.

2.3 Correspondence with the description of work – Annex 1

2.3.1 WP1

WP1 work will be dedicated to supervision of the overall activities undertaken within the OHEJP and the reporting activities, namely periodic report of the third second year, SPR of the fourth third year and AWP of the fifth fourth year. Financial follow-up of activities will be of utmost importance in the fourth third year of implementation in order to ensure a good budgetary trajectory for the last two years second half of the project allowing to have spent up to the maximum grant amount at the end of the OHEJP. The ST will also prepare the fourth third amendment to the Grant Agreement

Organisation support for the periodic meetings of the governance bodies as well as the Annual Scientific Meeting will be provided.

2.3.2 WP2

WP2 activities will be focused in the dissemination of the public version of the SRA to OHEJP partners, stakeholders and other EU projects. Strategic interactions with other EU projects and initiatives will be further explored and encouraged, with the aim to create synergies and avoid duplication (also through cogwheels workshops, WP4). These interactions will be coordinated by WP2, PMT members or OHEJP project leaders. Moreover, the web based database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives will be updated and share to all the OHEJP partners. Furthermore, relevant scientific developments, including the emergence of zoonotic threats and opportunities for scientific innovations will be monitored. For this, the output from OHEJP projects (e.g. deliverables, scientific publications) will be screened as well as relevant information from external sources. This information will be used as input for the development of the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) in WP7. During 2021, as an activity lead by WP7, WP2 will participate in the consultation of interested parties for future participation in the EU Partnerships of interest for OHEJP.

2.3.3 WP3

The fourth year is entirely dedicated to the monitoring of the ongoing Joint Research Projects, both those from round one and that have been extended in time and those of the second round. This follow-up will lead to the periodic JRP report (D3.15). For those JRP that will end in December 2020 and in

June 2021, external evaluators will assess the final reports. Their report will be D3.17: Report on evaluation of finalised JRP.

The third Annual Scientific Meeting will be held in Copenhagen (hosted by SSI and DTU-FOOD) and the abstract book will be delivered as D3.16.

2.3.4 WP4

WP4 will continue to support the JIPs, monitor the project progress and take part in project activities.

The guidelines for evaluation of the final JIP reports will be completed and external evaluators recruited.

New integrative activities will be identified and realised.

The planning for a simulation exercise will continue and a launch for participation drafted.

Two cogwheel workshops (#7 and #8) will be organised to support external integration, and one thematic integrative meeting will be arranged to support internal integration across domains.

The continuous management and updates of JRP and JIP Data Management Plans (DMP) will be supported and projects ending during the year will have their final DMPs evaluated and uploaded on Zenodo.

The additional integrative activities to further disseminate the output of the JIPs, including the simulation exercise, will need some extra resources (partly reallocated from the WP4 budget for Y3).

2.3.5 WP5

During the fourth year, the actions foreseen in WP5 include strengthening of communication and communication between the OHEJP and various stakeholders. The stakeholder committee will be further broadened with the incorporation of the OIE, and interaction with ECDC will be strengthened (in the third year impelling commitments of the ECDC representative who was involved the COVID-19 response limited the active collaboration with OHEJP). In the two Stakeholders Committee meetings of the fourth year, information on OHEJP outcomes will be shared and synergies will be identified to support consideration of OHEJP results in the policies and activities of the stakeholders. In addition, stakeholders will make the OHEJP aware of their upcoming research needs. WP5 will respond to these needs and support the closure of knowledge gaps. To link the stakeholders' identified needs with the activity of the OHEJP, WP5 will disseminate results of research and integrative activities following tailored approaches to maximize efficient uptake. In addition, WP5 will work on the organisation of the Stakeholders Forum in year 5.

2.3.6 WP6

During the fourth year, the WP6 will co-ordinate the following activities:

- In the fourth year, Work Package 6 will coordinate, support and monitor the 16 PhD studentship grants that were selected between Y1 and Y2, and commenced between Y2 and Y3. WP6 will routinely liaise with and provide guidance to the Principal Investigators (PIs) awarded the funding and their respective PhD students to ensure WP6 receives the relevant project progress updates, and to ensure the PhD dissemination and reporting procedure (provided by WP6) guidance document is adhered to. All dissemination activities are reported to the coordination team via the Internal Events Survey, and are also reported to WP6 and the Communications Team, who wherever possible, promote these dissemination activities through our social media channels. PhD students will showcase their projects at the ASM through either a poster or oral presentation, and

all PhD students will take part in the Three Minute Thesis (3MT) PhD competition. PhD students will also continue to contribute content to their dedicated project page on the website and for the OHEJP social media channels to raise the profiles of themselves, the OHEJP and their achievements, and to utilise the large network the OHEJP offers. The PhD students will be actively encouraged to join other delegates attending or participating in the remaining WP6 activities to build a new generation of 'One Health' researchers.

To report the progress of the project, PhD students will submit a 9-month summary progress report in addition to a 12-month annual summary report to WP6 through the templates provided, to inform the content for Deliverables 1.14 (Summary Progress Report Y4), 1.15 (Annual Work Plan for Y5) and 1.16 (Annual Report).

- WP6 will also monitor the progress of the four STMs funded in Y3. These missions will take place throughout the fourth year, and once the missions are completed, individual reports will be submitted to WP6 through the templates provided. These reports will be used to inform the content for both Deliverable 6.14 and the webpage dedicated for STMs in 2021. WP6 will work with the Communications Team to communicate this on the website through visually attractive and OHEJP-branded case studies.

WP6 will support and monitor the planning and organisation of the third ASM Satellite Workshop, Summer school and both CPD modules, which will all be held in the fourth year. WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the second and third CPD modules. (Note, an amendment was submitted for the deliverable report (D6.9) for the second CPD module in Y3. This CPD event will now take place in Y4). The local organisers were selected in the third year through the 2020 calls. All selected local organisers are informed of the roles of the local organising team, WP6 team and Communications Team to market and deliver the event successfully through a guidance document prepared by WP6.

- WP6 will also review and amend the protocols (if necessary) for selecting the organisers of the fourth and final satellite workshop, Summer School and CPD module to be held in Y5. WP6 will then co-ordinate the call ensuring the validated steps described in the protocol are followed.

WP6 will also review and amend the protocol (if necessary) for selecting the STMs for Y5. WP6 will then co-ordinate this call following the validated steps and will select the successful awardees of the STM funding. This will be communicated with the consortium as described on the protocol, and in addition will be communicated through the WP6 monthly bulletin which is disseminated to the entire consortium, WP6 alumni and collaborators, and finally the website will be updated with a webpage dedicated for STMs in 2021. WP6 will work with the Communications Team to communicate this on the website through visually attractive, OHEJP-branded case studies.

In the fourth year, WP6 will produce the deliverable reports for D6.10, D6.11, D6.12 and D6.13 as planned originally. In addition, WP6 will produce the deliverable report for D6.6, D6.7 and D6.9 as these tasks were delayed for reasons explained in D1.10.

2.3.7 WP7

Following the assessment of the SWOT analysis WP7 in collaboration with WP2 will elaborate on the SRIA, considering the scientific, funding and legal opportunities provided by the oncoming Horizon Europe, and in particular the EU Partnerships. A virtual workshop with stakeholders and ESAB on OHEJP sustainability will be held at month 42 and a report provided on month 48.

WP7 will also consider the results of the PhD project SUSTAIN launched to assess the constraints to an OH approach arising in different EU contexts.

2.4 Annual Work Plan

2.4.1 Timing of the different programmed activities and their components

		GANTT CHART													
WP	Task	Subtask	Title	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48
WP1	1.1		Management of EC contractual obligations									1.14			
												1.15			
	1.2		Project management	PMT	SSB		PMT		PMT		SSB	PMCPQC			
	1.3		Organisation of EJP management and governance meetings												
	1.4		Communication tools												
		1.4.0		Communication groups											
		1.4.1		Web site/interface											
		1.4.2		Internal communications	1.12										
		1.4.3		External communications: Press releases											
		1.4.4		External communications: Professional social networks											
	1.4.5		Special issue on One Health-Zoonoses for a scientific journal												
	1.4.6		External communications: Merchandise and branding												
	1.4.7		Annual and final report					1.13							
WP2	2.1		2.1.1 Identification and updating of priority research and integrative topics												
			2.1.2 Development and updating of the strategic research agenda						2.9						
	2.2		2.2.1 Identification of relevant EU-projects and initiatives												
			2.2.2 Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives						2.8						
WP3	3.1		Guidelines for project coordinators to report + request extension (JRP&JIP)												
			Updated guidelines for Submission and selection of project proposals (JRP&JIP)												
			Guidelines for WP3/WP4 to monitor projects (JRP&JIP) (at start, periodic and end-term reports)												
			Updated guidelines for Evaluation of proposal + Selection of projects (JRP&JIP)												
			Guidelines for WP3/WP4 on the evaluation of final reports												
		3.2.2		Follow up of recently started projects											
		3.2.3		Monitoring: mid- and end-term reports			3.15								
		3.2.4		Evaluation of JRP reports by external experts: final report										3.17	
		3.3		Second call for projects: Evaluation of full proposals											
		3.4		3.4.1 Protocol for Annual Scientific Meeting organisation											
			3.4.2 Abstract book for Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)				3.16								
WP4	4.1		4.1.1 Guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals												
			4.1.2 Instructions for reporting on, and monitoring of, JIP progress												
			4.1.3 Guidelines for final evaluation of JIPs												
		4.2.1		Start-up support											
		4.2.2		Project monitoring			4.22								
		4.2.3		Final evaluations										4.24	
		4.3.1		Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level					4.23					4.25	
		4.3.2		Support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIPs					4.21						
		4.3.3		Scientific meetings to enhance integration											
		4.4.1		Call for letters of intent											
		4.4.2		Prepare output from external peer review for project selection											
		4.5.1		Development of the Data Management Plan											
		4.5.2		Guidance and support for the implementation of the DMP											
	4.5.3		Open data access point												
WP5	5.1		5.1.1 Communication links with international stakeholders												
			5.1.2 Communication links with national stakeholders												
		5.2.1		Platform for interaction											
		5.2.2		Systematic screening											
		5.2.3		Consolidation of results											
		5.3.1		Capacity map											
		5.3.2		Scientific support to enhance exploitation of results											
		5.4.1		Dissemination strategy											
		5.4.2		Targeted communication										5.9	
	5.4.3		Stakeholder conference												
WP6	6.1		Short term missions			6.10									
	6.2		Workshop programme											6.11	
	6.3		One health' Summer School for medical and veterinary science undergraduates											6.12	
	6.4		Doctoral training programme												
	6.5		One-Health CPD Module											6.13	
	6.6		Communications workshop and media training												
WP7	7.1		Collection of end user Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations.												
	7.2		Definition of the One Health SRIA 2021-2030				7.2								
	7.3		Development of governance model and related financial plan						7.3						
	7.4		Definiton of the road map for institutionalisation of One Health across the EJP												

2.4.2 Detailed work description

2.4.2.1 Annual work plan activities

2.4.2.1.1 WP1-Coordination and Management

Overarching activity	WP1: Coordination and Management					Lead Beneficiary			P1-Anses	
						Deputy Lead Beneficiary			P4-Sciensano	
Start month	M1					End month			M60	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
		Anses	Agas	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI
PM	47	0,5	6,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5		0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	26.60	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
PM	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5		
Objectives										
T1.1: To carry out the EC contractual obligations regarding legal, financial and administrative management and coordination of the EJP.										
T1.2: To ensure efficient project management										
T1.3: To organize EJP management meetings of all the governance and management bodies of the EJP:										
T1.4: To set up and put in place and manage efficient communication tools										

Description of programmed activities

Task 1.1: Management of EC contractual obligations

The Coordination Team (CT) will supervise the preparation and submission of the deliverables due from M25 to M36 to the Research Executive Agency (REA). At the beginning of the period, the CT will carry out the annual technical and financial reporting. In addition, the CT will coordinate the preparation, compilation and submission to the EC of the Summary Progress Report (SPR) for fourth year and the Annual Work Plan (AWP) for fifth Year. At the end of the period, the Support Team will achieve the fourth amendment to the Grant Agreement.

Task 1.2 Project management

The Coordination Team will exchange on a weekly basis via teleconferences to ensure that administrative, financial and contractual requirements are met. The CT and the PMT will have monthly teleconference to ensure a smooth management and coordination of the WP activities. The CT will also regularly liaise with the REA project officers and report any issue that may arise.

Task 1.3: Organisation of EJP management and governance meetings

The ST will ensure the organisation of all the project governance bodies meetings in regards to the identified planning. There will be 2 SSB, 3 PMT, 1 POC and 1 PMC meetings organised.

Task 1-4: Communication tools

Subtask 1.4.0: Communication Groups:

Stronger working relationships with the CCP network will be established, this will be achieved by organising a face-to-face meeting with the CCPs at the University of Surrey. It is essential that we have strong relationships with the CCPs in each of the One Health EJP institutes to ensure that information is disseminated effectively throughout and outside the consortium.

Subtask 1.4.1 Web site/interface:

The website is the main information hub of the OHEJP and will continue to be improved and developed throughout the fourth year. In the first part of the third year a site map of the website was created as part of a communication package of information by the Communications Team to improve the user experience of the website. This work will continue into the fourth year as the website continued to grow and be a central resource for information. Furthermore, the front end of the website will be updated with all publications, deliverables and project updates. The private space of the website will continue to be improved based on consortium member feedback to ensure that the user experience is optimal. The "Latest News" page will be further utilised in the fourth year. This will be used to promote OHEJP success and case studies created by the Communications Team. Furthermore, the team will encourage the use of the private space of the website following the improvements made in the third year. The fourth year will see a focus on sustainability of the website and ensuring audiences can find the information they are looking for. It is important to ensure that the project pages are up to date, therefore close communication with all Project Leaders will be essential.

Subtask 1.4.2 Internal communications- Newsletters:

The Consortium Newsletter will be disseminated to the consortium quarterly (4 x per year). Additional newsletters may be sent to consortium contact lists where necessary. The quarterly newsletters will provide updates of OHEJP events, meetings, research, funding opportunities and any other information suggested by other consortium members or the Communications Team. Each newsletter will be sent using MailChimp as this allows the success of each newsletter to be

monitored. These newsletters will also be made available on the OHEJP website under “Newsletters” and advertised on the OHEJP social media accounts. The External Newsletters are also suitable for OHEJP consortium members. These newsletters are disseminated bi-annually and is sent to consortium members and to the OHEJP external mailing list (which is generated on the OHEJP website). External newsletters will be targeted to a wider audience, including the general public.

Subtask 1.4.3 External communications-Press Releases:

Press releases for OHEJP events will be published on the OHEJP website and advertised on the social media platforms. Press releases for the ASM and Work Package 6 activities will be the responsibility of the hosting institute, however the Communications Officer can assist if requested and will facilitate this information being disseminated by the OHEJP.

Subtask 1.4.4 External communications- Professional Social Networks:

The OHEJP social media platforms will continue to grow and this growth will be monitored against KPIs in the Communications Strategy to ensure we are meeting pre-determined goals. The key objective for the social media networks is to increase the number of followers, impressions and engagements with our content. This will work towards creating a One Health Community on social media and reaching a global audience. Advertising and live tweeting of One Health EJP events such as the ASM, meetings, events and funding opportunities will raise the profile of the One Health EJP and encourage engagement online.

Subtask 1.4.5 Special issue on One Health-Zoonoses for a scientific journal:

Not applicable- due in fifth Year.

Subtask 1.4.6 External communications: Merchandise and branding:

The OHEJP branding was strengthened in the third year by the recruitment of a new Communications Officer who has extensive experience in brand and creative communications. A bundle of information with guidance and tools for the procedure of dissemination of information was created by the Communications Team and disseminated to the consortium in the third year. Therefore, the success and uptake of all of this will be monitored in the fourth year. It is essential that all consortium members receive and use all of this information; the Communications Team created a short guide on the importance of communication to our audiences, which was made available as a pdf download on the OHEJP website. This information is reiterated as part of Communication Team presentations, where applicable. It is anticipated that the fourth year will require the Communications Team to work closely with Project Leaders etc. to ensure the OHEJP outcomes are disseminated. The OHEJP branding will continue to be used to improve our brand and its reputation. The Communications Team will continue to investigate other appropriate platforms and methods to strengthen the OHEJP brand. The OHEJP ASM 2021 will be a good platform to showcase our consortium, in addition to any other One Health events that we may attend in 2021. OHEJP merchandise is available to all consortium members and it will be important in the fourth year to ensure that all members are aware of this and that the Communications Team can support any events with merchandise.

Subtask 1.4.7 Annual and final report:

The annual report for Year 4 will be completed in this period. The final report is due in Year 5.

Task 1.5 Ethics

In fourth year the project leaders of first and second round projects (JRP and JIP) and the responsible for the PhD projects will indicate how they have complied with the recommendations drafted by the Ethics Advisors. Based on these ethics reports plus the 36-months scientific reports, the Ethics Advisors will be able to evaluate all ethics aspects.

Task 1.6 Declaration of Cofund

N/A

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D1.12	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the second year	M37
D1.13	Complete version of annual report for stakeholders n°2	M41
D1.14	Summary progress report year 3	M45
D1.15	Annual work plan for the fourth year	M45
D1.25	Ethical review report for Y2	M38

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS7	SSB Meeting n°6	M38
MS8	SSB Meeting n°7	M44
MS15	PMC/POC/ESAB & SC Annual meeting n°4	M45

2.4.2.1.2 WP2-Strategic Research Agenda

Set of Activity	WP2–Strategic Research Agenda						Lead Beneficiary		P30-RIVM	
							Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P17-UCM	
Start month	M37						End month		Month 48	
Partici	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
part	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Partici	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
part	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM					2,25					
Partici	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
part	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI
PM								2,25		
Partici	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
part	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
PM										
Objectives										
T2.1: Start developing the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA)										
T2.2: Update de EU-projects/initiatives and strategic interactions with EU-projects										
Description of programmed activities:										
Task 2.1: Development of the SRA										
Task Leader: RIVM										
Deputy Task Leader: UCM										
Participants: all partner organisations										
The public version of the SRA will be distributed to the Scientific Community and Stakeholders trough different channels and it will be the starting point to develop, under the leadership of WP7, the development of the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA). To provide input for the SRIA, WP2 will monitor relevant scientific developments, including the emergence of zoonotic threats and opportunities for scientific innovations. For this, the output from OHEJP projects (e.g.										

deliverables, scientific publications) will be screened as well as relevant information from external sources.

Task 2.2: Strategic interactions with EU projects and initiatives

Task Leader: UCM

Deputy Task Leader: RIVM

Participants: Anses, Sciensano, BfR, SVA

The web based database of relevant EU research projects and related initiatives will be regularly updated. Strategic interactions with other EU projects and initiatives will be further explored and encouraged by WP2, PMT members and project leaders, with the aim to create synergies and avoid duplication. WP2 will collaborate with WP4 for the selection of relevant EU projects/initiatives for the 2021 cogwheels workshops.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D2.8	Report on scientific developments	M42
D2.9	Report on strategic links established and strategic developments	M42

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS23	Inventory of scientific developments	M42
MS24	List of strategic synergies with EU projects and strategic developments	M42

2.4.2.1.3 WP3-Management of Joint Research Projects

Set of Activity	WP3-Joint Research Projects management					Lead Beneficiary					P04-Sciensano
						Deputy Lead Beneficiary					P31-WR
Start month	Month 37					End month					Month 48
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
PM			14								
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE	
PM	1,5										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI	
PM											
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41			
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA			
PM											
<p>Objectives</p> <p>Task 3.1: Drawing up of guidelines for submission, selection and evaluation of JRP proposals as well as request of extension of accepted JRPs.</p> <p>Task 3.2: Supervision of the JRP in the first round of projects</p> <p>Task 3.3: Organisation of a second round of projects and their supervision.</p> <p>Task 3.4: Organisation of annual scientific meetings (ASM) where results from JRP are presented</p>											
<p>Ongoing JRP will be monitored through 9M and 12M reports that WP3 will prepare and send to the Project Leaders. These documents will fit into the Summary Progress Report Y4 and Annual Working Plan of Y5, respectively.</p>											

Those JRP that come to an end in December 2020 and in June 2021 will report through a final report, which will be assessed by external evaluators. This process will be monitored by WP3 and reported in D3.17.

Subtask 3.2.2 Follow-up of recently started projects

There will be no such JRP in Y4.

Subtask 3.2.3: Mid- and end-term evaluations; monitoring of the KPI, deliverables and milestones detailed in the annual JRP reports

See above: monitoring of ongoing JRP.

Subtask 3.2.4: End-term evaluations by external experts: final report

See above: assessment of final JRP reports.

Task 3.3: Organisation of a second round of projects and their supervision. Task with help from WP4.

This task and its subtasks is finalised in Y2.

Task 3.4: Organisation of annual scientific meetings (ASM) where results from JRP are presented

Subtask 3.4.1: Protocol for organisation of annual scientific meetings

This subtask is finalised in Y1.

Subtask 3.4.2: Organisation of ASM, scientific part

WP3 will organise the third ASM in Copenhagen (DTU and SSI). The abstract book will be delivered as D3.16.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D3.15	3rd periodic report on JRP	M39
D3.16	Abstract book for 3rd Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)	M41
D3.17	Report n°2 on evaluation of finalised JRP	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS41	Third Annual Scientific Meeting	M41
MS40	Final reports n°2	M45
MS42	Interim report preparation n° 2	M47

2.4.2.1.4 WP4–Management of Joint Integrative Projects

Set of Activity	WP4–Joint Integrative Projects										Lead Beneficiary		P41-SVA
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P36- INSA
Start month	Month 37					End month			Month 48				
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
Participant	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU			
PM			1,25										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22			
Participant	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE			
PM													
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32			
Participant	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR	FHI			
PM													
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41					
Participant	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA					
PM	1			3,9				9,42					
Objectives													
T4.1: To develop guidelines for evaluation of final reports and keep already produced guidelines on JIP reporting up to date.													
T4.2: To follow and support the launch and implementation of the JIPs from the 1st and 2 nd call.													
T4.3: To support the alignment of EJP activities with two external EU initiatives/projects, and to support internal integration through the arrangement of integrative missions and a thematic workshop.													
T4.4: n/a													
T4.5: To provide support and follow the implementation of the Data Management Plan (DMP), and ensure alignment with the overarching dissemination plan.													
Description of programmed activities:													
Task 4.1 Development of procedures and guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals, and for reporting and evaluation.													

Subtask 4.1.1 Guidelines for submission and selection of JIP proposals

n/a

Subtask 4.1.2 Instructions for reporting on, and monitoring of JIP progress

n/a

Subtask 4.1.3 Guidelines for evaluation of JIPs

n/a

Task 4.2 Supervision of JIPs

Subtask 4.2.1 Start-up support

n/a

Subtask 4.2.2 Project monitoring

- Meetings between JIP PLs and the WP4 team will be arranged formally every three months and there will also be continuous support from WP4 available.
- The WP4 team will participate in JIP consortium meetings to inform about ongoing work and procedures and take part of progress and development.
- PLs will be informed about and updated regularly on activities which concern the JIPs.
- The WP4 will continue to follow-up on milestones and deliverables of ongoing JIPs.
- An amended AWP will be requested for the extended projects, which will be closely followed-up on by the WP4 team.
- The 3rd periodic report on the progress of the JIPs (D4.22 (M39)), will be produced.

Subtask 4.2.3 Final evaluations

- JIP-1 ORION and JIP-2 COHESIVE will finish in M42. External evaluators will be recruited. The recruitment process will build on the experience from and follow the same procedure as in WP3. Guidelines for evaluation D4.19 already exist.
- Report on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 1st round (D4.24 (M48)), will be delivered.
- Information from EJP partners to determine the overall status of integration of project outputs will be collected. This will be used as an input for the the planning and design of the simulation exercise.
- Planning for a simulation exercise will continue (provided that the budget is available), including the involvement of ECDC and EFSA. The exercise will build on the ECDC manual for simulation exercises "Handbook on simulation exercises in EU public health settings How to develop simulation exercises for supporting preparedness and response to communicable diseases" and be performed at the national level.

- A call will be launched among the OHEJP partners for participating in the simulation exercise. Additional partners of importance for the exercise will be identified and relevant partners invited to participate.

Task 4.3 Integrative support

Subtask 4.3.1 Alignment with strategic initiatives at EU level

- Two cogwheel workshops (#7 and #8) for alignment of activities with external strategic projects will be arranged (D4.23 (M42) and D4.25 (M48)).
- All OHEJP partners are invited to suggest projects for WP4 to arrange a cogwheel workshop with. Projects of interest are also compiled by WP2 and suggested to WP4.

Subtask 4.3.2 Support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIP.

- Encourage and support the JIPs to take on additional partners.
- Promote the development of training opportunities to disseminate the outputs from JIPs and in this way advocate the use of developed procedures by potential end-users.
- Support the integration of JIP outputs with the MedVetNet Association website and other relevant websites for displaying JIP outputs.
- Together with the JIPs identify and execute additional integrative activities to further disseminate the outcomes. If possible short-term integrative missions (STIM) and integrative mentoring (IM) activities will be performed.
- Provide WP5 with information about deliverables to be further disseminated to the stakeholders and to include the deliverables in the One Health Outcome Inventory.

Subtask 4.3.3 Scientific meetings to enhance and leverage integration

- The 4th thematic integrative meeting related to a theme identified by partners/experts within the project consortium will be arranged (D4.26 (M51)). A relevant topic for this cross domain, within theme meeting will be identified in consultation with WP3. The results from the survey on Common activities performed among all ongoing JRPs/JIPs in Y3 will serve as an input in this process.
- To contribute to the organisation of the annual ASM.

Task 4.4 Organisation of call for additional JIPs for the period Y3-Y5

n/a

Task 4.5 Open data management

Subtask 4.5.1 Development of the Data Management Plan

n/a

Subtask 4.5.2 Guidance and support for the implementation of the DMP

- Continuous supervision and support to project DMP leaders. The new software tool used for writing and managing the DMPs will be the basis for all 2nd call project DMPs .
- The final DMPs of projects ending during Y4 will be evaluated by the DMP Committee.
- Final DMPs will be uploaded on Zenodo.
- The overarching Data Management Plan (DMP) will be updated.

Subtask 4.5.3 Open data access point

- Feed the One Health Outcome Inventory with all deliverables from the JIPs, so that relevant ones can be uploaded. The inventory facilitates the access to open resources and is linked to the DMPs.
- The projects will be further encouraged to follow the OHEJP Dissemination procedure.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D4.21	Report from thematic meeting III	M42
D4.22	3rd periodic report on JIPs	M39
D4.23	Report from 7th cogwheel workshop	M42
D4.24	Report on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 1st round	M48
D4.25	Report from 8th cogwheel workshop	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS61	Thirty-five STIMs	M38
MS62	Fifteen IM visits	M40
MS60	External evaluators for JIPs	M45

2.4.2.1.5 WP5-Science to policy translation

Set of Activity	WP5-Science to policy translation						Lead Beneficiary		P09-BfR	
							Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P13-SSI	
Start month	Month 37			End month			Month 48			
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM							13,33			
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	12									
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM										
Objectives:										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To broaden the interaction with stakeholders, covering national, EU and international interests - To follow the established procedures for a good information flow and interaction between the OHEJP projects and national, EU and international stakeholders to support complementarity and synergy of activities and exploitation of results - To regularly update research and integrative needs of stakeholders identified in policy processes and to keep the interaction with the OHEJP consortium - To regularly integrate available science and activities and support alignment for closure of knowledge gaps of international stakeholders - To support identification of potential for synergies between OHEJP activities and other international projects by supporting communication and disseminating actively results - To foster dissemination of results from activities within the OHEJP following the targeted dissemination policy initiatives addressing the protection of consumers health 										
Description of programmed activities:										
Task 5.1: Identification of the stakeholders and establishment of communication links										
Subtask 5.1.1 Establish communication links with EU and international stakeholders										

- The consolidation of communication links will be achieved by the Stakeholders Committee Meetings (SCM, subtask 5.4.2), which takes place twice during Y4, and by inviting stakeholders' representatives to join meetings of selected JIPs and JRPs as well as the ASM.
- WP5 will actively update key EU stakeholders (ECDC and EFSA) and international stakeholders (EEA, EMA, FAO, OIE, WHO) regarding the scientific and integrative output of the consortium through the Targeted Reports, ad hoc Thematic Reports (subtask 5.4.2) and specific workshops (subtask 5.3.2).
- Interaction with ECDC will be strengthened to overcome the momentary loosening of the interaction during the third year due to the COVID-19 crisis and response, in which the representative of ECDC was deeply involved.
- Additional effort will be made to foster communication with OIE.

Subtask 5.1.2 Establish communication links to national stakeholders

- Interaction with national stakeholders will be consolidated by applying the OHEJP Outcome Inventory (subtask 5.3.1), and by communicating outcomes and achievements of the OHEJP as well as identified synergies and activities complementary to the OHEJP.
- Awareness on the outcomes of the OHEJP will be raised at national stakeholders' fora like the POC meeting.

Task 5.2: Identification of the research needs of EU stakeholders

Subtask 5.2.1 Platform for interaction

- WP5 will actively collaborate with the stakeholders to consolidate the way in which the needs and support requests are identified and communicated, in order to keep the process timely and flexible.
- Dynamic and timely communication will be continued through the use of the virtual groups of the OHEJP website and, most importantly, by personal communications including appointed representatives.
- Consolidation of research and integrative needs of the EU stakeholders will be continued to provide specific support and input for the SRIA.

Subtask 5.2.2 Systematic screening

- Regular and systematic screening of stakeholders' documents will be carried on in order to:
 - Identify synergies and potential overlaps with OHEJP research and address complementary activities.
 - Identify stakeholders' potential needs and knowledge gaps.
 - Keep the consortium up to date with upcoming EU regulations and strategies.
 - Identify emerging risks.
- WP5 will keep publishing monthly documents summarising the outcomes of the activity "scanning of stakeholders' documents" and making them available to consortium members and stakeholders.

Subtask 5.2.3 Consolidation of results

- Scientific output of the OHEJP will be collected and mapped against the outcomes of the systematic screening. The result will be regularly discussed with the stakeholders (task 5.1 and task 5.4.2).
- Stakeholders' identified research and integrative needs will be used to update the Strategic Research Agenda (SRIA).
- Action to close knowledge gaps will be discussed within the consortium and taken as appropriate.

Task 5.3: Linking of the scientific capacity available in the EJP with the stakeholders' identified needs: closure of knowledge gaps

Subtask 5.3.1 Capacity map

The One Health EJP Outcome Inventory (OHOI, formerly referred to as "capacity map") is an important tool for highlighting expertise, outcomes and updates of the OHEJP and of its activities, in particular JIPs, JRPs and PhDs. It allows broad dissemination of results of the various activities within the consortium and depicts to some extent complementarity with activities outside the OHEJP. The OHOI targets not just the key EU stakeholders, but also national and international stakeholders, and supports internal collaboration and dissemination. During the fourth year focus will be put on the following topics:

- Content of the capacity map will be regularly updated, as well as updated on a case base after request of projects' representatives.
- Suggestions on the content and on technical issues will be considered following discussions with the stakeholders and feedback within the consortium.
- To ensure timely identification of potential overlaps and synergies of OHEJP activities with similar activities of stakeholders, WP5 will screen stakeholders' documents (subtask 5.2.2) and accordingly incorporate relevant information in the OHOI.
- WP5 will discuss with WP4 a way to link the OHOI with the Data Management Plans in order to maximise transparency and avoid duplication of work.

Subtask 5.3.2: Scientific support to stakeholders

- WP5 will improve the strategy to achieve maximum exploitation of scientific results and integrative activities fulfilling the policy needs of various stakeholders. This will include the development of specific strategies addressing interests of national, EU and international stakeholders.
- Procedures to provide scientific support will be further developed and improved.
- Dissemination workshops will be organised in collaboration with WP3, WP4 and WP6. These workshops will focus on specific topics identified by the stakeholders of being of particular interest, and will target specific stakeholders. To facilitate participation, they might be organised at the stakeholders' premises.
- Allocation of resources to support specific stakeholders' needs with specific actions will be continued and optimized.
- Means of specific support will be discussed in the SCMs (subtask 5.4.2).

Task 5.4: Dissemination of new knowledge, tools and materials

Subtask 5.4.1 Dissemination strategy

WP5 will further develop the dissemination of science and integrative outputs to meet the stakeholders' identified needs:

- The OHOI (subtask 5.3.1) will be developed further to list scientific updates in a tidy and well-ordered way.
- Regular Targeted Reports (subtask 5.4.2) and ad hoc Thematic Reports (subtask 5.4.2) will be distributed to the stakeholders.
- The dissemination strategy will be discussed biannually in the SCM (subtask 5.4.2).

Subtask 5.4.2 Targeted communication

- Regarding the Targeted Reports to Key EU Stakeholders:
 - They will be compiled and distributed twice per year.

- Focus will be given on those topics of highest interests for ECDC and EFSA.
 - To give visibility also to projects not directly selected by ECDC and EFSA, brief summaries of all scientific publications produced by the OHEJP will be given
 - The reports will facilitate linkage with external resources in case more insights are needed.
- Regarding the Thematic Reports:
 - They will be produced ad hoc, in response to specific stakeholders' needs.
 - They will cover specific topics and depict how the OHEJP is closing specific knowledge gaps
 - The reports will facilitate linkage with external resources (primarily the OHEJP website) in case more insights are needed.
 - Stakeholders Committee Meetings (SCM) will be organized biannually, one in spring linked with the ASM and another in autumn:
 - During the fourth year SCMs OHEJP outcomes will be shared and synergies identified to support consideration of OHEJP results in the stakeholders' policies
 - The SCM will also be used to discuss the dissemination strategy, the procedures to meet various stakeholders' needs, and options for the sustainability of the activities and procedures.
 - Topics and points of discussion will be incorporated in the agenda as needs emerge.
- Subtask 5.4.3 Stakeholder conference**
- During the fourth year, activities which started during the third year will be carried on to prepare the stakeholders conference, scheduled for year 5.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D5.9	Fourth annual report on dissemination activities to international stakeholders	M48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
MS71	Identification of new knowledge gaps and research needs n°3	M48
MS75	Scientific support provided n°3	M48

2.4.2.1.6 WP6-Training and Education

Set of Activity	WP6-Training and Education					Lead Beneficiary		P23-UoS		
						Deputy Lead Beneficiary		P31-WbvR		
Start month	Month 37					End month		Month 48		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
Participant	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
Participant	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBvR	FHI
PM	38								1,5	
	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
Participant	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SYA		
PM										
Objectives :										
T6.1: Short Term Missions										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements from the missions which took place in Y3. From these reports, WP6 will compile D6.10. WP6 will coordinate, support and monitor the Short Term Missions selected through the third call; and will manage and support the reporting requirements. All missions will be uploaded onto the One Health EJP website. WP6 will coordinate the call to select the Short Term Missions to fund in Y5 										
T6.2: Workshop programme (satellite to Annual Scientific Meetings)										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the third satellite workshop ; and will manage and support the reporting requirements. From this report, WP6 will compile D6.11. WP6 will coordinate the call to select the organisers of the fourth and finalASM Satellite Workshop 										
T6.3: One health' Summer School for medical and veterinary science undergraduates										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the third Summer School ; and will manage and support the reporting requirements. From this report, WP6 will compile D6.12. 										

- WP6 will coordinate the call to select the organisers of the fourth and final Summer School

T6.4: Doctoral Training Programme

- WP6 will coordinate, support and monitor the 16 PhD grants which were selected to be funded in Y1 and Y2. WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements to inform the the Summary Progress Report (D1.14), Annual Work Plan for Y5 (D1.15), and finally the Annual Report (D1.16).

T6.5: One-Health Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Module

- WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the second and third CPD modules); and will manage and support the reporting requirements. From these reports, WP6 will compile D6.9 and D6.13.
- WP6 will coordinate the call to select the organisers of the fourth and final Summer School
-

T6.6: Communications workshop and media training

- This activity will take place in Y3 and the deliverable report (D6.2) will be submitted in Y3 as originally planned in the Grant Agreement. .

Description of programmed activities:

Task 6.1: Short Term Missions

WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements from each of the missions that took place in Y3. WP6 will then compile from individual reports to inform the official deliverable for D6.10, which is due in M38. All missions will be uploaded onto the One Health EJP website on the dedicated webpage for STMs in 2020. WP6 will work with the Communications Team to communicate this on the website through visually attractive and OHEJP-branded case studies.

WP6 will coordinate, support and monitor the Short Term Missions selected through the third call. The missions will all take place between M37 and M48. WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements from each of the missions for D6.14 (due in M50). All missions will be uploaded onto the One Health EJP website on the dedicated webpage for STMs in 2021. WP6 will work with the Communications Team to communicate this on the website through visually attractive and OHEJP-branded case studies.

WP6 will coordinate the call to select the Short Term Missions to fund in Y5 following the validated procedure.

Task 6.2: Workshop programme (satellite to Annual Scientific Meetings)

WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the third satellite workshop, which will be hosted alongside the ASM in Copenhagen, Denmark. After the event, WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements of D6.11.

WP6 will coordinate the call to select the organisers of the fourth and final ASM Satellite Workshop following the validated procedure.

Task 6.3: 'One health' Summer School for medical and veterinary science undergraduates

WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the third Summer School. After the event, WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements of D6.12.

W6 will coordinate the call to select the organisers of the fourth Summer School following the validated procedure.

Task 6.4: Doctoral Training Programme

WP6 will coordinate, support and monitor the 16 PhD studentship grants selected for funding in Y1 and Y2. The Y4 Annual Work Plans for each PhD can be found later in this report.

WP6 will routinely liaise with and provide guidance to the Principal Investigators (PIs) awarded the funding and their respective PhD students to ensure WP6 receives the relevant project progress updates, and to ensure the PhD dissemination and reporting procedure (provided by WP6) guidance document is adhered to. All dissemination activities are reported to the coordination team via the Internal Events Survey, and are also reported to WP6 and the Communications Team, who wherever possible, promote these dissemination activities through our social media channels. PhD students will showcase their projects at the ASM through either a poster or oral presentation, and all PhD students will take part in the Three Minute Thesis (3MT) PhD competition. PhD students will also continue to contribute content to their dedicated project page on the website and for the OHEJP social media channels to raise the profiles of themselves and their achievements, and to utilise the large network the OHEJP offers. The PhD students can also join students attending or participating in the remaining WP6 activities to build a new generation of ‘One Health’ researchers.

To report the progress of the project, PhD students will submit a 9-month summary progress report in addition to a 12-month annual summary report to WP6 through the templates provided, to inform the content to inform the Summary Progress Report (D1.14), Annual Work Plan for Y5 (D1.15), and finally the Annual Report (D1.16).

Task 6.5: One-Health Continuing Professional Development (CPD) Module

WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the second and third CPD modules. Note, an amendment was submitted for the deliverable report (D6.9) for the second CPD module in Y3. This CPD event will now take place in Y4. After the event, WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements of D6.9.

WP6 will coordinate and support the organisation of the third CPD module. After the event, WP6 will manage and support the reporting requirements of D6.13.

WP6 will coordinate the call to select the organisers of the fourth CPD module following the validated procedure.

Task 6.6: Communications workshop and media training

Not applicable. This training event takes place in Y3. WP6 will manage the submission of Deliverable 6.2 (due in Y3).

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D6.10	Report n°2 of the annual short term missions completed also uploaded onto the EJP webpage.	M38
D6.11	Report n°3 on one workshop per year associated with ASM (with WP1,3,4 and 5)	M48
D6.12	Report of the third One health summer school	M48
D6.13	Report of the third CPD module in one health	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
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Annual Work Plan
Fourth Year - 2021
M37-M48

MS80	Launching n°3	M40
MS85	Preparation and scheduling n°4	M48
MS89	Preparation and launching n°4	M48
MS95	CPD Module & annual course n°4	M48

2.4.2.1.7 WP7-Sustainability

Set of Activity	WP7-Sustainability										Lead Beneficiary		P27-ISS
											Deputy Lead Beneficiary		TBC
Start month	Month 37					End month				Month 48			
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
Participant	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU			
PM													
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22			
Participant	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE			
PM								1,5					
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32			
Participant	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI			
PM					4,5								
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41					
Participant	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA					
PM								7					
Objectives													
T7.1: Gathering Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations													
T7.2: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2021-2030 (SRIA 2021-2030);													
T7.3: Making the EJP sustainable through other funding and/or legal basis													
T7.4: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable													
Description of programmed activities													
Task 7.1: Gathering Stakeholders' Needs and Expectations (Task leader BfR/participants: ANSES, IP, ISS)													
<i>Subtask 7.1.1: Mapping the stakeholders at national, European and international stages</i>													
The consultation with stakeholders' forum will continue (led by Wp5) and inputs for OHEJP SRIA and sustainability will be consistently derived. Inputs from OIE and JRC will be also received starting from 2021.													
Relevant scientific initiatives (projects associations, network) and societal bodies (e.g., farming and consumer associations) are mapped and contacted.													

Task 7.2: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2021-2030 (SRIA 2021-2030)

Task leader: ISS / Participants: RIVM, ANSES, BfR, IP, SVA UCM.

Subtask 7.2.2: definition of the innovation activities to be included in the agenda, taking into account the SRA and the results of task 7.1

WP7 in collaboration with WP2 will elaborate on the SRIA, taking into account the indications of SWOT analysis, the scientific framework of Horizon Europe (starting on 2021) and the indications by stakeholders forum and ESAB. Considering that the current mission and activities of OHEJP are foreseen to be split in two many Horizon Europe partnerships, namely "Animal Health and Welfare" and "AMR", plus links with other Partnerships ("Pandemics", "Food safety") WPT and WP2 will summon experts from the OHEJP as well as from MedVetNet and other collaborating actions and networks and organize them in modules, in order to implement the survival and development of OHEJP activities into one or more partnerships of Horizon Europe. The activity the EC guidance on SRIA.

A virtual workshop with stakeholders is planned on month 42.

Task 7.3: Making the EJP sustainable through other funding and/or legal basis

Task leader: IP / Participants: all beneficiaries

Subtask 7.3.1: SRIA cofunded implementation program

Subtask 7.3.2: Funding opportunities

Subtask 7.3.3: Legal basis for sustainability

The implementation of SRIA, funding opportunities and legal forms for future sustainability of the OHEJP are examined in the context of new opportunities and challenges offered by Horizon Europe (starting on Jan. 2021) with special attention to the future Horizon Partnerships (foreseen to be launched on 2022) on Animal Health & Welfare and AMR-One Health as well as to a renewed role of METVEDNET as OH common structure linking the participation to different partnership

Task 7.4: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable

Task Leader: SVA / Participants: all beneficiaries

For the PhD project SUSTAIN, interviews are planned to be conducted in Italy at the Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise Giuseppe Caporale and Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia. The interviews are part of a qualitative study on the institutionalisation of One Health. After the fieldwork, the interviews will be analysed and compared to interviews conducted Sweden in spring 2020. Additionally, a cross-agency analysis will be conducted, which will be addressed to partner agencies of the OHEJP. The online survey will investigate One Health implementation and institutionalisation among different epistemological communities both cross-country and cross-sectoral. The data from the interviews and survey will be analysed and transformed into articles to disseminate the findings

Subtask 7.4.1 Application of framework for evaluation of One Health

TBC

Subtask 7.4.2 Institutional analysis

TBC

Subtask 7.4.3 Road map for institutionalisation of One Health

TBC

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D7.2	One Health SRIA 2021- 2030.	M40
D7.3	Document on governance model and related financial plan for a sustainable Partnership based on the SRIA 2021-2030	M42
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.4.2.1.8 JRP02-R1-AMR2-ARDIG

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		AMR 2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR								
Research Project Title		Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics: the influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment								
Research Project Acronym		ARDIG								
Leading Organisation		P21-APHA			Deputy Leading Organisation			P11-RKI		
Project Leader		Muna Anjum			Deputy Project leader			Tim Eckmanns		
Project Start month		M1			Project End month			M42		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	2,5						3		6	
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM					4			4,18	7,1	2,2
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	Uos	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	0								0	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PM	5,60									
Work-Package 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To compare AMR prevalence and AB usage in six different European regions collected through national surveillance, including EU and other surveillance programmes, from humans, animals, food and the environment. To correlate resistance trends with antibiotic sales or usage (available through research project or industry data and by collecting primary data), ecological factors and management practices. To provide recommendations for improved One Health surveillance. 										

Work-Package 2:

- Performing longitudinal studies to determine prevalence of ESBL/AmpC/carbapenemase producing or *mcr-1* and *-2*/PMQR-carrying Enterobacteriaceae in pig, poultry, cattle farms or hospitals and their environments.
- Comparing national AMR prevalence data by considering herd/hospital level prevalence.
- To set up a database integrating data from WP1 and 2 and accessible to all partner of the project.

Work-Package 3:

- To characterise antimicrobial resistance mechanisms in isolates of human and animal origin, and the fitness of multidrug resistant isolates in different environment.
- To understand the flux of antimicrobial resistance determinants and platforms, especially of those genes associated with antimicrobials that are used as human and animal therapeutics.

Description of work:

See project description by work package (WP) below.

WP1: Comparison of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic sales/usage (AMU) data collected through existing surveillance, monitoring and research programs and assessment of risk factors.

WP start month: 1 (first annual period)

WP end month: 42 (third annual period)

WP Leader: Bernd-Alois Tenhagen (9, BfR, DE)

Deputy WP Leader: Marianne Sunde (33, NVI, NO)

WP participants:

APHA (20): Pablo Alarcon

BfR (9): Bernd-Alois Tenhagen

NVI (33): Marianne Sunde

WBVR (30): Michael Brouwer

ANSES (1): Jean-Yves Madec

UCM (16): Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn

PHE (21): Neil Woodford

RKI (11): Tim Eckmanns

IP (19): Philippe Glaser

UoS (22): Roberto La Ragione

Description of the WP1:

WP1 will continue based upon achievements during the first and second annual period of the EJP. This WP will explore and use epidemiological data available from humans, animals (pig, poultry and cattle), food (including from retail sector), and the environment, and link data (geographically) to investigate emerging trends and possible associations between AMU and AMR, and with potential risk factors beyond usage. We will have a special focus on resistance to important antimicrobial agents such as extended spectrum cephalosporins, colistin and fluoroquinolones focusing on *E. coli*. However, as much as possible, data on other bacteria (e.g. *Salmonella* spp or *Campylobacter* spp.), will also be collected to validate results across bacterial species.

It is expected that this work package will also provide data supporting the selection of relevant farms/hospitals to be included in the longitudinal study in WP2 and samples/isolates to be included in WP3

Task 1.2: Investigation of trends, associations and risk factors

Task start month: 9 (first annual period)

Task end month: 42 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Pablo Alarcon (20, APHA)

Task Participants: BfR (9), NVI (33), APHA (20), RKI (11) and PHE (21)

Description of the task:

This task will be conducted during the first year of the EJP through to the 3rd year. It is based on the data collection in Task 1.1 but can already start by discussion on methodology issues before task 1.1 is finished.

Using the dataset obtained in task 1.1, a description of trends for specified AMR prevalence/frequency (primarily at the phenotypic level, and genotypic level where data is available, see WP3) at population/country/regional level will be carried out. Spatial analysis will be performed to assess and compare the coverage of the available data between countries, and investigate possible regional clusters of AMR and AMU in animals and humans. The spatial analysis done will allow for the identification of specific regions where available data will help perform in depth analysis. These will then be used to assess potential associations between AMR and AMU in livestock and humans in regional populations. The geographical regions identified will be used to investigate for risk factors for AMR beyond usage. This will consider ecological aspects like population density, urbanization, livestock density (or livestock to human relation), geographical features, but also livestock management practices (outdoor/indoor farms, farm size and distance between farms, level of integration, waste management, etc.). Existing datasets with potential risk factors that could be linked to the AMR/AMU data will be explored. Multilevel regression analyses will be performed to account for country and time (year) correlation.

Task 1.3: Develop recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance strategies

Task start month 25 (third annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Madeleine Norstrom (33 NVI)

Task Participants: BfR (9), NVI (33), APHA (20), RKI (11) and PHE (21)

Description of the task:

The results obtained in task 1.1 and 1.2 will be combined with results from WPs 2 and 3 to provide recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance. Development of surveillance target zones maps will be performed using (and extrapolating) the results from the AMR and AMU trends observed in humans and animals, and the risk factors found associated to these. The comparison of data between countries will help to understand the existing differences and problems, which would help to formulate recommendations to improve harmonization of surveillance activities.

WP2: Longitudinal studies of persistence ESBL/AmpC/carbapenem/mcr-1/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae on farms or hospitals

WP2 start month 1 (first annual period)

WP2 end month 42 (third annual period)

WP Leader: Philippe Glaser (19, IP)

Deputy WP Leader: Michael Brouwer (30, WBVR)

WP participants:

BfR (9): Bernd-Alois Tenhagen

ANSES (1): Jean-Yves Madec

UCM (16): Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn

IP (19): Philippe Glaser
APHA (20): Francesca Martelli
PHE (21): Neil Woodford
UoS (22): Roberto La Ragione
WBVR (30): Michael Brouwer
NVI (33): Marianne Sunde

Description of the WP2^{vii}:

WP2 will continue based upon achievements during the first and second annual period of the EJP. This work-package will study the persistence of ESBL/*AmpC*/carbapenemase/*mcr-1and -2*/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae at individual farm/slaughterhouse and hospital levels by collecting data on management and antibiotic usage as well as consecutive samples of faeces/meat and environmental samples through time. Furthermore, data from previous longitudinal studies that meet these criteria are present in the collection from several partners and will be included for an international comparative analysis. Retrospective and prospective collections will include samples from human, pig, poultry and cattle and related environmental isolates from all countries represented in the consortium.

Data and samples collected are expected to follow the national trends as analysed in WP1 but longitudinal samples from the same farms/hospitals and in certain cases from the same animals/patients will give a much higher resolution of the prevalence, spread, persistence and risk factors involved for resistant Enterobacteriaceae. An estimate of 100-1000 samples will be collected and analysed per project partner, taking into account variations between study designs. Prevalence of resistance over time in specific farms/hospitals will provide information on the seasonal trends, effects of age of the subjects and individual management practices such as cleaning or disinfection, in which sampling from environmental/waste water samples will be included in farm and hospital studies, where possible. Isolates from consecutive batches of animals will be collected in a selection of pig and poultry farms to investigate if the same clone/plasmid persists at the farms or if new strains are introduced with each batch/time point. In beef and dairy farms, as well as in hospitals, where no 'all in, all out' policy is present, persistence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae within the same cohort of animals/patients overtime will be investigated by longitudinal sampling of the same animals/patients.

While all samples collected will be analysed phenotypically for ESBL/*AmpC*/carbapenem/*mcr-1and -2*/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae, a representative number of samples will also be selected for detailed genotypic characterisation of resistance genes and associated plasmids using molecular methods and WGS, as described in WP3. For this in-depth analysis, samples will be chosen to maximise variability and to include infrequent types like CPE and *mcr-1/2* encoding isolates to address specific questions on the genetic environment of these resistance genes and on possible specificities of the corresponding lineages.

Task 2.2: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae on farms

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 42 (Third annual period)

Task leader: Michael Brouwer (30, WBVR)

Task Participants ANSES (1), UCM (16), APHA (20), WBVR (30) and NVI (33)

Description of the task:

Task 2.2 will be performed in the first, second and third year of the EJP. Longitudinal sampling will be performed at broiler, turkey or cattle farms/slaughterhouses and will be performed by all listed participants. Depending on individual study design, each site will be visited 2 to 40 times. Data on management and antibiotic usage over the period of the study will be recorded and faecal/meat swabs/samples will be analysed for the presence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae in these

environments. Phenotypic data will be recorded by established methods such as disc diffusion or broth dilution to determine the MIC of the isolates for panels of antibiotics. Methods for genotypic characterisation of the isolates, as well as plasmid composition will include genetic determination of the resistance genes via WGS, PCR, microarray, as well as other molecular methods such as PBRT, S1-PFGE, RFLP and NGS, as described in WP3. All information related to isolates on their origin, genotype and phenotype will be stored in a common database accessible through the internet to all member of the consortium.

Task 2.3: Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae in hospitals and care facilities

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task leader Philippe Glaser (19, IP)

Task Participants UCM (16), IP (19), PHE (21) and UoS (22)

Description of the task:

Task 2.3 will be performed in the first, second and third year of the EJP. Longitudinal sampling will be performed at hospitals and/or care facilities and will be performed by all listed participants for this Task. Data on patients including gender, age, disease, treatment and antibiotic treatment, as well as data on management will be recorded and faecal samples/swabs will be analysed for the presence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae. Phenotypic data will be recorded by established methods such as disc diffusion or broth dilution to determine the MIC of the isolates for panels of antibiotics. Methods for genotypic characterisation of the isolates, as well as plasmid composition will include genetic determination of the resistance genes via WGS, PCR, microarray, as well as other molecular methods such as PBRT, S1-PFGE, RFLP and NGS, as described in WP3. All information related to isolates on their origin, genotype and phenotype will be stored in a common database accessible through the internet to all member of the consortium.

Informed consent will be requested following national regulation and all data on patient will be anonymised.

Task 2.4: Data analysis of collected resistant Enterobacteriaceae on national levels

Task start month 22 (second annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task leader: Francesca Martelli (20, APHA)

Task Participants ANSES (1), BfR (9), RKI (11), UCM (16), IP (19), APHA (20), PHE (21), UoS (22), WBVR (30) and NVI (33)

Description of the task:

Task 2.4 will be performed over the second and third years of the EJP. The phenotypic and genotypic data on prevalence, spread and persistence of resistant Enterobacteriaceae collected in Tasks 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 will be analysed per sample source by each of the listed participants. Analysis will be performed according to predetermined criteria as determined in D-2.1 by all contributors to WP2 to ensure compatibility of the results.

A risk factor analysis on relation between management of farms/hospitals and presence/persistence of resistance will be performed. Persistence of resistance will be compared for conditions of between batch and within batch persistence. Phenotypic data will be complemented with the genotypic characterisation performed in WP3. Trends will be analysed in prevalence of resistance genes and associated plasmids.

Task 2.5: Comparative analysis of collected isolates on a Europe-wide level

Task start month 30 (third annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task leader Francesca Martelli (20, APHA)

Task Participants ANSES (1), BfR (9), RKI (11), UCM (16), IP (19), APHA (20), PHE (21), UoS (22), WBVR (30) and NVI (33)

Description of the task:

Task 2.5 will be performed in the third year of the EJP. All listed participants that have provided data for the longitudinal studies will contribute to the comparative analysis of resistant Enterobacteriaceae by taking advantage of the project isolate database. This analysis will include all data collected from the retrospective and prospective studies and compare national versus European-wide results of resistant Enterobacteriaceae. It will also incorporate the WGS data generated in WP3 defining clonal groups and their respective prevalence in the farms and hospitals and to deduce correlation between specific lineage and AMR profile.

WP3: AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates.

WP3 start month 6 (first annual period)

WP3end month 42 (third annual period)

WP3 Leader Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (16, UCM)

Deputy WP3 Leader: Roberto La Ragione (22, UoS)

WP3 participants:

ANSES (1): Dr Jean-Yves Madec

UCM (16): Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn

IP (19): Philippe Glaser

APHA (20): Muna Anjum

PHE (21): Neil Woodford

UoS (22): Roberto La Ragione

WBVR (30): Michael Brouwer

NVI (33): Marianne Sunde

BfR (9): Jens-Andre Hammerl

Description of the WP3:

To understand the epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance in bacteria it is essential to understand the flux of antimicrobial resistance determinants, especially of those genes associated with antimicrobials that are used as human and animal therapeutics. This is particularly important as several different genes/alleles can encode for the same antibiotic resistance, but can be from varied sources and be associated with different mobile elements.

WP3 will continue based on achievements during the first and second annual period of the EJP. In WP3, in-depth molecular characterisation of AMR genes present in a subset of isolates collected in WP1 and WP2 will be performed using WGS to add details of the mechanism of resistance present in isolates collected national and longitudinal studies. The prevalent circulating clones and/or plasmids which may be present in data sets from different compartments will be determined from the WGS data and compared between animal, human and environmental isolates from the same region and across different regions to determine their distribution. Conjugation experiments will be performed in vitro in the laboratory under standard culture conditions; in-vitro pig and poultry gut models and in-vivo animal models to determine transmission. Fitness studies performed experimentally in the laboratory both in-vitro (in culture) and in-vivo (in mice) will help determine the likely spread and persistence of dominant clones over time, which can then be compared with the on farm/hospital longitudinal data and national surveillance data gathered from different years. Such studies will not only help improve isolate characterization, which can be incorporated into future strategies, but will ultimately help in the accurate prediction of emergence and transmission of existing and novel AMR determinants across human and animal populations. It will also help understand why certain clones may be more successful than others and why some plasmids remain largely stable in their structure while others are highly variable and constantly evolving.

Task 3.3: Fitness cost of AMR and stability of plasmids in different host strain backgrounds

Task start month 18 (second annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Jean Yves Madec (1, ANSES)

Task Participants: ANSES (1), UCM (16), APHA (20), PHE (21), UoS (22), WBVR (30), NVI (33), IP (19), BfR (9)

Description of the task:

Fitness and survival of isolates harboring plasmids with both high and low AMR transfer rates, selected from Tasks 3.1 and 3.2, will be compared under different conditions, to determine the contribution they make in host survival and AMR dissemination. Combination of these experiments with WGS will identify the plasmid and host chromosome factors that determine plasmid stability, spread, and adaptation to new bacterial hosts and conditions. Bioinformatical analyses will provide an overview on the genome composition (i.e. genemaps, synteny plots) and the gene content of mobile genetic elements (transfer and mob-genes, resistances, stability factors). Studying plasmid stability and plasmid host adaptation in presence of subinhibitory concentrations of antibiotics / biocides, will determine the conditions that elicit emergence of High Risk clones or plasmids that ultimately spread successfully between humans, animals and the environment.

Task 3.4: Measuring AMR plasmid dissemination in mouse and Galleria, and chicken and pig in-vitro models

Task start month 24

Task end month 42

Task Leader: Muna Anjum (20, APHA)

Task Participants: UCM (16), IP (19), ANSES (1), APHA (20)

Description of the task:

At this stage, prevalent plasmids will have been identified, and characterized in vitro from Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3. With the knowledge acquired *in vitro*, the consortium will be able to assess conjugation and plasmid-host adaptation experiments in vivo. For this purpose, a chicken and/or a pig *in-vitro* gut model or *Galleria* model will be used, to identify the host factors that influence plasmid-host adaptation and conjugation rates. Furthermore, mouse conjugation models are set in place, and will be used to analyze transfer and adaptation of plasmids in the multicellular conditions of the mouse gut. WGS and analysis of the microbiome will help to identify plasmid-modifications and effects on the resident microbiota.

WP4: Project coordination and management.

WP4 start month 1 (first annual period)

WP4 end month 42 (third annual period)

WP4 Leader: Muna Anjum (20, APHA)

WP Participants: ALL

Description of the WP4^{vii}:

In WP4 the aim will be for the steering committee, with at least one member from each Institute, to ensure timely delivery of the Project. They will meet at least every 3 months to assess progress of the Project, whether virtually videoconference or physically, by each partner involved in the Project. Any problems or concerns that Partners or Scientists may have will be communicated to, and discussed by, the steering committee at the earliest opportunity. A kick-off and annual meetings of consortium members will be arranged in different countries. All publications and communications concerning the Project will be approved by members of the steering committee to ensure awareness and fair representation of all facts.

Task 4.1: Steering committee quarterly meeting

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Muna Anjum (20, APHA)

Task Participants: APHA (20), BfR (9), NVI (33), WBVR (30), ANSES (1), PHE (21), RKI (11), IP (19), UoS (22), UCM (16)

Description of the task:

To meet at least every 3 months between month 1 to month 36 of the project, to assess progress of the Project by each partner involved in the Project and discuss and address possible problems, risks, technical issues, project communication and publications.

Task 4.2: Consortium members annual meeting

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Muna Anjum (20, APHA)

Task Participants: APHA (20), BfR (9), NVI (33), WBVR (30), ANSES (1), PHE (21), RKI (11), IP (19), UoS (22), UCM (16)

Description of the task:

This Task will comprise of four annual meetings for the consortium partners and include a kick off meeting (Month 1); two progress meetings (Months 12 and 24); and a concluding meeting of the program (Month 42). The meetings will be organized in different countries and will include representatives from all partners.

Task 4.3: Reporting and communication

Task start month 1 (first annual period)

Task end month 42 (third annual period)

Task Leader: Muna Anjum (20, APHA)

Task Participants: APHA (20), BfR (9), NVI (33), WBVR (30), ANSES (1), PHE (21), RKI (11), IP (19), UoS (22), UCM (16)

Description of the task:

A summary annual communication from each WP for distribution to relevant organisations or stakeholders such as national governments, EU, international agencies and relevant industry/health partners. It is expected that members will also publish scientific papers and other communications from the results obtained in this study.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-1.4	A report of the assessment of risk factors for AMR and AMU	42
D-1.5	Recommendations and target zones for improved "One Health" surveillance	42
D-2.4	Data analysis of all collected isolates on a national level.	42
D-2.5	Comparative analysis of results from the various national studies.	42
D-2.6	Comparative analysis of strains persistence in farms and hospital through longitudinal studies	42
D 3.3.	Predictive modelling of plasmid spread	42
D-3.4	Validation of plasmid threats in animal models	42
D-4.3	Annual communication to stakeholders	42

Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-AMR2.ARDIG.8	Assessment of ecological and management factors associated with AMR and Antimicrobial usage (from WP1)	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.9	Recommendation for improved One Health surveillance	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.10	Collecting of samples and veterinary data, phenotypical testing of resistant isolates from farms and slaughterhouses.	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.11	Collecting of samples and clinical data, phenotypical testing of resistant isolates from hospitals and care homes.	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.12	Data analysis of all collected isolates on a national level.	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.13	Comparative analysis of results from the various national studies (WP2).	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.14	Identification of plasmid and host chromosome factors that determine plasmid stability, spread, and adaptation to new bacterial hosts and conditions.	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.15	Identification the host factors that influence plasmid-host adaptation and conjugation rates using animal models	42
M-AMR2.ARDIG.16	Identification of plasmid-modifications and effects on the resident microbiota through WGS.	42

2.4.2.1.9 JRP12-R2-AMRSH5-FARMED

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)			AMR-SH 5: Development of new tools for early (real-time) detection of resistant pathogens in humans and animals, as well as new diagnostic tools, in particular on-site tests for humans and animals							
Research Project Title			Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests							
Research Project Acronym			FARMED							
Leading Organisation			P21-APHA				Deputy Leading Organisation		P31-WbvR	
Project Leader			Manal AbuOun				Deputy Project leader		Michael Brouwer	
Project Start month			M25				Project End month		M54	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM			17,1				6,5			5
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	12				20				11,13	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbvR	FHI
PM					3,1	12,8			5,27	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM										
Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work Package 1: Assess feasibility of Long-read metagenome sequencing on exemplar matrices. Investigate the use of Hi-C metagenomics. • Work Package 2: Bioinformatics tools to analyse long-read metagenome samples • Work Package 3: Implementation of on-site protocols for long-read metagenomic DNA sequencing • Work Package 4: Project management, coordination and training workshop 										
Description of work										

JRP16-WP1 - Assess feasibility of Long-read metagenome sequencing on exemplar matrices. Investigate the use of Hi-C metagenomics.

JRP16-WP1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project.

WP start / end month: M25 – M44

WP Leader: Sigrid De Keersmaecker (4, Sciensano, BE)

Deputy WP Leader: Josephine Grützke (9, BfR, GE)

WP participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the WP:

WP1 will test and compare long-read sequencing to short-read sequencing to characterise the metagenome (including bacterial species) within 'simple' and 'complex' matrices. The aim will be to implement these methods for use with medical or veterinary practice. The ONT MinION, is a portable real-time device (100 grams), generating, in real-time, up to 30Gb of DNA sequencing. The longer lengths (>100kb) of DNA sequence data enable the user to find associations with bacteria, the plasmid and AMR genes, in real-time, without the need to traditional whole genome sequencing. Long-read sequencing technology has not been used broadly for metagenomics, so it will be compared to the current gold standard (short-read sequencing). A limited number of samples will also be compared to PacBio sequencing. Current laboratory based DNA extraction protocols will be used to establish if long-read sequencing is suitable for metagenome analysis.

A new sequencing technology, Hi-C that fuses DNA that is in close structural proximity during the DNA isolation and DNA-library preparation, will be investigated. This method uses short-read sequencing technology but during the analysis, this method will reveal information about the genetic context in which AMR genes are present. Together with long-read sequencing data, this information will be used to determine which bacterial species (pathogen and commensal) the AMR gene is present and whether it is harboured on the chromosome or a plasmid.

JRP16-WP1-T1 - Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'defined' microbial community and spiked samples.

JRP16-WP1-T1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project.

Task start / end month: M27-M40

Task Leader: Sigrid De Keersmaecker (4, Sciensano, BE)

Deputy Task Leader: Josephine Grützke (9, BfR, GE)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: In the first instance, we will use DNA isolated, using standard techniques, from a defined bacterial community containing isolates from various bacterial species (Gram negative and Gram positive, with available whole genome sequencing) to demonstrate that long-read sequencing is able to resolve the community. We will then use MinION sequencing to analyse various sample types of interest such as faeces (human and animal), saliva, milk, urine, environmental (e.g. water, dust) and food/feed samples spiked with characterized microorganisms (including uncommon bacteria harbouring AMR genes on extrachromosomal elements or in the chromosome for which we already have WGS data). Different concentrations of bacteria will be tested to determine limits of detection, and evaluate the accuracy of bacterial species and its association with genetic characteristics (such as AMR and mobile genetic elements) prediction. The long-read sequencing output will be compared to i) the known spiked AMR/species content and ii) the output of short read sequencing. A selection of samples will also be analysed using PacBio sequencing.

JRP16-WP1-T2 - Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'simple' sample matrices.

JRP16-WP1-T2 takes place over the first and the second year of the project.

Task start / end month: M27-M42

Task Leader: Sigrid De Keersmaecker (4, Sciensano, BE)

Deputy Task Leader: Soren Persson (27, SSI, DK)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), IZSAM (28)

Description of the task: We will use current standard DNA isolation techniques, on a selection of 'simple' sample matrices (i.e. a limited number of bacteria expected, such as water, urine, blood), to will evaluate the capability and practical feasibility of long-read sequencing to analyse the microbiome, and compare this to short-read sequencing. 'Simple' sample matrices present challenges such a potentially low concentration of the bacterial community, which could affect ability of sequencing to resolve the community, to a level that is diagnostically beneficial to detect bacterial species and AMR determinant for the clinician or veterinarian. Different spiking concentrations of bacteria will be tested to determine limits of detection, and evaluate the accuracy of bacterial species and its association with genetic characteristics (such as AMR and mobile genetic elements) prediction. We will compare the sensitivity and specificity for species and subspecies identification, as well as the acquisition of information regarding the genetic context of AMR genes.

JRP16-WP1-T3 - Assess feasibility/perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'complex' sample matrices.

JRP16-WP1-T3 takes place over the first and the second year of the project.

Task start / end month: M29-M44

Task Leader: Josephine Grützke (9, BfR, GE)

Deputy Task Leader: Sigrid De Keersmaecker (4, Sciensano, BE)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: For a selection of 'complex' sample matrices (i.e. either multiple bacteria present, or difficult DNA extraction, such as faeces (human and animal), milk, environmental (e.g. dust, wastewater, boot swabs) and food/feed samples), we will evaluate the capability and practical feasibility of long-read sequencing to analyse the microbiome, and compare this to short-read sequencing. 'Complex' sample matrices present several challenges such as the large microbial load as well as the presence of contaminants, which could inhibit DNA sequencing and the presence of non-bacterial DNA. We will compare the sensitivity and specificity for species and subspecies identification, as well as the acquisition of information regarding the genetic context of AMR genes. Amongst others, already microbiologically well-characterized poultry faecal samples collected from in vivo animal experiments, carried out during the EFFORT project for which short-read sequencing data which is already available, will be analysed. This task will be completed in second year of project.

JRP16-WP1-T4 - Perform Hi-C metagenomics.

JRP16-WP1-T4 takes place over the first and the second year of the project.

Task start / end month: M33-M42

Task Leader: Josephine Grützke (9, BfR, GE)

Deputy Task Leader: Sigrid De Keersmaecker (4, Sciensano, BE)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), UCM (17), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: A 'defined' bacterial community, containing various bacterial species (with known complete sequences) and harbouring different AMR plasmids will be prepared and analysed using Hi-C library preparation and short-read sequencing. This analysis will reveal the feasibility, specificity, and sensitivity of Hi-C. Available bioinformatics tools will be used to analyse the

sequencing data, although these tools may require adaptation, which will take place in WP2. In the next step, spiked samples (T1.1) and samples from the EFFORT project (T1.3) will be analysed by this approach and compared to long-read and conventional short-read metagenomic sequencing. Additionally, where possible, approaches for a combined analysis of Hi-C and long-read data will be explored to improve the analysis.

WP2 - Bioinformatics tools to analyse the sequencing data and defining the characteristics within the sample.

JRP16-WP2 will take place over first, second and third year of the project.

WP start / end month: M28 – M54

WP Leader: Frank Aarestrup (12, DTU, DK)

Deputy WP Leader: Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (17, UCM, Spain)

WP participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the WP:

WP2 will implement a ready-to-use package (MGMapper) to assess, analyse, and perform reference-based taxonomic assignment of metagenomics DNA sequence data. The package can also carry out a post-processing analysis to produce reliable taxonomic annotation for species and strain resolution of both metagenomics and single isolate samples. MGMapper also employs a novel mapping method, KMA (*k*-mer alignment), which outperforms any currently available method in both accuracy and speed, without increased computational demands. The package and the mapping method are already in use in our routine daily analyses at DTU and will be available to analyse the data generated in WP1. These bioinformatics tools will markedly improve both taxon detection, and AMR and mobile element characterisations and dynamics in metagenomics samples. The current high performance computing (HPC) based tools will be established as a laptop version for further validation and testing. During the second and third year of the project, the bioinformatics pipeline will be evaluated using metagenome data from the project participants, on laptop versions used on-site.

JRP16-WP2-T1 - Development/adaptation of a pipeline that can predict species within sample/matrix

JRP16-WP2-T1 will take place over first and second year of the project.

Task start / end month: M28-M45

Task Leader: Frank Aarestrup (12, DTU, DK)

Deputy Task Leader: Josephine Grützke, (9, BfR, GE)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21)

Description of the task: The pipelines (MGMapper) will be tested and evaluated, and improved based on data submitted from the project participants. The performance of the MGMapper to produce reliable taxonomic annotation will be assessed using long-read sequencing data from defined mock communities, spiked samples and 'real' samples, established in WP1 and WP3. Bioinformatics tools for analysis of Hi-C/short-read sequencing will also require testing and optimisation to allow integration with MGMapper.

JRP16-WP2-T2 - Development/adaptation of a Resfinder-'like' pipeline for identification of AMR for long-read sequences

JRP16-WP2-T2 will take place over year the first, second and third year of the project.

Task start / end month: M30-M51

Task Leader: Frank Aarestrup (12, DTU, DK)

Deputy Task Leader: Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (17, UCM, Spain)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27)

Description of the task: The MGMapper tool will be further developed and tested for use with long-read sequencing to map and identify AMR, virulence and plasmid genes as well as their genetic origin with a metagenomics sample. Bioinformatics tools for analysis of Hi-C/short-read sequencing will also require testing and optimisation to allow integration with MGMapper.

JRP16-WP2-T3 - Benchmarking of tools with spiked samples in WP1 and WP3.

JRP16-WP2-T3 will take place over second and third year of the project.

Task start / end month: M40-M54

Task Leader: Soren Persson (27, SSI, DK)

Deputy Task Leader: Frank Aarestrup (12, DTU, DK)

Task Participants: BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: The tools developed in WP2 (e.g. KMA, MGMapper), used for the detection of known genes/species from the metagenomics sequencing, will be shared with the partners for evaluation against other established tools such as kraken, centrifuge and Resfinder.

JRP16-WP2-T4 - Test protocols on-site

JRP16-WP2-T4 will take place over second and third year of the project.

Task start / end month: M42-M54

Task Leader: Manal AbuOun (21, APHA, UK)

Deputy Task Leader: Soren Persson (27, SSI, DK)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: The bioinformatics tools developed on high performance computers (in T2.1 and T2.2) within partner institutes will be implemented on to portable laptop computers. The performance of the bioinformatics tools on these laptops will be tested and further validated, on-site, outside of the laboratory setting, with limited access to WiFi and mobile data connectivity.

WP3 - Implementation of on-site protocols for long-read metagenomic DNA sequencing

JRP16-WP3 will take place over first, second and third year of the project.

WP start / end month: M25 – M54

WP Leader: Mike Brouwer (31, WBVR, NL)

Deputy WP Leader: Soren Persson (27, SSI, DK)

WP participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the WP:

WP3 will focus on the necessary protocols and technologies to prepare samples in an on-site setting such as on a farm or in a hospital ward. To allow for on-site DNA sequencing and analysis, all steps will need to be carefully considered, including the DNA isolation from various sample matrices (WP1), sequencing library preparation, and downstream analysis. DNA isolations for on-site molecular applications have previously been described but the DNA quality and yield are likely to be low in many protocols as other molecular methods often rely on amplification of nucleic acids, for which low amounts of starting material is needed. For the on-site preparation of the sequencing libraries, two strategies will be investigated. The first will rely on the VolTRAX automated sample preparation unit. The second strategy will include investigation of the feasibility of the standard DNA extraction protocols used in WP1 to be adopted for on-site usage.

JRP16-WP3-T2 - Investigate the use of Voltrax

JRP16-WP3-T2 will take place over first and second year of the project.

Task start / end month: M30-M41

Task Leader: Manal AbuOun (21, APHA, UK)

Deputy Task Leader: Mike Brouwer (31, WBVR, NL)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: The use of the newly released ONT VolTRAX V2 will be examined for its capacity to extract high quality DNA from the samples matrices tested in WP1. The VolTRAX is a small, portable, and automated sample preparation device, which uses magnetic beads for DNA library preparation using magnetic beads, checks DNA quality, and has multiple reagent ports. In addition to a harmonised on-site DNA extraction protocol, the VolTRAX provides the option for on-site DNA library preparation so it can be directly loaded onto the MinION for sequencing.

JRP16-WP3-T3 - Assess DNA isolation methods for suitability, test on matrices (faeces, blood, dust, (environmental), milk).

JRP16-WP3-T3 will take place over first and second year of the project.

Task start / end month: M33-M54

Task Leader: Giuliano Garofolo (28, IZSAM, Italy)

Deputy Task Leader: Sigrid De Keersmaecker (4, Sciensano, BE)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: DNA isolation methods that have been determined most suitable for on-site application in the literature study of Task WP3-T1, will be assessed for 'simple' and 'complex' matrices as described in WP1. These experiments will be evaluated whilst replicating on-site conditions, within the laboratory, to determine which methods are most suitable for downstream NGS library preparation. Numerous parameters will be taken under consideration such as DNA yield, absence of contaminants and host DNA, limitations on use of specialised equipment, ease of use by trained but non-expert personnel, and cost.

JRP16-WP3-T4 - Test protocols on-site

JRP16-WP3-T4 will take place over second and third year of the project.

Task start / end month: M37-M54

Task Leader: Manal AbuOun (21, APHA, UK)

Deputy Task Leader: Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (17, UCM, Spain)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: The DNA isolation and library preparation protocols will be performed outside of the laboratory environment, with limited use of specialised equipment. These tests in real-world settings are essential to determine if the protocols perform as expected and will eliminate any overseen obstacles. On-site test sites may include farms, veterinary practices, hospitals, GP practices, university teaching sites (outside of the laboratory) and other locations that will be determined in the final year of the project.

WP4 - Project management, coordination and training workshop

JRP16-WP4 will take place over first, second and third year of the project.

WP start / end month: M25 – M54

WP Leader: Manal AbuOun (21, APHA, UK)

Deputy WP Leader: Mike Brouwer (31, WBVR, NL)

WP participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the WP:

This work package will manage and steer the project, all institutes will contribute with at least one member present on the management committee, to ensure successful and timely delivery. Four videoconference meetings per year and one annual physical meetings, between all institutes will assess progress of the project. The annual meetings will take place at three different participating

institutes. Any issues or concerns raised by any participating institutes will be communicated to the project lead and deputy lead, to allow rapid resolution. The management committee will also be in regular email contact with WP leaders, deputy leaders and task leaders, and project participants in general to ensure awareness and transparency, as well as to approve all documents and communications about the FARMED project.

JRP16-WP4-T1 - Annual physical project meetings

JRP16-WP4-T1 will take place over first, second and third year of the project.

Task start / end month: M30-M54

Task Leader: Mike Brouwer (31, WBVR, NL)

Deputy Task Leader: Manal AbuOun (21, APHA, UK)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task Three 'physical' annual meetings will take place to enable an open exchange of ideas and project outcomes between FARMED partners. These annual meetings will be organised in different countries and will include representatives from all partners. The meeting will take place in Month 30, Month 41 and a concluding meeting in Month 50.

JRP16-WP4-T2 - Teleconferences will be organised every 3 months, between partners

JRP16-WP4-T2 will take place over first, second and third year of the project.

Task start / end month: M25-M54

Task Leader: Nick Duggett (21, APHA, UK)

Deputy Task Leader Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn (17, UCM, Spain)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: All project partners/management committee will meet or communicate every quarter, to assess progress of the project by each partner. This will also allow partners to discuss and address possible problems, risks, technical issues, project communication, and publications. Partners will be encouraged to continue email communication, contacting the management committee at the earliest opportunity, as and when required, especially if any issues arise.

JRP16-WP4-T3 - Training/dissemination of developed protocols

JRP16-WP4-T3 will take place over second and third year of the project

Task start / end month: M48-M54

Task Leader: Frank Aarestrup (12, DTU, DK)

Deputy Task Leader: Soren Persson (27, SSI, DK)

Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)

Description of the task: Towards the end of the project period we will collect and condense the developed protocols for on-site DNA purification and library prep into a standardised protocol for practical metagenome sequencing at decentral locations across Europe. This work will be divided in two parts: 1) a simple protocol for robust on-site DNA extractions (SSI); 2) a data-analysis pipeline for either local or cloud-based screening of DNA sequences that immediately returns species identifications and antibiotic-resistance profiles to the local sites (DTU). This harmonisation will form the topic for a two-day workshop in Denmark, Copenhagen/Lyngby, with the first day focussing on on-site DNA extractions and the second day focussing on bioinformatic analyses and returning answers immediately to on-site users.

JRP16-WP4-T4 - Annual reports

JRP16-WP4-T4 will take place in the final 2 months of first, second and third year of the project.
Task start / end month: M36-M54
Task Leader: Manal AbuOun (21, APHA, UK)
Deputy Task Leader: Mike Brouwer (31, WBVR, NL)
Task Participants: Sciensano (4), BfR (9), DTU (12), SSI (13), UCM (17), APHA (21), ISS (27), IZSAM (28), WBVR (31)
Description of the task An annual report will be compiled by project partners to provide updates on progress of work packages and tasks. These communications will be distributed to relevant organisations or stakeholders such as national governments, EU, international agencies, and relevant industry/health partners. On-site DNA extraction and sequencing protocols, as well as bioinformatics pipeline/tools generated from this project will be published in appropriate scientific journals and coding repositories.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP16-WP1.1	Report on an initial assessment of long-read sequencing for metagenome (community and AMR) analysis (defined community, spiked and real simple and complex matrices) and comparison to current short-read standard.	M44
D-JRP16-WP1.2	Report on the feasibility of using Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.	M42
D-JRP16-WP3.2	Protocol for use of Voltrax on-site for extraction and library preparation from clinical, veterinary and environmental samples, suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing.	M41
D-JRP16-WP4.1	Annual communication to stakeholders and OH EJP coordinators	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP16-02	Assessment of long-read sequencing for resolving a 'defined' microbial community and their AMR genes, using current DNA extraction methods; and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard.	M40
M-JRP16-03	Assessment of long-read sequencing on spiked metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M40
M-JRP16-04	Protocols for on-site high-quality DNA extraction using Voltrax and library preparation ready for testing on-site	M41
M-JRP16-05	Assessment of long-read sequencing for 'simple' metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M42
M-JRP16-06	Assessment of the feasibility of Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.	M42
M-JRP16-07	Protocols for extraction of high-quality DNA (using different methods than Voltrax) from clinical, veterinary and environmental samples (simple and complex), suitable for long-	M44

	read metagenome sequencing distributed amongst FARMED consortium for testing.	
M-JRP16-08	Assessment of long-read sequencing for 'complex' metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M44
M-JRP16-09	Development/adaptation of a pipeline that can predict species within sample/matrix	M45
M-JRP16-10	Finalised protocol for on-site long-read sequencing of sample matrix distributed amongst FARMED consortium for testing.	M45

2.4.2.1.10 JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		AMR-SH 5: Development of new tools for early (real-time) detection of resistant pathogens in humans and animals, as well as new diagnostic tools, in particular on-site tests for humans and animals								
Research Project Title		Development of new tools for real-time detection of zoonotic bacteria and antimicrobial resistance in veterinary, human and environmental sources								
Research Project Acronym		WorldCom								
Leading Organisation		P25-NUIG			Deputy Leading Organisation			P23 UoS		
Project Leader		Prof. Terry Smith			Deputy Project leader			Prof. R. La Ragione		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLU	RKI	DTU
PM								19,2		
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM		15			21,7					
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	12,8		28,8							
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM				26						
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and performance evaluation of multiplex assays for pathogens and resistance genes • Integration of isothermal amplification assays onto lateral flow detection format • Development of mobile technology for communication of on-site results • Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests for detection of pathogens and resistance genes <p>WP: 2 Assay Development</p>										

WP start month: Month 36
 WP end month: Month 45
 WP Leader: National University of Ireland Galway.
 Deputy WP Leader: University of Surrey
 WP participants: NUI Galway, University of Surrey, University of Tartu, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge.
Description of the WP: Assay Development for selected pathogens and AMR genes
 Tasks 1 and 2 of this work-package will be carried out in annual period one M31-36
Task 3 (JPR15-AMR2.1-WP2-T3): Development and performance evaluation of multiplex assays for pathogens and resistance genes This task will be carried out over two annual periods starting in month 36 of the first and finishing in month 45 of the second.
 Task start month: 36
 Task end month: 45
 Task Leader: NUI Galway
 Deputy Task Leader: University of Surrey
 Task Participants: NUI Galway, University of Surrey, University of Tartu, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge.
Description of the task: This task will involve incorporating the singleplex assays developed for pathogens and resistance markers into multiplex assays. Evaluation of performance of the multiplex assays will include determination of analytical sensitivity and specificity. Assays will be evaluated by partners involved in this task directly with various sample types including human and animal faecal material and water from recreational and drinking sources.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP2.1	Multiplex real-time isothermal assays for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes which will be suitable for use in laboratory and optimised further in WP3 into a format suitable for on-site use	41

Milestones: Milestones for these work-packages will have been reached in the second annual and third annual periods period M45

WP: 3 Development of Lateral Flow Diagnostics Detection and Mobile Communication system
 WP start month: 44
 WP end month: 48
 WP Leader: University of Surrey
 Deputy WP Leader: NUI Galway
 WP participants: University of Surrey, NUI Galway, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut.
Description of the WP: Development of nucleic acid lateral flow (NALF) diagnostics detection system and mobile communication system
Task 1 (JPR15-AMR2.1-WP3-T1): Integration of isothermal amplification assays onto lateral flow detection format
 Task start month: 44
 Task end month: 48
 Task Leader: University of Surrey
 Deputy Task Leader: University of Surrey
 Task Participants: University of Surrey, NUI Galway
Description of the task: This task will entail integration of the isothermal amplification assays developed in work-package 1 onto a nucleic acid lateral flow biosensor. This will involve transfer of the singleplex and multiplex assays developed at NUI Galway to University of Surrey for

incorporation onto the nucleic acid lateral flow device. The performance assessment of the lateral flow detection including analytical sensitivity and specificity will be evaluated. Testing of samples from various environments including farm, environment and clinical will be carried out.

Task 2 (JPR15-AMR2.1-WP2-T2): Development of mobile technology for communication of on-site results

Task start month: 44

Task end month: 48

Task Leader: University of Surrey

Deputy Task Leader: VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM

Task Participants: University of Surrey, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut

Description of the task: Mobile technology will be developed which will enable communication of the results obtained on-site/pen-side with the reference laboratory. The project will link with the engineering department and vHive (Veterinary Health Innovation Centre) at the University of Surrey to develop an app for reading and curating the assay results. The results will then be transmitted to a central database which can be accessed by the relevant reference laboratories. This technology will be 5G-based, but could also be developed as a visual recognition App for environments where 5G signals may not be available.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP3.1	Lateral flow test for use on-site use together with Smartphone App for collection of data and transmission of test results to reference laboratory	48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JPR15-AMR2.1-07	Performance testing of lateral flow detection completed	48
M-JPR15-AMR2.1-08	Smartphone App for curation of assay results developed	48

WP: 4 Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed

WP start month: 48

WP end month: 54

WP Leader: Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut

Deputy WP Leader: Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA)

WP participants: Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM, University of Tartu, University of Surrey, NUI Galway.

Description of the WP: Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed

This work-package will be carried out over two annual periods from month 48 of second annual period and month 49-54 of third annual period.

Task 1 (JPR15-AMR2.1-WP4-T1): Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests for detection of pathogens and resistance genes

Task start month: 48

Task end month:51

Task Leader: Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut

Deputy Task Leader: Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge

Task Participants: Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM, University of Tartu, University of Surrey, NUI Galway.
Description of the task: Laboratory-based and on-site tests will be evaluated by veterinary, medical and environmental partners on the project team using animal, environmental, food and human clinical samples. Comparison of results from partner testing sites will be carried out. Additionally, organisms of interest will be isolated from the various sample types and phenotypically characterised. Isolates of interest will subsequently be sequenced and the outputs will be tested using the algorithms developed as part of WP1 to predict antimicrobial resistance.

Deliverables: There will be no deliverable at month 48 as the WP runs over two annual periods from month 48 of second annual period and month 49-54 of third annual period and deliverables are scheduled for M54

Ref	Title	Due month
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JPR15-AMR2.1-09	Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests underway	51
M-JPR15-AMR2.1-10	Feasibility testing of novel algorithms underway	51

WP: 5 Project Management
 WP start month: 25
 WP end month: 54
 WP Leader: NUI Galway
 Deputy WP Leader: University of Surrey
 WP participants: Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM, University of Tartu, University of Surrey, NUI Galway.
Description of the WP: Overall WorldCom project management.
 Task start month: 37
 Task end month: 48
 Task Leader: NUI Galway
 Deputy Task Leader: University of Surrey
 Task Participants: NUI Galway, University of Surrey, Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM, University of Tartu.
Description of the task:
Task 1 (JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5-T1): One project review meeting will be organised in the second annual period. The data management plan will be reviewed and updated. Technical and financial reports will be prepared. These activities will be overseen and co-ordinated by the project lead. Throughout the second annual period the project lead will be responsible for co-ordination of all technical and project management conference calls and other communication activities.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.1	Organisation of project review meeting	41
D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.2	Data management plan reviewed	41
D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP5.3	Preparation of technical and financial reports	48

Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month

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M-JPR15-AMR2.1-11	Project review meeting organised	41
M-JPR15-AMR2.1-12	Technical and financial reports prepared	48

2.4.2.1.11 JRP14-R2-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		AMR 2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread								
Research Project Title		Full-length sequencing for an enhanced EFFORT to map and understand drivers and reservoirs of antimicrobial resistance								
Research Project Acronym		FULL_FORCE								
Leading Organisation		P4-Sciensano			Deputy Leading Organisation			P31-WbvR		
Project Leader		Pieter-Jan Ceysens			Deputy Project leader			Michael Brouwer		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	8		12,19				7,5			7,05
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	3,75			6,05			6,5		6,13	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAMI	IZSLER	RIVM	WbvR	FHI
PM					8,3			3,69	12,38	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM	2,97	9,28	10,75	4,19					7,5	
<p>Main Objectives</p> <p>In the second year of the FULL_FORCE project, the long-read sequencing tools developed in Y1 will be applied on a selection of multidrug resistant (MDR) <i>E. coli</i> strains from the EFFORT/COMPARE/ARDIG programs, and to Enterobacteriaceae resistant to critically important antimicrobials isolated in the context of different national monitoring programmes. More specifically, we will target the following research questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do MGEs evolve in longitudinal sample sets? • Which genetic environment is associated with most common AMR in indicator <i>E. coli</i>? 										

- Do we find novel MGEs in *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and would this mean this bacterium is a superior indicator organism?
- Which MGE are responsible for increasing resistance in horses?
- What might explain the evolutionary success of MDR *Salmonella enterica* serovars Infantis and Kentucky in the EU?
- Are in-house and publicly available tools performant to detect MGEs ?

These genome studies will be supported from detailed MGE typing (WP4), and will serve to enhance mining of available metagenomic data sets for the presence of these dominating MGE and correlate them to AMR-gene abundances (WP3). In the modelling WP, we will continue the optimization of the broiler production model, and start the exposure assessment of horizontal and vertical transmission of AMR.

WP 0: PROJECT MANAGEMENT

WP start/end month: M25 – M54

WP Leader: Pieter-Jan Ceysens (SCI); WP participants: all

This overarching WP ensures proper coordination at both the overall project and the individual WPs, as well as timely reporting of results and budgets according to the formal EU requirements. It will also involve knowledge transfer for data storage at ENA from the COMPARE project, and the development of a data management plan. WPO takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Task 0.1: MEETINGS AND TELCALLS

Task start/end month: M25-M54

Task Leader: Pieter-Jan Ceysens (SCI); Task Participants: all (incl. UU, IZSLT, UG)

This task takes place over the three annual periods of the EJP. In its second year, the FULL_FORCE consortium will physically meet at ECCMID 2021. Here, detailed task overviews will be presented by the WP leaders for the coming project year as well as task achievements that will be disseminated by both WP leaders and relevant project participants.

Apart from these, the project coordinator and deputy coordinator will perform teleconferences with all WP leaders at the start of every quarter to ensure momentum of the overall project. Dates for teleconferences will be determined using the Doodle web tool. In addition, WP leaders will perform WP teleconferences with relevant WP members according to the individual requirements and deliverables.

Task 0.2: REPORTING

Start/end month: M25-M54

Leader: Pieter-Jan Ceysens (SCI); Task Participants: WP leaders (SSI, DTU, APHA, INRAE, SVA)

This task takes place over the three annual periods of the EJP. The project coordinator will collect detailed reports on deliverables and milestones from WP leaders according to the work plan outlined below. Also, budget information will be collected at the end of each project year from all participants and reported according to the requirements of EU.

Task 0.3: CENTRAL DATA REPOSITORY (finished)

Task 0.4: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Start/end month: M25-M54

Leader: Pieter-Jan Ceysens (SCI); Task Participants: all.

This task takes place over the three annual periods of the EJP. During the consortium meeting in ECCMID 2021, we will discuss the first version of FULL_FORCE's Data Management plan (DMP) and

propose amendments if deemed necessary. These modifications need to be improved by each participating partner.

Deliverables

D-JRP19-WP0.D4	Annual meeting report with (re-)approval of DMP	M42
D-JRP19-WP0.D5	Financial and activity report Y4	M48

WP 1: SMRT IMPLEMENTATION

WP start/end month: M25 – M40. This WP takes place in the first and second annual year on FULL_FORCE.

WP Leader: Henrik Hasman (SSI); **WP participants:** SCI, ANSES, INSA, BfR, DTU, APHA, INIA, INRAE, ISS, PIWET, PHAS, SSI, RIVM, SVA, WbvR, NVI (+UG, UU, IZSLT)

Task 1.3 PROFICIENCY TEST FOR MGE SEQUENCING

Start/end month: M31-M42

Leader: Henrik Hasman (SSI); Task Participants: ANSES, INSA, BfR, DTU, APHA, INIA, INRAE, ISS, PIWET, PHAS, SSI, RIVM, SVA, WbvR, NVI (+ IZSLT, UG, UU)

After completion of T1.2, all relevant partners will be invited to participate in a dry-lab proficiency test, where Illumina and MinION sequencing data from a set of isolates carrying well-characterized MGEs are distributed for the participants to analyse using protocols from T1.1 and methods presented during the workshop (T1.2). The results of the proficiency tests will be reported to, and discussed with, participants individually and furthermore aggregated into an anonymized final report.

Deliverables

D-JRP19-WP1.D7	Delivery of analysis results of proficiency test by partners to SSI	M39
D-JRP19-WP1.D8	Completion of final report of proficiency tests	M40

Milestone

M-JRP19-M15	Analysis of proficiency test data by all partners	M38
M-JRP19-M16	Individual reports of proficiency test sent to partners	M40

WP 2: GENOME STUDIES

WP start/end month: M25 – M54. This WP takes place over the three annual years of the project.

WP Leader: Muna Anjum (APHA); **Deputy Leader:** Pieter-Jan Ceysens (SCI); **WP participants:** SSI, ANSES, INSA, BfR, DTU, INIA, INRAE, ISS, PIWET, PHAS, SSI, RIVM, SVA, WbvR, NVI (+UU, IZSLT)

The general goal of this WP is to apply SMRT sequencing technology on six selected case studies, from cross-sectional and longitudinal studies from research and surveillance projects including EU projects such as EFFORT, COMPARE, ENGAGE and ARDIG, as well as national and EU surveillance activities, for which short read Illumina sequences may already available. Using this additional layer of information, we will be able to compare specific MGEs and their possible evolution in different environments and geography.

Task 2.1 MGE evolution in longitudinal sample sets (ARDIG, ABRES)

Start/end month: M25-M54. This task takes place over the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Muna Anjum (APHA); Task Participants: NVI, ANSES, RIVM, WBVR

Long-read sequencing of isolates will be performed using SMRT sequencing on up to 20 isolates per partner collected from different time points, in at least one longitudinal study. The methodologies used for both wet and dry lab work will be based on WP1. Long-read WGS data will be combined

with short read data, hybrid genomes assembled and circularised. A subset of MGEs, such as multidrug resistant (MDR) plasmids, harbouring AMR genes from 3 or more different AMR families, including high-priority critically important antimicrobials (HP-CIAs) such as 3rd/4th generation cephalosporin, ciprofloxacin, or colistin, present in isolates collected at different time points, will be interrogated. For these isolates, the size and gene content of selected plasmids with MDR profiles will be compared over time to detect any changes that may have occurred; the multilocus sequence type of bacterial hosts harbouring these plasmids from each time point will be determined and used to correlate with any changes in the plasmid genome (size, content). This will ascertain the possible influence of host and time in plasmid evolution.

Task 2.2 MGE evolution in cross-sectional data sets (EFFORT, ENGAGE & National Surveillance)

Start/end month: M28-M54. This task takes place over the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Jens A. Hammerl (BfR); Task Participants: WBVR, INIA, INSA, PIWET, PHAS, SSI, DTU, RIVM, APHA, SCI, (IZSLT)

The focus of the second year will be on SMRT sequencing and the subsequent dissection of the genetic structure (i.e. modular composition) of the plasmids types. Apart from analyses described in T2.1, detailed analyses are also planned for the detection of hot spots for transposon or insertion elements, the diversity of genes involved in plasmid transfer (mobilisation, conjugation) and systems for plasmid exclusion/incompatibility/addiction systems. On the basis of the available plasmid genomes from different sections the gene content, sequence insertions and deletions and nucleotide composition of the plasmid genomes are assessed and compared to estimate probable host-specific mechanistic events in plasmid evolution. Plasmid types that are linked to specific AMRs or of important incompatibility groups (esp. broad host range plasmids) will be dissected to gain insight in the variability of a plasmid type within different sources (human, environmental, livestock, food, etc.).

Task 2.3 *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: the canary in the coalmine

Start/end month: M28-M54. This task takes place over the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Petra Edquist and Alma Brolund (FOHM); Task Participants: ISS, INSA, SCI, INIA, NVI, SSI, BfR, (IZSLT)

In this task we will perform short and long read sequencing of ~100 *K. pneumoniae* from each contributing site. *K. pneumoniae* from different sectors will be compared, such as human patients, environment and infected animals as well as geographic origin of the strains. We will also be able to compare *K. pneumoniae* strains with different antibiotic resistance genes, i.e. CPO vs. ESBL. During year 2, the long read sequencing of the selected *K. pneumoniae* isolates will be performed. The sequence data from both short and long read sequencing will be collected in the AMR data hub. The analysis will be initiated as largely defined in Tasks 2.1 and 2.2.

Task 2.4 ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae in horses – A separated epidemiology of plasmids?

Start/end month: M28-M54. This task takes place over the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Stefan Borjesson (SVA); Task Participants: ANSES, INRAE, RIVM, (UU, IZSLT)

This task objective is to investigate the spread of ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae in horses in Europe. The focus will be on bla_{CTX-M-1} and bla_{SHV-12} genes. Hybrid assemblies and genome analyses and comparisons will be performed as described in tasks 2.1-2.3.

Task 2.5 *Salmonella Infantis* and *S. Kentucky* across reservoirs: role of MGEs

Start/end month: M28-M54. This task takes place over the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Laura Villa (ISS); Task Participants: ISS, SCI, INRAE, INSA, PHAS, PIWET, RIVM, SVA, (IZSLT)

For *S. Infantis* and *S. Kentucky* short read data will be combined with long-read WGS data, where available, and hybrid genomes assembled and plasmids circularized. The AMR, replicon, transposase and insertion sequence gene content using the pipelines such as DTU ResFinder, PlasmidFinder and BioTool ISFinder, respectively will be identified. The analysis of the link of AMR genes and plasmid types emerging in *S. Infantis* (pESI megaplasmid and also other plasmids co-resident with the ESBL plasmid) and in *S. Kentucky* (with particular attention to the detection of the CTX-M-14b emerging plasmid) will be performed over time and from different source to detect possible changes that may have occurred.

Task 2.6 Evaluation of publicly available and in-house tools for MGE typing

Start/end month: M30-M54. This task takes place over the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Jannice Schau Slettemeås (NVI); Task Participants: ANSES, Bfr, DTU, APHA, INSA, (UU, IZSLT)

The best tools identified and explored during the first year of FULL_FORCE will during the second year be tested on the full-length genomes for characterization of various MGEs from task 2.1 to 2.5 in WP2.

Deliverables

D-JRP19-WP2.D7	Submission of long-read sequencing data of longitudinal samples to ENA hub	M46
D-JRP19-WP2.D8	Submission of long-read sequencing data of cross-sectional samples to ENA hub	M46
D-JRP19-WP2.D9	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>S. Infantis</i> and <i>S. Kentucky</i> to ENA hub	M46
D-JRP19-WP2.D10	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> samples to ENA hub	M46
D-JRP19-WP2.D11	Submission of long-read sequencing data AMR horse samples to ENA hub	M46
D-JRP19-WP2.D12	Report on MGE tool testing for MGE characterization using full-length genomes	M48

Milestones

M-JRP19-M24	Finalised hybrid assemblies of longitudinal samples	M46
M-JRP19-M25	Finalised hybrid assemblies of cross-sectional samples	M46
M-JRP19-M26	Finalised hybrid assemblies of <i>S. Infantis</i> and <i>S. Kentucky</i> isolates	M46
M-JRP19-M27	Finalised hybrid assemblies of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> isolates	M46
M-JRP19-M28	Finalised hybrid assemblies of AMR horse samples	M46

WP 3: CULTURE-INDEPENDENT TYPING AND METAGENOMICS

WP start/end month: M30 – M54

WP Leader: Frank Aarestrup (DTU); **WP participants:** WBVR, APHA, NVI, INIA, (UU, IZSLT)

At least an 80% of bacteria present in complex samples such as faeces and soil are uncultivable under routine microbiological procedures. The development of culture-independent methods for detect, quantify and identify bacterial plasmids carrying antimicrobial resistance genes is greatly encouraged for future surveillance efforts. This WP will focus on (i) enhanced mining of existing metagenomics data, including those from the EFFORT and COMPARE projects, and correlate this to AMR-gene abundance, and (ii) development of diagnostic tools for direct identification of

MGE/plasmid identifications from various sample types. WP3 takes place over Y3, Y4, and Y5 of the EJP.

Task 3.1 MGE ANALYSES IN METAGENOMIC DATASETS

Start/end month: M30-54. This task will take place in the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Frank Aarestrup (DTU); Task Participants: WBVR, APHA, NVI, (UU, IZSLT)

This task takes place over the three years of FULL_FORCE. In Y4 (2021), we will update the MGE database with full-length MGEs coming from WP2, and integrate it into available bioinformatics pipelines which will include MGmapper as well as novel developments hereof (KMA) at DTU, and from UU and NVI. These *plug and play* pipeline processes animal and human metagenomic samples: filtering/trimming, automated host detection and removal (any vertebrate species), community profiling, detection of specific AMR gene alleles using KMA (tool from dtu), and will be made available. The tool will identify the number of chromosomal marker genes, plasmid replication genes and plasmid typing genes using CheckM and DIAMOND Blast, and determines pentamer frequencies and contig sizes per contig. A prediction model will be trained using Random Forest on an extensive set of plasmids and chromosomes from 19 different bacterial species and validated on separate test sets of known chromosomal and plasmid contigs of the different bacteria. An alpha version of tool is available including benchmarks. Correlation between presence of genes and phylogeny and origin will be determined using logistic and multivariate regression and de-seq analyses.

Task 3.2 CULTURE INDEPENDENT METHODS FOR PLASMID IDENTIFICATION

Start/end month: M30-54. This task will take place in the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Fernando Esperón (INIA); Task Participants: WBVR, (IZSLT)

During Y4 the proposed objectives are: 1- to validate the protocol for plasmid DNA full sequencing by SMRT and 2- to start the design of the high throughput method for AMR gene detection. Plasmid DNA from samples of EFFORT program will be fully sequenced by SMRT and compared with short and long reads available. Regarding the second objective, up to 32 ARGs will be prioritized based on the results obtained based on EFFORT project, and singleplex real time PCRs will be designed or adapted from literature.

Deliverables

D-JRP19-WP3.D3	Publication of the validated method for plasmid DNA extraction on environmental samples.	M40
D-JRP19-WP3.D4	Report on the comparison of available pipelines for metagenome analyses	M48
D-JRP19-WP3.D5	Protocols for real time PCR detection of up to 32 ARGs in singleplex format.	M48

Milestones

M-JRP19-M19	Successful implementation of SMRT sequencing of field samples	M42
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WP 4: FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF AMR MOBILE GENETIC ELEMENTS (MGE)-CARRYING AMR GENES AND BACTERIAL HOST ASSOCIATIONS

WP start/end month: M25 – M54.

WP Leader: Benoit Doublet (INRAE, 19); Deputy WP Leader: Laura Villa (ISS, 27); WP participants: ANSES, INSA, BfR, DTU, APHA, INIA, SCI, PIWET, PHAS, SSI, RIVM, SVA, WbvR, NVI (+UU, UG, IZSLT)

The overall goals of this WP are to (i) gain knowledge on molecular mechanisms of spread and persistence of main MGEs carrying critically/highly important antimicrobial resistances, (ii) identify key molecular interactions between AMR-MGEs and bacterial host important for dissemination and maintenance, and (iii) provide first line evidences for the development of novel exploratory strategies to curb the spread of major AMR-MGEs. WP4 takes place over Y3, Y4, and Y5 of the EJP.

Task 4.1 SELECTION of MGEs and HOST STRAINS FOR DETAILED CHARACTERIZATION

Start/end month: M25-42. This task will take place in the first and second annual year of the project.
Leader: Laura Villa (ISS); Deputy Task Leader: Benoît Doublet (INRAE); Task Participants: ANSES, INSA, BfR, DTU, APHA, INIA, SCI, PIWET, PHAS, SSI, RIVM, SVA, WbvR, NVI (+UU, UG, IZSLT)

The initial selection contained plasmids such as pESI of *S. Infantis*, pKpQIL of KPC-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, IncX3-SHV and IncHI1-CTX-M plasmids from horses, Inc11-ampC/ESBL plasmids, *Salmonella* genomic island 1, IncC plasmids of *S. Kentucky* ST198 and IncX4, IncI2, IncHI2 and ColE-like plasmids carrying *mcr* genes in *Salmonella* and *Escherichia coli*.

In the second annual EJP year, this initial selection of epidemic plasmids and integrative elements can be refined based on results in WP2 and WP3. The focus will be on MGEs found in different bacteria, at distant geographical regions and/or associated with emerging clones, with the following selection criteria are/will be discussed:

- Host strains belonging to pathogens, opportunistic and commensals linked to WP2.
- Carrying critically/highly-important AMR genes that encode extended-spectrum β -lactamases (ESBLs: CTX-M, SHV, TEM, PER), carbapenemases (NDM, OXA-48-type, VIM, IMP, KPC), mobile colistin resistance determinant (MCR-type).

Task 4.2 FUNCTIONAL CHARACTERIZATION of MGEs

Start/end month: M31-54. This task will take place in the three annual years of FULL_FORCE.
Leader: Benoît Doublet (INRAE); Deputy Task Leader: Michael Brouwer (WBVR); Task Participants: ANSES, SCI, INRAE, ISS, WBVR, INSA, IZSLT

AMR-MGEs considered of interest will continued to be investigated by molecular functional analysis to identify both the MGE-encoded factors and the bacterial host factors important for dissemination, stability and maintenance. The initial selected targets are specified in the Annual Work Plan of Y3 (2020), and can be adapted upon results of T4.1. Briefly, *in vitro* conjugation studies will be conducted with selected type- MGEs and host strains. Conjugation assays will be performed from different genetic backgrounds (*Salmonella*, *Klebsiella*, *E. coli*, *Proteus*, etc) of donor strains and recipient strains. AMR-MGEs will be introduced in different host strains and studied for their ability to persist over time in the bacterial host without antimicrobial selective pressure. Genetic factors from MGEs and the host that may influence persistence will be investigated. Beyond the known incompatibility between plasmids of the same Inc group, the capacity of different AMR-MGEs “to live together” in the same host will be also studied. We will share approaches, protocols, molecular tools between involved participants.

Task 4.3 HOST ASSOCIATION STUDIES

Start/end month: M43-54. This task will take place in the second and third annual year of the EJP
Leader: Valeria Bortolaia (DTU); Task Participants: DTU, (UU; IZLST)

The hosts of AMR plasmids can be described using at least two levels of complexity: the bacterial host, i.e. the bacterial cell bearing the plasmid, and the microbiota, i.e. the complex bacterial community hosting the plasmid-bearing bacteria. To understand AMR plasmid epidemiology and possibly prevent AMR spread by horizontal gene transfer, it is important to consider that an AMR

plasmid can persist in a complex bacterial community longer and in higher numbers than its bacterial host if it is able to transfer to other bacteria in such community. In task 4.3, the epidemic successful associations between MGEs and hosts (defined both at the bacterial and at the microbiota level) will be investigated in vitro using functional assays and in silico by genome wide association studies (GWAS) to identify ecological factors favoring plasmid persistence.

This functional typing, not only based on conjugative properties and fitness cost imposed on the bacterial host, but also for example estimating “plasmid persistence” in complex bacterial communities such as those of faeces and/or sewage, would constitute an additional layer to the “plasmid typing” outcome. In year 2, we will set up its necessary protocols and perform a small-scale test in which the persistence of a reference plasmid (as selected in task 4.1) is measured in complex microbiota (i.e. faecal microbiota from five humans and five chickens, and sewage microbiota from 5 sampling sites) for up to 15 days.

Deliverables

D-JRP19-WP4.D2	Refine additional collection of type-materials (MGEs and strains) to be shared between involved partners	M42
D-JRP19-WP4.D3	Set-up of protocols for measuring plasmid persistence in complex microbiota and small-scale testing	M46

Milestones

M-JRP19-M18	Selection of additional MGEs and host strains based on first outcomes of JRP18-R2-AMR2-FULL-FORCE-WPs-2 and -3.	M40
M-JRP19-M21	Construction of Isogenic CIP ^R S. Kentucky ST198 strains carrying different SGI1-related elements	M45
M-JRP19-M22	Transfer frequency data of representative IncHI1-CTX-M1 plasmids	M45
M-JRP19-M29	Transfer frequency data of <i>mcr</i> plasmids of different incompatibility groups	M48
M-JRP19-M23	Data on conjugative transfer of pESI plasmid from S. Infantis to other <i>Salmonella</i> serovars and other microbial species	M45

WP 5: MODELLING

WP start/end month: M25 – M54. WP5 takes place over Y3, Y4, and Y5 of the EJP.

WP Leader: Stefan Widgren (SVA, 41); **WP participants:** RIVM, BfR, UU - Farm Animal Health

The objectives of WP5 are to address: i) gaps in quantitative knowledge on the spread of pAMR which will be essential to direct future focused research, ii) insight in the uncertainty around the effect of measures reducing pAMR prevalence in the production chains, and iii) identification of key elements in the production chains to mitigate the risk of human exposure.

Task 5.1 MODEL DESIGN for AMR TRANSMISSION

Start/end month: M25-42. This task will take place in the first and second annual year of the project.

Leader: Stefan Widgren (SVA, 41); **Task Participants:** RIVM, BfR, UU - Farm Animal Health

In the second annual year, SVA will continue the **parameterization of the model** using ABC methodology (**M34-42**). Estimating model parameters from observed data is a major challenge in stochastic modelling. However, it is a necessary and critical step in order to evaluate a model's explanatory power. Parameterization is preferably conducted within a Bayesian framework, when prior knowledge is present, as in the case of transmission in a production chain. In WP5 we will focus on Approximate Bayesian computation (ABC), a recent computational approach for parameterisation of complex problems, for example, in epidemiology. ABC is appropriate as we can use the SimInf-simulator as a so-called generative model. However, since ABC is computationally challenging it is important to explore how to efficiently perform parameter inference within an AMR

transmission simulation framework. There are several open source software tools available for ABC analysis that potentially can be used in combination with the SimInf modelling R package. In WP5 we will investigate approaches and tools for using ABC methodology for parameter inference in order to facilitate complex epidemiological research of AMR transmission in the broiler production chain. The methodology developed within the WP5 will be made publicly available - it will thus become possible to adapt the modelling to other similar applications.

Task 5.2 EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT of HORIZONTAL and VERTICAL TRANSMITTED AMR

Start/end month: M25-54. This task will take place in the three annual years of the project.

Leader: Eric Evers (RIVM); Task Participants: SVA, UU - Farm Animal Health

During the second annual year, RIVM will continue to **quantify the fraction contribution** of horizontal vs. vertical transmission to human AMR exposure (**M25-39**). These fractions might vary between the different stages in the food chain. Information for this will be gained from discussions with experts, mainly within this work package but also outside, and from literature study.

In a final subtask, RIVM will lead the **calculation of human AMR exposure** by SimInf and sQMRA, trying to distinguish between horizontal and vertical transmission (**M37-54**). Important will be to reach consensus on demarcations of the work in terms of food animals and AMR types. Also, coupling of SimInf and sQMRA will need careful assessment of input-output relationships. The result will be food-product specific, indicating product-specific public health significance.

Deliverables

D-JRP19-WP5.D2	A report on quantification of horizontal vs. vertical transmission of AMR	M39
D-JRP19-WP5.D3	A report on using ABC methodology for parameter inference of a SimInf model designed for pAMR.	M42

Milestones

M-JRP19-M20	A parameterised SimInf model designed for pAMR transmission to be studied in T5.2	M42
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2.4.2.1.12 JRP15-R2-AMR2.1-FED-AMR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		AMR 2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread								
Research Project Title		The role of free extracellular DNA in dissemination of antimicrobial resistance over ecosystem boundaries along the food/feed chain								
Research Project Acronym		FED-AMR								
Leading Organisation		P2-AGES			Deputy Leading Organisation			P36-INSA		
Project Leader		Wögerbauer			Deputy Project leader			Canica		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agès	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLU	RKI	DTU
PM		13,95			1,13		2,75	8,4		
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	8	14						1,25		
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	Uos	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAMI	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	12,96		18							
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM	2,72	9,3		62,3						
<p>Description of work</p> <p>WP1: Project Management and Communication --> as described in Y3</p> <p>WP1 takes place over the first, the second year and the third year of the project (Y3, Y4, Y5)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Task 1.1, subtasks sT1.1.2, sT1.1.2, task T1.2 and task 1.3 take place over the first, the second year and the third year of the project (Y3, Y4, Y5) subtask sT1.1.1 takes place in the first year of the project (Y3) <p>WP start month: M25 WP end month: M54</p>										

WP Leader: Werner Ruppitsch (2-AGES)

Deputy WP Leader: Adriana Cabal Rosel (2-AGES)

WP participants: All (2-AGES, 7-SZU, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 14-UT, 20-IP, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA)

Description of the WP: WP 1 will consist of 3 primary tasks: Task 1.1. will organize the scientific management (SM) of the project. Task 1.2. describes the measures applied for managing administrative and legal activities (AM). Task 1.3. deals with data and protocol management (DPMP). A Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) constituted by a single representative of each of the 12 participating organizations will control all FED-AMR scientific and administrative activities and decides about all key issues concerning project execution and exploitation of the results. Management is organized by 2-AGES, all remaining institutes nominate a Representative responsible for communicating management issues to and from their local institutions.

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP1-T1**: *Scientific Management*

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Manuela Caniça (36-INSA)

Deputy Task Leader: Adriana Cabal Rosel (2-AGES)

Task Participants: All (2-AGES, 7-SZU, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 14-UT, 20-IP, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA)

Description of the task: The scientific management (SM) of the FED-AMR project will be organized by an INSA senior expert who has experience in the management of scientific projects for over 20 years (M. Caniça). She will be assisted by A. Cabal Rosel. The other partners nominate a Representative for the Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB). The SSB will meet in regular intervals to control the progress of the project. A risk management strategy for the project will be defined by the Administrative Manager (AM) and the Scientific Manager (SM), in consultation with the SSB to ensure that adverse situations are properly handled along the course of the project.

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP1-T1.1**: *Coordination of sampling, laboratory experiments and building a database.*

Finished in Y3.

Sub-Task: JRP17-R2-**WP1-T1.2**: *Webinar forum and Skype meetings for instant scientific interactions*

Sub-Task start month: M30

Sub-Task end month: M50

Sub-Task Leader: Mónica Oleastro (36-INSA)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Markus Wögerbauer (2-AGES)

Sub-Task Participants: 2-AGES, 36-INSA

Description of the task: To facilitate interaction and problem solving at regular intervals Webinars will be organized as well as ad hoc Skype meetings. These activities will be co-ordinated by 2-AGES and 36-INSA.

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP1-T1.3**: *Project Meetings*

Sub-Task start month: M25

Sub-Task end month: M52

Sub-Task Leader: Manuela Caniça (36-INSA)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Karin Rainer (2-AGES)

Sub-Task Participants: 2-AGES, 36-INSA;

Description of the task: Project meetings will be held in Vienna (M26, M52) and Lisbon (M41) trying to bring as many members of the FED-AMR consortium together. However, the meetings will be

broadcast via Adobe Connect to those who cannot attend. 2-AGES and 36-INSA will organize the events.

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP1-T2**: *Administrative Management*

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Karin Rainer (2-AGES)

Deputy Task Leader: Christine Feiertag (2-AGES)

Task Participants: 2-AGES

Description of the task: The administrative management (AM) will be supported by the infrastructure of the AGES academy and the secretariat of the AGES knowledge transfer department. The coordination of joint activities in the frame of the FED-AMR project will be coordinated by AGES (see above). Additionally, each partner will appoint an Administrative Representative who will be in direct contact with the AGES Administrative Manager (AM). A risk management strategy for the project will be defined by the Administrative Manager (AM) and the Scientific Manager (SM), in consultation with the Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) to ensure that adverse situations are properly handled along the course of the project.

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP1-T3**: *Data and Protocol Management*

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M52

Task Leader: Manuela Caniça (36-INSA)

Deputy Task Leader: Alexandre de Menezes (25-NUIG)

Task Participants: All (2-AGES, 7-SZU, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 14-UT, 20-IP, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA)

Description of the task: The SSB of the FED-AMR consortium will start to develop a Data and Protocol Management Plan (DPMP) at the Kick-off Meeting and aims to have a final DPMP available by M31. The DPMP will determine which data will be collected, processed or produced, which techniques and standards will be used, whether data and/or protocols will be shared and made publicly available, whether and how they will be made accessible for verification and/or reuse, and how they will be curated and stored (even after the end of the project period). The database will be curated and updated at regular intervals.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP15- FED-AMR - WP1.6	Interim project report (T1.3.)	M47

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP15- FED-AMR - 04	Interim meeting	M41

WP2: Field experiments: Determination of the naturally occurring ARG background load and microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments – Longitudinal study over a crop growing season (1 year).

WP2 takes place over the first, second and third of the project (Y3, Y4 and Y5). Tasks 2.1. and 2.2. take place in the first year (Y3). Tasks 2.3., and 2.4. take place over the first and second year of the project (Y3 and Y4). Tasks 2.5. and 2.6. take place over the second year (Y4). Task 2.7 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project (Y3, Y4 and Y5).

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M50

WP Leader: Manuela Caniça (36-INSA)

Deputy WP Leader: Adriana Cabal Rosel (2-AGES)

WP participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 36-INSA

Description of the WP: Please see relevant description for WP2 in the annual work plan for year 3.

Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T1**: *Assemble list of sampling compartments and points. Determination of test areas representative for the European regions (North, West, East, South).*

Finished in Y3.

Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T2**: *Establish common protocol for sampling and data analyses to facilitate comparability of the results between European test areas (North, West, East, South) and local sampling locations*

Finished in Y3.

Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T3**: *Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in the selected test environments (metagenomics). Compare microbial and ARG diversity between ecosystems and over ecosystem boundaries. Characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media.*

Will be performed as described for WP2-T3 in the annual work plan for year 3.

Sub-Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T3.1**: *Shotgun sequencing and bioinformatic analyses of AMR genes and MGEs.*

Sub-Task start month: M37

Sub-Task end month: M48

Sub-Task Leader: Alexandre De Menezes (25-NUIG)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Werner Ruppitsch (2-AGES)

Sub-Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 36-INSA

Description of the task: Shotgun sequencing to obtain an overview over the variety of ARGs present in the diverse environmental compartments will be started after the DNA of all samples was purified. Certain reference samples as decided by the Scientific Board will be analysed according to the cheapest offer obtained. Bioinformatics and statistical analysis will be performed at the Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC) at 25-NUIG using metaSPAdes, SNPfinder, MEGAN and similar appropriate software. Resistomes will be determined using the Resfinder reference database. Normalized fragments resistance genes per kilobase reference per million bacterial fragments (FPKM) will be calculated for quantitative evaluations. This subtask is based upon results from and methodology applied by the EFFORT project. The remaining partners supply samples. The results will be forwarded to WP5 and WP6.

Sub-Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T3.2**: *Gene enrichment with gene capture probes*

Will be performed as described for WP2-T3.2 in the annual work plan for year 3.

Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T4**: *Quantify clinically relevant ARGs in the tested compartments (qPCR; qPCR arrays).*

Will be performed as described for WP2-T3.2 in the annual work plan for year 3.

Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T5**: *Identify naturally transformable bacterial species in the tested compartments (NGS).*

Task start month: M41

Task end month: M44

Task Leader: Alexandre De Menezes (25-NUIG)

Deputy Task Leader: Zdislava Boštíková (7-SZU)
Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 36-INSA
Description of the task: Illumina 16S targeted amplicon and shotgun sequencing data obtained in **WP2-T3** will be analysed for the presence of known naturally transformable bacterial species using the reference list generated in Woegerbauer et al. 2015. The obtained sequence data will be searched for competence gene homologs. The alignment studies will be performed at 2-AGES, 33-NVI and 25-NUIG. The results will be provided for WP5 and WP6. This data will inform about the availability of bacteria capable to take up free DNA from the environment and, thus, fuel AMR dissemination via bacterial transformation.

Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T6**: *Assess clonal/lineage diversity in selected ARB species.*

Task start month: M43

Task end month: M46

Task Leader: Dr. Tanel Tenson (14-UT)

Deputy Task Leader: Dr. Sølverød Mo (33-NVI)

Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI, 36-INSA

Description of the task: Phylogenetic trees will be established between bacterial species present in different but interconnected compartments using Illumina 16S targeted amplicon and shotgun sequencing data obtained in **WP2-T3**. Preferentially, T-REX, PhyML, TreeView and the UGENE, MEGA and Illumina software packages will be used for this purpose. All participating institutes will pre-analyse and preformat their own samples/sequences. A synopsis of all relevant species-specific sequences obtained throughout Europe will be performed at 25-NUIG. The results will indicate potential ARG/ARB transmission pathways over ecosystem boundaries and will identify critical control points for implementing measures to decrease the risk for AMR dissemination from identified environmental sources. The results will be forwarded to WP5 and WP6.

Task: JRP17-R2-**WP2-T7**: *Isolate and assess quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in the tested environments. Sequence comparisons.*

Will be performed as described for WP2-T7 in the annual work plan for year 3.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.4	Determination of naturally transformable bacteria in tested environmental compartments (T2.5)	M44
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.5	Shotgun sequencing: ARG diversity in tested environmental compartments (T2.3.1)	M46
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6	16S metagenomics results: Microbial biodiversity and phylogenetic relationships of ARBs over ecosystem boundaries (T2.3, T2.6)	M46
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.7	Quantity and stability of free extracellular DNA observed in environmental compartments tested so far (T2.7)	M42
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.8	Annual report for Y4 (WP2)	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-14	Starting preparations for shotgun sequencing (T2.3.1)	M37

M-JRP15-FED-AMR-15	Stop: field sampling campaign (T2.3), DNA isolations (T2.7)	M40
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-16	Starting 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates. Batch format (T2.3)	M40
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-17	Start: Determination of naturally transformable bacteria (T2.5)	M41
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-18	Finalizing ARG qPCRs (T2.4)	M42
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-19	Finalizing determination of transformable bacteria (T2.5)	M44
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-20	Start: Assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6)	M43
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-21	Finalizing 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates (T2.3)	M46
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-22	Finalizing assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6)	M46
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-23	Finalizing shot gun sequencing and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of NGS data (T2.3.1, T3.2.2, T2.3)	M48
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-64	Finishing annual report (WP2)	M48

WP3: Elucidating the role of *Clostridium difficile* as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and its linkage between human and non-human (zoonotic) reservoirs
WP3 takes place over the third and the fourth year of the project

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M50

WP Leader: Mónica Oleastro (36-INSA)

Deputy WP Leader: Søren Persson (13-SSI)

WP participants: 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 14-UT, 20-IP, 36-INSA

Description of the WP: *C. difficile* is one of the most important causes of healthcare-associated infections worldwide, and is capable of causing significant enteric disease in various animal species, including farm animals. There is increasing evidence that *C. difficile* may have a foodborne or zoonotic etiology. In addition, AMR is frequently reported in epidemic *C. difficile* strains and is thought to play a major role in the infection and dissemination of this pathogen. *C. difficile* has also been suggested as a reservoir/receptor of resistance genes that might be transferred to other species in the host gut as well as in the environment. The existence of indistinguishable ribotypes and toxin gene profile is extensively described in the literature suggesting that zoonotic or anthropogenic transmission of *C. difficile* may be occurring, although the true extent of genetic overlap between these populations and the environment remains to be determined. Characterising the overlap of *C. difficile* genotypes in different reservoirs can improve our understanding of possible transmission routes of this pathogen and AMR associated determinants. This WP is organized into four tasks that will address the epidemiology of zoonotic *C. difficile*, the genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages, as well as its role as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries.

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP3-T2** - WGS and AMR characterization of human and non-human *C. difficile* isolates

Task start month: M34

Task end month: M46

Task Leader: Mónica Oleastro (36-INSA)

Deputy Task Leader: Sven Maurischat (9-BfR)

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 14-UT, 20-IP, 36-INSA

Description of the task: WGS and AMR characterization will be carried out for the zoonotic isolates identified among the consortium in task 3.1, and not previously characterized, as well as for the isolates obtained within the project, specifically in task 3.4. For determination of AMR profile, the outputs of project JRP1 IMPART (<https://onehealthejp.eu/projects/jrp1-impair/>), regarding the development of a suitable and cost-effective method for AMR surveillance of *C. difficile*, will be used to harmonise methods between the consortium participants. WGS will be performed by each participating partner.

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP3-T3** - Evaluation of the extent of genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages

Task start month: M41

Task end month: M50

Task Leader: Mónica Oleastro (36-INSA)

Deputy Task Leader: Søren Persson (13-SSI)

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 14-UT, 20-IP

Description of the task: Characterising the overlap of *C. difficile* genotypes in different reservoirs can improve our understanding of possible transmission routes of this pathogen. This aim of this task is to define the extent of genetic overlap and potential transmission between human and non-human lineages. Whole-genome sequencing data from strains isolated from different sources will be analysed in order to: i) infer the phylogenetic relationship between strains, through the alignment of genomes and extraction of core single-nucleotide variant positions, ii) describe the general trends of the core-genome determined within the dataset, and iii) identification of mobile genetic elements (MGE), such as prophages, transposons or plasmids, and potentially associated antimicrobial resistance (AR) determinants, using several assembly- and read-based tools (MGE: plasmidFinder, pATLAS, PHASTER; AR: Abricate, ARIBA) and public reference databases (NCBI, ResFinder, CARD). The required bioinformatics workflows are well established in the Bioinformatics Unit of INSA.

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP3-T4** - *C. difficile* / AMR dissemination between the human, animal and the environment: pig farm as a proof of concept

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M50

Task Leader: Christian Seyboldt (10-FLI)

Deputy Task Leader: Sven Maurischat (9-BfR)

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 14-UT, 20-IP, 36-INSA

Description of the task: The aim of this task is to evaluate *C. difficile* strains/AMR dissemination between humans, animals and the environment using the pig farm as proof of concept. *C. difficile* prevalence and variety regarding ribotypes and AMR profile will be described in the different compartments: the presence of zoonotic *C. difficile* ribotypes; presence of a variety of ribotypes; presence of *C. difficile* toxin-genes (tcdA, tcdB, cdt) and presence of AMR genes with possibility for exchange of these genes between *C. difficile* ribotypes and environments. Based on this information the compartments will be classified according to their possible role in *C. difficile* epidemiology, e.g. a compartment that contains a specific ribotype in higher numbers may be critical for dissemination. We expect to identify transmission networks for *C. difficile* and AMR dissemination and respective critical compartments.

Representative aliquots of samples collected in the course of WP2, from compartments 1, 2, 3, 9, 10 (Figure 1. Potential pathways for ARG dissemination over environmental ecosystem barriers) will be analysed for the presence of *C. difficile*. One aliquot will be used for toxicogenic culture,

consisting of an enrichment step in broth selective medium, followed by culture on agar selective medium, in anaerobic conditions. *C. difficile* colonies will then be tested for toxin genes by multiplex PCR. Toxicogenic isolates will be then characterized regarding ribotype, WGS and AMR.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP15–FED-AMR-WP3.2	Overview of genetic overlap between human and non-human <i>C. difficile</i> isolates (task 3.2 and task 3.3)	M50
D-JRP15–FED-AMR-WP3.3	Classification of pig farm compartments according to their role in the epidemiology of <i>C. difficile</i> (task 3.4).	M50

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP15–FED-AMR-26	Complete WGS on all included isolates	M46
M-JRP15–FED-AMR-27	Complete AMR profiles on all included isolates	M46
M-JRP15–FED-AMR-28	Genetic overlap-analysis human vs. non-human	M50
M-JRP15–FED-AMR-29	Identification of transmission network as described above	M50

WP4: Determination of the selection pressures in the tested compartments of human, animal and environmental ecosystems

WP4 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project (Y3, Y4, Y5). Tasks 4.1. and 4.2. take place in the first year (Y3). Tasks 4.3 - 4.7. take place over the first, second and third year of the project (Y3, Y4, Y5).

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M50

WP Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES).

Deputy WP Leader: Anna Gajda/Małgorzata Gbylik-Sikorska (34-PIWET).

WP participants: 2-AGES, 23-UoS, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA

In this WP selection pressures will be determined by the quantification of residues of antimicrobials (like tetracyclines, sulfonamides, macrolides and fluoroquinolones), herbicides, and heavy metals. Measurements of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples from participant countries will reveal their relationship to induction of competence in naturally transformable bacteria. The analysis of antibiotics in animal faeces is important to obtain more insight in the possible formation of bacterial resistance in the animals' gut. The quantification of antimicrobials will be performed with an Agilent Series 1200 HPLC system connected with an API 4000 triple quadrupole mass analyser with a TurbolonSpray source (Sciex, Canada) or on the UHPLC/HPLC Shimadzu Nexera X2 (Shi-madzu, Japan) system connected to the QTRAP®4500/QTRAP®5500 triplequadrupole mass spectrometer (Sciex, Framingham the USA); liquid chromatography - tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS).

Task JRP15-R2-WP4-T1 Selection of essential antimicrobials to be quantified in the tested compartments (published antibiotic consumption data, farmers' questionnaire, personal experience, expert interviews (veterinarians))

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M30

Task Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES)
Deputy Task Leader: Małgorzata Gbylik-Sikorska (34-PIWET)
Task Participants: 2-AGES, 23-UoS, 34-PIWET
Task finished in Y3

Task JRP15-R2-WP4-T2 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in aqueous matrices (water)

Task 4.2 start month: M31
Task 4.2 end month: M50
Task Leader: Anna Gajda/ Małgorzata Gbylik-Sikorska (34-PIWET)
Deputy Task Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES)
Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 25-NUIG, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA
Task is executed as described in WP4 T4.2 in year 3 (Y3)

Task JRP15-R2-WP4-T3 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in manure

Task start month: M31
Task end month: M50
Task Leader: Anna Gajda/Małgorzata Gbylik-Sikorska (34-PIWET)
Deputy Task Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES)
Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA
Task is executed as described in WP4 T4.2 in year 3 (Y3)

Task JRP15-R2-WP4-T4 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in faeces

Task start month: M35
Task end month: M50
Task Leader: Anna Gajda/Małgorzata Gbylik-Sikorska (34-PIWET)
Deputy Task Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES)
Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA
For technical details on the execution of this task see task 4.2.

Task JRP15-R2-WP4-T5 Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in soil

Task start month: M31.
Task end month: M50.
Task Leader: Anna Gajda/Małgorzata Gbylik-Sikorska (34-PIWET).
Deputy Task Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES).
Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA
For technical details on the execution of this task see task 4.2.

Task JRP15-R2-WP4-T6 Quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil

Task start month: M31.
Task end month: M50.
Task Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES).
Deputy Task Leader: Adriana Cabal Rosel (2-AGES).
Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 36-INSA.

In this task a representative list of herbicides will be quantified by an AGES associated sister company (UBA: Environmental Protection Agency in Vienna) according to established in-house/standard protocols.

Task JRP15-R2-WP4-T7 Measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples gathered across participants countries

Task start month: M31

Task end month: M50

Task Leader: Mónica Felipe-Sotelo (23-UoS).

Deputy Task Leader: Martin Brandtner (2-AGES).

Task Participants: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT, 23-UoS, 36-INSA

In this task the sample preparation involves replicate procedures and different chemical methods depending on the 'nature' of the sample. All bio-materials (fluids/tissues, plants) are dried at 80°C or 6 hours (to constant weight). The samples will be analysed by an Agilent 7700 inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer. The resultant data is checked for accuracy and precision by Excel and the subsequent sample data is calculated (blank and internal standard checked) to produce the final database of elemental values for statistical analysis

Deliverables

See year 3 and 5

Milestones

See year 3

WP5: Identification of environmental conditions modulating transformation frequencies in soil microcosms and an *in vitro* porcine gut model (poGutMo) (laboratory studies).

WP5 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

T5.1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project. T5.1 is split into 4 sub-tasks, each lasting 2-3 months. T5.2 takes place over the second and the third year of the project. T5.2 is split into 3 sub-tasks, each representing a block of experiments that build iteratively with input from WP4 and input from, and output to, WP6. The first 2 sub-tasks take place in the second year and the final sub-task takes place in the third year. T5.3 takes place over the second and the third year of the project.

WP start month: M32

WP end month: M52

WP Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy WP Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

WP participants: 23-UoS

Description of the WP: The focus of this work package will be novel work to assess the environmental effects on transformation and conjugation frequencies in a porcine gut model (poGutMo). The experiments described in **Task 1** will be performed in the absence of the selective pressure of antibiotics or herbicides to establish baseline levels of HGT in the model organisms (*E. coli* and *Clostridium*) arising from transformation and conjugation, respectively. As we are also interested in the role of trace/heavy metals in driving HGT, we shall subject a portion of each sample taken from the poGutMo to ICP-MS (WP4) so we can relate the frequency of HGT by transformation and conjugation to the concentration of metals within the sample. Work undertaken in WP4 and WP6 will identify the most likely drivers of HGT through transformation and the emergence of AMR. We suspect these will be a combination antibiotic/herbicide and heavy metals, including other environmental conditions that favour the development of transformation competence. These candidate drivers will be evaluated in the gut model in **Task 2** using the approaches described for T1, but this time supplementing the poGutMo with appropriate concentrations of antibiotic,

herbicide, cation. **Task 3** will establish a soil microcosm according to Trevors et al., 1990, and test the effects of environmental stimuli on transformation of *E. coli*.

MC will take responsibility for delivery of this WP to time and to budget. Should he be absent for any reason, this responsibility will be undertaken by RLR. The laboratory work will be undertaken by the PDRA who will meet weekly with MC and/or RLR to review progress. The PDRA will be supported in the laboratory by other PDRAs working the gut models in the group of RLR.

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP5-T1-ST2** Determine the optimal growth parameters for cultivating *E. coli* strains within the gut model

Sub-Task start month: M39

Sub-Task end month: M39

Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP5-T1-ST3** Rates of transconjugation calculated by taking samples from the gut model and plating on TSC agar plates supplemented with the appropriate antibiotics

Sub-Task start: M41

Sub-Task end month: M45

Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP5-T1-ST4** Plasmid transfer rates via bacterial conjugation will be calculated using the endpoint method

Sub-Task start month: M36

Sub-Task end month: M46

Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP5-T2** Evaluate conditions that drive HGT and the emergence of AMR via transformation

Task start month: M45

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy Task Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

Task Participants: 23-UoS

Description of the task: Work undertaken in WP4 and WP6 will identify the most likely drivers of HGT through transformation and the emergence of AMR. We suspect these will be a combination antibiotic/herbicide and heavy metals, including other environmental conditions that favour the development of transformation competence. These candidate drivers will be evaluated in the gut model in **Task 2** using the approaches described for T1, but this time supplementing the poGutMo with appropriate concentrations of antibiotic, herbicide, cation.

Depending on the antibiotics identified for testing in WP2 and WP4, we shall make sub-strains of *E. coli* with appropriate antibiotic resistances by inserting the required resistance gene(s) into the chromosome. Chromosomal DNA and lysates will then be derived from these strains for introduction into the gut model. Results from these experiments regarding **the impact these drivers have on HGT and AMR through transformation in contrast to conjugation** will be used to inform the model development work undertaken through WP6.

In total we envisage three experiments (sT2.1-2.3) with a one month gap between the first and second and between the second and third, during which time the experimental findings will be fed into the model development and the outputs from the models used to refine the test conditions for the next poGutMo experiment. This iterative approach of modelling, controlled testing, and model refinement is a particular strength of our approach.

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP5-T2-ST1** Iterative evaluation of candidate drivers (antibiotic, herbicide, cation) of HGT evaluated in the gut model – round 1

Sub-Task start month: M45

Sub-Task end month: M50

Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP5-T2-ST2** Iterative evaluation of candidate drivers (antibiotic, herbicide, cation) of HGT evaluated in the gut model – round 2

Sub-Task start month: M50

Sub-Task end month: M54

Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP5-T3** Effect of different environmental conditions on the expression of competence genes in *E. coli* determined using soil microcosms

Task start month: M44

Task end month: M52

Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Deputy Task Leader: Roberto La Ragione (23-UoS)

Task Participants: 23-UoS

Description of the task: will establish a soil microcosm according to Trevors et al., 1990 and test the effects of environmental stimuli on transformation of *E. coli*.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.5	Conjugation-mediated HGT between the clostridial donor and recipient strains within the gut model determined	M44
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.6	Results from using chromosomal DNA derived from <i>E. coli</i> as ARG donor	M43
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.7	Results from using lysate of <i>E. coli</i> as ARG donor	M44
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.8	Clostridial transconjugates characterised by whole-genome sequencing	M44
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.9	Results from pig gut model regarding HGT by transformation and conjugation in presence of selected antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals	M49
D-JRP17-FED-AMR-WP5.10	Results from pig gut model regarding HGT by transformation and conjugation in presence of selected antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals	M53
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.11	First results from soil microcosm experiments on effects of environmental conditions on transformation	M47

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
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M-JRP15-FED-AMR-40	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M41
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-41	Antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals most likely to drive HGT through transformation supplied to UoS.	M47
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-42	Sub-strains of <i>E. coli</i> with appropriate antibiotic resistances made and chromosomal DNA and lysates prepared	M36
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-43	Porcine gut model set up using faecal samples obtained through WP2, samples stored for trace element analysis (WP4) – experiments can start	M40
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-44	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M42
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-45	DNA sent for whole-genome sequencing	M43
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-46	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M43
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-47	Deliver results from 1 st round of gut model experiments to WP6 leader for further modelling	M45
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-48	Results from modelling in WP6 communicated to inform parameters for use in 2 nd round of gut model experiments	M46
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-49	Deliver results from 2 nd round of gut model experiments to WP6 leader for further modelling	M50
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-50	Results from modelling in WP6 communicated to inform parameters for use in 3 rd and final round of gut model experiments	M51

WP6 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. It consists of two tasks (T6.1 and T6.2).

WP6 Probabilistic and mechanistic models of the links between antimicrobial usage in animals, AMR in the environment, and the risks for public health.

WP start month: M32

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: Giovanni Lo Iacono (23-UoS)

Deputy WP Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

WP participants: 23-UoS

Description of the WP: In line with Objective O5, WP6 is intrinsically multidisciplinary. Accordingly, we will use mathematical modelling and machine learning as a powerful tool to:

- i) *Detect relevant variables (predictors) which can predict observed appearance and transmission of ARGs in different environmental compartments (Task 6.1).* To address Objective 4, in Task 6.1 we will use a machine learning approach, trained with data provided by WP4 and WP5 to identify the most relevant drivers of AMR emergence by analysing phenotypic and genotypic markers of AMR in association with environmental conditions, such as use of antibiotic and/or herbicide and trace element concentrations.
- ii) *Gain insight of the mechanisms underlying transmission dynamics of resistant bacteria (Task 6.2).* Microbiological communities (either within host or in the natural environment) are affected by the external environmental drivers (e.g. temperature and pH) and by mutual influences within the community (e.g. competition for resources). Both factors impact on the spatiotemporal patterns of the community, potentially leading to the extinction/establishment of specific (e.g. resistant) microorganisms. In Task 6.2, we will develop and apply models to investigate if and how the resilience of microbiological communities changes when subjected to: i) different external drivers and ii) internal drivers

represented, for instance by richer biodiversity; this last point will provide a theoretical testing of Hypothesis H2. Furthermore, we will investigate how perturbation of the environmental drivers (which we can reproduce in the porcine gut model, Task 5.1) can critically reduce/enhance the population of specific microorganism (1). This will lead to a better understanding of the mechanism, at population level, of extinction/emergence and transmission dynamics of resistant microorganisms (in line with objective O1 in WP2). The WP will also help in understanding some macro-ecological relationships observed in the gut (2) and potentially relevant to other systems.

iii) *Assess and identify associated risks to public health and strategies to mitigate these (Task 6.1 and 6.2).*

The WP will identify relevant environmental drivers (i.e. risk factors) of observed AMR. It will elucidate the possible mechanism leading to the observed spatiotemporal dynamics (increasing/decreasing the risk) of the microbiological communities. The modelling approach can be formulated and applied to within-host microbiological communities (e.g. in the gut) or in the natural environment (e.g. in soil). In the latter case, as these dynamics depends on environmental drivers which are varying geographically, the task is relevant to objective O3. Insights from the model will provide crucial information for risk management options for public health (WP6).

Finally, understanding how environmental perturbations affect the extinction or establishment of a pathogen will provide risk management options for the control of disease (e.g. developing a protocol which maximizes efficiency in the use of antibiotics by identifying optimal temporal patterns in their deployment (1)).

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP6-T1**

Task start month: M32

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Giovanni Lo Iacono (23-UoS)

Deputy Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Task Participants: 23-UoS

Description of the task: **A Machine Learning Approach for AMR phenotype prediction and gene sequence analysis.** This task will focus on developing mathematical and machine learning models that will shorten the time and will significantly reduce the cost and resources required for the identification of AMR. This will be performed by analysing large volumes of genomic data and by detecting and interpreting the complex associations between the underlying AMR phenotypes. We will create methods that will allow to identify and predict which genes will contribute AMR.

Overall machines learn in two ways: by example or by experience. To create effective machine learning models in this domain we will create classification models that will predict AMR phenotypes by learning the genetic signatures. The existing models in this domain rely on probabilistic models such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) or Deep Learning models such as deep convolutional neural networks. The probabilistic models usually have several parameters that need to be set appropriately to allow the model perform at its best and this usually make it difficult to train models that can deal with changes in the data or work effectively with noisy data and missing values (which is common in real world datasets). The deep learning models often require large number of samples, can become overfit and their findings is not easy to interpret (as they do not provide any strong theoretical foundation for their outcomes). In this task we will create semi-supervised machine learning models that will use large volume of unlabelled data to learn and extract the features and complex interplays underlying these features and will then create probabilistic classifiers to learn from the existing labelled data (i.e. example) to predict the genomic signatures that cause AMR.

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP6-T1-ST2**

Data Integration, Annotation and Association Analysis. This sub-task will focus on integration of genomic and AMR data from multiple sources. We will use entropy based models and mutual information measures to identify the associations and determine AMR related phenotypes.

Sub-Task start month: M38

Sub-Task end month: M48

Sub-Task Leader: Giovanni Lo Iacono (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

Task: JRP15-R2-**WP6-T2**

Task start month: M32

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Giovanni Lo Iacono (23-UoS)

Deputy Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Task Participants: 23-UoS

Description of the task: T6.2 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. T6.2 is split into 2 sub-tasks, representing two broad specific scientific questions identified in point (ii) in the description of the WP6 ("Gain insight of the mechanisms.."); these issues will be investigated in parallel with point (iii) to identify which mechanisms and how they are potentially responsible for increasing the risk for public health. Sub-tasks T6.2.1 takes place over the first year of the project for 15 months. Sub-tasks T6.2.2 takes place over the second-half of the second year for the remaining 15 months to the end of the project.

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP6-T2.1**

In this subtask we will address two questions:

a) What is the resilience of microbial communities in the different situations (e.g. environmental conditions, geographical compartments, etc.)

b) How is resilience affected by the diversity and 'richness' of the microbial community? (H1)

Resilience is the ability of a community to recover from perturbation. Example of perturbations are the introduction of an antibiotic targeting particular bacteria in the gut, or fluctuations in temperature affecting the survival of free-living bacteria in the soil. Resilience is expected to depend on environmental drivers and also on the richness and diversity of the community.

Inspired by models of ecological communities (3), we will develop a dynamic model for the population of the micro-organism (either within host or in the environment) as a set of differential equations, to track the changes in the abundance of each microbiological subpopulation (e.g. bacterial species or aggregated species if their number is too large). Important interaction mechanisms, such as competition for shared resources, will be included. Resilience will be studied by investigating the stability of solutions in different settings similar to what has been done previously (4).

GL will supervise the task while an appointed PDRA will lead the work. We will interact with relevant member of the consortium (e.g. MAC, PA) for refinement of scientific questions, formulation of assumptions, feedback on the modelling approach and results etc.

Sub-Task start month: M32

Sub-Task end month: M41

Sub-Task Leader: Giovanni Lo Iacono (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

Sub-Task: JRP15-R2-**WP6-T2.2**

In this subtask we will investigate *How a periodic perturbation in the drivers (e.g. temperature or pH, identified in WP4) affects the dynamics of the microbial community and whether this can be the origin of the emergence of new strains.*

We want to understand if and how the evolution of a pathogen can be delayed/accelerated by temporal fluctuations (resulting in bottlenecks) occurring in the system (1). According to the model (1), large fluctuations in a dynamic system can enhance extinction of the pathogen, especially of the emerging mutant strains. Furthermore, periodically forced systems oscillate at larger amplitude at some frequencies than at others (resonance), then by adequately perturbing the system we can cause massive fluctuations in the small pathogen population increasing the chances of extinction. To address this point, we will analyse the data produced in the porcine gut model (in Task 5.1) by using wavelet analysis (5) (we will ensure that the temporal domain is long enough). The technique will detect potential natural frequencies of the system, i.e. the frequency at which a system tends to oscillate in the absence of any driving or damping force.

Identifying the existence of natural frequencies in a microbial community is already an important result *per se*, in addition we will link the data with the model to investigate how these frequencies depend on the relevant parameters (e.g. growth rate of bacterial species).

Finally, if feasible, we propose to use the gut model in Task 5.1 to alternate the external drivers (e.g. source of nutrient) according to the natural frequencies of the system and thus test the hypothesis that the perturbation will cause massive fluctuations. If this will be experimentally confirmed, we could exploit the source of temporal fluctuations to alleviate the disease, reduce chemical control or drugs, and in general, mitigate the risk of developing highly harmful pathogens (e.g. superbugs insensitive to antibiotics).

For the modelling part, GL will supervise the task while an appointed PDRA will lead the work. MAC and the appointed PDRA in WP5 will lead the experimental part in the gut model.

Sub-Task start month: M40

Sub-Task end month: M54

Sub-Task Leader: Giovanni Lo Iacono (23-UoS)

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Mark Chambers (23-UoS)

Sub-Task Participants: 23-UoS

1. G. Lo Iacono, F. van den Bosch, C. A. Gilligan, *PLoS Comp. Bio.* **9**, e1002870 (2013).
2. B. W. Ji, R. U. Sheth, P. D. Dixit, D. Vitkup, *bioRxiv.* **1**, 370676 (2018).
3. R. M. (Robert M. May, *Stability and complexity in model ecosystems* (Princeton University Press, second., 2001).
4. G. Lo Iacono *et al.*, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 201803264 (2018).

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.4	Submission/publication of 1/2 paper(s) on how resilience of microbial communities depends on external environmental drivers and richness and diversity of the community.	M44
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5	Main code for the mathematical modelling made available in public repository (e.g. GitHub) with associated documentation (which can be used as "Material and Method" section of the forthcoming publications).	M44
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.6	Update of codes and documentations in public repository (e.g. GitHub).	M50

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
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M-JRP15-FED-AMR-56	Literature review on fluctuating ecological systems and gut model approach.	M45
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-57	Analysis of data produced from the 1 st round of gut model experiments. Formulation and implementation of the model to identify how natural fluctuations depend on the drivers. Results communicated to WP5 leader.	M46
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-58	Analysis of data produced from the 2 nd round of gut model experiments. Formulation and implementation of the model to identify how natural fluctuations depend on the drivers. Results communicated to WP5 leader.	M50
M-JRP15-FED-AMR-59	Application of the model to address specific questions and dissemination of findings in peer-reviewed publications and conferences.	M50

2.4.2.1.13 JRP05-R1-ET1-TOXdetect

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		ET 1: Development and harmonisation of non-NGS-based methods for detection of FBZ agents and emerging threats								
Research Project Title		Development and harmonization of innovativemethods for comprehensive analysis of food-borne toxigenic bacteria, ie. Staphylococci, Bacillus cereus and Clostridium perfringens								
Research Project Acronym		TOX-Detect								
Leading Organisation		P1-Anses			Deputy Leading Organisation			P1-Anses		
Project Leader		JA Hennekinne			Deputy Project leader			Yacine Nia		
Project Start month		M1			Project End month			M42		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	11,6		9,27				3			
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM							4,6	6,77		
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAMI	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM	3,2									
<p>This document describes the work planned on the additional period of 6 months obtained for Tox-Detect project. The principal objective of this extended period is to perform the remaining tasks, especially methods transfer and inter-laboratory comparison tests.</p> <p>WP2, WP3 and WP4 deliverables are extended until month 36. Therefore, tasks dedicated to the development of methods and (WP3 and WP4) and those of WP2 should be finished on M36, as agreed during the annual meeting organized on 15 et 16 January 2020.</p>										
<p>Description of work:</p> <p>WP0 Coordination, management and communication</p>										

WPO continues based upon what was achieved during the first and second annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M0

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: Yacine Nia (P1)

Deputy WP Leader:

WP participants: P1, P4, P9, P18, P19

Description of the WP:

General management strategy

During the year 4, management structures, implemented during the 3 first years will be conserved. Tasks supported/dedicated to project coordinator (PC) and work Package Leader (WPL) will be also conserved during the year 4.

Jacques Antoine Hennekinne PC and WPL 6 left ANSES in 31 August 2020. Yacine NIA, which was coordinator deputy, will support the coordination of Tox-Detect project during year 4. Also, M Gohar which was WPL 6 deputy, will support the coordination of WP6 during year 4.

Meetings and reports

Although electronic communication will be used extensively for the implementation of the WPs and the management of the project, face-to-face meetings will be organised depending on Covid19 crisis.

Consortium meetings with partners will take place at the end of the project (wrap-up meeting, meeting 3).

During year 4. Minutes and reports on all formal meetings and decisions will be distributed to all partners.

Although the coordinator has overall responsibility for the preparation of the financial reports, it is the sole responsibility of each participating institution to ensure proper accounting and timely reporting to the PC and the EJP. As link between the project contractors and the EJP, the coordinator will be responsible for scientific reporting to the EJP.

Risk management

Due to covid 19 crisis, changes necessary in order to deliver milestones delays and problems in achieving the milestones will be reported in advance of partner meetings by the WPL, including a suggestion for alternative strategies.

During the year 4, only modifications to the WP5, which depend on the availability of the method developed in WP1, WP3 and WP4, could occur. A general "additional meeting" will be organized during M38 in order to exchange information on the progress of the transfer of methods, their implementation and progress of interlaboratory tests organisation.

- **Task 0.1: General coordination and management of the project (administrative and financial)**

T0.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of EJP.

- **Task 0.5: Organisation of four face-to-face meetings with all partners.**

- T0.5 Meeting 3: results of technical WP3, WP4 and WP5 and overall results of the project
- T0.5 will takes place at the end of the EJP.*

- **Task 0.6: mandatory reports on network activities: interim activity report, final report**

T0.6 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third period of the EJP.

Ref	Title	Initial due month	New proposed due month
Deliverables			
D0.7	Report of additional	Not programed	M39
D0.5	Report of meeting 3	M36	M42
D0.6	Final report	M36	M45

WP2. Characterization of toxins/virulence factors

WP start month: M4

WP end month: M39

WP Leader: Nalini Rama-Rao (P18)

Deputy WP Leader: Kevin Hogeveen (P1)

WP participants: P1, P18, P19

This WP2 is not concerned by the additional period. End of WP2 expected on M 36.

WP3. Development of Mass Spectrometry-based proteomics procedures for detection of bacterial toxins and virulence factors

WP start month: M4

WP end month: M36 (**should be achieved on M36**)

WP Leader: Julien Masquelier (P4)

WP participants: P1, P4, P18, P19

Task T3.1: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of new enterotoxins (eg SEG, SEH, SEI) from *S. aureus*

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M36 (**should be achieved on M36**)

Task Leader: Julien Masquelier (P4)

Task Participants: P1, P4

Task T3.2: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *B. cereus*

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M36 (**should be achieved on M36**)

Task Leader: Julia Chamot-Rooke (P19)

Task Participants: P1, P4, P19

Task T3.3: development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *C. perfringens*

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M36 (**should be achieved on M36**)

Task Leader: Michel Hebraud (P18)

Task Participants: P1, P18, P19

Task T3.4. Transfer of LC-MS/MS methods

Task start month: M36

Task end month: M39

Task Leader: Julien Masquelier (P4)

Task Participants: P1, P4, P18, P19

Description of the task:

The new LC-MS/MS methods developed will be in-house validated. For each analytical method, a detailed analytical protocol and validation report will be written. These protocols will include all QA criteria, which have to be fulfilled for a sensitive and reliable analysis. Among others, these QA parameters are scope definition, analytical range, chromatographic separation/selectivity, sensitivity - Control of LOD and LOQ, control of the calibration standards and exchange of standard solutions, recovery of the isotopically labelled internal standards (if available), matrix additions experiments at regular intervals, duplo analysis at regular intervals, control of the blank concentrations/ blank samples, quality control during analyses. Once validated the methods will be transferred to the partners of the WP3 in order to test applicability of the methods before further implementation in WP5. As an important step towards harmonisation of technical approaches, performance criteria for those developed analytical techniques will be defined. This will be requirement set up for WP5 participants.

Ref	Title	Initial due month	New proposed due month
Deliverables			
D3.4	Report on the performance criteria for method harmonisation	M 30	M 40
Milestones			
MS3.3	Methods transferred to partners	M 30	M 39

WP4. Development of new immuno-enzymatic assays for detection of *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence determinants

WP4 continues based upon what was achieved during the first and second annual period of the EJP.

WP start month: M4

WP end month: M40

WP Leader: Stephen Marino (P9) Michel Gohar (P18)

WP participants: P1, P4, P9, P18, P33

Task T4.1. Development of quantitative immunoassays for five known *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence factors

T4.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first and second annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M4

Task end month: M36 (**should be achieved on M36**)

Task Leader: Stephen Marino (P9)

Deputy Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Task Participants: P9, P18

Task T4.2. Development of a quantitative immunoassay on a new *B. cereus* toxin or virulence factor

Task start month: M18

Task end month: M36 (**should be achieved on M36**)

Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Task Participants: P18

Ref	Title	Initial due month	New proposed due month
Deliverables			
D4.1.	Report on the immuno-enzymatic assays	M 33	M 40
Milestones			
MS4.7	Immuno-enzymatic assays transferred to partners	M 33	M 39

WP5. Inter-laboratory ring trial scheme

WP start month: M 33

WP end month: M 42

WP Leader: Yacine Nia (P1)

Deputy WP Leader: Manon Michaut (P1)

WP participants: P1, P4, P9, P18, P19, P33

Description of the WP:

Background and objectives

The inter-lab comparison tests will enable the transfer of the methods developed in this project to different partners within the consortium and will allow the identification of success factors critical for bacterial strains characterization and detection of their toxins. They will also help in identification of “best practices” for the analysis of these toxins. Based on the results and evaluation of the inter-lab tests, an identification of critical gaps in the detection technology, both under qualitative and quantitative aspects will be carried out. These ring tests are prerequisite for the use of the developed methods in routine analysis in the longer term.

Eight inter-laboratory comparison tests will be organized in order to check performance of (i) MALDI-ToF based analysis for a selection of reference bacterial strains as established in the frame of the WP1, and (ii) Mass Spectrometry methods and immuno-enzymatic assays developed in the framework of WP3 and WP4, respectively.

Approach

The inter-laboratory comparison tests will be organized in order to transfer and assess the methods established or developed in WP1, WP3, and WP4. In total, 8 inter-lab tests will be organized within the framework of WP5 and more than 8 laboratories from the EJP project will participate. As the methods tested will be developed by a few laboratories from a limited number of instruments, the inter-lab tests will be performed at a larger scope using various additional instruments, with some variations expected according to the method. The differences in the results obtained from the participating laboratories will be analyzed in depth in order to optimize the interpretation procedures of raw data and develop more robust methods. This will also be a basis for harmonization of the methods by establishing the general criteria. Results of the inter-lab tests will not be used therefore as a certification of the participating laboratory’s proficiency.

The 8 inter-lab tests will be organized and planned in year 4 of the project, after the complete transfer and the successful implementation of the methods by the participating laboratories. For MALDI-ToF and Mass Spectrometry based methods, the inter-lab comparison tests will be organized to evaluate the methods performance for detection of the three pathogens (i.e. CPS, Bc and Cp) and their toxins (10 to 15 strains or culture supernatants in total per pathogen) while for immuno-enzymatic assays, the inter-lab comparison tests will be organized to evaluate the detection capabilities of the participants for two CPS toxins and three *B. cereus* toxins. The final selection of

the toxins to be assessed in WP5 will be confirmed after the deliverables from linked WPs (i.e. WP3 and WP4).

These inter-lab tests will be prepared according to the regulation ISO/IEC 17043 (inter-lab test announcement, tests schedules, instructions for the participants, samples preparation and identification, homogeneity and stability studies, reporting forms...). The WP5 leader will prepare the inter-lab tests documents according to this regulation, and task leaders will adapt them to the specific characteristics of each method. For each inter-lab test, an organizer and a list of participants have been identified. The organizer will prepare the inter-lab items, perform the homogeneity and stability tests, and organize the dispatch of items. The organizer will prepare together the inter-lab evaluation report. If needed, possibly further collaborators within the EU-RL/NRLs network or other laboratories will be invited to participate to the trials. Finally, a final report including the results and assessment of the eight inter-lab tests will be prepared by the WP5 leader.

Task T5.1. Inter-lab test on Maldi-ToF for species identification

Task start month: M 36

Task end month: M 42

Task Leader: Taran Skjerdal (P33)

Deputy Task Leader: /

Task Participants: P1, P4, P9, P19, P33

Description of the task:

For Maldi-Tof, the inter-laboratory comparison testing will be organized for the three pathogens: *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* (10 to 15 strains in total/pathogen).

Task T5.2. Inter-lab test on LC-MS/MS

Task start month: M 36

Task end month: M 42

Task Leader: Julien Masquelier(P4)

Deputy Task Leader: /

Task Participants: P1, P4, P18, P19

Description of the task:

For Mass Spectrometry, the inter-laboratory comparison testing will be organized for the three pathogens: *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* (10 to 15 culture supernatants in total/pathogen).

Task T5.3. Inter-lab test on immuno-enzymatic assays

Task start month: M 36

Task end month: M 42

Task Leader: Manon Michaut (P1)

Deputy Task Leader: /

Task Participants: P1, P4, P18, P33

Description of the task:

For immuno-enzymatic assays, the inter-laboratory comparison testing will be organized for two *S. aureus* toxins, and three bacillus toxins/factors (contained within culture supernatants)

Ref	Title	Initial due month	New proposed due month
Deliverables			
D5.2	Final report including results from the eight inter-lab tests	M34	M45
Milestones			
MS5.2	Dispatch of samples and evaluation report to be filled by partners	M 27	M37

MS5.3	Samples analysed by partners	M 34	M42
MS5.4	Dispatch of final report	M 34	M45

WP6. Dissemination, protection and exploitation of results

WP6 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP.

WP start month: M 0

WP end month: M 45

WP Leader: Michel Gohar (P18)

Deputy WP Leader:

WP participants: P1, P4, P9, P18, P19, P33

Description of the WP:

As described in WP0, the partners will set up a committee, composed of at least one representative from each partner, which will be in charge of evaluating the results, and suggesting appropriate means of protection and valorization of the results. For results concerning fundamental research or public health, the results are meant to be freely published through both oral presentations and publications in open access journals. If some of the results may constitute an invention which can be protected by a patent application, publication will be delayed until the proper protection is sought. If results might be commercially exploited, the committee will be in charge of suggesting plans for their exploitation (choice of a party in charge of valorization, actions for finding one or several commercial exploitation partners). Exploitation, ruled by a commercial exploitation license, will include a fair financial return for the (co)owners. If an application is predicted, the patents service of the institutions hosting the research teams associated to the discovery will also be consulted, to obtain help with the administrative tasks linked to filing a patent. A consortium agreement will also be prepared by the partners that will detail the rules concerning intellectual property rights, classification of results stemming from the project and their valorization.

Partners, through their respective valorization departments, will take appropriate decisions to protect results and to file a patent regarding the developed assays. The scientific and technico-economic outcome of these findings will be assessed by realizing a technico-economic study of the trade environment, of the technological and legal constraints, and of the market expectations. An analysis of the freedom to operate will be performed, in which the filed patent dependence upon patents held by third parties will be examined. Partners will also search for industrial partners, by elaborating and distributing technological offers to targeted private firms. Terms and conditions of the technology transfer (license or license option according to development stage of the invention) will be negotiated with industrial partners. A support group will be organized to follow up the administrative and financial issues of the contractant, and to keep the invention on the forefront of the technology. Results not directly involved in the patent filing will be published in open access peer-reviewed journals and presented in international meetings.

Task T6.1: dissemination of information within the partners

T6.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M 0

Task end month: M 45

Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P19)

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: all participants involved

Description of the task:

Based on the developed methods, an exchange of standard operating procedures and tools will be initiated, wherever possible.

Task T6.2: dissemination of information to the outside.

T6.2. continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M 0

Task end month: M 42

Task Leader: Michel Gohar (P19)

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: all participants involved

Description of the task:

Presentation of network activities at international conferences (talks, posters, flyer) and to respective national and international decision makers in different networks and institutions

Publication of results in open access peer-reviewed journals.

Ref	Title	Initial due month	New proposed due month
Deliverables			
D6.1	Dispatch of SOPs	M33	M36
D6.2	Dissemination of results (publications, conferences...)	M36	M 42
Milestones			
MS6.1	Final report dispatched	M36	M 45

2.4.2.1.14 JRP16-R2-ET2.2-TELE-Vir

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		ET 2.2: Development of a toolkit to characterize emerging threats by combining genomic and phenotypic information								
Research Project Title		Point-of-incidence toolbox for emerging virus threats								
Research Project Acronym		TELE-Vir								
Leading Organisation		P13-SSI			Deputy Leading Organisation			P16-INIA		
Project Leader		Anders Fomsgaard			Deputy Project leader			Jovita Fernández-Pinero		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	13		5,5			0				
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	29			3,7						
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	9,7					18,5	0,5			
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PM	1,66	7		26,31					6	
<p>Objectives: The overall objective is to develop a very fast point-of-incidence (poi) toolbox for identification and characterization of potentially all emerging virus threats for humans and/or domestic and wildlife animals.</p>										
<p>Description of work for the second year of the project</p> <p>WP1: Coordination and data management WP start month: M25 WP end month: M54 WP Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI Deputy WP Leader: Miguel Ángel Jiménez-Clavero, INIA WP participants: All</p>										

Description of the WP1: WP1 is the coordination WP and takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the TELE-Vir project.

WP1 is divided into 6 tasks:

WP1-T1: Coordination and project management

WP1-T2: Data management

WP1-T3: Kick-off-meeting at IZSAM, Italy

WP1-T4: 1st TELE-Vir meeting at Sciensano, Belgium

WP1-T5: 2nd TELE-Vir meeting at SSI, Denmark

WP1-T6: Poi-Toolbox workshop

Description of the WP1-Tasks for the 2nd year of the TELE-Vir project:

WP1-T1: Coordination and project management

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Deputy Task Leader: Miguel Ángel Jiménez-Clavero, INIA

Task Participants: All

Description of the WP1-T1: WP1-T1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. The main tasks of WP1-T1 are;

- 1) Overall project management including contact to OHEJP, reporting to OHEJP etc.
- 2) Coordinate regular telecoms between the participating laboratories
- 3) Write project newsletters to participants

WP1-T2: Data management

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Deputy Task Leader: Miguel Ángel Jiménez-Clavero, INIA

Task Participants: All

Description of the WP1-T2: WP1-T2 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. The main tasks of WP1-T2 are;

- 1) Development of a TELE-Vir data management plan (DMP)
- 2) Continuously updating of the TELE-Vir DMP

WP1-T4: 1st TELE-Vir at Sciensano, Belgium

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M38

Task Leader: Steven Van Borm, Sciensano

Deputy Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Task Participants: ALL

Description of the WP1-T4: WP1-T4 takes place over the second year of the project. The main task of WP1-T4 is to;

- 1) Organize and host the 1st TELE-Vir meeting in Belgium in January 2021

WP1-T6: Poi-Toolbox workshop

Task start month: M44

Task end month: M49

Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Deputy Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA

Task Participants: ALL

Description of the WP1-T6: WP1-T6 takes place over the second and third year of the project. The main tasks of WP1-T6 are to;

- 1) Organize the 3 day workshop in the Poi-toolbox in Copenhagen, Denmark in January 2022
- 2) Train all participants in the poi protocol for MinION sequencing in the field
- 3) Train all participants in the poi data analysis

WP2: Development of a Bioinformatics tool-kit for POI data analysis

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA

Deputy WP Leader: Daniel Horton, UoS

WP Participants: INSA, UoS

Description of the WP2: WP2 is the bioinformatics WP and takes place over the first, second and third year of the project.

The goal is to develop an open-sourced bioinformatics platform that allows the user-friendly handling of high-throughput sequencing data (second and third generation) for detection and monitoring of viral emerging threats.

WP2 is divided into 5 tasks:

WP2-T1: Survey and collection of databases for genotype-phenotype associations

WP2-T2: Development of bioinformatics modules for third-generation sequencing analysis and pathogen identification

WP2-T3: Development of bioinformatics modules for sequence curation and phenotypic association

WP2-T4: Development of bioinformatics modules for genomic and metadata integration towards enhanced surveillance

WP2-T5: Development of a user- and surveillance-oriented web-based interface

Description of the WP2-Tasks for the 2nd year of the TELE-Vir project:

WP2-T2: Development of bioinformatics modules for third-generation sequencing analysis and pathogen identification

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M39

Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA

Deputy Task Leader: Daniel Horton, UoS

Task Participants: INSA, UoS

Description of the WP2-T2: WP2-T2 takes place over the first and second year of the project.

The main tasks of WP2-T2 are:

- 1) Upgrade existing platform for third generation sequencing data (from reads quality assessment and improvement to de novo assembly- and reference-based analysis);
- 2) Implement methods for automatic pathogen identification/confirmation and *in silico* traditional sub-typing (when applicable), for viral pathogens other than influenza;

WP2-T3: Development of bioinformatics modules for sequence curation and phenotypic association

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA

Deputy Task Leader: Daniel Horton, UoS

Task Participants:

Description of the WP2-T3: WP2-3 takes place over the first and second year of the project.

The main tasks of WP2-T3 are:

- 1) Upgrade existing platform with functionalities for robust gene/genome sequence curation/analysis (i.e., generation of consensus sequences, SNP/indel identification, minor variants detection) based on both reference- and/or de novo assembly. This will involve the expansion of the existing modules for influenza virus available at the platform INSaFLU, so that the toolbox can deal with multiple virus
- 2) Develop tools for screening/validation of phenotypically informative mutations (by querying, for instance, virus-specific mutation databases for antigenicity and drug susceptibility prediction). We will investigate the feasibility and reliability of inferring biochemical and immunological properties of mutations using existing molecular dynamics models and machine learning approaches that are already being tested at UoS.

WP2-T4: Development of bioinformatics modules for genomic and metadata integration towards enhanced surveillance

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Daniel Horton, UoS

Deputy Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA

Task Participants:

Description of the WP2-T4: WP2-4 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project.

The main tasks of WP2-T4 are:

- 1) Upgrade existing platform with functionalities for detailed comparative genomics against genome sequences from known viruses (by querying virus-specific gene- or genome-based databases)
- 2) Develop bioinformatics functionalities for surveillance-oriented phylogeny (e.g., for disclosing transmission chains and/or source attribution) and for temporal and geographical metadata integration/sharing.

WP2-T5: Development of a user- and surveillance-oriented web-based interface

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: Daniel Horton, UoS

Deputy Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA

Task Participants:

Description of the WP2-T5: WP2-5 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project.

The main task of WP2-T5 is:

- 1) To optimize the existing web-based user interface so that it can provide final graphical outputs (e.g., phylogeography charts enriched with associated sample metadata and relevant viral genotypic and phenotypic features) that can be easily interpreted by a broad audience, not only bioinformaticians, but also other scientists (e.g., virologists, epidemiologists) and decision makers with little computational background.

WP3: Development of a protocol for POI MinION sequencing

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M48

WP Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Deputy WP Leader: Jovita Fernandez Pinero, INIA

WP Participants: SSI, INIA, SVA, Sciensano, NVI, IZSAM, PIWET

Description of the WP3: WP3 is the lab-based WP and takes place over the first and the second year of the project.

The goal is to develop a poi toolbox (size of a suitcase) that only contains a battery-driven heater, a MinION device, a MinIT/laptop and a cool box with reagents.

WP3 is divided into 3 tasks:

WP3-T1: Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment

WP3-T2: Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample NA purification

WP3-T3: Development and validation of a S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing (DNA & RNA)

Description of the WP3-Tasks for the 2nd year of the TELE-Vir project:

WP3-T1: Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Deputy Task Leader: Artur Rzeżutka, PIWET

Task Participants: SSI, INIA, SVA, PIWET

Description of the WP3-T1: WP3-T1 takes place over the first and second year of the project. The main tasks of the WP3-T1 are;

- 1) Validation of the 1st S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment mimicking field scenarios in the laboratory using a wide variety of biological specimens.
- 2) Development of the Final S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment

WP3-T2: Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample NA purification

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Deputy Task Leader: Lihong Liu, SVA

Task Participants: SSI, SVA, INIA, Sciensano

Description of the WP3-T2: WP3-T2 takes place over the first and second year of the project. The main tasks of the WP3-T2 are;

- 1) Validation of the 1st S.O.P for sample NA purification mimicking field scenarios in the laboratory using a wide variety of biological specimens.
- 2) Development of the Final S.O.P for sample NA purification

WP3-T3: Development and validation of a S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing (DNA & RNA)

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: Lihong Liu, SVA

Deputy Task Leader: Maiken W. Rosenstjerne, SSI

Task Participants: SSI, SVA, INIA, Sciensano, NVI, IZSAM

Description of the WP3-T3: WP3-T3 takes place over the first and second year of the project. The main tasks of the WP3-T3 are;

- 1) Validation of the 1st S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing (DNA & RNA) mimicking field scenarios in the laboratory using a wide variety of biological specimens.
- 2) Development of the Final S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing (DNA & RNA)

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP#-WP1.3	1 st TELE-Vir meeting (Sciensano, Belgium)	M37

D-JRP#-WP1.4	2 nd version of the DMP	M42
D-JRP#-WP2.1	Open-sourced bioinformatics platform that allows the user-friendly handling of high-throughput sequencing data (second and third generation) for detection and monitoring of viral emerging threats	M48
D-JRP#-WP3.1	Final version of a poi S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment	M48
D-JRP#-WP3.2	Final version of a poi S.O.P for sample NA purification	M48
D-JRP#-WP3.3	Final version of a poi S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing	M48
D-JRP#-WP3.4	Report on the validation of MinION sequencing mimicking the field scenario in lab conditions	M48
Milestones		
Re	Title	Due month
M-JRP#-02	Software modules for third-generation sequencing data handling	M39
M-JRP#-03	Software modules for viral rapid detection and classification	M42
M-JRP#-04	Software module for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes (e.g., antigenicity, tropism, anti-viral drug resistance)	M45
M-JRP#-05	Advertisement of the poi-toolbox workshop finished	M47
M-JRP#-06	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and OHEJP participants in the POI protocol for MinION sequencing performed incl. training materials, manuals & lectures and personal	M48
M-JRP#-07	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and OHEJP participants in the POI data analysis performed incl. training materials, manuals & lectures and personal	M48
M-JRP#-08	Registration of participants for training in the POI-toolbox finished (max. 30 participants)	M48
M-JRP#-09	Software module for locus- and genome-based comparative phylogenomics	M48

2.4.2.1.15 JRP17-R2-ET2.2-IDEMBRU

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		ET 2.2: Development of a toolkit to characterize emerging threats by combining genomic and phenotypic information									
Research Project Title		Identification of emerging Brucella species: new threats for human and animals									
Research Project Acronym		IDEMBRU									
Leading Organisation		P1-ANSES				Deputy Leading Organisation			P35-INIAV		
Project Leader		C Ponsart				Deputy Project leader			AC Ferreira		
Project Start month		M25				Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU	
PM	30,3			19			10,3	8,4			
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE	
PM									10,99		
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	
	UOS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	Wbvr	FHI	
PM						13,9			6,15		
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
PM			14,3	10,5							
Objectives											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a “one health” common database to share information about emerging <i>Brucella</i> and reservoirs among the consortium partners; • Harmonisation and implementation of “one health” sampling protocols and collections (serum, samples, strains) focusing on emerging <i>Brucella</i> species and related reservoirs; • Standardisation and implementation of protocols for detection, identification and phenotyping of emerging <i>Brucella</i> species; • Definition and redaction of the data management plan; • Organisation of the first annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders. 											
WP 1-Recording the situation of brucellosis in emergent wild and environmental reservoirs											

- WP1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T2 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T3 takes place over the second year of the project

WP start month: 37

WP end month: 50

WP Leader: Ana Cristina Ferreira

Deputy WP Leader: Hristo Dalaskov

WP participants : ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV, IZSAM, NDRVMI–BFSA

Description of the WP: The second part of this WP will be dedicated to additional sampling campaigns in different wildlife animals, such as amphibians, bats, cervidae, marine mammals, rodents, suidae. After definition of harmonised protocols for Brucella detection (M-JRP19-M7), all collected samples will be tested. Collection of appropriate samples (animal and environmental) will be performed for detection and isolation of emerging Brucella and reservoirs by each involved partner. Integrative analysis of collected data will be done in order to develop a flowchart and related tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging Brucella outbreaks.

Task JRP19-WP1-T2: Sampling and analytical strategy according to previous epidemiological information from the different partners

Task start month: 37

Task end month: 50

Task Leader: Ana Cristina Ferreira

Deputy Task Leader: Hristo Dalaskov

Task Participants: ANSES, BfR, FLI, INIAV, IZSAM, NDRVMI–BFSA

Description of the task: This task is devoted to sampling and analytical protocols. It will enable the creation of new biological collections (serum, samples, and strains) including emerging Brucella species and related reservoirs. Selection of countries, regions, targeted animal species and their surrounding environment will be based on practical possibilities related to relevant contexts in terms of natural landscape, livestock demographics, and wildlife populations of each participating country. Sampling and analytical protocols will be harmonized among partners and shared. Collection of appropriate samples (animal and environmental) for detection and isolation of emerging Brucella spp. as agreed by the consortium will be performed. All strains will be characterized according to conventional microbiological methods. When available, blood samples will be collected to characterise serological responses using rough and smooth antigens based methods. Each involved partner will collaborate in producing the sampling and the analytical protocols and undertaking collection of biological samples.

Task JRP19-WP1-T3: Synthesis and analysis of data

Task start month: 37

Task end month: 50

Task Leader: Ana Cristina Ferreira

Deputy Task Leader: Hristo Dalaskov

Task Participants: ANSES, BfR, FLI, INIAV, IZSAM, NDRVMI–BFSA

Description of the task: Tasks JRP19-WP1-T2 will provide epidemiological and phenotypic data that will be used to complete the database created in JRP19-WP1-T1. Integrative analysis of data will improve knowledge regarding emergent Brucella species infections and will be used to define new strategies to detect and monitor emerging infections. This analysis will result in the development of

a flowchart and related tools facilitating investigation and decision-making of emerging *Brucella* outbreaks, which will be integrated in the final toolkit (WP6).

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP19-M19	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging <i>Brucella</i> species	46

WP2 - Recording the situation of brucellosis in human

- WP2 takes place over the first and the second of the project
- T2 takes place over the first and second year of the project
- T3 takes place over the second year of the project

WP start month: 37

WP end month: 50

WP Leader: Ana Pelerito

Deputy WP Leader: Sascha Al Dahouk

WP participants: ANSES, BfR, INSA

Description of the WP: In the second year of WP2, additional sampling design will be continued according to selected emerging reservoirs and characterisation of metadata. The analysis of data should allow the identification of geographic distribution, contributing to the better understanding of emerging brucellosis epidemiology. By the end of the work package, the newly collected *Brucella* strains and serums will be shared among partners for further investigations in WPs 3 to 5. Both leading organisations (INSA and BfR) will ensure coordination, implementation of the surveillance network for human brucellosis and harmonisation of protocols applied in this work package. Partners will contribute through collection of appropriate samples, dissemination of the questionnaire and / or through existing strain collections of emerging *Brucella* and reservoirs. All strains will be characterized according direct methods (microbiological methods and molecular biology).

Task JRP19-WP2-T2: Sampling and analytical strategy according to epidemiological information from the surveillance network

Task start month: 37

Task end month: 50

Task Leader: Ana Pelerito

Deputy Task Leader: Sascha Al Dahouk

Task Participants: ANSES, BfR, INSA

Description of the task: This task is devoted to sampling and analytical protocols. It will enable the creation of human biological collections (serum, samples, and strains) including emerging *Brucella* species and related reservoirs. In order to establish a “One Health” approach, the selection of countries and regions will be based on information derived from WP1, responses to the epidemiological questionnaire, practical possibilities and ethical constraints. Blood samples will be collected by INSA from potentially exposed people for serological testing and direct diagnosis. Methods for blood culture and molecular protocols will be standardised and shared among partners. ANSES and BfR have expertise in isolation and molecular detection of this agent and INSA routinely uses all these techniques.

Task JRP19-WP2-T3: Analysis of data and constitutions of biobank

Task start month: 43
Task end month: 50
Task Leader: Ana Pelerito
Deputy Task Leader: Sascha Al Dahouk
Task Participants: ANSES, BfR, INSA

Description of the task: In this task, collected sera and isolated emerging *Brucella* species will contribute to extend existing biobanks including metadata derived from the questionnaire. The analysis of infection situations will improve knowledge on emerging *Brucella* and reservoirs. This will be used to select the most relevant strains for further characterization in WPs 3 to 5. Moreover, integrative analysis of genomic and epidemiological data collected in WP1 and WP2 will be combined using “One Health” approach in order to develop the final toolkit. Additionally, isolates of bacterial species for which emerging *Brucella* sp. isolates have previously been frequently mis-identified by culture methods (see JRP19-WP2-T1) will be collected for detailed phenotypic and genetic characterisation.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
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Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
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M-JRP19-M20	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging <i>Brucella</i> species	46
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WP3 - Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

- WP3 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T3 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T4 takes place over the second year of the project

WP start month: 37
WP end month: 54
WP Leader: Roland Ashford
Deputy WP Leader: Giuliano Garofolo
WP participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the WP: The objectives of the second year are (i) to apply molecular typing data to the epidemiological investigation of emerging and atypical *Brucella* spp. strains (JRP19-WP3-T1); (ii) to ensure that existing molecular typing schemes remain applicable to the full diversity of the genus, and to develop discriminatory typing assay(s) to identify emerging and atypical *Brucella* spp. strains (JRP19-WP3-T3). Genotyping data will be combined with existing metadata from samples and isolates to perform epidemiological analyses of atypical and emerging *Brucella* spp. isolates (JRP19-WP3-T4).

Task JRP19-WP3-T1: Optimisation of methods for generating molecular typing data from complex samples

Task start month: 37
Task end month: 52
Task Leader: Roland Ashford
Deputy Task Leader: Giuliano Garofolo
Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task: Optimal protocols will be applied amongst other partner institutes (ANSES, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, WBVR) to relevant sample sets generated under WPs 1 & 2. This will enable us to apply existing molecular typing methods (e.g. qPCR, HRM, MLVA, and MLST) to samples directly, without the need to isolate organisms. Identification of clinical and environmental samples of most relevance will be informed by WP 1 (JRP19-WP1-T1) & WP2 (JRP19-WP2-T1). The diagnostic sample collection will additionally be tested using discriminatory single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) retrieved from the whole genome sequencing datasets (JRP19-WP3-T3). Initial work under JRP19-WP3-T1 will primarily be undertaken by the WP3 Lead institute (APHA), with input from Deputy WP Lead institute (IZSAM).

Task JRP19-WP3-T2: Harmonisation and standardisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing

Task start month: 37

Task end month: 42

Task Leader: Roland Ashford

Deputy Task Leader: Giuliano Garofolo

Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task: We will standardise the performance of library preparation and sequencing procedures undertaken in partner institutes (quality; number of reads, coverage, etc.). In order to do this a representative panel of *Brucella* spp. isolates will be identified, and (inactivated) bacterial suspensions will be shared with partner institutes. In the case of bioinformatics protocols we will benchmark assembly and alignment metrics, to ensure data are comparable between partner institutes, using shared samples and reference strains. Task JRP19-WP3-T2 will be led by the WP3 lead institute (APHA) with input from Deputy WP Lead institute (IZSAM). Standardised bioinformatics protocols will be shared with all other participating institutes (ANSES, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, WBVR) to ensure that data generated under JRP19-WP3-T3 can be comparable. Data generated using standardised whole genome sequencing and bioinformatics protocols will be applied in WP4 and WP6.

Task JRP19-WP3-T3: Identification of emerging *Brucella* species: adaptation of molecular tools

Task start month: 37

Task end month: 52

Task Leader: Roland Ashford

Deputy Task Leader: Giuliano Garofolo

Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task: Molecular typing methods such as multiple locus VNTR analysis (MLVA), multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) and specific gene sequencing (e.g. 16S) are widely applied to molecular typing of *Brucella*. We will apply whole genome sequencing using next generation sequencing platform to the emerging *Brucella* collection obtained from the activities related to WP1 and WP2. We will continue to generate *in silico* 9 & 21 locus MLST, core genome (cg)MLST and whole genome SNP typing data; *in silico* 16-locus MLVA profiles, supported by conventional fragment analysis approaches where necessary. Using expanded genomic databases (incorporating data generated under this project) we will identify discriminatory SNP typing assay(s) to identify atypical *Brucella* spp. strains. The WP3 lead institute (APHA) with input from Deputy WP Lead institute (IZSAM) will lead JRP19-WP3-T3.

Task JRP19-WP3-T4: Integrative analysis of genomic and epidemiological data collected in WP1 and WP2

Task start month: 47
Task end month: 54
Task Leader: Roland Ashford
Deputy Task Leader: Giuliano Garofolo
Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV, INSA, IZSAM, WBVR
Description of the task: Genomic analyses of atypical *Brucella* spp. isolates have focused primarily on their phylogenetic placement relative to other emerging and classical *Brucella* species. We will combine data for isolates generated under work packages WP1 and 2, in order to undertake epidemiological analyses of atypical and emerging *Brucella* spp. isolates in Europe across different emerging reservoirs. Outputs of this combined analysis will be integrated into the final toolkit (WP6).

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP19-WP2.Del1	Standard operating procedures for the extraction of <i>Brucella</i> DNA from complex matrices	42
D-JRP19-WP2.Del2	Harmonised whole genome sequencing and bioinformatic protocols	42

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP19-M15	Harmonisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing	41
M-JRP19-M16	Optimised protocols for the extraction of <i>Brucella</i> DNA from complex matrices	42

WP4 - Phenotypic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

- WP4 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project
- T1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T2 takes place over the second and the third year of the project
- T3 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project
- T4 takes place over the third year of the project

WP start month: 37
WP end month: 60
WP Leader: Falk Melzer
Deputy WP Leader: Sascha Al Dahouk
WP participants: ANSES, APHA, FLI, BfR, IZSAM, INIAV, INSA

Description of the WP: The major aim of WP4 is to identify diagnostically relevant features to characterize and differentiate novel emerging *Brucella* spp. from the classical species. This includes conventional phenotyping procedures as well as commercial biotyping. We will test and adapt existing AMR protocols in this project to comparatively analyse antibiotic resistance in the novel emerging strains of *Brucella*. The differences in metabolic activity between classical and emerging species shall be characterized using a combined RNASeq and peptidomic (mass spectrometry) approach after inactivation of the living agent. We will also analyse whether the detection of RNA in clinical samples which has a higher abundance is more sensitive than the detection of genomic *Brucella* DNA. For this purpose, the efficacy of RNASeq and 16S metagenomics for the detection of *Brucella* in clinical samples will be compared.

Task JRP19-WP4-T1: Phenotyping of novel emerging *Brucella* spp.

Task start month: 37
Task end month: 54

Task Leader: Falk Melzer
Deputy Task Leader: Sascha Al Dahouk
Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, FLI, BfR, IZSAM, INIAV, INSA

Description of the task:

JRP19-WP4-T1-ST1: Emerging *Brucella* species that have been recently described or that are isolated in the context of this proposal (WP1; WP2) will be phenotyped using all appropriate conventional methods under biosafety level 3 conditions. Phenotypic results from partners will be used for overall characterization. Lab work will start after the arrival of the first isolates at FLI.

JRP19-WP4-T1-ST3: Previous studies have shown that the atypical *Brucella* species *B. microti* exhibits expanded metabolic activities, clearly distinguishable to those of classical *Brucella* species like *B. abortus* and *B. melitensis*. The Micronaut™ test developed by BfR provides valuable information about the presence of distinct substrate utilizing enzymes and will contribute not only to the functional characterization of the emerging *Brucella* species but also to their discrimination and classification into biovars/subspecies. Therefore, we will analyze *B. microti* and other emerging *Brucella* species that have been recently described or will be isolated from wildlife in the context of this proposal (WP1; WP2) with this assay. In the context of this proposal, we will analyse with this assay *B. microti* and other emerging *Brucella* species that have been and will be isolated from wildlife (WP1; WP2).

Task **JRP19-WP4-T2**: Antimicrobial resistance testing of emerging *Brucella* spp.

Task start month: 43

Task end month: 56

Task Leader: Falk Melzer

Deputy Task Leader: Sascha Al Dahouk

Task Participants: FLI, ANSES, APHA, FLI, BfR, IZSAM, INIAV, INSA

Description of the task :

JRP19-WP4-T2-ST1: Etest™ and microdilution to measure MICs will be adapted and used to test antibiotic resistance of the isolates. This work will be finished by the end of second year of the project.

JRP19-WP4-T2-ST2: Analysis of AMR results and determination of ECOFFs will be done and results will be made available to all WP members.

Task **JRP19-WP4-T3**: RNA sequencing of a representative panel of classical and novel *Brucella* spp.

Task start month: 37

Task end month: 60

Task Leader: Sascha Al Dahouk

Deputy Task Leader : Dirk Hofreuter

Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, FLI, BfR, IZSAM, INIAV, INSA

Description of the task :

JRP19-WP4-T3-ST2: After examining the transcriptomes of atypical *Brucella* species, the generated results will be compared with the transcriptome analyses of *Brucella* isolate from classical species such as *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus*, *B. suis* and especially *B. ovis* whose metabolic properties are very different when compared to other classical isolates.

JRP19-WP4-T3-ST3: For certain non-classical *Brucella* isolates, distinct gene expression and metabolic patterns identified in task JRP19-WP4-T1-ST3 and task JRP19-WP4-T3-ST2 might correlate with protein profile differences that may result in MALDI-TOF MS spectra variations of respective

strains. Consequently, we will use these atypical strains to complement our current peptide profile database in order to improve the MALDI-TOF MS based identification of *Brucella*.

JRP19-WP4-T3-ST4: Integrative bioinformatics analyses of the generated genome, transcriptome and metabolic phenotyping (Micronaut™/BIOLOG™) data will be used to clarify, which metabolic pathways are active in all *Brucella* spp. and which pathways are specifically present in the atypical *Brucella* species identified and characterized within the planned research program of IDEMBRU.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
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Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
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M-JRP19-M9	Drafted RNASeq protocols to identify regulatory differences between classical species and emerging <i>Brucella</i> strains	40
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WP5 - Zoonotic potential and virulence

- WP5 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project
- T1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T2 takes place over the first and the second year of the project
- T3 takes place over the second and the third year of the project

WP start month: 41

WP end month: 60

WP Leader: Alexander Umanets

Deputy WP Leader: Luca Freddi

WP participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the WP: Understanding the zoonotic potential and virulence of a pathogen is necessary to assess risk to the public and for the development of appropriate preventive and control measures. The most reliable approach is the collection of historical and epidemiological data, but unfortunately this cannot be applied to an emerging disease. Several laboratory animal species, cell lines of human and animal origin, in combination with genomics have been used to understand *Brucella* pathogenesis. However, with the exception of *B. microti*, the virulence of these emerging *Brucella* strains has not been investigated. Hereby we propose to develop a pipeline for evaluation of virulence and zoonotic potential mediated by *in vitro* and *in vivo* infection models.

WBVR and ANSES will be executive parties for WP5. Collaboration between ANSES, APHA, BfR, FLI, IZSAM and WBVR will allow the harmonization of *in vitro* and *in vivo* protocols and provide access to all necessary facilities for successful development, execution and benchmarking of the proposed above pipeline. All involved partners will provide selected emerging *Brucella* strains from its own strain bank.

Task JRP19-WP5-T1: Develop an *in silico* pipeline for preliminary assessment of overall virulence and zoonotic potential.

Task start month: 41

Task end month: 48

Task Leader: Alexander Umanets

Deputy Task Leader: Luca Freddi

Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task: Common and unique virulence factors will be identified by genome wide comparison of a novel emerging *Brucella* isolate with a reference panel of *Brucella* species. A panel

of classical and emerging *Brucella* species will be selected according to their zoonotic potential based on historical, genomic and phenotypic data. Data generated in the course of the WP3 and from publicly available databases will be used for selection and benchmarking of bioinformatics tools for virulence factor detection, with the purpose of creating a reliable *in silico* pipeline for rapid preliminary zoonotic potential assessment. WBVR will be in charge of selecting bioinformatics tools for identification and comparison of virulence factors, as well as creating an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes. ANSES will set up *Brucella* genomes database from publicly available and novel isolates (WP3). All involved partners will support the creation of *Brucella* genomes database and bioinformatics pipeline development.

Task JRP19-WP5-T2: Develop an *in vitro* protocol to investigate zoonotic potential based on macrophage cell lines originated from human and animals.

Task start month: 41

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: Alexander Umanets

Deputy Task Leader: Luca Freddi

Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, BfR, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task: A panel of classical and emerging *Brucella* species will be selected according to their zoonotic potential based on historical, genomic and phenotypic data. As the next step an *in vitro* infection model based on macrophage cell lines derived from human and animals will be developed. The *in vitro* models will be used for comparison of a target isolate with reference panel of *Brucella* species. For analytical analysis of cell-pathogen interactions, a list of representative virulence genes based on published research will be created and their expression in the course of infection will be quantified by RT-qPCR. In addition, cytokines secreted by the host cell lines will be analysed using specific ELISA kits. WBVR will develop and test *Brucella in vitro* infection protocol, to assess *Brucella spp.* infectivity, cell toxicity and ability for intracellular replication. Moreover, WBVR will perform RT-qPCR quantification of virulence genes expression in the course of infection. ANSES will continue to identify representative virulence genes, design qPCR primers, analyse cytokines secretion by ELISA kits. Finally, IZSAM will support investigation of virulence factors expression

Task JRP19-WP5-T3: *In vivo* testing of *Brucella* isolates with high zoonotic potential.

Task start month: 45

Task end month: 60

Task Leader: Alexander Umanets

Deputy Task Leader: Luca Freddi

Task Participants: ANSES, BfR, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task: Experimental *in vivo* infection of guinea pigs (*Cavia porcellus*) will be performed with the objective of investigating the virulence of emerging *Brucella* stains. In agreement with other partners, a final panel of emerging *Brucella* species will be selected according to their *in vitro* (JRP19-WP5-T2) pathogenic potential, historical, genomic (JRP19-WP5-T1) and phenotypic data. Using ANSES BSL3 graded vivarium *in vivo* infection of experimental animals will be conducted. In the course of *in vivo* experiment major aspects of pathogenesis, such as, minimal infection dose, routes of infection, infective agent tropism, host morbidity and immune response will be investigated. All partners will design the animal experiment and select a panel of *Brucella* strains suitable for *in vivo* investigation. Finally, ANSES will start animal experimentations.

Ref	Title	Due month
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D-JRP19-WP5.Del1	Bioinformatics pipeline for detection and classification of <i>Brucella</i> virulence factors in context of zoonotic potential	48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP19-M17	Creation of <i>Brucella</i> genomes database from publicly available and emerging isolates (WP 2)	44
M-JRP19-M21	Selection of bioinformatics tools for identification and comparison of virulence factors	46
M-JRP19-M22	Assembly of macrophage cell lines collection derived from human and animals	46
M-JRP19-M24	Creation of an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes	48
M-JRP19-M25	Development of <i>in vitro</i> infection protocol	48
Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP19-WP6.Del1	Review of toolkits for infectious diseases	48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP19-M27	List of toolkits available from previous experience	47
M-JRP19-M28	Literature reviewing	47
<p>WP7 - Coordination, management and communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP7 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project • T1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project • T2 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project • T3 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project • T4 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project <p>WP start month: 37 WP end month: 58 WP Leader: Claire Ponsart Deputy WP Leader: Ana Cristina Ferreira WP participants: All the partners</p> <p>Description of the WP: This work package is dedicated to the general coordination and management of the project including all administrative and financial issues. This will ensure the timely implementation of the tasks, the smooth running of the project and successful dissemination of outputs. Specific tasks will be dedicated to data and risk management. Three workshops will be used for coordination of work, exchanges of information and collaborative development of the toolkit. The coordinator will ensure successful management, integration and delivery of the project, and will coordinate and provide effective reporting and communications between project partners. A steering committee composed of one representative for each participating institute will be set up to discuss the advancement of the project through progress reports. The WP leaders report on their respective WP, whereas the coordinator is responsible for the final report.</p> <p>Task JRP19-WP7-T1: Coordination and organisation Task start month: 37 Task end month: 58</p>		

Task Leader: Claire Ponsart
Deputy Task Leader: Ana Cristina Ferreira
Task Participants: All the partners

Description of the task: WP leaders assisted by Deputy WP leaders will be in charge of coordination and management inside WPs and of the preparation of activity reports to be compiled by the project coordinator. According to results obtained during the first year, adjustments in the work-plan will be discussed within the steering committee. Regular exchanges within the steering committee will be organised by video- or telephone conferences. INSA will organize the second annual workshop, including collaborative work with all the partners to define the structure and main components of the final toolkit.

Task JRP19-WP7-T2: Data management

Task start month: 37
Task end month: 58
Task Leader: Guillaume Girault
Deputy Task Leader: Ana Pelerito
Task Participants: All the partners

Description of the task: The DMP will be updated. Data generated during the first year will be listed and stored in the shared common platform. During the second year, the relevance and opportunity to make those cofounded data accessible to external partners will be assessed case by case.

Task JRP19-WP7-T3: Risk management

Task start month: 37
Task end month: 58
Task Leader: Claire Ponsart
Deputy Task Leader: Ana Cristina Ferreira
Task Participants: All the partners

Description of the task: Changes necessary in order to deliver milestones on time as well as delays and problems in achieving the milestones will be reported in advance of workshops by work package leader and deputy leader. Modifications to the project made possible by newly available materials and techniques will be discussed, evaluated and, if considered appropriate, implemented in a coordinated manner, as will possible changes in emphasis based on developments in perceived threats and newly published work appearing in the literature.

Task JRP19-WP7-T4: Synthesis and dissemination of recommendations coming from the project outputs

Task start month: 25
Task end month: 58
Task Leader: Claire Ponsart
Deputy Task Leader: Ana Cristina Ferreira
Task Participants: All the partners

Description of the task: The first results will be disseminated through existing networks, such as the EU reference laboratories network and the European institutions (DG Sante, ECDC and EFSA).

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
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D-JRP19-WP7.Del4	Report of the first annual workshop including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders	40
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP19-M12	Implementation of first annual workshop	38
M-JRP19-M13	Definition of criteria to be included in the notification system	38
M-JRP19-M14	Choice of the informatic system to implement the notification system	38
M-JRP19-M18	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders and deputy leaders	42
M-JRP19-M23	Definition of the programme of the annual workshop	44
M-JRP19-M26	Organisation of accommodation and logistic aspects	46
M-JRP19-M32	Implementation of 2nd annual workshop	48
M-JRP19-M33	Mailing list of people / institutes receiving notifications	48

2.4.2.1.16 JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		ET 1.1: Development and harmonization of NGS and non-NGS methods (e.g. pheno-genotypic and histochemical methods) for the detection of foodborne parasites								
Research Project Title		Multi-centre study on <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> and <i>Echinococcus granulosus s.l.</i> in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain.								
Research Project Acronym		MEmE								
Leading Organisation		P27-ISS			Deputy Leading Organisation			N/A		
Project Leader		Adriano Casulli			Deputy Project leader			N/A		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	29,5							9		
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	7,3	15,5	2							
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM					32,5			2,46		
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM	6,8	9,2	7	5					9	
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SAMPLING of different matrices from experimentally infected definitive and intermediate hosts (WP1-T3) to feed WP2, WP3 and WP4 on 1) validation of parasitological/molecular assays; 2) development and validation of new tools and production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments, and 3) Proficiency Testing Schemes. • Ending the validation of MOLECULAR diagnostic procedures (multiplex PCRs and Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay) to detect <i>E. multilocularis</i> (Em) and <i>E. granulosus s.l.</i> (Eg) in different matrices along the food chain (WP2-T2,T3). 										

- Ending the development and validation of NEW TOOLS: 1) new molecular markers (from rapid diagnostics to source attribution); 2) new multiplex qPCR for detection and discrimination of Em/Eg and Eg genotypes; 3) sequencing using Region-Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS for the detection of Em/Eg in complex samples.
- Assessment of selected newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques (WP3-T5).
- Ending the production of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS on: 1) contamination of vegetables for human consumption by eggs of Em/Eg; 2) prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces; and 3) identification of potential risk factors for human CE/AE infection through questionnaires (WP3-T6,T7,T8).
- TRAINING scientists of MEmE in parasitological and molecular identification of Echinococcus spp. by exchange of key staff members (WP4-T1).
- Implementation of selected PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES organized by the MEmE network to consolidate and improve laboratory skills in the parasitological and molecular procedures (WP4-T3).
- DISSEMINATING PROJECT RESULTS at different levels (general public, populations at risk, biologists, veterinarians, clinicians, health authorities, policy makers and media) (WP4-T2).

Description of work

• WP: 1 (SAMPLING STRATEGY) (takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)
 WP start month: **25**; WP end month: **48**; WP Leader: **PIWET**
 WP participants: **ISS, FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, VFL, CVRL, BIOR, CMRIXJ, JLU, VRIXJ**
 Description of the WP: This WP is aiming to **collect (in the field/research facilities) and produce in the laboratory, the biological material** needed to implement the activities of **MEmE**. Samples will be used for validation of parasitological/molecular methods (**WP2**), to generate innovative tools and epidemiological data (**WP3**), and prepare Proficiency Testing Schemes (**WP4**).

WP1	M25-26	M27-28	M29-30	M31-32	M33-34	M35-36	M37-38	M39-40	M41-42	M43-44	M45-46	M47-48	M49-50	M51-52	M53-54
T1.															
T2.															
T3.												D1. 3			

Task: **JRP-WP1-T3. Matrices collection from experimental fox model**
 (takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP22-WP1.3	Collection of samples from experimental animal model finalized	M48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP22-15	Interim evaluation of collection of samples from experimental animal model	M42

WP: **2 (VALIDATION of PARASITOLOGICAL and MOLECULAR ASSAYS)**
 (takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

WP start month: **29**; WP end month: **44**; WP Leader: **ANSES**
 WP participants: **ISS, FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, UT, VFL, CVRL, BIOR**

Description of the WP: This WP will focus on the **harmonization and validation of selected parasitological and molecular procedures**. Validation will include estimates of the analytical and diagnostic performance characteristics of tests. This research will be conducted in line with OIE principles and methods of validation of diagnostic assays for infectious diseases. Development and validation of analytical methods will be performed, where possible, in a quality system according to **UNI CEI EN ISO/IEC 17025:2005** (*General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories*). In the absence of an acceptable gold standard, the performance of the diagnostic tests will be assessed by means of **Bayesian modelling** (Branscum et al., 2005).

WP2	M25-26	M27-28	M29-30	M31-32	M33-34	M35-36	M37-38	M39-40	M41-42	M43-44	M45-46	M47-48	M49-50	M51-52	M53-54
T1.															
T2.										D2.2					
T3.										D2.3					

Task: **JRP-WP2-T2. Comparison of multiplex PCRs**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Task: **JRP-WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP22-WP2.2	Validation of multiplex PCRs	M44
D-JRP22-WP2.3	Validation of Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay	M44
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month

WP: 3 (DEVELOPMENT/VALIDATION of NEW TOOLS and PRODUCTION of DATA RELEVANT for EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENTS)

(takes place over the 3rd, 4th and 5th year)

WP start month: **27**; WP end month: **52**; WP Leader: **FLI**

WP participants: **ISS, FLI, ANSES, PIWET, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, UT, BIOR, CMRIXJ, JLU, VRIXJ**

Description of the WP: This WP is aiming to **generate new innovative tools** for rapid detection, differential diagnosis, and tracking of infection, both at large and small-scale settings. The tools will include:

- 1) new molecular markers (new mitochondrial and microsatellite markers, and NGS-based method);
- 2) new multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Eg s.l. and Em;
- 3) new NGS approach instead of the current sequencing methods;
- 4) biomarker discovery through proteomics in sheep plasma exosomes.

This WP will also collect field samples and data to generate **data relevant for epidemiological assessments** on:

- 1) contamination of vegetables for human consumption by eggs of Em/Eg;
- 2) prevalence of Em/Eg in dogs;
- 3) potential risk factors for human CE/AE infection.

WP3	M25-26	M27-28	M29-30	M31-32	M33-34	M35-36	M37-38	M39-40	M41-42	M43-44	M45-46	M47-48	M49-50	M51-52	M53-54
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T1.												D3.1			
T2.												D3.2			
T3.												D3.3			
T4.															
T5.															
T6.												D3.6			
T7.												D3.7			
T8.												D3.8			

Task: **JRP-WP3-T1. New molecular markers for Em and Eg s.l.: from rapid diagnostics to source attribution**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Task: **JRP-WP3-T2. New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Eg s.l. and Em**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Task: **JRP-WP3-T3. Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using RSE and NGS**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Task: **JRP-WP3-T4. Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma**

(takes place over the 3rd, 4th and 5th year)

Task: **JRP-WP3-T5. Assessment of newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques**

(takes place over the 4th and 5th year)

Task start month: 43; Task end month: 52; Task Leader: FLI, ANSES

Task Participants: ISS, FLI, ANSES, NVI, SSI, INIAV, UT, CMRIXJ, JLU

Description of the task: In this task, the diagnostic performances of new and existing molecular and parasitological techniques will be compared. This will be performed with two sets of comparisons:

1) comparison of multiplex PCRs techniques (WP2-T2), magnetic capture-Real Time PCR technique (WP2-T3), and the newly developed multiplex Taqman qPCR (WP3-T2) using reference DNA obtained from adult *E. multilocularis* worms and *E. granulosus* cysts (WP1-T2);

2) comparison of the parasitological Segmental Sedimentation and Counting technique (SSCT) (WP2-T1) with the above-mentioned molecular techniques (WP2-T2,T3 and WP3-T2) using intestines and DNA extracted from the faeces of the same experimentally infected foxes (WP1-T3), respectively.

Task: **JRP-WP3-T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Task: **JRP-WP3-T7. Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Task: **JRP-WP3-T8. Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires**

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP22-WP3.1	New molecular markers	M48
D-JRP22-WP3.2	New multiplex TaqMan qPCR	M48
D-JRP22-WP3.3	New NGS method for the detection in complex samples	M48
D-JRP22-WP3.6	Contamination of vegetables by Em/Eg	M48
D-JRP22-WP3.7	Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog from selected geographical areas	M48
D-JRP22-WP3.8	Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires	M48
Milestones		

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP22-16	Selection of new/old methods to be compared	M44

WP: 4 (TRAINING, DISSEMINATION and PROFICIENCY TESTING SCHEMES)

(takes place over the 3rd, 4th and 5th year)

WP start month: **27**; WP end month: **54**; WP Leader: **ISS**

WP participants: **ISS, FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, UT, VFL, CVRL, BIOR, CMRIXJ, JLU, VRIXJ**

Description of the WP: This WP will focus on:

- 1) establishing the most effective methods for disseminating project results** at different levels (general public, population at risk, biologists, veterinarians, clinicians, health authorities, policy makers and media);
- 2) training scientists** from institutions participating to **MEEmE** in the parasitological and molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. This WP will also focus on the dissemination and training within **International Networks** linked to **MEEmE** such as the **NRL for Parasites/Echinococcus** (<https://w3.iss.it/site/EURLPMaps/MapsInfo.asp>);
- 3) organization and delivery of PTs** for the harmonization and validation of selected parasitological and molecular procedures.

WP4	M25-26	M27-28	M29-30	M31-32	M33-34	M35-36	M37-38	M39-40	M41-42	M43-44	M45-46	M47-48	M49-50	M51-52	M53-54
T1.												D4.1			
T2.															
T3.															

Task: JRP-WP4-T1. Trainings (parasitological and molecular approaches, NGS included)

(takes place over the 3rd and 4th year)

Task: JRP-WP4-T2. Dissemination of project results

(takes place over the 3rd, 4th and 5th year)

Task: JRP-WP4-T3. Organization of selected PTs from WP2 and WP3

(takes place over the 4th and 5th year)

Task start month: **43**; Task end month: **52**; Task Leader: **ISS, ANSES, SVA, NVI**

WP participants: **ISS, FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, UT, VFL, BIOR, JLU**

Description of the task: This task will aim to validate and harmonize selected methods developed/validated in the project by means of the organization of proficiency testing schemes (PTs). PTs will be organized, where possible, in a quality system for the detection of zoonotic parasites according to **UNI CEI EN ISO/IEC 17043:2010** (*Conformity assessment - General requirements for proficiency testing*). This ISO standard defines the proficiency testing as evaluation of participant performance against pre-established criteria. The process of PTs involves distribution of different test materials over a period to a laboratory population within **MEEmE** and including the **NRL for Parasites/Echinococcus**. PTs will be used to assess the inter-laboratory performance of analytical methods and, in some cases, compare particular methods directly.

The following PTs will be organized to support validation and harmonization processes:

- 1) Validation of Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT** (Umhang et al., 2011). Both intestines from naturally infected foxes and uninfected intestinal mucosae spiked with *E. multilocularis* adult worms will be tested. Organized by **ANSES**. WP participants: **FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, NVI, SSI, INIAV, UT, VFL, BIOR, JLU**.

- 2)** Harmonization of **Multiplex PCRs** (Trachsel et al., 2007; Boubaker et al., 2013). Uninfected faeces spiked with *E. multilocularis* eggs will be tested. Organized by **ISS**. WP participants: **ISS, FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, NVI, SSI, INIAV, UT, VFL, BIOR, JLU**.
- 3)** Harmonization of **Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assays** (Isaksson et al., 2014). Both faeces from naturally infected foxes and faeces spiked with *E. multilocularis* eggs/adult worms from uninfected foxes will be tested. Organized by **NVI** and **SVA**. WP participants: **FLI, ANSES, RIVM, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, UT, VFL, BIOR, JLU**.
- 4)** Harmonization of Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: **sequencing using RSE and NGS**. Uninfected faeces spiked with *E. multilocularis* eggs will be tested. Organized by **SSI**. WP participants: **FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, UT, JLU**.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP22-WP4.1	Analysis and evaluation of training activities	M48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month

WP: 5 (SCIENTIFIC and ADMINISTRATIVE MANAGEMENT)

(takes place over the 3rd, 4th and 5th year)

WP start month: **25**; WP end month: **54**; WP Leader: **ISS**

WP participants: **ISS, FLI, ANSES, RIVM, PIWET, SVA, NVI, SSI, INIAV, INSA, UT, VFL, CVRL, BIOR, CMRIXJ, JLU, VRXJ**

Description of the WP: **This WP will focus on the scientific and administrative coordination, which** are foreseen in the project work plan to ensure efficient and successful cooperation between the project partners. This requires the setting up of effective decision-making bodies, clear external communication and operational internal communication, and effective administrative and technical control. As such, **coordination** will be based on the following major principles: **1)** effective quality management; **2)** compliance with all relevant EC regulations and implementation of sound monitoring and professional administration to prevent time and cost escalation; **3)** strong research commitment from the entire team to enable efficient execution of activities, timely delivery of results and horizontal data dissemination across the Consortium and stakeholders to ensure the exploitation of the results; **4)** flexible and responsive management to accommodate the need for changes as the Consortium advances its scientific agenda; **5)** identification, protection and management of the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) generated by the project; **6)** management of ethical issues. This WP will ensure also the good management of the research data through the development of a **Data Management Plan (DMP)**.

WP5	M25-26	M27-28	M29-30	M31-32	M33-34	M35-36	M37-38	M39-40	M41-42	M43-44	M45-46	M47-48	M49-50	M51-52	M53-54
T1.															
T2.							D5.6					D5.3			
T3.															

Task: **JRP-WP5-T2. Administrative and scientific management**

(takes place over the 3rd, 4th and 5th year)

Task: **JRP-WP5-T3. Ethics management**

(takes place over the 3rd, 4th and 5th year)		
Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP22-WP5.3	Periodic technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M48
D-JRP22-WP5.6	Interim annual meeting in Greifswald (Germany) by FLI	M38
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP22-17	Organization of Interim annual meeting by FLI	M37
M-JRP22-18	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M47

2.4.2.1.17 JRP19-R2-ET1.1-PARADISE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		ET 1.1: Development and harmonization of NGS and non-NGS methods (e.g. pheno-genotypic and histochemical methods) for the detection of foodborne parasites								
Research Project Title		PARADISE– PARASite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation								
Research Project Acronym		PARADISE								
Leading Organisation		P27-ISS			Deputy Leading Organisation			P41-SVA		
Project Leader		Simone M. Cacciò			Deputy Project leader			Karin Troell		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	6,5					4,1	2,3		11	
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	6,7									
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	5,15	2			27,5			3,34		
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM	0,8	4,1	2,92				1,1	1	17	
Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To organize the Annual meeting, ensuring timely completion and reporting of Deliverables (WP1) <i>In silico</i> detection of FBPs in publicly available metagenomes (WP2) Detection of FBPs on spiked food matrices by amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics approaches (WP2) <i>In silico</i> selection of markers suitable for high-resolution typing of <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> (WP3) Testing of the selected markers by a team of expert laboratories for development of MLST schemes for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> (WP3) Analyse up to 2000 samples supplied by all project partners to investigate genetic variation and population structure (WP3) 										

- Inter-laboratory comparison of MLST schemes (WP3)
- Development of pre-DNA nanobodies- and aptamers-based enrichment approaches for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts (WP4)
- Development of post-DNA approaches to enrich for target DNA of low abundance in various matrices (WP4)

Description of work

The work is organized into 4 work packages (WPs), with specific tasks (T). The 2.5-year project spans over three Annual Periods (Y3, Y4 and Y5) and is described in three Work Plans.

WP JRP-PARADISE_WP1 Coordination and impact

WP start month M25; WP end month M54

WP Leader: **Simone M Cacciò, ISS**; WP Deputy: **Karin Troell, SVA**.

WP participants: **ANSES, BFR, FOHM, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PIWET, RIVM, RKI, SLV, SSI, SVA, UoS, VRI, BIOR, CRU, HZAU, JLU, NMBU, UoM**

Description of the WP:

- WP1 takes place over the first, the second and the third annual period of the project. WP1 works closely with all the WPs of the project.

WP1 will be responsible for all reporting to the OHEJP coordinating body and will coordinate three annual meetings during the 3-year project. Because of the large number of partners in the consortium, and the need for interaction between WPs, WP1 will play an important role in ensuring that milestones and final deliverables of the consortium are successfully completed and communicated.

The Coordinator at ISS and the Co-coordinator at SVA will collaborate in keeping continuous contact between the WPs and ensure proper dissemination of results.

A PARADISE Project Management Team (PA-PMT) comprising the Coordinator, Co-coordinator and WP leaders will be established. The project will also have a Steering Committee, with one representative per partner Institute. The Committee will meet during the three annual assemblies planned within PARADISE.

In addition to these, an Advisory Board comprising relevant stakeholders, including a representative from CDC and from EFSA, will be included. Members for the Advisory Board will be recruited at the start of the project. The Board will meet with the coordinators through Skype-meetings, and will be asked for advice on project directions two times in the project period.

Task: JRP-PARADISE-WP1-T1 T-0.1 Management, coordination and communication

Task start month: **M25**; Task end month: **M54**

Task Leader: **Simone M Cacciò, ISS**; Deputy Task Leader: **Karin Troell, SVA**

Task Participants: **ANSES, BFR, FOHM, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PIWET, RIVM, RKI, SLV, SSI, SVA, UoS, VRI, BIOR, CRU, HZAU, JLU, NMBU, UoM**

Description of the task :

- WP1-T1 takes place over the first, second, and third annual period of the project.

This task will include communication to all partners about project progress, upcoming deadlines, follow-up of deliverable completion, and reporting of deliverables to the OHEJP.

Coordination and management of the project. A PARADISE Management Team (PAMT) comprising the Coordinator, Co-coordinator and WP leaders will be established. Throughout the project, the PAMT will have regular teleconferences (at least four times per year or more often, if needed) to

communicate across WPs and ensure that the work flow within and between WPs proceeds as expected. A common platform will be set up to facilitate sharing of information and documents. Adherence to H2020 rules regarding e.g. ethics, dissemination and publication will be ensured. The Coordinator at ISS will support all partners in the project with any questions regarding financial or procurement of goods and services.

In Y4, an Annual meeting (AM) will be organized by OKI (Budapest, Hungary) where the consortium participants discuss and integrate all results in view of their dissemination to the scientific community and the public.

WP: JRP-PARADISE_WP2 NGS-based genomics and metagenomics

Task start month: **M25**; Task end month: **M52**

WP Leader: **Yannick Blanchard, ANSES**; WP Deputy: **Simone M Cacciò, ISS**

WP Participants; **ANSES, BFR, FOHM, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PIWET, RIVM, RKI, SLV, SSI, SVA, UoS, VRI**

Description of the WP:

- WP2 takes place over the first, the second and the third annual period of the project.

WP2 aims at 1) generating novel genome data from selected isolates of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (WP2-T1); 2) using *in silico* approaches and a referenced database to interrogate available metagenomes to detect foodborne parasites (WP2-T2); and 3) using amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics approaches to detect target parasites using spiked food matrices (WP2-T3).

Task: JRP-PARADISE-WP2-T2 *In silico* analyses of metagenomes for detection of foodborne parasites (protozoa and helminths)

Task start month **M25**; Task end month **M52**

Task Leader: **Frits Franssen, RIVM**; Deputy Task Leader: **Yannick Blanchard, ANSES**.

Task Participants: **RIVM, ISS, SSI, VRI**

Description of the task:

- WP2-T2 takes place over the first, second and third annual period of the project.

This task will continue to interrogate metagenomes from human and animal gut microbiomes, environmental samples (soil, water, and wastewater/sludge), and food (plant-related), for the detection of foodborne parasites. It is anticipated that the number of publicly available metagenomes will considerably increase during the project. In parallel, raw sequence reads from the experimental amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics study planned in WP2-T3 will be processed at RIVM with the established pipeline. This will inform on important parameters of the metagenomics approaches, including the limit of detection for the different target parasites used to spike food.

Task: JRP-PARADISE-WP2-T3 Experimental amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics for detection of foodborne parasites

Task start month **M25**; Task end month **M52**

Task Leader: **Rune C. Stensvold, SSI**; Deputy task Leader: **Petr Kralik, VRI**

Task Participants: **SSI, ISS, RIVM, VRI**

Description of the task:

- WP3-T3 takes place over the first, second and third annual period of the project.

This task will continue by applying amplicon-based and metagenomics approaches to spiked food matrices. Ready-to-eat vegetables (cut vegetable, sprouts) will be spiked with known number of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts. The spiking dose will range from 10^1 to 10^4 to reflect the low infective dose of these parasites for humans and the low level of contamination observed in naturally contaminated food. Food will be spiked and processed at VRI. Parasites will be eluted from

the food in a buffer solution using a stomacher, the eluates will be centrifuged and DNA isolated from pelleted material by robust commercially available kits (e.g., FastDNA for soil). The DNAs will be distributed to partners (SSI, ISS) for metagenomics experiments in order to determine performance and level of detection. The performance parameters of the two metagenomics approaches will be assessed by comparison with qPCR assays established at VRI for the quantification of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*.

Description of work

WP: JRP-PARADISE_WP3 Design, implementation and validation of multi-locus typing schemes

Task start month **M25**; Task end month **M54**

WP Leader: **Karin Troell, SVA**; Deputy WP Leader: **Christian Klotz, RKI**

WP participants: **ANSES, BFR, FOHM, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PIWET, RIVM, RKI, SLV, SSI, SVA, UoS, VRI**

Description of the WP :

- WP3 takes place over the first, the second and the third annual period of the project.

Based on WGS data generated in WP2-T1, and on those available from within the consortium and public databases, this WP aims to identify new markers suitable for robust genotyping (WP3-T1). The new markers will be tested by expert laboratories and the markers and typing approach will be iteratively developed with WP3-T1 until respective typing protocols are produced (WP3-T2). The protocols will then be assessed for performance parameters by inter-laboratory comparison (WP3-T3).

Task: JRP-PARADISE-WP3-T1 *In silico* selection of informative loci from comparative genomics data.

Task start month **M25**, Task end month **M42**

Task Leader: **Christian Klotz, RKI**; Deputy Task Leader : **Karin Troell, SVA**

Task Participants: **RKI, SVA, ISS**

Description of the task :

- WP3-T1 takes place over the first and second annual period of the project.

This task will continue to use the data and information generated in WP2-T1, as well as data already generated by consortium members, to provide a comparative analysis of all available genome sequence data from which a suite of unlinked multi-locus sequence markers will be identified. This analysis will be performed separately for the two parasites, *C. parvum* (at SVA) and *G. duodenalis* (at RKI). It is expected that a larger set of WGS data from WP2-T1 will be available in Y4 to confirm suitability of the identified markers from year 1. Depending on the results, re-evaluation of new and more suitable markers will be performed, and further tested by WP3-T2.

Loci will be selected based on: (i) sufficient physical distance between loci to minimize genetic linkage; (ii) coverage of all chromosomes; (iii) high genetic variability across genomes; (iv) *in silico* specificity for *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis*. Suitability of the selected markers for MLST approaches will be tested within Task 3.2, and iteratively improved until appropriate discrimination of parasite strains will be possible.

Task : JRP-PARADISE-WP3-T2 Development of MLST schemes for *G. duodenalis* and *C. parvum*

Task start month **M31**; Task end month **M50**

Task Leader: **Martha Betson, UoS**; Deputy Task Leader: **Simone M. Cacciò, ISS**

Task Participants: **ANSES, BFR, FOHM, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PIWET, RIVM, RKI, SLV, SSI, SVA, UoS, VRI**

Description of the task :

- WP3-T2 takes place over the first, second and third annual period of the project.

The iterative approach will be further employed in collaboration with WP3-T1 to ensure selection of the most appropriate markers for the MLST scheme. PCR amplification and Sanger sequencing will be used for marker typing, as this technology is readily available across the EU, the cost is continually decreasing and it allows detection of all SNPs in the loci of interest. However, alternative methods such as restriction fragment length polymorphism or fragment length analysis of microsatellites will also be considered. A collection of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* isolates of human, animal, water and food origin, covering different EU regions and additional countries is currently available within the project consortium. This includes about 900 *C. parvum* and 600 *G. duodenalis* samples. Markers will initially be tested on a smaller group of samples representing parasites of different genotypes and from different geographical regions. The marker panel will be refined to a smaller set markers (approximately 6-10 markers expected) based on ease of amplification and typing, and ability to discriminate between parasite strains. Subsequently, the refined marker set will be tested on the complete sample collection to assess parameters such as typability and resolution. The four expert laboratories involved in WP3-T-2 have strong experience with *Cryptosporidium* and/or *Giardia* genotyping. After validation, a typing protocol will be developed for each parasite. It is envisaged that the protocols will be flexible depending on the resolution required, with the possibility of using a smaller marker set for particular applications. Validation of marker should be completed at the end of the second year of the project. Of note, the data generated during the marker validation will also provide the opportunity to conduct an analysis of the population structure of *C. parvum* and of *G. duodenalis* across Europe.

Task : JRP-PARADISE-WP3-T3 Inter-laboratory comparison of MLST schemes

Task start month **M43**; Task end month **M54**

Task Leader: **Anne Mayer-Scholl, BfR** ; Deputy Task Leader: **Jeroen Roelfsema, RIVM**

Task Participants: **ANSES, BFR, FOHM, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PIWET, RIVM, RKI, SLV, SSI, SVA, UoS, VRI**

Description of the task :

- WP3.3 takes place only over the second and third year of the project

Based on the MLST protocols for each parasite, an inter-laboratory comparison will be organized between all partners to assess their robustness and reproducibility. BfR will distribute extracted DNA samples of 8-10 MLST types per pathogen and reagents needed to perform the test, which will be shipped under controlled conditions. In the second annual period, the MLST protocols will be implemented at the BfR. In preparation of the inter-laboratory comparison, homogeneity and stability of selected samples will be assessed, and a questionnaire focusing on technical details and practicability of the method (including equipment used, any variation to the protocols, hands-on and turnaround times, problems encountered) created.

Description of work

WP : JRP-PARADISE_WP4 Parasite enrichment strategies

WP start month **M25**; WP end month **M54**

WP Leader **Marco Lalle, ISS**; Deputy WP Leader: **Mats Isaksson, SVA**

WP participants **ISS, SVA, RKI, ANSES, VRI, INIAV, FOHM, SLV, SSI, RIVM**

Description of the WP :

- WP4 takes place over the first, the second and the third annual period of the project.

In Y4, WP4 continues based upon what achieved during the first annual period of the project. The objectives are the development and inter-laboratory comparison of i) two pre-DNA extraction protocols based on new affinity reagents (nanobodies and aptamers) for magnetic capture of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in different matrices; ii) a protocol for post-DNA extraction enrichment strategy to concentrate parasite DNA based on hybridization of target-specific biotinylated probes.

Task : JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP4-T1 Development of pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

Task start month **M25**; Task end month **M54**

Task Leader: **Christian Klotz, RKI**; Deputy Task Leader: **Gregory Karadjian, ANSES**

Task Participants: **RKI, ANSES, ISS, SVA, VRI**

Description of the task

- WP4-T1 takes place over the first, the second and the third annual period of the project.

In Y4, WP4-T1 continues based upon what achieved during the first annual period of the project. Establishment of magnetic capture procedures for (oo)cyst enrichment in different matrices (i.e. fresh produce, feces, water) using new affinity reagents (nanobodies and aptamers). Nanobodies and fluorochrome-tagged aptamers will be further characterized for binding to *C. parvum* and/or *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts by flow cytometry and fluorescence microscopy.

Aptamers identified in Y3 will be synthesized with a biotin tag (Apt) and incubated with magnetic beads tagged with streptavidin (MB) to generate an Apt-MB complex able to capture and retain the (oo)cysts on a magnetic separator stand. Similarly, selected nanobodies will be coupled to magnetic beads using the most appropriate approach to retain binding capacity (e.g., biotinylated nanobodies). The specificity and sensitivity of the procedure to capture *C. parvum* and/or *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts spiked in different matrices will be evaluated. The performance parameters will be compared to those of the available ISO standard for detection of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* (oo)cys in water and selected vegetables. Commercially available fluorescent labelled *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* (oo)cysts will be used for spiking.

Task: JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP4-T2 Development of post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

Task start month **M25**; Task end month **M54**

Task Leader: **Mats Isaksson, SVA**; Deputy Task Leader : **Marieke Opsteegh, RIVM**

Task Participants: **RKI, ANSES, VRI, SVA, FOHM, SLV, INIAV, RIVM**

Description of the task :

- WP4-T2 takes place over the first, the second and the third annual period of the project.

The objective of this task is the development and evaluation of a protocol for post-DNA extraction enrichment based on sequence-based capture of low abundance target DNA in matrices such as faeces, water (drinking, recreational and wastewater as well as washing water from fresh produce) and archived DNA from suspected foodborne outbreaks. WP4 participants will test the developed strategies by in a ring test.

In Y4, WP4-T2 continues based upon what achieved during the first annual period of the project, towards the establishment of hybridization probe magnetic capture procedures for enrichment of DNA sequences of *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in different matrices (i.e. feces, different types of

water, and archived DNA material). SVA and RIVM will test and optimize the magnetic procedure system as soon as appropriate probes will be available. For this purpose, individual or mixed *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* DNA at different concentration will be used to spike different matrices. Although a standard molecular test is not available for *Cryptosporidium* or *Giardia*, the sensitivity of detection between enriched and non-enriched samples will be compared based on qPCR protocols established at VRI. In the case of *Cryptosporidium*, the qPCR guideline experimentally defined by the EFSA founded project IMPACT will also be considered. A protocol will be prepared and further used by inter-laboratory comparison.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.2	Report of Annual meeting	M42
D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.2	Report on the FBPs detected in metagenomics datasets by <i>in silico</i> analysis	M48
D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2	Report on the identification of MLST markers for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M42
D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.3	SOPs for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> MLST schemes	M48
D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3	Report on the probes designed to targets developed in WP3 for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M44

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP-PARADISE-14	Annual meeting (WP1)	M42
M-JRP-PARADISE-15	Technical Workshop on enrichment strategies (WP4)	M42
M-JRP-PARADISE-16	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>C. parvum</i> available	M42
M-JRP-PARADISE-17	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>G. duodenalis</i> available	M42
M-JRP-PARADISE-18	Technical Workshop for training on MLST (WP3)	M48
M-JRP-PARADISE-19	Validation of marker for typability and resolution accomplished	M48
M-JRP-PARADISE-20	Magnetic bead coupled nanobodies suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M48
M-JRP-PARADISE-21	Magnetic bead coupled aptamers suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M48
M-JRP-PARADISE-22	Hybridization probes tested for robustness and sensitivity available	M48

2.4.2.1.18 JRP06-R1-FBZ1-NOVA

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)			FBZ 1: Improved surveillance system and harmonized data analyses							
Research Project Title			Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain							
Research Project Acronym			NOVA							
Leading Organisation			P41-SVA				Deputy Leading Organisation		P13-SSI	
Project Leader			Jenny Frössling				Deputy Project leader		Steen Ethelberg	
Project Start month			M1				Project End month		M36	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	11,74		8,67				3,5		5,5	3,5
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M	7			6,5	2				3,32	0,53
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
P.M						3,42		0,64		16
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M	0,5							4,45	15	
Objectives: Integrative research <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of the effect of different surveillance programs in the food production on human health through mathematical modelling • Assessing the effect of using metagenomics in surveillance of foodborne zoonoses. • Developing models to answer questions of cost-efficiency and prioritisation of surveillance • Common framework of terms describing foodborne zoonosis surveillance across sectors 										

- Descriptive mapping of unused potential food-chain surveillance resources across countries and of impediments towards their use

Use of electronic food purchase data for surveillance

- Description by member state of food purchase data sources and their availability
- Structured review of the field of the use of food purchase data for outbreak investigation.
- Manual of how to use food purchase data for outbreak investigations.
- Case control studies of food risk factors for sporadic infections of important pathogens using electronic datasets of food purchase data.
- Analysis of food consumption patterns in hospitals in relation to hospitals outbreaks of foodborne zoonotic diseases.
- Tool for food risk mapping and trace-back as a computer software

Syndromic surveillance tools

- Inventory of data availability, quality and suitability
- Evaluation of statistical syndromic surveillance approaches to detect foodborne diseases outbreaks
- Evaluation of multivariate syndromic surveillance methods for foodborne diseases surveillance

Spatial analysis tools

- Maps of livestock prevalence and geographical patterns of Salmonella transmission in areas of varying infection intensity
- Analyses of the spatio-temporal associations with human salmonella cases
- Geographically aided evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies.
- Assessment of the potential effect of relevant interventions
- Cartographic map of hot spot areas for Salmonella transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.
- Potential new environmental surveillance indicators identified.

Description of work:

See project description by work package (WP) below.

WPO: Coordination and project management

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: Jenny Frössling, SVA

Deputy WP Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

WP participants: SVA, SSI, and all other partners

Description of the WP: WPO continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. This WP will be responsible for all reporting to OHEJP coordinating body and will coordinate 3 annual assemblies during the 3-year project. Because of the large number of partners in the consortium and the need for interaction between WPs, this coordinating WP will play an important role in ensuring that milestones and final deliverables of the consortium are successfully completed and communicated.

The project leader at SVA and a deputy project leader at SSI will collaborate in keeping continuous contact between the WPs and secure dissemination of results. Coordination and communication between WPs is performed in the Project Management Team which includes the project leader and

WP leaders. In Year 4, coordination activities will have an extra focus on dissemination of developed methods and results.

Within NOVA, we originally planned three annual assemblies, where representatives from all partner institutes and other project participants would meet. In 2020, the annual meeting was transformed into an online meeting. Depending on the development of the covid-19 outbreak in Europe, we will decide early 2021 whether to have a final project online or travel for a physical meeting.

T-0.1 Project management

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Jenny Frössling, SVA

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

Task Participants: SVA, SSI, SCIENSANO, ANSES, INIA, DTU

Description of the task: T-0.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. This task will include communication to all partners about project progress, upcoming deadlines, follow-up of deliverable completion, and reporting of deliverables to the EJP. The Project Management Team will have continue having monthly meetings to communicate across WPs and ensure that the work flow within and between WP proceed as expected.

T-0.2 Organise annual assemblies

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Jenny Frössling, SVA

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI, and the partner institutes that will host the meetings

Task Participants: SVA, SSI, and hosting partner institute

Description of the task: T-0.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. During the course of the project two physical assemblies and one online assembly have been held. In Year 4, we plan to have a final meeting.

The purpose of the annual project meetings is to introduce the consortium participants to one another, to discuss how to achieve the defined milestones in the work packages most efficiently, and to present results to the group. In connection to these assemblies, smaller meetings with discussions and planning within WPs also take place.

T-0.3 Economic reporting and financial management

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Anna Nordenfelt, SVA

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

Task Participants: All partners

Description of the task: T-0.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. Upon request, SVA will coordinate replies to the OHEJP coordinating body for financial reporting for the project.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-0.4	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	M42

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
-	-	-

Annual Work Plan
Fourth Year - 2021
M37-M48

WP1: Food chain surveillance mapping

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: Maria Eleni Filippitzi, Sciensano

Deputy WP Leader: Solveig Jore, NIPH

WP participants: SVA, SSI, DTU, ANSES, INIA, NVI, NIPH, RIVM, APHA, BfR, UCM, RKI, FLI, SpFrance, ISS, IZS, PHAS, PHE

Description of the WP: WP1 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the OHEJP. Effective and cost-efficient surveillance demands an integrated approach across the food chain, harmonised practices and communication among the different stakeholders. For the surveillance of foodborne zoonoses, a common understanding of the surveillance systems in place, their potential gaps, and alternative approaches, is needed. In this context, a common language is one important baseline for surveillance communication; i.e. terminology with Med-Vet joint definitions of phrases used to describe, analyse, and evaluate surveillance.

Various methods and tools for collecting information about foodborne pathogens and human health exist or are being developed at national and regional levels. Different stakeholders at different levels of the food chain process reveal different perceptions, needs and priorities. Development and implementation of traditional and new surveillance tools relies on effective communication among the parts involved, an issue particularly important when communication cross-domains is needed.

Objective: This WP aims at aligning perceptions and needs along the food chain, and across the Med-Vet domains, in two main ways: by providing a common language for discussion, and by performing a full mapping of the surveillance opportunities and hurdles along these dimensions. The tasks outlined below aim at analysing the different levels of the food chain in order to obtain a comprehensive overview of the different stakeholders involved as well as their terminology perception, needs and priorities. In addition, this WP aims at identifying stakeholders' perceptions on critical gaps and hurdles reducing the cost effectiveness of surveillance (i.e. legal, ethical and technical barriers to data communication). This, in turn, will enable a comprehensive approach to foodborne zoonosis surveillance optimisation. The study may use one specific pathogen as a proof-of-concept for other foodborne pathogens. Parts of the feed-to-fork data chain analysis may be focused in a specific sector (such as poultry, or pork). The pathogen and sectors will be defined in the start of the task, among partners. This WP will mainly be descriptive and will involve all partners. This WP can be partly linked to and will have continuous contact with the other WPs in this project, as well as WPs in some other OHEJP projects.

T-1.2 Mapping of surveillance: data, regulatory framework, key stakeholders, opportunities and barriers

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Maria Eleni Filippitzi, Sciensano

Deputy Task Leader: Solveig Jore, NIPH

Task Participants: ALL

Description: T-1.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the OHEJP. Within this task the participating partners will make a detailed overview of available surveillance information sources in the different MS, including both databases and other type of sources. Traditional surveillance data, but also all kind of other potential usable data sources such as registers, surveys, and reports, will be included. Understanding the context and drivers to surveillance is critical for designing successful interventions actions and that these intervention actions will only be effective if key players in the system accept them. In this task, the different

surveillance strategies implemented in each MS, and the involved stakeholders, will also be described. This will provide input and support to the other WPs, in particular the simulation of alternative surveillance strategies in WP5. This task will be performed in close collaboration with WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5

Objective: A methodology has been developed and has been currently put in practice to identify barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health perspective. This information has been collected through interviews with professionals with selected profiles from four countries (Belgium, France, Sweden, Norway) and after development of a number of tools: map of food chain (used as a visual tool for cueing), interview guide document, demographic questionnaire, excel files for collection of data, training on performing interviews and qualitative research, interview try-outs.

The 20 interviews have been performed by three WP1 participants who have received the same training on performing interviews. The information collected by the interviewers has been double-checked and validated from the interviewees to ensure credibility. The months from Year 4 will be used to finalize the work of this task. During autumn 2020, the information collected through the interviews performed in previous months will be analysed in a standardized qualitative way. After this step, a report and a manuscript will be then drafted in the first months of Year 4.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-1.2	Mapping of food chain surveillance across countries	M41

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
-	-	-

WP2: Analysis of food purchase data

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI

Deputy WP Leader: Katja Alt, BfR

WP participants: SSI, RKI, BfR, ISS, SpFrance (InVS), PHE, RIVM, SCIENSANO, PHAS, NIPH, NVI, IZS.

Description of the WP: In order to understand the transmission of foodborne diseases it's important to understand food exposures. This is done by applying questionnaires for patients and non-ill control subjects, asking them to report food histories. Often, however, such data are heavily biased or incomplete and their collection costly and difficult to obtain in a timely manner. Therefore, ways to obtain data on everything a patient or household consumes during an outbreak period have been pursued for some years, progressing from manual collection of receipts to capture of electronic purchasing data. Also, purchase data from restaurants or caterers for hospitals or other institutions for vulnerable populations can be tracked. Additionally, information obtained from food sales data (big data covering affected regions) and tracing analyses potentially enhance evidence during outbreak investigations. This WP aims to use food consumption patterns as a new digital surveillance tool to aid our understanding of both outbreaks as well as determinants for sporadic foodborne illness.

Objective: This WP will perform research into how surveillance of food consumption patterns can be used to better understand foodborne zoonoses: to aid surveillance, to explore risk factors and for outbreak investigations.

Structure: The WP is divided into five separate, partly interdependent tasks, each containing subtasks (T-2.1 completed).

T-2.2 Food purchase data for outbreak investigations

Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI.

Deputy Task Leader: Helle Daugaard Larsen, SSI.

Task Participants: SSI, ISS, SpFrance, PHE, BfR, RIVM, SCIENSANO, PHAS, NIPH

Description: We will continue to work within our network of stakeholders from across Europe that have experience or interest in working with CPD in relation to outbreak investigations. Due to the COVID-19 situation, the first manuscript (which is finished) has still not been submitted for publication; hopefully a deeper analysis of the most recent development per country and the new possibilities can also be done. We hope to extend our work with Health Canada; the Canadians are world leaders in using CPD for outbreak investigations.

Secondly, the simulation analyses were also put on complete hold and we hope to do them in Y4 instead. This is a cooperation between FHI and SSI. Following a series of meetings with Norwegian supermarket chains, a large dataset with purchase data from more than 900,000 households has been obtained, a really interesting and otherwise difficult to obtain dataset. This will form the basis for analyses of simulated outbreaks.

T-2.3 Big data analysis of risk factors for sporadic disease

Task Leader: Frederik Trier Møller, SSI.

Deputy Task Leader: Steen Ethelberg, SSI.

Task Participants: SSI, PHAS, PHE, RIVM, NIPH.

Description: We have built a secure webportal to achieve consent from citizens in Denmark for use of their CPD. We hope to send invitations out to registered sporadic cases of salmonella in Denmark

from year 2018 and 2019 and also invite population controls. The aim is then to do a retrospective case-control study for risk factors within the purchase data for salmonellosis.

T-2.4 Food distribution data for hospital outbreaks

Task Leader: Hendrik Wilking, RKI.
Deputy Task Leader: Sebastian Haller, RKI.
Task Participants: RKI, IZS, ISS.

Description: This task has fulfilled all its deliverables, but the group will keep working on the data that have been collected. It would be interesting to extend the results made for Germany and Italy to more countries in Europe, building on what we now know.

T-2.5 Trace back and food risk mapping

Task Leader: Katja Alt, BfR.
Deputy Task Leader: Madelaine Norström, NVI.
Task Participants: BfR, NVI, NIPH, ISS.

Description: T-2.5 has also been paused due to COVID-19. The remaining work aims to develop the published likelihood-based tool so that it handles data on time together with GTIN and to decide on ways to handle inaccurate and missing information on case purchase patterns and distribution patterns. Further, to be able to import available food sales and eventually food purchase data structures into FoodChain-Lab.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-2.4	Assessment of the use of the method as an analytical tool, rather than merely hypothesis-generation.	M42
D-JRP6-2.6	Case control study of food risk factors for sporadic campylobacter infections.	M42
D-JRP6-2.10	Description and documentation of software, development of tutorials and training material.	M42

Milestones

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WP3. Syndromic surveillance

WP start month: M1
WP end month: M42
WP Leader: Adeline Huneau, ANSES
Deputy WP Leader: Fernanda Dórea, SVA
WP participants: ANSES, NIPH, SVA, NVI

Description of the WP: WP3 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP.

Task 3.3. Evaluation of multivariate syndromic surveillance for FBD

Task start month: M11
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: Gry Marysol Grøneng, NIPH
Deputy Task Leader: Fernanda Dórea, SVA
Task Participants: NIPH, SVA, NVI, ANSES, SCIENSANO

Description: T-3.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. In addition, Y4 will be devoted to publication of results.

Objective: Assess whether the combination of surveillance results from different SyS components could lead to an improvement of the surveillance system for the selected FDB cases study. That is, to investigate how results from different SyS components, developed in Task 2, can support the evidence from the others, and lead to improved decision making. Different strategies are tested in Task 3: the combination of several algorithms and tools for result visualization, inclusion of additional time series as explanatory factors (e.g climate time series) and the development of detection algorithms that can process temporal signals from correlated time series simultaneously.

Method: We will combine results from independent monitoring of epidemiological data (along the food chain), to monitor FDB risk from farm to fork. A possible example of case study is the use of the results from veterinary and food monitoring system such as *Campylobacter* detection in broilers and meat, to support results from the human syndromic surveillance system based on primary health consultations for gastro- intestinal diseases (Sykdomspulsen) in Norway. Another example will be based on Salmonella surveillance along the food production chain in France (following results from univariate analysis presented in deliverable 3.5).

Result: Identify possible methods to improve the global surveillance by integrating and consolidating results from different sources across the med-vet domains.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
-	-	-

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
-	-	-

WP4: Spatial risk mapping

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: Ana de la Torre, INIA

Deputy WP Leader: Stefan Widgren, SVA

WP participants: INIA, RIVM, UCM-VISAVET, SSI, SVA, FLI, CODA

Description of the WP: The WP continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. This WP deals with the development of modelling tools for spatial analysis of FBZ and the identification and assessment of new surveillance indicators/risk factors. Spatial epidemiological tools are increasingly being applied for the study of emerging zoonoses, partly because of improving analytical methods and technologies for data capture and management, and partly because the demand for more objective ways of allocating limited resources in the face of the emerging threat posed by these diseases is growing.

Objective: This WP performs research into how spatial analysis can improve the knowledge on disease behaviour (spatio-temporal patterns) and identify risk factors/indicators for designing efficient risk-based surveillance strategies and favour timely interventions. Following the recommendation of the Special report on eradication, control and monitoring programmes to contain animal diseases (EU, 2016), new indicators related to the environment, including wildlife, will be explored to optimize the effectiveness of surveillance programs.

Scope: The practical approach of this WP will be done using *Salmonella* infection in swine as a proof of concept. *Salmonella* has been selected as example of FBD as it is one of the most common public health problems, causing significant human morbidity and even mortality and consequently high economic losses in both developing and developed countries. Foods of animal origin are still one of the major sources of infection for the general public, with eggs, broiler chickens and pigs being consistently identified among the top attributed food sources. Whereas control programmes for *Salmonella* in poultry have been applied in the whole UE with high success, only few European countries have implemented eradication or control programmes of *Salmonella* in swine, beef, or dairy production. Results from efforts made in Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Norway, Ireland, Germany, Great Britain and Holland, are somewhat inconsistent. So far, there are no national control programmes established in any Mediterranean country, where >40% of the pig farms were positive to *Salmonella* (EFSA baseline study, 2009). In consequence, further efforts to implement control programs for reduction of the prevalence of *Salmonella* infection in swine in the near future are envisioned. Prerequisites to the implementation of such an approach; scientific efforts directed to improve our preparedness and develop an effective risk-based surveillance system should be carried out. Results from this WP would also be relevant for surveillance of many other FBZ diseases, as the explored risk mapping techniques and developed tools will be generic.

Structure: The WP is divided into 3 tasks. Task 4.1 has been completed and dealt with disease behaviour to identify spatial relationships and patterns in *Salmonella* prevalence in livestock, slaughterhouses and its association with human cases. Task 4.2 and Task 4.3 deals with the identification of new risk factors, namely animal feed (Task 4.2) and wildlife and the environment (Task 4.3).

Links with other WP: The current *Salmonella* surveillance programmes compiled under WP1 will be reviewed to identify the main requirements for applying risk mapping techniques. Data on *Salmonella* prevalence in livestock and human will be explored through the source data explored in WP3. Usefulness of the risk mapping tools developed and new risk factors identified will be evaluated in close collaboration with WP5, where alternative surveillance approaches will be tested. Results applicability: The spatio-temporal patterns of disease occurrence in livestock and human would allow finding an optimized strategy for each epidemiological scenario, e.g. by identifying high risk administrative areas to focus resources for prevention and control of diseases. The identification of new surveillance indicators will allow designing more cost-effective surveillance and control strategies as recommended in the special report on eradication, control and monitoring programmes to contain animal diseases (EU, 2016). Finally, the cartographic map of hot spot areas for *Salmonella* will improve disease awareness in pig producers and hunters, and development of contingency plans and control strategies in EU member states with low biosecurity farms.

All the information generated will be available at the Internet as interactive high resolutions maps, graphs and visual information. As such it will improve the technology transference of on-going research effort and help educators, veterinarians, technicians and policy makers to better understand, evaluate and fight FBD.

Task 4.2. Risk of introduction of *Salmonella* in pig farms through animal feed.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: UCM-VISAVET

Deputy Task Leader: INIA

Task Participants: INIA, UCM-VISAVET, SCIENSANO

Description of the task: T-4.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. *Salmonella* present in animal feed is a significant source of infection in pigs. In order to develop systems for its inclusion in risk assessment/mapping, feeding flows for some of the largest swine systems in high prevalence regions will be described and mapped.

Objective: The aim of this task is to assess the risk of *Salmonella* introduction in pig farms through contaminated animal feed.

Methods: The spatial network structure (feed plants-swine farms) has been explored by spatial analysis techniques (e.g. spatial modelling, network analyses) [M1-M12]. Data on prevalence of *Salmonella* infection, and serotypes and antimicrobial resistance patterns in intensively managed pig farms has been explored in combination with information on animal feed data to analyse the importance of unsterilized animal feed in the introduction of *Salmonella* in the farms and to improve zoonotic hazard management in the pork food chain [M13-M24]. Using this model, the potential effect of changes in feed management will be explicitly considered and evaluated [M25-M42]. The original plan was to focus this study on formaldehyde-based feed treatments, however, because formaldehyde is now forbidden in the EU, we are evaluating changing focus to the use of surveillance AMR data for monitoring emergence of *Salmonella* strains in swine (UCM).

Outcome: Characterize the feeding flows for large swine systems in a high prevalence region using sociograms. Assess the potential effect of changes in feed conservation treatments.

Task 4.3. Role of the environment in the occurrence and maintenance of *Salmonella* infection in extensive farming.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: INIA

Deputy Task Leader: RIVM

Task Participants: INIA, UCM-VISAVET, RIVM, FLI, SCIENSANO

Description of the task: T-4.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. Wildlife often serves as a reservoir for (re-)emerging zoonoses. Infection of wildlife or vectors is frequently linked to environmental and climatic conditions, which largely take place outside the field of view of medical and veterinary experts and affect transmission in a complex manner. This lack of insight in the mechanisms that drive the occurrence and spread of wildlife zoonoses hinders appropriate risk assessment and the development of interventions to reduce public health risks, particularly in a changing environment.

Objective: The aim of this task is to investigate the overlap between habitats of suitable wildlife, e.g. wild boar, with primary production and other environmental variables, which may influence transmission of pathogens from wildlife to livestock farming. *Salmonella* transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems such as extensive farming-oriented systems or backyard farms will be selected as a working example. It will be studied in selected Mediterranean countries, e.g. Spain, where this type of non-controlled housing is present and there is a high prevalence of infection in livestock.

Methods: First, available data on infection and serotype prevalence in extensively managed pig farms have been mapped and analysed to characterize its spatial distribution and identify patterns, processes, and relationships (e.g. smoothing technique, cluster analyses) [M1-M12]. Second, hot spot areas with higher potential for *Salmonella* transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity

systems have been identified by overlapping wild boar distribution maps (Bosch et al., 2016), extensive farming systems geodata and known serotype spatial distribution (spatial autocorrelation analyses) [M13-M24]. Finally, state-of-the art machine learning algorithms will be employed to correlate infection data with environmental drivers. They will be spatially explored and analysed through Bayesian classical and stochastic modelling approaches (correlating covariates, expert opinion, mapping techniques....) to assess their availability/competence as surveillance indicators [M25-M42]. Reliable data of paramount importance will be gathered from free sources such as 'worldclim' (climate), 'CORINE' (land-use) and 'MODIS' (satellite imagery). The model will be an extension of a previously developed model, which was successfully used for tick presence forecasting. In Year 4, activities will focus on presentation and dissemination of results .

Outcome: A high-quality cartographic map of hot spot areas will be developed that would help to understand and visualize risk scenarios to make decisions based on the best available information. This tool could also be potentially used for implementing the surveillance systems of other FBZ diseases shared between wild boar and domestic pigs, as trichinellosis. Identification of potential new surveillance indicators will be shared with WP5, where alternative surveillance approaches will be tested.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-4.6	Assessment of the potential effect of the withdrawal of the use of formaldehyde-based feed treatments done.	M42

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
-	-	-

WP5: Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: Håkan Vigre, DTU

Deputy WP-leader: Eric Evers, RIVM

WP Participants: DTU, SVA, APHA, RIVM, ANSES, SCIENSANO, FLI

Description of the WP: WP5 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the OHEJP. To support the identification and prioritization of control measures in food production, mathematical models have become an important tool as they help a risk manager to predict the effect of different intervention strategies. Thus far, different mathematical frameworks have been developed for i) estimating the occurrence of pathogens in the food chain e.g QMRA), ii) develop probability theorems around sampling and detection of pathogens, iii) estimate the importance of different sources for human disease (source attribution) and iv) estimate the consequence of different diseases (burden of disease).

The overall objective of this WP is to develop modelling approaches to predict the impact of surveillance programs applied in the food production chain on human exposure and public health. Initially, all models will be developed using case-studies focusing on specific pathogen-food combinations that are of primary importance to the public health within the EU. Each case study will utilise nation and region specific data within the farm to fork approach (e.g. population structure in animal production systems, prevalence and concentration of pathogens in animals or specific food products, consumption patterns and food handling by consumers). These will then be used to develop a framework that can be applied to other pathogens and food items. The output will be a modelling-tool that will form the scientific basis for the design of surveillance programs across Europe, which will enhance the comparability of surveillance data between countries.

The novelty in this WP is that it will combine and further develop currently segregated mathematical frameworks to model the efficiency of different surveillance programs in a human health and cost efficiency context. This approach will advance the focus on human health impact when developing surveillance programs in food production, thereby optimizing decisions about how to distribute limited capacity for surveillance.

T-5.1: Adapt infectious disease models for assessing the effect of surveillance programs in primary animal production on consumer exposure to foodborne pathogens.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Mark Arnold APHA

Deputy Task Leader: Thomas Rosendal, SVA

Task Participants: APHA, DTU, SVA, SCIENSANO

Description of the task: T-5.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the OHEJP. In this task we adapt existing risk assessment models for foodborne zoonotic pathogens to include modules for simulating the effect of surveillance programs (detection and control) in the food-chain on human exposure to zoonotic pathogens.

sT-5.1.1

Sub-Task Leader: Mark Arnold, APHA

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, SVA, DTU

For several foodborne zoonoses, the difficulty of detection is compounded by the lack of clinical signs in the animals. Therefore, improved surveillance measures are required to detect infected animals, and thus limit the exposure of humans to contaminated products by prevention of further spread in the animal population, and/or withdrawal of products from the market. The objective of this task is to adapt existing models for the transmission of Salmonella in pigs in GB (PHA), in cattle in SWE (SVA) and in eggs in DK (DTU) to (i) take into account the effect surveillance activities on consumer exposure to Salmonella and (ii) if applicable, adapt the models to represent additional pathogens.

sT-5.1.2

Sub-Task Leader: Thomas Rosendal, SVA

Sub-Task Participants: SVA, Sciensano

The surveillance layer of existing models describing spread of a food-borne zoonosis in an animal population will be adapted to generate different global metrics of performance. These will include: time to detection, extent of an outbreak, spread at the time of detection and animal population strata affected. Other surveillance metrics will also be explored to find those that are most descriptive in situations of endemic disease, freedom from disease and low prevalence disease states. These metrics will be used to assess different surveillance strategies and their capacity to minimize the exposure of foodborne pathogens among the citizens in a country or region in case of an outbreak or change in prevalence of disease in the animal population.

T-5.3 Modelling the effect of surveillance programs in the food production on human health.

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Eric Evers, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: DBD

Task Participants: RIVM, APHA, DTU, SVA, SCIENSANO, FLI, ANSES

Description of the task: T-5.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. We broaden the assessment of surveillance from one specific pathogen-food combination at a specific stage in the food chain to surveillance of different pathogens in several food production chains simultaneously up until the moment of consumption. Disability Adjusted Life

Years (DALYs) will be used as a consistent measure for the subsequent public health risk. Accounting for mortality, severity and duration of a disease in a single method is a powerful tool to compare the actual health impact of a given intervention in the surveillance of different zoonoses.

sT-5.3.1.

Sub-Task Leader: Håkan Vigre, DTU

Sub-Task Participants: DTU, ANSES, RIVM, FLI

In this subtask we develop a model consisting of parallel parts for surveillance of a pathogen in several sources based on the cases studies in sT-5.1.1 (Salmonella in egg, pork, poultry and beef). The objective is to combine the effect on human health based on individual surveillance programs into an overall effect on human health when different programs are combined. Connecting surveillance in several sources allows the simulation of changing the distribution of surveillance capacity across sources. This modelling approach will consider countries having several sources for a zoonotic infection (e.g. *Salmonella* in pork from Denmark is one source and *Salmonella* in pork from France is another source, and so on). By parameterizing each country-specific model by country-specific data and weighting the contribution from each country by import/export data, this approach can support the prioritization of surveillance across European countries.

sT-5.3.2

Sub-Task Leader: Eric Evers, RIVM

Sub-Task Participants: RIVM, DTU, SVA, FLI, ANSES, SCIENSANO, APHA

In this subtask we develop a modelling approach for optimizing the distribution of sampling capacity of different food safety authorities in the EU over products in retail according to their contribution to the microbiological public health risk in a most cost-efficient way. DALYs will be used as a consistent measure for the public health risk of different food pathogens over Europe. Exposure assessment (including consumption data and food preparation at home) from St-5.3.1 will be combined with DALYs and a monitoring budget to define an optimizing criterion for risk based sampling. The method has already been implemented in The Netherlands for *Campylobacter* in pork and poultry, *Salmonella* and *Toxoplasma gondii* in pork, Shiga-toxin producing *E. coli* and ESBL *E.coli* in beef. In this subtask we will improve the current methodology through the contribution of other data sources as identified in this project (e.g. retail purchase data following the EFSA zoonoses report) and other methods for surveillance.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP6-5.1	Report comparing performance of surveillance strategies	M42
D-JRP6-5.2	Recommendations for metrics to evaluate surveillance performance	M42
D-JRP6-5.4	Report assessing the quantitative effect on human health of changing surveillance capacity across different sources in an MS	M42

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
-	-	-

2.4.2.1.19 JRP10-R1-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 3: Biosecurity and other interventions								
Research Project Title		Monitoring the gut microbiota and immune response to predict, prevent and control zoonoses in humans and livestock in order to minimize the use of antimicrobials.								
Research Project Acronym		MoMIR-PPC								
Leading Organisation		P19-INRAE			Deputy Leading Organisation			P17-UCM		
Project Leader		Velge Philippe			Deputy Project leader			María Ugarte Ruiz		
Project Start month		M1			Project End month			M42		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	0,85			8		3,85				
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M					1		5,5			
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
P.M	0				4,25		19,91		1,46	6,90
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
P.M										
<p>Objectives: We will finalize the analysis of the data obtained for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of tools to predict Super-shedder animals and human prolonged <i>Salmonella</i> carriers - Development of pro- and pre-biotics to prevent the appearance of Super-shedders - Development of new models of pathogen transmission - Development of new intervention strategies to fight zoonotic pathogens <p>Dissemination of the original information acquired during this project</p>										
Description of work:										

Heterogeneity of infection is influenced by a complex set of variables involving the intestinal microbiota, mucosal immunity, intestinal physiology and pathogen adaptation to its host. This phenotype has been observed in pigs and chickens. We have demonstrated that immune status before infection can modulate *Salmonella* infection and we can transfer the Super shedder phenotype through transfer of gut microbiota. These results open new avenues to identify immunological and microbiota markers that are associated to high/low shedding and thus to predict the animals which will be Super shedders.

In these WP, we will analyze 1- immunological and microbiota parameters related to the super/low shedder phenotypes and to chronic infection in humans, as well as the modification of *Salmonella* virulence; 2- the effect of pre- and pro-biotics on the *Salmonella* colonization levels under experimental and field conditions; 3- parameters involved in transmission to improve mathematical models of transmission of zoonotic agents, which will allow us to refine intervention strategies on livestock farms.

WPO: Management

WPO takes place throughout the project
WP Leader: **P19-Tours** Philippe Velge
Deputy WP Leader: **P16**, María Ugarte
Ruiz WP participants: **All partners**

Description of the WP:

WPO exists to ensure effective and efficient management of the project. The objectives of this work package are:

☐ To facilitate communications and collaboration between partners and with the EC and its representatives. To coordinate the technical work carried out in the project across all work packages

- To ensure that the project objectives are achieved within the planned time and budget and provide management reports to the EC.
- To ensure the quality of work including deliverables; to track technical and financial risks to the project and manage the response to ameliorate them.

The majority of the tasks has been finished, we will continue the tasks:

Task-0.3 Control and manage activity progresses, the timely delivery of project tasks and outputs

T-0.3 takes place over the project

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: **P19-Tours**, Philippe Velge
Task Participants: **All partners**

Description of the task:

The steering committee will have the responsibility for ensuring that milestones and deliverables will be accomplished on time. **He will facilitate the day-to-day running of the project.** These will include regular and effective communication, troubleshooting and the overseeing of general administrative duties.

Task-0.4 Control and manage the project closure and outputs

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: **P18-Tours**, Philippe Velge
Deputy Task Leader: **P18-Tours**, Beatrice Laroche
Task Participants: **All partners**

Description of the task:

The final meeting was scheduled to take place at the University of Surrey in Autumn 2020. However, in line with COVID-19 guidance, this meeting will now be a virtual meeting. Due to the extension of the project, and depending of the evolution of the COVID-19 restrictions measures, it may be possible to organize a final meeting in May 2021, where stakeholder could be invited. The closing meeting will also facilitate discussion about future initiatives.

Project closure plans will be developed in line with Horizon 2020 requirements and OHEJP rules.

WP1: Risk prediction for Super-shedder animals and human prolonged *Salmonella* carriers through the use of gut microbiota and immune status analyses.

WP1 takes place over the first and the second annual period of the

WP end month: **M40**

WP Leader: **P23**, Roberto La Ragione

Deputy WP Leader: **P29**, Giovanni Loris Alborali

WP participants: **P1, P8, P19, P23, P27, P29, P32**

Description of the WP:

The goal of this WP is to identify immunological and microbiota markers that are associated to high/low shedding before and/or after infection, which allow us to predict and identify the animals which will be Super shedders. For this WP, we will use already developed infection models (P1, 19 and 27) but also animal (Task 1 and 2) and human infections (Task 3) in “field condition” (P29, P32). Taking into account the great adaptability of pathogens for their hosts, the virulence and immunogenicity of *Salmonella* strains of animal origins and from high and low-shedders will be compared (P19-Tours). The gut microbiota composition (P8, P23), the cellular biomarkers and the immune response parameters (P19, P27, P29) will be studied with the same chickens and pigs. **The final year will be devoted to the analysis of the data recovered the first years in order to define the markers associated to high and low shedders.**

This WP is divided into 4 tasks:

Task-1.1: Predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

T-1.1 takes place over the first and the second annual period

of the EJP Task start month: M37

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: **P27**, Barbara Chirullo

Deputy Task Leader: **P1**, Martine Denis

Task Participants: **P1, P19-Tours, P27, P29**

Description of the task:

The goal of the task will be to identify immune markers able to identify the high-Shedders and other able to predict the most susceptible animals and/or the animals that will become super-

shedders, if infected. All the experiments have been finished and the Deliverable should be upload before M37. The corresponding articles should be submitted during this period

Task-1.2: Predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

Task end month: 40

Task Leader: **P8**, Ivan Rychlick

Deputy Task Leader: **P23**, Roberto La Ragione

Task Participants: **P1, P8, P19-Tours, P23, P27, P29, P32**

Description of the task:

The goal of the task is to analyse the gut microbiota composition before and after *Salmonella* infection in pig and poultry to identify Predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens. Samples from poultry and pigs (P1, P19, P27, P29) will be analyzed (P8 and P22 respectively) based on Illumina sequencing of V3/V4 variable region of 16S rRNA genes and the microbiomes related to shedding status for *Salmonella*.

All animal experiments have been performed. Analysis of the chicken experiments has been done. Analysis of the data from pigs will continue during this period.

Task-1.3: Risk factors associated with prolonged convalescent *Salmonella* shedding in humans

T-1.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first periods of the EJP

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: **P32**, Mohammed Umaer Naseer

Task Participants: **P32**

Description of the task:

Sample collection has started on the 1st of January 2019. The recruitment of study participants continued until the 31st of December 2019, to complete a full year of sampling. In total 323 participants sent stool samples and questionnaires. The local laboratory cultured the stool samples. For the moment, sequencing of all the isolates received at the NIPH is ongoing until M36. Data analysis is about to commence (to be done by M42). Completion of metagenome sequencing and analyses of selected samples is due by M42.

Task-1.4: Virulence of *Salmonella* strains originated from high and low shedders

T-1.4 will be finished before Y4

Task Leader: **P19-Tours**, Ignacio Caballero

Deputy Task Leader: **P23**, Roberto La Ragione

Task Participants: **P19-Tours, P23,**

Description of the task:

This task will be finished before M37.

WP2: Prevention of the appearance of Super-shedders by modifying feed and/or microbiota

WP end month: **M42**

WP Leader: **P16** VISA VET-UCM. Antonio Rodríguez Bertos

Deputy WP Leader: **P29**, Giovanni Loris Alborali

WP participants: **P6, P8, P17, P19-Tours, P23, P27, P29,**

Description of the WP:

Production animals when infected by a foodborne pathogen such as *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* or toxigenic *E. coli*, are in most cases asymptomatic carriers which release the bacteria to the environment through their faeces. The removal of super-shedders from a population may significantly reduce transmission and contamination with these foodborne pathogens. The aim of WP2 is to ascertain, through the use of –omics technology, whether pre-biotics, pro-biotics or nutraceutical formula would be able to considerably lower the numbers of *Salmonella* (and other foodborne pathogens such as *Campylobacter*) released by super-shedders (P6, P17, P27, P29). The impact of these food supplement formula on gut microbiota composition, immune response and susceptibility to pathogens like *Salmonella* will be investigated. We will also analyze their impact on animal's parameters (P29, P6). Close cooperation with the other partners will allow us to better understand super-shedding basis and to set up the best options to achieve a drastic reduction of *Salmonella* release to the environment. We will test the efficacy of a series of commensal bacteria (probiotics) and of natural diet additives which are expected to alter the intestinal microbiota by promoting the growth of "beneficial" microorganisms, whilst avoiding the use of antibiotics.

Task-2.1: Use of probiotics in chicken and pig

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: **P6**, Hristo Daskalov

Deputy Task Leader: **P8**, Ivan Rychlick

Task Participants: **P6, P8, P19-Tours, P23, P27, P29**,

Description of the task:

The main objective of this task will be to improve the immune response and barrier effect procured by the gut microbiota by introducing previously identified probiotics. Moreover, novel candidate probiotics will also be identified in WP1 (isolated from healthy pigs and poultry). These commensal bacteria will be phenotypically and genotypically characterised. The effect on the gut microbiota and pathogen infection will be evaluated in established experimental avian and porcine models described in WP1 (P8, P19-Tours, P23, P27), but also on farms with presence of *Salmonella* (P6, P29).

Several probiotics have increase resistance of chickens to *Salmonella* colonization (1 article published). The mechanisms of action are under investigation and **should be published before M40**.

Several probiotics have been tested in field condition (P6, P23) in chicken and pig. **The Year 4 period will be devoted to the analysis of the recovered data.**

Task-2.2: Use of pre-biotics and nutraceutical already defined by the consortium partners in chicken and pig.

Task end month: **M36**

Task Leader: **P16**, María Ugarte Ruiz

Deputy Task Leader: **P6, Hristo Daskalov**

Task Participants: **P6, P8, P17, P23**

Description of the task:

The activities included in this task will be finished for year 4. Two articles have been published and one paper will be sent by the end of September. However, Partner 16 proposes additional studies for this task taking into account the project extension:

- 1) Immunocytochemical study concerning to the immune response in chickens fed with "alperujo" and challenged with *Salmonella* spp.
- 2) A secondary study with MalDI-ToF Imaging that will be carried out using adequate material (different regions of the gut) that have been frozen in liquid nitrogen from 10 animals (5 control and 5 challenged with *Salmonella* spp.). This study would be conditioned to the availability of the equipment according to the new situation of COVID pandemic.

Several prebiotics, obtained from a commercial sponsor, have been tested in vivo in field condition (P6, P23) in chicken and pig. **The Year 4 period will be devoted to the analysis of the recovered data.**

WP3: Modelling the transmission of zoonotic agents to improve intervention strategies on livestock farms

WP end month: **M42**

WP Leader: **P31** Thomas Hagenaaars

Deputy WP Leader: **P19-Jouy**, Beatrice Laroche

WP participants: **P19-Tours, P31**

Description of the WP:

WP3 will focus on the problem of *Salmonella* in poultry and pig in order to develop the building blocks and tools that are needed for design and assessment of intervention strategies. For this purpose we will develop multiscale computational models (from within-host to between-host scale) of heterogeneous pathogen transmission by integrating data from WP1 and 2 and already available datasets by consortium partners in order to design and assess intervention strategies. The models will be designed to allow assessment of the efficiency and/or cost-effectiveness of different intervention strategies.

T-3.1: Transmission modelling at within-host and between-host scales

Task end month: M40

Task Leader: **P19-Jouy**, Beatrice Laroche

Deputy Task Leader: **P31**, Thomas Hagenaaars

Task Participants: **P19-Jouy, P31**,

Description of the task:

In this task, mathematical models will be developed to integrate quantitative knowledge on the heterogeneity of infection and the role of gut microbiota, linking up two scales. **The models**, build the first year, **will be improved during the next period**. Our ambition is to develop simplified, but relevant models of the host including key features of the gut microbiota dynamics and key features of the immune system response.

A new experiment has been carried out, studying the indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* between broilers. Whereas the previous experiment used three different spatial setups, this experiment used one spatial setup but in this setup simultaneously studies the transmission from source animals to both animals in direct contact as well as to spatially separated animals. This enables us further validate (and possibly adjust) the mathematical model(s) describing indirect transmission by testing predictions in an experimental setting. The model can be used for designing and quantitatively assessing candidate bio-security based intervention strategies against indirect

transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*. The results of the experiment are currently being analyzed. This analysis is being delayed by COVID-19. This modelling task is planned to run until the end of the project (M42).

T-3.2: Interventions strategies: Identification and evaluation tools

Task end month: **M42**

Task Leader: **P31**, Thomas Hagenars

Deputy Task Leader: **P19-Jouy**, Béatrice Laroche

Task Participants: **P19-Jouy, P31**,

Description of the task:

The results of WP1 and WP2 will help designing intervention strategies targeting super-shedders and based on probiotic and/or prebiotic treatments. As these rely on a complex interplay between the ecological behaviour of the gut microbiota and the host immune response, the multi-scale modelling approach is essential to assess and improve the efficiency of these intervention strategies. Moreover, such strategies can be combined with other biosecurity measures based on hygiene and movement restriction.

A draft inventory of relevant intervention measures against *Salmonella* in laying hens has been developed within the framework of a HACCP analysis and involved both literature study and elicitation of expert opinion. This draft still needs to be worked out to a systematic inventory. This was planned in M25-M30, but due to illness it is postponed to 2021, M35-M42.

At within-host scale, Partner 19 (INRAEE-Jouy) completed the realization of a C++ software and the corresponding Matlab and R plugins allowing to analyse time series of microbial concentrations. We have encountered problems for frequency time series analyses (see annual report 2019) that are currently being fixed, and we plan to analyse time series from WP1 and include knowledge from probiotic strategies in WP2 to include probiotic based strategies in the model developed in WP3-T1. Due to COVID19 disturbances, this part of the subtask is postponed to of the beginning of 2021. Economic analysis tools as well as an evaluation scheme for cost effectiveness of intervention strategies have been developed. These are applicable to and have been applied to a cost-effectiveness analysis of using probiotics, prebiotics, or synbiotics to control *Campylobacter* in broilers, as described in the following publication: Van Wagenberg CPA, van Horne PLM, van Asseldonk MAPM. Cost-effectiveness analysis of using probiotics, prebiotics, or synbiotics to control *Campylobacter* in broilers. *Poultry Science* 2020;99: 4077-4084.

WP4: Communication and Dissemination for Impact

WP end month: **M42**

WP Leader: **P19-Tours**, Philippe Velge

WP participants: **All partners**

Description of the WP:

This WP will be embedded in the animal and human value chain through all work being carried out. It aims to raise awareness of the progress and benefits of the project by communicating with stakeholders through the targeted routes and media. Dissemination and communication strategies will acknowledge demand from beyond Europe for new knowledge that will afford effective infection-control measures.

Clearly, this WP has been highly impacted by the Covid19 crisis and the confinement.

Nevertheless, four articles have been already accepted for publication and several communications in have been presented in several congresses. New articles should be published during the M37-

M42 periods as well as new communications will be presented. Moreover, communications to the popular media, and the press offices will be done.
The high level strategy meeting, which was supposed to enable us to disseminate the results of the project in the areas of animal husbandry and animal and human health, has been cancelled due to Covid-19. However, the steering committee will discuss how to disseminate our results to the stakeholders in the next period.

Deliverables

JRP code	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>Original name, if different from the actual one</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 10)
10	D-JRP10-1.04	In vitro virulence levels of different <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low-shedders in animals and humans (first round)	30	36	this deliverable will be merged with D-JRP10-1.05	8 report
10	D-JRP10-1.05	In vitro virulence levels of different <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low-shedders in animals and humans (second round)	30	36	This deliverable should be finished before Y4	8 report
10	D-JRP10-1.09	Definition of predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low-shedders in chickens and in pigs.	32	40	Significant differences were noted in OTUs composition of high, intermediate and low-shedders in pigs and chickens. Further analysis are needed to understand the biological meaning of this result	1 ; 7 ; 8 report
10	D-JRP10-1.10	Definition of microbiota markers associated to the high and low-shedders in chickens and in pigs.	32	40	At least two microbiota markers have been identified in chickens. Small, but significant differences were noted in OTUs composition of high, intermediate and low-shedders in pigs. Further analysis are needed to understand the biological meaning of this result	1 ; 7 ; 8 report
10	D-JRP10-1.11	Recovery of all human samples	32	42	The sampling has been achieved. The sequencing is ongoing	10
10	D-JRP10-1.14	Identification, from in vitro studies, of immune	30	42	No differences have been detected. The report should be uploaded	7, 8 report

JRP code	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>Original name, if different from the actual one</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 10)
		parameters related to high and low-shedders				
10	D-JRP10-2.01	In vitro effect of already characterized probiotics on Salmonella growth and cell invasion	30	36	This deliverable should be finished before Y4	7, 8 report
10	D-JRP10-2.04	Characterization of protective commensal bacteria able to inhibit Salmonella colonization (two rounds)	30	36	An in vivo test performed in chicks demonstrated the protective activity of a mix of 4 commensal bacteria. The article has been uploaded	7, 8 report
10	D-JRP10-2.05	Determine the influence of defined and undefined probiotics on the microbiome signature, the immune response, gut physiology and welfare of pig and/ or chicken	30	42	The experiment has been completed. Data analysis is ongoing	7
10	D-JRP10-2.06	Impact of defined and undefined probiotics on Salmonella colonization in pig and chicken	26	42	Done for chicken. Studies with pigs are ongoing, but delayed by COVID-19.	7
10	D-JRP10-2.07	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on the immune parameters, the microbiome and resistome, gut physiology and welfare of pig and chicken.	30	42	Numerous studies have been finished. Few studies, delayed by COVID-19, are ongoing.	7
10	D-JRP10-2.08	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on Salmonella colonization in pig, chicken. Effect on the super-shedders and low-shedders.	30	42	Numerous studies have been finished. Few studies, delayed by COVID-19, are ongoing.	7
10	D-JRP10-3.03	Intervention measures inventory	30	40		6
10	D-JRP10-3.04	Economic analysis tools combined with D-JRP10-3.06	28	30		9
10	D-JRP10-3.05	Definition of intervention measures to target super-shedders	28	42		6
10	D-JRP10-3.06	Evaluation scheme for cost effectiveness of the intervention strategies	28	30		9

JRP code	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name <i>Original name, if different from the actual one</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference and other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 10)
		combined with D-JRP10-3.04				

2.4.2.1.20 JRP20-R2-FBZSH3-DiSCoVeR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ-SH 3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance considering also the environment and non-livestock reservoirs (e.g. pets and wildlife) as sources								
Research Project Title		Discovering the sources of Salmonella, Campylobacter, VTEC and antimicrobial Resistance								
Research Project Acronym		DiSCoVeR								
Leading Organisation		P12-DTU			Deputy Leading Organisation			P30-RIVM		
Project Leader		Tine Hald			Deputy Project leader			Eelco Franz		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	12,5					16	9			8
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	7				16				8,78	1,25
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM				2,28	13			7,73	5,3	2,42
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM	3,03	5,25	9,9	13,5				4		
<p>Objectives</p> <p>DiSCoVeR's objectives are in alignment with objectives of priority topic FBZ 2.1. for three of the main zoonotic bacterial pathogens (Salmonella, Campylobacter, and STEC/VTEC) and antimicrobial resistance (AMR). We will</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fill knowledge gaps regarding potential sources of foodborne zoonoses by including data on non-livestock reservoirs and non-food sources and by providing source attribution estimates at different points in the exposure chain (e.g. at reservoir, retail and exposure) level and across EU regions and countries. 										

- Critically assess and improve existing source attribution models including approaches based on microbial subtyping, case-control studies, outbreak investigations and exposure assessment.
- Quantify the contributions of animal reservoirs, including wildlife and companion animals, food and environmental sources and their transmission routes to the burden of foodborne zoonotic disease, considering geographical differences throughout Europe and consortium partners.
- Use both phenotypic and genomic typing techniques for pathogen and antimicrobial resistance characterization, as well as epidemiological data, for the purposes of source attribution.
- Improve existing and develop new models for source attribution that account for multi-directionality of transmission incl. transmission among reservoirs and within the human population.
- Providing a critical evaluation of the evidence and uncertainty obtained by the source attribution models to improve the characterisation of the sources and transmission pathways implicated in the epidemiological cycles of the hazards focused by the project.
- Provide recommendations on how to transfer results from source attribution models in to actions for prevention and control.
- Evaluate the transferability of the source attribution approach in terms of opportunity to strengthen the technical and institutional capacity building for the One-Health surveillance.

The focus of this project will be on three of the main bacterial foodborne zoonotic pathogens in the EU for which previous source attribution analyses have generally neglected the environment and non-livestock reservoirs: non-typhoid *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter jejuni/coli*, and Shiga toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* (STEC/VTEC), incl. their antimicrobial resistant strains. Because of the transfer of antimicrobial resistant determinants between bacterial species, e.g. between commensals and pathogens, we will also attempt to include attribution approaches for AMR using metagenomics data. When relevant for the models applied, we will attempt to include data from all parts of the food production chain including the retail level. Finally, it should be noted that not all source attribution models are relevant or applicable to all the focus pathogens, and that data availability and accessibility often influence the choice of methods.

Description of work

WP 1. Project coordination, administration, and stakeholder relations.

WP start month 25

WP end month 54

WP Leader: Tine Hald (DTU)

Deputy WP Leader: Eelco Franz (RIVM)

WP participants: All partners

Description of the WP: WP1 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project.

This WP will be responsible for all reporting to the One Health EJP coordinating body and will organise 3 face-to-face meetings and quarterly web-based meetings during the 2.5-year project. Due to the relatively large number of consortium partners and the need for interaction between WPs, WP1 will play an important role in ensuring that milestones and final deliverables of the consortium are successfully completed and communicated. The WP leader at DTU and deputy leader at RIVM are also the overall project coordinator and project deputy leader, which creates integrity

throughout the project and ensure a continuous communication between the WPs and the timely dissemination of results. A Project Management Team (PMT) will be formed consisting of all WP and Task Leaders and their deputies. The PMT will hold monthly webmeetings.

To ensure coordination of work between WPs and the different hazard-specific tasks, WP1 will start out by mapping the existing knowledge gaps and recommend new studies and/or methods that are needed to fill them. This will be done in close collaboration with WP2, which will be initiated by mapping the existing data available to the consortium members. This can be data generated directly by the partners or publicly available data. As several of the consortium partners plan to collect new data during the course of the project, the recommendations from this WP may include the collection of specific samples from the environment and non-livestock reservoirs, and non-animal derived food sources, different water sources and soil.

In close collaboration with WP5, WP1 also takes responsibility for communicating with stakeholders at the EU-level (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA) and Member State-level authorities, farmers' organisations and representatives from the food industry, as well as other projects within and outside the One Health EJP. In M30 and back-to-back with the final annual project meeting, we will organise a 1-day stakeholder workshop, where newly developed methods, results and recommendations for future actions will be presented and discussed. The stakeholder workshop is included as Milestone 5.2 in WP5.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP1-T1 Project management

Task start month 25; Task end month 54

Task Leader: Tine Hald (DTU); **Deputy Task Leader:** Eelco Franz (RIVM)

Task Participants: SVA, ANSES, ISS

Description of the task: The monthly PMT webmeetings and quarterly webmeetings with all consortium partners will continue. The second annual project meeting including all project participants will be hosted by ANSES in M41.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP1-T3 Data Management Plan (DMP)

Task start month 25; Task end month 30

Task Leader: Tine Hald (DTU); **Deputy Task Leader:** Marianne Chemaly (ANSES)

Task Participants: All partners

Description of the task: The DMP will be updated.

WP 2. Data – Coordination of the collection of genomic data, other microbiological data and epidemiological data.

WP start month 25

WP end month 48

WP Leader: Marianne Chemaly (ANSES)

Deputy WP Leader: Robert Söderlund (SVA)

WP participants; All partners

Description of the WP: WP2 takes place over the first and second year of the project.

The purpose of this WP is to coordinate the identification and collection of relevant data between the projects partners considering the data requirements established by WP1, which identify data gaps, and WP3, which identify data for the specific methods. The work will start by mapping existing

data and establishing a joint data-sharing platform. Data will be organised according to pathogen and type of attribution approach, although some data will be useful for more than one approach e.g. WGS data. Besides genomic and phenotypic data and their metadata, and bioinformatics data (e.g. SNP matrices, cg/wg MLST), the data to be collected includes epidemiological data (i.e. from case-control studies, outbreaks, prevalence and microbial count data), and demographic and population data (consumption patterns, production and trade, travels, etc.). We will also collect data from available metagenomics samples to analyse the resistomes from different sources including humans for the purpose of source attribution.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP2-T2 Data collection for *Salmonella*

Task start month 25; Task end month 48

Task Leader: Magdalena Zajac (PIWET); **Deputy Task Leader:** Angela Pista (INSA)

Task Participants: ANSES, VISAVET-UCM, NIPH, APHA, Teagasc, WBVR, VRI, INIAV, PHE

Description of the task: Completing the activities on data collection from previous year including actually generated data collected in 2021.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP2-T3 Data collection for *Campylobacter*

Task start month 25; Task end month 42

Task Leader: Eva M. Nielsen (SSI); **Deputy Task Leader:** Mónica Oleastro (INSA)

Task Participants: DTU, ANSES, VISAVET-UCM, Teagasc, PIWET, SVA, WBVR, INIAV

Description of the task: Completing the activities on data collection from previous year including actually generated data collected in 2021.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP2-T4 Data collection for Verocytotoxin-producing *E. coli* (VTEC)

Task start month 25; Task end month 48

Task Leader: Camilla Sekse (NVI); **Deputy Task Leader:** Rosangela Tozzoli (ISS)

Task Participants: VISAVET, NIPH, APHA, SVA, INSA, PIWET, Teagasc, VRI, INIAV

Description of the task: Completing the activities on data collection from previous year including actually generated data collected in 2021.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP2-T5 Data collection for AMR

Task start month 25; Task end month 48

Task Leader: Julio Alvarez (VISAVET-UCM); **Deputy Task Leader:** Kaye Burgess (Teagasc)

Task Participants: NIPH, ANSES, INSA, PIWET, WBVR, VRI, INIAV, SSI

Description of the task: Completing the activities on data collection from previous year including actually generated data collected in 2021.

WP 3 Methods - Critical assessment/improvement of existing and development of new source attribution models.

WP start month 25

WP end month 48

WP Leader: Thomas Rosendal (SVA)

Deputy WP Leader: Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)

WP participants: SSI, ANSES, NIPH, NCOH-UU, DTU, BfR, WBVR, ISS, PHE, INIAV

WP description: WP4 takes place over first and second year of the project.

This WP will focus on the cataloguing, evaluation and development of existing methods for source attribution and will also develop new methods for the critical assessment of source attribution models and finally suggest novel approaches for source attribution. To fully utilise risk factor studies and risk/exposure assessments to subtyping and WGS information, this WP will identify and develop novel approaches of source attribution and will pass on these findings to WP4.

Task: JRPFZ-1-WP3-T1 Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on microbial subtyping

Task start month 25; Task end month 48

Task Leader: Thomas Rosendal (SVA); **Deputy Task Leader:** Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)

Task Participants: DTU, NIPH, ANSES, BfR, NCOH-UU, SSI, WBVR, INIAV, APHA, PHE

Description of the task: Completing the activities from previous year.

Task: JRPFZ-1-WP3-T2 Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on phylogenetic data

Task start month 25; Task end month 48

Task Leader: Eva Møller Nielsen (SSI); **Deputy Task Leader:** Umaer Naseer (NIPH)

Task Participants: SVA, DTU, APHA, PHE

Description of the task: Completing the activities from previous year.

Task: JRPFZ-1-WP3-T3 Evaluation of microbial subtyping source attribution by infectious disease modelling

Task start month 25; Task end month 48

Task Leader: Thomas Rosendal (SVA); **Deputy Task Leader:** Laurent Guillier (ANSES)

Task Participants: RIVM, DTU

Description of the task: Completing the activities from previous year.

Task: JRPFZ-1-WP3-T4 Assessing and developing approaches for source attribution of antimicrobial resistance based on metagenomics

Task start month: 31; Task end month: 48

Task Leader: Tine Hald (DTU); **Deputy Task Leader:** Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)

Task Participants: INIAV

Description of the task: Completing the activities from previous year.

Task: JRPFZ-1-WP3-T7 Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on Risk-assessment

Task start month: 30; Task end month: 38

Task Leader: Eric Evers (RIVM); **Deputy Task Leader:** Annemarie Käsbohrer (BfR)

Task Participants:

Description of the task: Completing the activities from previous year.

WP 4 Results – Quantifying the contribution of various sources of foodborne zoonoses and AMR.

WP start month: 30;

WP end month: 49

WP Leader: Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM);

Deputy WP Leader: Sara M. Pires (DTU)

WP participants: PIWET, NCOH-UU, BfR, TEAGASC, NVI, NIPH, ANSES, WBVR, VRI, SVA, INSA, VISAVET-UCM, SSI, ISS, APHA, PHE

WP description: WP4 takes place over first, the second and the third year of the project.

In WP4, data collected in WP2 and the methods assessed/developed in WP3 will be used to quantify the contributions of the main sources of the three focus pathogens and AMR. Results will be presented per pathogen, attribution method, data type and, when/if applicable, geographical region/country. While overall ('European or multi-country') analyses will be performed, an important goal will be to identify country differences for pathogen-method combinations, which may reflect differences in their epidemiology. Particular attention will be given to environmental and non-livestock (pets and wildlife) sources besides the 'traditional' livestock/food sources. Different methods will be used in parallel to identify the best source attribution method for the type/amount of data available and the pathogen in question. The results of applied methods for each pathogen will be compared in light of data availability and robustness, underlying uncertainties, the point in the food production chain where source attribution takes place, and the usefulness of different methods to answer different One Health questions.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP4-T1 Salmonella source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches

Task start month: 30; Task end month: 40

Task Leader: Sara Pires (DTU); **Deputy Task Leader:** Dariusz Wasyl (PIWET)

Task Participants: RIVM, ANSES, NIPH, VRI, INSA, VISAVET-UCM, APHA, PHE

Description of the task: Completing the activities from previous year.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP4-T2 Campylobacter source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches

Task start month: 30; Task end month: 42

Task Leader: Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM); **Deputy Task Leader:** Katel Rivoal (ANSES)

Task Participants: NCOH-UU, DTU, SVA, INSA, VISAVET-UCM, SSI, PHE

Description of the task: Completing the activities from previous year.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP4-T3 VTEC source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches

Task start month: 30; Task end month: 49

Task Leader: Eelco Franz (RIVM); **Deputy Task Leader:** Gaia Scavia (ISS)

Task Participants: TEAGASC, DTU, ANSES, NVI, NIPH, VRI, SVA, INSA, VISAVET-UCM

Description of the task: Continued from previous year.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP4-T4 AMR source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated

Task start month: 30; Task end month: 49

Task Leader: Sofia Duarte (DTU); **Deputy Task Leader:** Thomas Hagenaars (WBVR)

Task Participants: VRI, INSA, VISAVET-UCM, RIVM

Description of the task: Continued from previous year.

WP5 - Conclusions, recommendations and policy translation.

WP start month: 33

WP end month: 54

WP Leader: Gaia Scavia (ISS)

Deputy WP Leader: Tine Hald (DTU)

WP participants: all partner institutions

Description of the WP: WP5 takes place over first, the second and the third year of the project.

WP5 aims at providing a critical evaluation of the evidence and uncertainty obtained by the source attribution models to improve the characterisation of the sources and transmission pathways implicated in the epidemiological cycles of the hazards in focus (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC and AMR). In addition, the transferability of the source attribution approach will be evaluated in terms of opportunity to strengthen the technical and institutional capacity building for the One-Health surveillance. Technical evaluations will allow to describe strength, limitation and fit for purposes of methodologies for source attribution modelling being applied, in light of the current availability and gaps of data in the various sectors (clinical, food, animal, environment), and considering the limitations and barriers connected to the current operational field context (Task 5.1). Expert evaluation will allow to elucidate how project outcomes could be interpreted and used to improve hazard control policies at both EU and national level and to identify which resources and components of the surveillance programmes would be needed to optimise the applicability of source attribution approach in the field (Task 5.2). On this basis, conclusions and recommendations will be formulated with the support of the relevant stakeholders (in particular EFSA and ECDC) and taking into account the control policies in place at the EU and national level, in the various sectors. In particular, the existing hazard specific control programmes such as the National Control Programme (NCP) for *Salmonella*, at the primary production level and other intervention strategies will be focused. Final recommendations will also be delivered in close cooperation with the WP2 of the EJP focusing 'Science to policy translation' to ensure an optimal level of harmonization within the EJP (Task 5.3).

This WP includes all the participant institutes. Activities will be organised into three separate, interdependent tasks. These will be carried out in close cooperation with the WP2, WP3 and WP4 leaders for the purposes of integration of contributions and comprehensive interpretation of the methodologies and output. Since the critical evaluation of the outcomes will require specific a robust knowledge on the epidemiology and surveillance context for each specific hazards, single hazard specific experts will be identified among participants and involved in the WP activities (expert group). Alignment with other projects within and outside the EJP (NOVA, Cohesive, Orion) will also be established in order to guarantee full internal harmonization and avoid duplication of the activities.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP5-T1 Technical expert evaluation of the methodologies for source attribution and their optimal requirements for infield applicability

Task start month: 41; Task end month: 51

Task Leader: Lapo Mughini Gras (RIVM); **Deputy Task Leader:** Thomas Rosendal (SVA)

Task Participants: ANSES, DTU, ISS, INSA, VRI

Description of the task: This task will take place over the second and third year of the project. It deals with the evaluation of the strength, limitation and fit for purposes of the methods for source attribution modelling being applied (WP3) for each hazard, in light of the current data availability and data gaps, limiting the applicability of the models (WP2). This activity will allow describing how source attribution approach could be optimised, for each hazard, for its infield applicability, taking into account the current context for surveillance, the hazard epidemiology and the future needs. On this basis a final prioritization of the best methodological options for source attribution approach, by hazard will be delivered. Expert group support will be needed where appropriate.

Task: JRPFBZ-1-WP5-T2 Translating source attribution estimates into options for control policies

Task start month: 33; Task end month: 50

Task Leader: Gaia Scavia (ISS); **Deputy Task Leader:** Sara Pires (DTU)

Task Participants: SVA, SSI, INSA, NVI VRI

Description of the task: Continued from previous year.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRPFBZ-1-WP2.6	Description of data generated for Salmonella, Campylobacter, Shigatoxin-producing E. coli (STEC) and their AMR determinants	48
D-JRPFBZ-1-WP3.1	Describe novel approaches for source attribution using microbial subtyping	48
D-JRPFBZ-1-WP3.2	Report on the critical and quantitative evaluation of existing and novel source attribution methods	48
D-JRPFBZ-1-WP4.1	Salmonella source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method	40
D-JRPFBZ-1-WP4.2	Campylobacter source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated	42
D-JRPFBZ-1-WP5.1	Map of the current existing control programme and intervention strategies to mitigate the risk of transmission of Salmonella, Campylobacter, VTEC, and antimicrobial resistance to human at the EU and national level.	42

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRPFBZ-1-15	Framework for using metagenomic data for attribution of antimicrobial resistant	39
M-JRPFBZ-1-16	Results from evaluation of microbial subtyping methods using artificial data	40
M-JRPFBZ-1-17	Description of method of source attribution using existing case-control	42
M-JRPFBZ-1-18	Method for source attribution by risk assessment evaluated	42

M-JRPFBZ-1-19	Second annual project meeting hosted by ANSES	41
M-JRPFBZ-1-20	Completion of control programme and intervention strategies mapping	41
M-JRPFBZ-1-21	Update of Data Management Plan	41
M-JRPFBZ-1-22	Completion of data collection	42
M-JRPFBZ-1-23	Completion of dataset for all species	48

2.4.2.1.21 JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 3.1: Benchmarking biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe using national surveillance data and management standards for identifying best practice to prevent biological hazards, particularly Salmonella and hepatitis E virus, from entering the food supply chain								
Research Project Title		Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe								
Research Project Acronym		BIOPIGEE								
Leading Organisation		P9-BfR			Deputy Leading Organisation			N/A		
Project Leader		Chris Kollas			Deputy Project leader			N/A		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	6	15,5		32		11	26		13	
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM			7,9						22,1	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM					13	16	5,85	0,62	7,02	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM	7,5	12,25						9,5		

Objectives:

WP1

- Coordination of the project BIOPIGEE
- Development of data management plan

WP2

- Collect biosecurity protocol data from farms within participant countries categorised as either high or low risk for Salmonella and/or Hepatitis E
- Review the effect of biosecurity measures at slaughterhouses and transport.

- Complete field studies to determine the effectiveness of biosecurity controls.
- Quantify effect of biosecurity measures and compile evidence from all tasks to inform the catalogue of effective biosecurity measures (WP5),.
- Incorporate Hepatitis E isolate sequences into HEVnet to allow for comparisons and analysis of strains detected in countries.

WP3

- Main objective: to obtain better knowledge on how to combat Salmonella and HEV in biofilms/surface microlayers by disinfection in pig farms, so that this knowledge can be used for further development of a common biosecurity protocol
- Sub-objective 1: To establish a standardized method for testing the effect of disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm.
- Sub-objective 2: To obtain knowledge on the effect of relevant disinfectants on Salmonella I biofilm by using the standardized method and a panel of relevant Salmonella strains from herds and abattoirs
- Sub-objective 3: To use the evaluated models to test disinfectants on HEV in biofilms/surface microlayers
- Sub-objective 4: To develop a suitable HEV infectivity assay to test different kind of samples that can be contaminated with HEV.
- Sub-objective 5: To implement, optimize and adapt a HEV infectivity assay for pig and environmental samples.
- Sub-objective 6: To assess HEV stability in relation to disinfection approaches in pig farms.

WP4

- Quantification of the number of infected pigs and human cases depending on the effectiveness of (biosecurity) intervention measures
- Economic assessments depending on the effectiveness of (biosecurity) intervention measures and associated costs

WP5

- Continued integration of gained knowledge on effectiveness and costs of biosecurity measures studied in WP2-4 into the catalogue of biosecurity measures
- Continued systematic review/meta-analysis to further fill the catalogue with relevant effective measures
- Applying machine learning approaches to generate further information on measure's effectiveness
- Survey of the expert panel to add estimations on effectiveness/ weights
- Development of a benchmark system to assess biosecurity practice for its effectiveness and relevance to reduce/limit Salmonella and HEV occurrence in pig production

WP6

- To produce dissemination material on best biosecurity practices to reduce the presence of Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus in pigs, at farm level and along the food chain.
- To develop a support tool for calculating cost effectiveness of biosecurity related interventions.
- To organise a workshop series to enable exchange between researchers and stakeholders on biosecurity in pig production

Description of work:

WP1

WPiv: 1 Project coordination and integration of results
WP start month: 25

WP end month: 54

WP Leader: BfR (Chris Kollas)

Deputy WP: BfR (Elke Burow)

WP participants: All members of BIOPIGEE

Description of the WPv: The first work package leads and coordinates the project. Exchange between work packages and integration of results, as well as active linking to external partners and projects (EU activities) will be organised. Three major project meetings will be organised: First, a kick-off meeting will be held with all participants in month M26. Next, a mid-term meeting is planned for all WP-leaders and finally, the final project meeting or conference will be conducted in M53. All parts for the project reports, deliverables and milestones will be collected from WP-leaders and delivered to OHEJP. The contact to EJP coordinators will be maintained. A data management plan will be evaluated and revised throughout the project lifetime. A database structure to store data among all WP will be provided.

Taskvi: JRP#-WP1-T1 Project management and meeting organisation
Task start month: 25

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: BfR (Chris Kollas)

Deputy Task Leader: BfR (Elke Burow)

Task Participants: BfR, all BIOPIGEE members

Description of the taskviii: The project organisation will keep the information flow between the WPs. Problems of participants will be solved, a place for common data exchange will be established and a smooth working atmosphere will be supported. For this, emails, web-conferences and eventually newsletters will be used. During the whole project period, the coordinators will take part in at least two European conferences that deal with the proposed project's topic, in order to inform the scientific and non-scientific audience about the BIOPIGEE project and its results.

Furthermore, a smooth communication will be guaranteed between the WP3 of OHEJP and the BIOPIGEE consortium. Participant's inquiries will be collected, answered (if possible) and forwarded to the board (if necessary). The main contact person of the proposed project will be Chris Kollas.

All kind of exchange between WPs will be supported. The connections between WPs, as shown in the Pert chart, need to be kept vital. Not only data, but also ideas and criticism will be exchanged with the help of the project coordination. For this, inter alia surveys will be circulated periodically, asking for progress, cooperation and exchange.

The coordination team will actively search for further external partners and projects and funding that fit to the topic of BIOPIGEE.

A kick-off meeting will be organised and held with all participants of BIOPIGEE in month M26. A mid-term meeting is planned (together with APHA) to join all WP-leader and the final project meeting / conference will be conducted (together with IZSAM) for all BIOPIGEE participants and eventually also guests in M53 or M54.

The task will mainly be carried out by C. Kollas and E. Burow.

Taskix: JRP#-WP1-T2 Development of data management plan
Task start month: 43

Task end month: 48

Task Leader: BfR (Chris Kollas)

Deputy Task Leader: BfR (Elke Burow)

Task Participants: all BIOPIGEE

members

Description of the taskxi: Following H2020 rules a comprehensive data management plan will be developed for the BIOPIGEE project. The plan will include the following points: data summary, making data findable, making data openly accessible, making data interoperable, increase data re- use, allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects. This will be achieved by close cooperation with the EJP-OneHealth WP4-group, which proposed support in developing the data management plan. The second and final version of the data management plan will be provided to EJP-PMT.

Task JRP#-WP1-T3 Provision of project deliverables and reports Task start month: 47

Task end month: 48

Task Leader: BfR (Chris Kollas)

Deputy Task Leaderxiii: BfR (Elke Burow)

Task Participants: BfR, AGES, ANSES, APHA, BfR, ISS, IZSAM, NDRVI, NVI, PIWET, RKI, SVA, VFL, WBVR

Description of the taskxiv: Project deliverables of all WPs will be collected, checked and transferred to the board of EJP-OneHealth. Further, yearly project reports will be compiled with the help of WP-Leaders and also delivered to the board.

WP : JRP#-WP2 Biosecurity effectiveness

studies WP start month 25

WP end month 50

WP Leader APHA (Richard

Smith) Deputy WP Leader BfR

WP participants APHA, SVA, WBVR (UU), BfR, VFL (EMU), PIWET, VRI, IZSAM, ISS, AGES (VMU), NDRVMI, RIVM, IZSLER

Description of the WP^{xv}: A review of biosecurity audit protocols supplemented by brief, focused review of relevant literature on the effectiveness of biosecurity practices will define the most suitable protocol(s) to be used on a selection of pig farms in each participating country, covering a representation of European climates and production types. The farms will be identified as high or low risk, focusing on Salmonella and/ or Hepatitis E (HEV), to allow for case-control analysis in order to quantify the benefits of each practice. A structured approach will be used to standardise farm selection to reduce known biases and to provide criteria for ranking high/ low risk. Information collected on slaughterhouse biosecurity best practice will also define the impact on carcass contamination. The results will benchmark standards in each country and define overall best practice. Field studies will be completed to provide evidence for key knowledge gaps on the effectiveness of controls, particularly focused on the effect of biosecurity on HEV. The work on HEV will be supported by the HEVnet project providing a facility to upload sequences and metadata to allow investigation of HEV subtype diversity. This integrative approach, drawing evidence from a wide range of sources, will inform quantification of the benefit of the biosecurity practices against Salmonella and HEV at farm and at slaughter, which will be vital to the assessments of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity analyses (WP4) and benchmarking biosecurity practice (WP5).

Task^{xvi}: JRP#-WP2-T2 Application of the biosecurity protocol Task start month 27

Task end month 42

Task Leader:

PIWET

Deputy Task Leader^{xvii}: AGES

Task Participants: BfR, APHA, WBVR, SVA, VFL, PIWET, IZSAM, AGES, ISS, NDRVMI, VRI, IZSLER

Description of the task^{xviii}: The biosecurity protocol will be applied to the remaining selected farms within the European partner countries. Once collected, the dataset will be cleaned and collated for an initial descriptive analysis to compare the use of biosecurity practices within and between countries.

This will lead to two case-control risk factor analyses comparing practices on high and low risk farms in order to determine and quantify the biological effectiveness of biosecurity measures to reduce Salmonella and HEV prevalence.

Univariable screening will be used to determine the biosecurity practices that are associated with either outcome ($P < 0.25$) and are subjected to multivariable analysis to determine those practices that are retained in the final model and are significantly associated with either outcome. Composite variables (biosecurity categories), combining information on multiple biosecurity practices (such as batch cleaning and disinfection of buildings, troughs and waterlines), will also be tested to see how they fit the data and are associated with the outcomes. The dataset will also be evaluated to determine whether the analysis can be completed at the sample level (within a mixed-effects model), which could provide greater statistical power, or whether the relatively small number of samples per farm means that data is too sparse to provide an effective dataset for analysis and whether analysis on herd or country level is possible. The analyses will provide information on the effectiveness of each practice or group of practices. In case no multivariate statistical analysis is possible/model converges, alternatively more descriptive analyses like correspondence analysis can display and summarise the biosecurity variables in two-dimensional graphical form (contingency table) for herds of different status of Salmonella or HEV prevalence. Thereby, typical patterns/combinations of biosecurity characteristics for herds with high prevalence and for those with low prevalence of Salmonella and HEV will be made visible for comparison in order to inform about biosecurity practice in herds of low prevalence.

A report will be produced summarising the results and the findings will be shared with WP4 and 5.

Task^{xix}: JRP#-WP2-T3 Slaughterhouse biosecurity practices

Task start month 37

Task end month

42 Task Leader:

VFL

Deputy Task Leader^{xx}: ISS

Task Participants: VFL, APHA, ISS, VRI, BfR, AGES, WBVR, IZSLER

Description of the task^{xxi}: Work will be completed to collate relevant evidence on the impact of slaughterhouse biosecurity practices on carcass contamination/cross-contamination to define best practice. A literature review will be completed on biosecurity effectiveness in slaughterhouses, possibly using proxy organisms (e.g. The use of evidence on *E. coli* reduction where evidence for Salmonella is missing). A short, focused questionnaire will be used to collect data from at least seven BIOPIGEE partner countries (UK, IT, EE, AT, NL, DE, BE) on currently implemented pig slaughterhouse biosecurity practices. Organisations within each country will facilitate the sending of questionnaires to pig abattoirs and returning the data to the task team. The questionnaire will cover areas such as lorry washing facilities, management of the lairage, hygiene procedures on the line etc. Any data already collected on slaughterhouse biosecurity by partners will be supplied for analysis, and slaughterhouse industry bodies or regulatory authorities will be contacted for any relevant information. The results will be compared to inform best practice and where possible, the results will be compared to ongoing slaughterhouse Salmonella monitoring results (e.g. process hygiene criteria). At three exemplarily slaughterhouses (2 Italian and 1 Czech slaughterhouses) will be visited and sampled to provide proof of principle on whether the level of contamination correlates with the biosecurity practices identified in the literature and to fill specific data gaps. Sampling would be completed by taking swabs at different points down the slaughter line to indicate faecal contamination and evaluate occurrence of Salmonella or HEV. It is expected that faecal contamination indicators would reflect contamination with HEV as well and these visits will provide opportunities for testing to corroborate whether this assumption is true.

The data gathered will identify the biological effectiveness of slaughterhouse biosecurity, which will

be supplied to WP5. A guidance document and assessment protocol for slaughterhouse biosecurity best practice will be produced, which will be supplied to WP6 for dissemination.

Task^{xxii}: JRP#-WP2-T4 Field studies

Task start month 25

Task end month

48 Task Leader:

APHA

Deputy Task Leader^{xxiii}: IZSAM

Task Participants: APHA, IZSAM, WBVR, ISS, IZSLER

Description of the task: The field study visits and the testing of samples will be completed in this reporting year. The data generated from the visits will be collated and cleaned. Descriptive analysis and modelling of results will be carried out to produce evidence relevant to the effectiveness of biosecurity on Salmonella and HEV. The results will be summarised in a report and supplied to WP4 and 5.

Task^{xxiv}: JRP#-WP2-T5 Analysis of Hepatitis E prevalence and subtypes

Task start month 37

Task end month

50 Task Leader:

RIVM

Deputy Task Leader^{xxv}: ISS

Task Participants: RIVM, WBVR, APHA, VRI, ISS, PIWET

Description of the task^{xxvi}: To increase our understanding of the epidemiology of HEV in pigs, genome sequences generated from field studies completed within the project (cooperation with T2.2, sample collection at farms in the UK, PL, AT, NL, EE, IT, NL) and from other available information held by the partner institutes, will be submitted to the HEVnet database. HEVnet is an international One Health network of HEV experts, who collect HEV genome sequences from patients, human materials, animals, food and the environment across Europe. The HEVnet database will be modified to provide an online platform for BIOPIGEE collection of HEV sequences and data relevant to HEV biosecurity. An analysis of this HEV sequence data will be conducted in order to trace the movement of HEV pig strains in Europe, among partner countries and over time, and to understand if strains are newly introduced or if strains persist in certain populations (e.g. a farm or a region). Furthermore, a correlation of that information on persistence of HEV strains or movement of strains among partner countries with biosecurity measures collected within T2.2 will bring insights to potential effectiveness of general biosecurity measures on HEV circulation. Collaboration with HEVnet will support this evaluation and the routines linked to the HEVnet database will be used for data visualization through geographical maps, phylogenetic trees and pie charts. These evaluations can be only effectively performed by sequencing HEV strains and by comparison to large sequence datasets. In this project year, the HEVnet team will adapt their database to collect the BIOPIGEE data and sequences collected by the field studies will be uploaded.

WP3

WP3^{xxvii}: Impact of disinfection on persistence of Salmonella and HEV in biofilm

WP start month: 25

WP end month: 54

WP Leader: Wim van der Poel (WBVR)

Deputy WP Leader: Live L. Nesse (NVI)

WP participants: WBVR, NVI, RKI, APHA

Description of the WP: The aim of the present WP is to obtain better knowledge on how to avoid and combat the build-up of environmental reservoirs of Salmonella and HEV in pig farms by disinfection. This knowledge will be the basis for rating effectiveness of cleaning and disinfection included in the catalogue of biosecurity measures and the subsequent benchmarking (WP5).

This will also contribute information to WP4 as the cost of disinfections to remove biofilms will impact overall biosecurity cost and effectiveness, and also to WP6 to raise awareness of the risks

of biofilms and the difficulty in removing them.

Salmonella may be introduced into herds by contaminated feed or breeding animals. However, once introduced, it is well known that Salmonella can persist in farm environments from several months to years. Cleaning and disinfection are therefore important biosecurity measures. Salmonella are in general good biofilm-formers, and when residing in biofilms in the environment they are extremely well protected against environmental stress, including various disinfectants. Consequently, it is imperative to use disinfectants able to eradicate Salmonella in biofilm. Today, however, disinfectants are chosen based on their ability to kill planktonic bacteria in standard laboratory tests, and these tests cannot be used to predict the effect on the bacteria in biofilm. Standard Methods for testing the effectivity of disinfectants against salmonella do not include biofilm-associated forms of the pathogens, thus making it difficult to give advice on which disinfectants to use. This problem will be addressed in WP3.

The aim of the Salmonella part of WP3 is to establish a standardized test for assessing the effect of disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm, and apply this test to evaluate disinfectants for use in swine production. The work will be organized into three subtasks.

HEV may be introduced in pig herd via different routes. The most important introduction routes in pig herds are not really known. Contaminated feed, breeding animals as well as workers coming to farms may all play a role. Once introduced, HEV may persist in herds and farm environments for years. Good biosecurity protocols for HEV have not been developed yet. Usefulness of cleaning and disinfection are not really known because research is hampered by the fact that there is not a method available to test for HEV infectivity. It is possible that HEV persists better in environments with good biofilm-forming bacteria. Consequently, it may be indicated to use disinfectants able to inactivate biofilm forming bacteria as well as Hepatitis E virus itself. This approach will be tested in WP3.

For HEV, the selected HEV infectivity test will be further developed and optimized in order to correlate the presence of HEV RNA to infectious virus. This method will be implemented to assess the effect of HEV biosecurity practices, e.g. disinfection, on surface microlayers/biofilms contaminated with infectious HEV.

Task JRP#-WP3-T1: Comparison of methods for testing the effect of disinfectants
Task start month: 25

Task end month:

40 Task Leader: RKI

Deputy Task Leader: NVI

Task Participants: RKI, NVI, APHA

Description of the task: The objective of this task is to select a method for testing the effect of disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm. Known methods with a potential for testing the effect of disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilms will be validated and standardized, thanks to collaboration of institutes working for both human (RKI) and animal health (NVI, APHA) with high level expertise within this area. Representative strains of Salmonella and *E. coli* in biofilm-associated will be assessed in terms of efficacy of disinfectants. The results for the Salmonella strains will be evaluated by comparing them with the results for the *E. coli* reference test organism as listed in the European Standard Norm

DIN EN 14885. Results obtained from different laboratories will be compared with each other and one biofilm model will be selected.

Task JRP#-WP3-T2: Effect of disinfectants on biofilm-associated wild type Salmonella Task start month:25

Task end month:

50 Task Leader:

NVI

Deputy Task Leader : APHA

Task Participants: RKI, NVI, APHA

Description of the task: The objective of this task is to test the effect of relevant disinfectants against biofilm residing wild type Salmonella isolated from farm and abattoirs. The validated method established in T 3.1 and the strain panel selected in T 3.2-ST-1 will be used to test the effect of disinfectants commonly used in swine production. Several disinfectant types will be included, e.g. quaternary ammonium compounds (QAC), glutaraldehyde and oxidizing agents. Through this testing, we will identify the disinfectants most effective against Salmonella in biofilm. The results on the effectiveness of disinfectants will be added to the catalogue of biosecurity measures (WP5).

Sub-Task JRP#-WP3-T2-ST2 ^{xxviii} Assessing the effect of disinfectants

Sub-Task start month: 37

Sub-Task end month:

50 Sub-Task Leader:

NVI

Deputy Sub-Task Leader^{xxix}: RKI

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, RKI, NVI

Description of the sub-task: The objective of this sub-task is to assess the effect of various disinfectants on wild type Salmonella in biofilm. The validated method established in T 3.1 and the strain panel selected in T 3.2-ST-1 will be used to test the effect of disinfectants commonly used in swine production. Several disinfectant types will be included, e.g. quaternary ammonium compounds (QAC), glutaraldehyde and oxidizing agents. The recommended user concentrations and exposure times for each disinfectant will be used in the testing. Depending on the results, other concentrations and exposure times may also be tested, and separate testing of different active substances may also be done.

To assess the efficacy of disinfectants for HEV in environmental samples containing biofilm forming bacteria this will be studied in environmental matter spiked with the selected biofilm forming Salmonella strains using the developed infectivity methods. The disinfectants which are most effective against salmonella in biofilm will also be tested for their effect on HEV inactivation (T3.1-3.2).

Task JRP#-WP3-T3: Study of HEV stability in relation to disinfection approaches Task start month:25

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: WBVR

Deputy Task Leader^{xxx}:

Task Participants:

WBVR Description of the task:

The objective of this subtask will be to develop and optimize a culture system for Hepatitis E virus using primary pig liver cells and ultrathin pig liver slices. Primary pig liver cells will be harvested by flushing fresh pig livers obtained from SPF piglets. Ultrathin pig liver slices of one or two cell thick will be obtained from fresh pig livers (also from SPF-piglets) using a dedicated microtome procedure. Primary cells will be kept in monolayer cultures and ultrathin pig liver slices will also be kept in cell

culture media to keep the cells alive as long as possible. Both methods will be assessed for suitability to test for HEV infectivity in different kind of HEV-positive pig and environmental samples The most suitable method will be implemented to assess the effect of HEV biosecurity practices, e.g. disinfection, on surface microlayers/biofilms contaminated with infectious HEV. Sub-Task JRP#-WP3-T3-ST2^{xxxii}

Sub-Task start month:

37 Sub-Task end month:

48 Sub-Task Leader:

Deputy Sub-Task Leader^{xxxii}:

Sub-Task Participants:

Description of the sub-task:

The objective of this subtask will be to assess the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers in the presence of biofilm forming bacteria. For this purpose different

microlayers/biofilm matrices, containing (or spiked with) biofilm forming salmonella strains identified in subtask 1, obtained from pig farms, will be tested for infectious HEV. Disinfectant treatments as described under subtask 2 will be assessed for effectivity in HEV inactivation in surface microlayers/biofilms.

WP4

WP 4: Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity

measures WP start month: 25

WP end month: 50

WP Leader: Beate Pinior

Deputy WP Leader: Simon Robin

WP participants: AGES (VMU), APHA, ANSES, SVA

Description of the WP 4: This work package will take place over years 3, 4, and 5 of the EJP. The overall aim of the work package is to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the implementation of standard and specific intervention measures on prevalence reduction of Salmonella and HEV along the pig supply chain by consideration of e.g. differences in the effectiveness of intervention measures, pig production systems across Europe (e.g. herd size), temporal aspects (i.e. dynamic pig cycle, disease prevalence dynamics), spatial aspects (i.e. individual MS and EU), supply structure, fluctuations of supply, demand and prices on the market (e.g. meat and feed price, which are necessary for the economic welfare analysis). The partners of the present work package will maintain close contact to partners of WP 1, 2, 3 and 5 for legal implications of data sharing and the BIOPIGEE database structure (catalogue of biosecurity measures, WP5) will be used for insertion and extraction of measure's effectiveness and costs. The goals of work package 4 will be delivered via 4 tasks.

Task 4.2: Stochastic simulations on the effectiveness of biosecurity

measures Task start month: 33

Task end month: 49

Task Leader: Simon

Robin Deputy Task

Leader:

Task Participants: APHA, ANSES, SVA

Description of the task 4.2: Task 4.2 takes place over years 3, 4, and 5 of EJP. In this task we will adapt currently available transmission models such as QMRA for Salmonella and SimInF model for HEV and/or Salmonella of the consortium partners in order to analyse the impact of biosecurity measures on prevalence reduction of the zoonotic pathogens. The stochastic transmission models will simulate the spread of Salmonella and HEV across the production stage at the farm level with the provided set

of biosecurity measures from WP 2 and WP 3, as well as with evidence-based best-practice measures from the literature search in **WP5** (catalogue of biosecurity measures, accessed via collective database structure). The models will be developed for three countries, including the UK, GER, and IT. The models will be adapted with the current knowledge from epidemiology, such as transmission parameters, available demographical data, herd management data, and the provided collected data on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures from WP 2, 3 and 5.

The outcome of **WP 4.2** will be the level of prevalence (i.e. number of infected pigs at the farm level) i) without such biosecurity measures, ii) with individual standard biosecurity measures, iii) with individual specific mitigation measures, and/or iv) combination of a set of biosecurity measures.

Sub-Task 4.2.2: Adaption of the models based on the available data
Sub-Task start month: 37

Sub-Task end month: 42

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, ANSES, SVA

Description of the Sub-Task: Adaption i.e. reprogramming of the currently available transmission models of the consortium partners based on the data collected from WP 2, WP 3 and WP 5.

Sub-Task 4.2.3: Simulation runs for the identified effective biosecurity measures

Sub-Task start month: 37

Sub-Task end month: 49

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, ANSES, SVA

Description of the Sub-Task: The models (QMRA model for Salmonella and SimInF model for HEV and/or Salmonella) will simulate the spread of the transmission of Salmonella and HEV infection at the farm level i) without biosecurity measures, ii) with individual standard biosecurity measures, iii) with individual specific mitigation measures, and/or iv) combination of a set of biosecurity measures.

In this context, we will also consider the fact that biosecurity measures are implemented only for a proportion of the farms, compared to the scenario that all farms implement such standard measures. This is important because biosecurity measures are not universally applied within Member States and this will influence the effectiveness of the measures to reduce human illness overall (see WP 4.3). However, the outcome of **WP 4.2.3** will be the level of prevalence at farm level for the scenarios i-iv) and will be used in WP 4.3. and WP 4.4.

Task 4.3: Merge of models into one

QMRA Task start month: 34

Task end month: 50

Task Leader: Simon

Robin Deputy Task

Leader:

Task Participants: APHA, ANSES, SVA

Description of the task 4.3: Task 4.3 takes place over the years 4, and 5 of EJP. In **WP 4.3** the different outcomes of the transmission models (i.e. estimated prevalence at the farm level from the SimInF and QMRA models) at the primary production stage will be matched to a single QMRA model on Salmonella and HEV, which covers the entire food supply chain (i.e. subsequent processing stages as slaughterhouses but also the human sector). Data on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures at the slaughterhouse level from **WP2 (T2.3)**, collected in BIOPIGEE's database structure in the catalogue of biosecurity measures in WP5) and/or the temperature impact on contamination reduction on the subsequent processing stages, and consumption data for pig meat in different countries will be incorporated in the single QMRA model. The final outcome of the one QMRA model will be the number of human cases for each considered pathogen. The same three countries (UK, GER, IT) will be used to cover the range of potentially heterogeneous country-specific circumstances, such as the

effectiveness of biosecurity measures, herd demographical data, and consumption data. The consideration of different country-specific circumstances is necessary in order to identify the “best” combination of cost-effective biosecurity measures across European countries. The outcome of **WP 4.3**, i.e. Salmonella and HEV prevalences at animal level and human level will feed into **WP 4.4**.

Sub-Task 4.3.1: Different transmission models will be matched to one QMRA zoonotic pathogen model

Sub-Task start month:

34 Sub-Task end month:

47

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, ANSES, SVA

Description of the Sub-Task: The different simulation models i.e. SimInF and QMRA model will be matched to a single QMRA zoonotic pathogen model because the outcome of the models, such as the SimInF model, will be the number of pigs infected with Salmonella and/or HEV at the production stages. Therefore, it will be necessary to match the different modelling approaches and considered pathogens in the models to one simulation QMRA model to obtain also the number of human cases. In this context, data of subsequent processing stages such as effective measures on the slaughterhouses from **WP 2** and/or the temperature impact, and consumption data for pig meat in different countries will also be incorporated in this single QMRA zoonotic pathogen model. The outcome will be the number of human cases for each considered pathogen, when no (biosecurity) intervention measures are implemented along the supply chain, compared to the scenario when intervention measures were implemented.

Sub-Task 4.3.2: Simulation runs with one QMRA zoonotic pathogen model Sub-Task start month: 45

Sub-Task end month: 50

Sub-Task Participants:

APHA

Description of the Sub-Task: Different simulation runs with the one QMRA zoonotic pathogen model.

Task 4.4: Economic model of biosecurity measures across

Europe Task start month: 37

Task end month: 50

Task Leader: Beate Pinior

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: AGES (VMU)

Description of the task 4.4: Task 4.4 takes place over the years 4 and 5 of EJP. In this task we will assess the economic profitability of the implementation of standard and specific intervention measures along the pig supply chain using the outputs of WP 2, and WP 4.1-4.3. The provided prevalence, with and without mitigation measures, from **WP.4.2 and WP 4.3** will be translated into a monetary benefit and compared with the associated cost of the respective biosecurity measures collected in WP 2 and WP 4.1 (i.e. the WP 4 will highlight whether the proposed

combination of biosecurity measures from **WP 2, WP 3 and WP 5** offer an economic advantage). The economic model will integrate different financial and economic assessments such as cost-benefit-analysis, optimization approach (i.e. least-cost combinations of most effective sets of biosecurity measures), general production and welfare approaches, and if the monetary benefit for certain measures cannot be determined, we will use the cost-effectiveness approach. The overall output of WP 4 will be an efficiency combination of effective biosecurity measures, which consider the highest efficiency in the reduction of zoonotic pathogens, but also the least expensive of the implemented

measures in Europe. The economic calculation will provide statements of the efficiency for i) individual standard biosecurity measures, ii) individual specific mitigation measures, or iii) a combination of a set of biosecurity measures for the entire pork production chain and also for individual stages in the production stages, in order to determine the surplus or losses per stage in the supply chain, when specific biosecurity measures are implemented. These different economic assessments and associated methods (economic models) as well as the collected economic data in WP 2.1 and WP 4.1 will be incorporated in a user-friendly interface tool (see WP 6).

Sub-Task 4.4.1: Performing economic assessments of best practice biosecurity measures
Sub-Task start month: 37

Sub-Task end month: 50

Sub-Task Participants: AGES (VMU)

Description of the Sub-Task: In this task we will use the outputs of WP 2 and WP 4.1 (i.e. collected cost data of biosecurity measures and data about the pig performance), and WP 4.2 and 4.3 (i.e. number of infected pigs and humans without and with (combined) biosecurity measures). Different economic methods will be applied depending on the stage of the supply chain and considered number of biosecurity measures. While the benefit-cost ratio provides information about the efficiency of individual implemented measures, the optimization approach, attempts to find a combination of mitigation measures that cause the highest benefit for society. The economically optimal disease-biosecurity policy is that which incurs the lowest attainable economic costs i.e. the least-cost combination of biosecurity expenditures and losses. In this context, the combination of different effective biosecurity measures will be analysed to determine the maximum net benefit i.e. maximizing the reduction of losses by consideration of the resources invested. If the monetary benefit for certain measures cannot be determined, we will use the cost-effectiveness approach. The economic calculation will provide statements of the efficiency for i) individual standard biosecurity measures, ii) individual specific mitigation measures, or iii) a combination of a set of biosecurity measures for the entire pork production chain and also for individual stages in the production stages, in order to determine the surplus or losses per stage in the supply chain, when specific biosecurity measures are implemented. This WP will highlight whether the proposed standard-, specific or combination of biosecurity measures from **WP 2, WP 3 and WP 5** offer an economic advantage for the three individual EU members or across Europe (represented by UK, GER, and IT) to reduce the prevalence of *Salmonella* and/or *HEV* in the pig supply chain.

Sub-Task 4.4.2: Performing production and welfare economic assessments
Sub-Task start month: 45

Sub-Task end month: 48

Sub-Task Participants: AGES (VMU)

Description of the Sub-Task: In this Sub-Task of WP 4, welfare economic calculations will be carried out in order to provide information on the prices at which producers would have to offer

their products in order to be profitable with the implemented biosecurity measures (**WP 4.4**). This calculation is necessary as individual benefits (e.g. low number of human cases) are often visible at the end of the production stages, and not directly at the farm level. N.B. the reduction of human cases can be an (partially) effect due to the implemented measures at the primary production. An equilibrium market price for Europe (based for the three countries chosen: UK, GER, IT) will be estimated for the implemented mitigation measures at the production and/or subsequently stages in the pig production chain in order to reduce the prevalences of salmonella and HEV.

Benchmark of biosecurity practice WP start month: 27

WP end month:

52 WP Leader: :

BfR Deputy WP:

APHA

WP participants: BfR, APHA, IZSAM, NDRVMI, AGES, PIWET, SVA, WBVR, VRI

In **WP5**, first 1) a catalogue of biosecurity measures and their effectiveness, confidence and costs to reduce/limit occurrence of Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus (HEV) in pig production and abattoir will be compiled and filled with information from different sources (studies, literature, machine learning, panel) (see sample spreadsheet Table 2 in the full proposal document). In a second step, 2) biosecurity practices (measures, categories, overall) will be benchmarked for their relevance to limit/reduce Salmonella and HEV in pig production. Different production stages and European regions will be considered.

In T5.1, the gained knowledge on effectiveness, confidence and costs of biosecurity measures from WP2-4 (results from cross-sectional on-farm study, study on slaughterhouse biosecurity, specific field studies, disinfection and biofilm, modelling effectiveness and costs) will be integrated in the catalogue of biosecurity measures which will refine the initial list of potentially relevant effective measures (biosecurity protocol developed in T2.1) for Salmonella and HEV. Knowledge gaps in the effectiveness will be filled by a literature search on peer-reviewed articles (T5.2) which will continue the brief search in T2.1, expand to a meta-analysis and last until M50 in order to collect most current published knowledge. If necessary, information from machine learning (T5.3) and an expert panel (T5.4) will supplement. Finally (5.5), biosecurity practice will be benchmarked for its effectiveness/relevance in order to limit/ reduce Salmonella and HEV occurrence in pig production. The results of WP5 will feed into WP4 and will be incorporated into the development of a support tool offered to veterinarians/consultants/farmers (T6.2) and be disseminated to stakeholders at a final workshop in (T6.3).

Taskxxxiv: JRP#-WP5-T1: Data integration from WP2-4 in catalogue of biosecurity measures Task start month: 27

Task end month:

50 Task Leader: BfR

Deputy Task Leaderxxxv: NDRVMI

Task Participants: BfR, NDRVMI, PIWET, SVA, APHA, AGES, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task: The catalogue of biosecurity measures relevant to limit/reduce Salmonella and HEV occurrence will be developed and continuously filled with findings on biosecurity measures' effectiveness and costs from WP2-4 throughout the project according to each WP's and Task's milestones and deliverables (results from cross-sectional on-farm study, study on slaughterhouse biosecurity, specific field studies, disinfection and biofilm, effectiveness and costs). This task will run until month 50.

Additionally, information on effectiveness from the current literature/meta-analysis, machine learning and panel information, gained in WP5, will be incorporated in the catalogue throughout the project. The reference origin will be noted (e.g. review, T2.2, meta-analysis, panel, machine learning, ...) in the catalogue of biosecurity measures. The catalogue will, thanks to the database structure implemented in WP1, be accessible for insertion and extraction to all partners and thereby continuously inform all WPs on current knowledge. The catalogue will form the base of the final benchmarking and dissemination of most current knowledge.

Task: JRP#-WP5-T2 Literature review/meta-analysis

Task start month: 27

Task end month:

50 Task Leader:

IZSAM

Deputy Task Leader^{xxxvii}: BfR

Task Participants: PIWET, SVA, APHA, BfR, AGES, NDRVMI, IZSAM, WBVR, VRI

Description of the task:

A literature review and meta-analysis on peer-reviewed articles will fill knowledge gaps identified during the preparatory work and the brief initial review for the common biosecurity protocol in WP2. This work will begin in month 27, continue until month 50 and include on-going incorporation of current knowledge on biosecurity effectiveness into the catalogue of biosecurity measures. In case of a lack of information from the literature search (using terms like “biosecurity, pig, Salmonella and HEV”), the search will be expanded and articles on pathogens similar to Salmonella, namely Enterobacteriaceae (pathogenic *E. coli* from intestine and all *E. coli* in the environment of pigs) will be used for extrapolation on Salmonella (Filippitzi et al. 2018 and expert opinion*). Correspondingly, possible consideration of literature regarding biosecurity effectiveness for Salmonella/HEV in production systems of alternative livestock species as e.g. chicken will be clarified in expert interviews. Here also the use of effectiveness-information from non-European regions will be discussed.

The literature review will reveal biosecurity measures relevant for both Salmonella and HEV, for Salmonella only and for HEV only. Additionally, there may be measures relevant for all production stages or for only a part of the production stages. The catalogue of biosecurity measures will thus be stratified by pathogen (Salmonella, HEV) and production stage (breeding, weaner/fattener, farrow- to-finish, abattoir). Moreover, the country of origin will be documented. For the analysis, partner countries will be grouped by meaningful European regions (e.g. north, east, south) (see sample spreadsheet Table 2 in the full proposal document).

*

Filippitzi et al. 2018. Review of transmission routes of 24 infectious diseases preventable by biosecurity measures and comparison of the implementation of these measures in pig herds in six European countries. *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*. 65, 381-398.

Task: JRP#-WP5-T3 Machine learning approaches

Task start month: 47

Task end month:

51 Task Leader: BfR

Deputy Task Leader^{xl}:

APHA Task Participants: BfR, APHA

Description of the task:

We will use a deep learning technique on our database structure to make predictions on certain features missing in the catalogue of biosecurity measures: If, e.g. effectiveness of floor disinfection in stables in southern countries may not be deduced from the literature, we will predict it. Machine learning approaches have been shown to automatically detect pattern in big datasets and to make predictions when learned on sufficient data. At this stage, the project consortium will have assembled a huge amount of data given the vast number of biosecurity measures and the associated features (cost, effectiveness, pathogen, country & region of application, production stage, in-/external measure, confidence, source of information). A deep learning approach can make use of automatic feature learning, i.e. the algorithm can learn to combine multiple features into a new set of abstract features. The latter set can contain new information that we want to make use of. To achieve this, the program consists of multiple layers of connected nodes. The connections are built by the learning of the algorithm using the big dataset.

Task^{xlii}: JRP#-WP5-T4 Expert panel to add estimations on effectiveness/ weights Task start month: 33

Task end month:

51 Task Leader:

SVA

Deputy Task Leader: BfR

Task Participants: BfR, SVA, APHA, AGES, PIWET, NDRVMI, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task:

An expert panel will support the completion of information on biosecurity effectiveness and finally assess biosecurity practices in pig production. In the second year of BIOPIGEE, relevant experts will be further identified and recruited among project partners, their collaborations and known experts from the literature (e.g. researchers, veterinarians, production consultants, pig production associations).

In a first step, the panel will help to close gaps in effectiveness information for some of the biosecurity measures considered and to specify categories of measures relevant for Salmonella and HEV. For this, a questionnaire will be developed and distributed to experts in the field of biosecurity. This survey will be carried out at the 2nd workshop in WP6 and sent to the experts via email/online. Using the questionnaire, experts will be asked to provide effectiveness-information for certain measures and to confirm or modify suggested categories of measures.

Task: JRP#-WP5-T5 Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity practice
Task start month: 45

Task end month:

52 Task Leader: BfR

Deputy Task Leader: APHA

Task Participants: BfR, SVA, APHA, AGES, PIWET, NDRVMI, IZSAM, WBVR

Description of the task:

Based on the catalogue of biosecurity measures built in the former tasks of WP5 and the assessment of the panel, biosecurity practice (measures, categories, overall) relevant for Salmonella and HEV in pig production will be benchmarked, i.e. we will provide a scheme that enables biosecurity practices to be compared amongst each other. At the end of the second BIOPIGEE year, the listed measures will be grouped into categories, according to the results of the first survey of the panel.

WP 6

WP: JRP#-WP6 Dissemination

WP start month 25

WP end month 54

WP Leader Marie Sjölund, SVA

Deputy WP Leader BfR

WP participants SVA, BfR, AGES (VMU), APHA, VFL, IZSLER

Description of the WP

Project results will be made available to students, farmers, veterinarians and the food industry through a number of tools and activities: Results will be presented and supplied as education and information material as well as through user-friendly interfaces on relevant existing websites. A support tool (Excel) to calculate cost effectiveness of interventions will be developed. A workshop-series will be organised to connect researchers and stakeholders "from farm to fork" in order to extract, discuss, inform about and rate country-specific biosecurity practices.

Collaboration with stakeholders in BIOPIGEE will build on previous activities and collaborations in the field of biosecurity. Building on these collaborations, knowledge and experience available in the field of biosecurity on the prevalence of Salmonella and Hepatitis E virus will be gathered and shared. Furthermore, these established collaborations will be used to disseminate the outcomes of BIOPIGEE to the stakeholders and have impact on the policy level.

Building on these collaborations, available data will be collected and new data retrieved on the

prevalence of Salmonella and Hepatitis E Virus in pig production in several countries, as well as on the knowledge and experience available in the field of biosecurity on a general level, and more specifically for the two pathogens addressed.

Task JRP#-WP6-T1: Assembly and development of biosecurity information Task

start month 25

Task end month 54

Task Leader: APHA

Deputy Task Leader^l: AGES (VMU)

Task Participants: SVA, BfR, AGES (VMU), APHA, VFL

Description of the task^{li}: Results from WP2-5 will be provided by the respective work packages to WP6 to be assembled and further adopted for publishing. The results will be made available for farming schools through engaging and catchy education material. Moreover, the results will also be made available in a user-friendly interface on already existing websites of the One Health EJP, BIOPIGEE partners and relevant stakeholders such as associations of pig producers and veterinarians, authorities, educational bodies and companies along the food chain.

Sub-Task JRP#-WP6-T1-ST1 Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

Sub-Task start month 25

Sub-Task end month

54 Sub-Task Leader:

SVA

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: APHA

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, SVA, BfR, AGES (VMU)

Description of the sub-task: Already existing websites of partner organisations and interested relevant stakeholders such as associations of previously identified pig producers and veterinarians, authorities, educational bodies and companies along the food chain will be used to publish project results to reach out most efficiently. Both passive and active observations will be conducted throughout the project period to identify the at the time most appropriate organisations including their websites.

Sub-Task^{liv} JRP#-WP6-T1-ST2a Provision of information for farming schools and websites

Sub-Task start month 31

Sub-Task end month

52 Sub-Task Leader:

BfR

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: APHA

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, SVA, BfR, AGES (VMU), VFL

Description of the sub-task: Relevant information material such as pictures of examples of good biosecurity practices will continuously be collected in WP2 (T2.4), forwarded to WP6 (sT6.1.2) and here be supplemented by existing and available material gathered from BIOPIGEE participants and cooperation partners. Information material (e.g. pictures) will be assembled, discussed with animal health services, training institutions and farming schools, and complemented with short messages by sT6.1.2 for dissemination towards e.g. farming schools at the end of the project. The material will also be available for the use on websites and be offered to relevant collaboration partners of BIOPIGEE participants.

Sub-Task JRP#-WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

Sub-Task start month

31 Sub-Task end month

52 Sub-Task Leader: BfR

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: APHA

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, BfR, AGES (VMU); VFL, IZSAM, ISS, WBVR, RIVM, VFL

Description of the sub-task:

A slaughterhouse biosecurity protocol applied and evaluated in WP2 T2.3 will be disseminated to inform slaughterhouses about effective biosecurity measures in participating countries.

Task^{lviii} JRP#-WP6-T3: Organisation of a workshop-series

Task start month 25

Task end

month54 Task

Leader: BfR

Deputy Task Leader: SVA

Task Participants: APHA, SVA, BfR, AGES (VMU) , IZSLER

Description of the task 6.3: Workshops will be organised to connect researchers and stakeholders in a farm-to-fork fashion to discuss and rate specific biosecurity measures and inform about obtained results. Three one-day-workshops will be co-organised by SVA and BfR in conjunction to relevant conferences such as the One Health EJP ASM, SafePork and the European Symposium of Porcine Health Management. Researchers and stakeholders representing all regions in Europe will have the opportunity to participate in discussions on biosecurity practices and to share their views on appropriate practices. Care will be taken to encompass participants from the different stages of the food chain from farm to fork. We seek to:

- extract and discuss country-specific biosecurity practices
- conduct an expert rating of biosecurity measures
- evaluate on the actors' responsibility of Salmonella-infection regarding the stages of the food chain
- inform stakeholders (results of WP2-5)

Sub-Task JRP#-WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

Sub-Task start month 25

Sub-Task end month

52 Sub-Task Leader:

BfR

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: SVA

Sub-Task Participants: APHA, SVA, BfR, AGES (VMU) , IZSLER

Description of the sub-task: The identification process will be carried out continuously to reach out to the at the time most relevant stakeholders of pig producers and veterinarians, authorities, educational bodies and companies along the food chain. This process will shift from being an active process at times to a more passive process of observations performed during everyday work and contact with stakeholders.

Sub-Task^l JRP#-WP6-T3-ST4 Organisation of Workshop 2

Sub-Task start month 37

Sub-Task end month

42 Sub-Task Leader:

SVA

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP#-WP3.7	Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on Salmonella in biofilm	M40
D-JRP#-WP2.8	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at slaughterhouses	M42

D-JRP#-WP2.9	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at farm	M42
D-JRP#-WP6.10	Workshop 2 completed	M42
D-JRP#-WP4.11	Model Output: Number of animal cases with and without biosecurity measures	M47
D-JRP#-WP2.12	Produce report on evidence gathered by field studies	M48
D-JRP#-WP1.13	Project report 2nd year submitted	M48
D-JRP#-WP1.19	Revised data management plan submitted	M48
D-JRP#-WP3.14	Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers/biofilm	M48
D-JRP#-WP6.15	Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided	M48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP#-12	Mid-term meeting successfully organized	M39
M-JRP#-13	Application of protocols across countries	M40
M-JRP#-14	Relevant stakeholders re-identified	M40
M-JRP#-15	Transmission model adaption based on available data	M40
M-JRP#-16	Test methods to be used in JRP#-WP3-T2-ST2 are selected	M40
M-JRP#-17	Produce summary of evidence of slaughterhouse biosecurity effectiveness	M42
M-JRP#-18	Workshop 2 completed	M42
M-JRP#-19	Completion of farm visits and lab work	M44
M-JRP#-20	Application of appropriate economic methods based on available data	M45
M-JRP#-21	Uploading of sequences to HEVnet	M48

2.4.2.1.22 JRP22-R2-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)			FBZ 4.1: Source attribution and transmission routes of foodborne pathogens other than bacteria, with emphasis on <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>							
Research Project Title			<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> sources quantified							
Research Project Acronym			TOXOSOURCES							
Leading Organisation			P13-SSI			Deputy Leading Organisation			P30-RIVM	
Project Leader			Pikka Jokelainen			Deputy Project leader			Joke van der Giessen	
Project Start month			M25			Project End month			M54	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	11,2				6,6	11	7,6	9	6,05	1,05
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	15,95				11,4					
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	3,25				36,3			8,86	0,15	1,55
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM	2,88	7,55	6,1	2		1				
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ TOXOSOURCES evaluates existing source attribution models for their suitability to a parasitic foodborne pathogen, improves them, and applies them (WP2). Quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA) existing at national basis for the meatborne pathway (tissue cysts) will be extended to a European level. Moreover, QMRA for the environmental pathway (oocysts) will be developed. Innovative integration of available data is emphasized, and existing major data gaps are identified and filled by targeted multicentre studies (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5). 										

- ✓ TOXOSOURCES yields the first quantitative and comparable estimates of contribution of the different sources for the four regions within Europe (WP2). Moreover, TOXOSOURCES yields an overview of consumption habits that are also relevant for other foodborne pathogens (WP2, WP3). TOXOSOURCES addresses geographical differences in the epidemiology of *T. gondii*, in animals, humans and the environment (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5). The consortium has excellent geographical balance within Europe for multicentre studies, and external partners from China add to the global trade aspect. The work includes collaboration with the food production and retail sectors (WP2, WP3, Interest Group).
- ✓ TOXOSOURCES will develop a novel serological method that specifically explores detection of infections caused by the oocysts (WP4) in Europe, and a novel NGS-MLST typing method that can detect within-genotype patterns that are important for understanding transmission routes (WP5). The latter will be a tool for source tracing, and improves preparedness to identify outbreaks and imported emerging atypical strains. The development processes will make optimal use of existing sample collections from suitable epidemiological frameworks.
- ✓ TOXOSOURCES consortium is very well aware of research that has been done previously in this field. Emphasis is put on complementarity, avoiding redundancy and overlap, and on impact, measurably advancing the knowledge on this major zoonotic pathogen. The results from the different approaches are integrated and compared to yield robust new information that is of importance to the Key EU Stakeholders and will contribute to the development of innovative and effective interventions at national, regional, European and global levels (WP1).

Description of work

The work is organized into 5 work packages (WPs) with tasks (T) and some subtasks (sT). The 2.5-year project spans over three Annual Periods (Y3-Y5) and is described in three Work Plans.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1 Coordination and impact

WP start month M25 - WP end month M54

WP Leader Pikka Jokelainen, SSI; Deputy WP Leader Joke van der Giessen, RIVM

WP participants SSI, RIVM, ISS, FLI, BfR, RKI, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, FHI, INIAV, INSA, NVI, SLV, SVA, SZÚ, UoS, VRI, WBVR, BIOR, CVRL, NMBU, BRCT/NRCT, AUTH, UASVMCN, HZAU, JLU

WP1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. WP1 works closely with all the WPs of the project. Objectives of WP1:

- To manage and coordinate the project.
- To draft and implement the Data Management Plan for TOXOSOURCES.
- To integrate all the results to contribute to developing interventions.
- To ensure the results will be useful (dissemination).

WP1 manages the project and is responsible for its progress, and integrates all the results of the project to make them useful, in particular to contribute to developing interventions.

WP1 ensures the project adheres to H2020 rules regarding e.g. ethics, IRP, dissemination and publication. Moreover, WP1 is responsible for the Data Management Plan of the project. WP1 coordinates the compiling of deliverables and reports and their timely submission to the Support Team, as well as the organizing of project meetings and communication. Science-to-policy translation and efficient dissemination are emphasized to maximize the impact. Interest Group facilitates targeted dissemination to stakeholders. During Y4, the main focus is ensuring the project progresses efficiently as planned, and organizing the Annual Meeting.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1-T1 Management, coordination and communication

Task start month M25 - Task end month M54

Task Leader: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI; Deputy Task Leader: Joke van der Giessen, RIVM

Task Participants: SSI, RIVM, ISS, FLI, BfR, RKI, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, FHI, INIAV, INSA, NVI, SLV, SVA, SZÚ, UoS, VRI, WBVR, BIOR, CVRL, NMBU, BRCT/NRCT, AUTH, UASVMCN, HZAU, JLU

WP1-T1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Coordination and management of the project. Coordination of compiling of deliverables and reports and their timely submission to the Support Team. Ensuring that the project adheres to H2020 rules regarding e.g. ethics, dissemination and publication. Coordination of organizing project meetings: during the second year of the project: Annual Meeting (AM), in connection to the Annual Scientific Meeting of the OHEJP. Communication within the consortium: teleconference of the WP Leaders and Co-Leaders monthly, email correspondence with the WP Leaders and the whole consortium. Dialogue with the Interest Group is continued.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1-T2 Integration of all results to contribute to developing interventions, dissemination

Task start month M37 - Task end month M52

Task Leader: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI; Deputy Task Leader: Joke van der Giessen, RIVM

Task Participants: SSI, RIVM, ISS, FLI, BfR, RKI, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, FHI, INIAV, INSA, NVI, SLV, SVA, SZÚ, UoS, VRI, WBVR, BIOR, CVRL, NMBU, BRCT/NRCT, AUTH, UASVMCN, HZAU, JLU

WP1-T2 takes places over the second and the third year of the project. Efficient dissemination and science-to-policy activities at national, European and global levels include facilitating the use of the new knowledge, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, and advocating multidisciplinary approaches.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2 Multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii* infections

WP start month M25 - WP end month M54

WP Leader: Marieke Opsteegh, RIVM; Deputy WP Leader: Sara Monteiro Pires, DTU

WP participants: SSI, RIVM, ISS, FLI, BfR, RKI, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, FHI, INIAV, INSA, NVI, SLV, SVA, SZÚ, UoS, VRI, WBVR, UASMVCN

WP2 takes place over the first (Y3), the second (Y4) and the third year (Y5). WP2 works closely with WP1 and WP3. Objectives of WP2:

- To estimate the relative contribution of food and environmental transmission routes (T1)
- To provide an overview of the prevalence in food animals and cats (T2)
- To quantify human exposure to possible sources of infection (T3)
- To provide an overview of the processing parameters for relevant meat products (T4)
- To provide an overview of prevalence and risk factors of human infection (T5)

WP2 estimates the relative contribution of different sources of *T. gondii* infection by quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA). QMRA models for infection via tissue cysts (meat) and oocysts (fruits, vegetables and environmental pathways) will be developed and applied for nine countries (DK, NO, CZ, PL, PT, ES, FR, DE, NL) representing all four regions of Europe. During Y4, the main focus is finalising the data collection and running the QMRA model. The exposure survey will be rolled out, meat processing information is collected and the literature reviews are finalised.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T1 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections

Task start month M25 - Task end month M54

Task Leader: Arno Swart, RIVM; Deputy Task Leader: Jakob Ottoson, SLV

Task Participants: SSI, RIVM, FLI, BfR, RKI, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, FHI, INIAV, INSA, NVI, SLV, SZÚ, VRI

WP2-T1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. During Y4, the main focus is checking input data from WP2-T2-T3-T4 and WP3 and running the QMRA model. In addition, sensitivity analyses (to identify the most influential input parameters) and scenario analyses (in case of large uncertainty regarding input parameters) will be initiated.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T2 Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* infection in animals

Task start month M25 - Task end month M40

Task Leader: Radu Blaga, ANSES; Deputy Task Leader: Helga Waap, INIAV

Task Participants: SSI, RIVM, ISS, FLI, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, INIAV, NVI, SVA, UoS, VRI, WBVR, BIOR, UASVMCN

WP2-T2 takes place over the first and the second year of the project. The results will be prepared for scientific publication in Y4.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T3 Quantitative exposure survey

Task start month M25 - Task end month M48

Task Leader: Arno Swart, RIVM; Deputy Task Leader: Jurgen Chardon, RIVM

Task Participants: SSI, RIVM, BfR, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, FHI, INIAV, VRI

WP2-T3 takes place over the first and second year of the project. During Y4, the questionnaires developed in Y3 will be distributed via a market research agency to collect harmonised data on food consumption and handling and exposure to oocysts from the countries included in the QMRA. The data will be delivered to WP2-T1 and made publically available to be used for QMRA modelling of other foodborne pathogens.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T4 Overview of processing parameters for relevant meat products

Task start month M25 - Task end month M45

Task Leader: Bretislav Koudela, VRI; Deputy Task Leader: Jacek Sroka, PIWET

Task Participants: SSI, RIVM, BfR, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, DTU, INIAV, NVI, SVA, VRI

WP2-T4 takes place over the first and second year of the project. During Y4, the data from WP2-T3 are used to decide which meat products are included in the QMRA model. Subsequently, product-specific parameter values for freezing, salting and heating (e.g. time, temperature, concentration) are collated. The information will be obtained using meat processing handbooks, communication with meat producers, or from package information in retail, and delivered as input data to WP2-T1.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T5 Review of prevalence and risk factors for human *T. gondii* infection

Task start month M25 - Task end month M54

Task Leader: Agnetha Hofhuis, RIVM; Deputy Task Leader: Lasse S. Vestergaard, SSI

Task Participants: SSI, RIVM, RKI, UCM, ANSES, PIWET, FHI, INSA, SVA, SZÚ, UoS

WP2-T5 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. During Y4, the main focus is to finalize data extraction, analyse the results and deliver data to WP2-T1. The data will be analysed by Bayesian hierarchical modelling to estimate the prevalence/incidence by country.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3 Multicentre survey to fill the key existing gap: role of fresh produce (i.e. Ready-to-Eat salads)

WP start month M25 - WP end month M54

WP Leader: Marco Lalle, ISS; Deputy WP Leader: Anne Mayer-Scholl, BfR

WP participants: ISS, BfR, UCM, UoS, VRI, RIVM, NVI, PIWET, INIAV, ANSES, SSI, UCM, ISS, BIOR, AUTH, NMBU

WP3 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. WP3 works closely with WP1, WP2 and WP5. Objectives of TOXOSOURCES WP3:

- To identify and assess the most appropriate procedure to detect *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce.
- To provide an overview of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce and the environment.
- To conduct a risk-based pilot study based on available prevalence data (literature review), data on food production chains, EU trade patterns of selected fresh produce and available consumption data (WP2).
- To evaluate *T. gondii* oocyst contamination in selected fresh produce commodities by a multicentre pilot survey in representative EU regions.

WP3 aims to fill the knowledge gap concerning the relevance of fresh produce contamination by *T. gondii* oocysts as an infection source for humans. WP3 selects the most reliable methods for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce (i.e. vegetables, fruits and fruit juice) using a literature review and experimental evaluation through inter-laboratory comparison. Harmonised detection method(s) are implemented among the partners of WP3 by providing a standard operating procedure (SOP) and organizing a technical workshop. In Y4, the focus is to: i) perform a ring trial to assess the implementation of the molecular detection method(s) among partners; ii) to complete the collection by literature review of existing data for *T. gondii* oocysts in environment to be provided to WP2; iii) to perform the multicentre survey.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3-T1 Selection, evaluation and implementation of detection procedure for *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce

Task start month M25 - Task end month M39

Task Leader: Marco Lalle, ISS; Deputy Task Leader: Iva Slana, VRI

Task Participants: ISS, BfR, UCM, UoS, VRI, NVI, PIWET, BIOR, INIAV, ANSES, SSI, AUTH, NMBU

WP3-T1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project. The overall goal of this task is to select the most reliable published methods (sensitive and/or quantitative) for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce to be applied during the survey, experimentally assess the method(s) performance and ensure the method (s) implementation and harmonization among the partners that will contribute to the survey. The SOPs provided in Y3 will be implemented in the partner laboratories. E-meetings will promote problem solving among the laboratories. To complete the validation process of the SOP, ISS will organize a ring trial among the partners (BfR, UCM; NVI, PIWET, NVI), and ring trial results will be analysed and SOP amended accordingly.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3-T2 Design of a risk-based sampling strategy

Task start month M26 - Task end month M48

Task Leader: Rafael Calero, UCM; Deputy Task Leader: Martha Betson, UoS

Task Participants: ISS, BfR, UCM, UoS, VRI, RIVM, NVI, PIWET, BIOR, INIAV, ANSES, SSI, AUTH, NMBU

WP3-T2 takes place over the first and the second year of the project. Existing data will be compiled on the prevalence of *T. gondii* oocysts on fresh produce, as well as the environment, together with information on food production chains, trade patterns and consumption of fresh produce commodities (e.g. ready-to-eat (RTE) products) within EU. Data are combined to design a sampling plan for WP3-T2, taking into account sample size calculations, feasibility and costs. In Y4, the extensive literature review of existing data on *T. gondii* prevalence in environment (including soil and water) in Europe is completed and data delivered to WP2 to be integrated in the QMRA. Moreover, the sampling strategy for WP3-T3 is defined.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3-T3 Multicentre pilot survey on *T. gondii* in fresh produce in Europe

Task start month M40 - Task end month M54

Task Leader: Nadja Bier, BfR; Deputy Task Leader: Marco Lalle, ISS

Task Participants: ISS, BfR, UCM, UoS, VRI, NVI, PIWET, BIOR, INIAV, ANSES, SSI, AUTH
WP3-T3 takes place over the second and third year of the project. A multicentre pilot survey for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce in Europe is performed based on outputs of WP3-T1 and WP3-T2. Samples are collected, during one year, in 12 countries representative of the four EU regions (DK, NO, LV, PL, CZ, IT, ES, PT, GR, DE, FR, UK), according to the strategy developed in WP3-T2. Fresh produce samples are dispatched refrigerated, within 24h-48h, to partner institutions to be analysed using the SOP defined in WP3-T1. Satellite partners (UoS, BIOR, INIAV, ANSES, SSI, AUTH) perform only the oocysts recovery step of the SOP, store frozen the processed samples and deliver once, under frozen condition, to main partners (ISS, BfR, UCM, VRI, NVI, PIWET) to complete the molecular testing. This approach will ensure faster processing of the perishable fresh produce thus increasing the overall amount of tested samples.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4 Serology method based on novel antigens to discriminate *T. gondii* infections acquired from oocysts

WP start month M25 - WP end month M54

WP Leader: Furio Spano, ISS; Deputy WP Leader: Frank Seeber, RKI

WP participants: ISS, RKI, UCM, NVI, RIVM, SSI, ANSES, FLI, PIWET, INIAV, WBVR, INSA, VRI, BIOR, HZAU, JLU

WP4 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. Objectives of WP4:

- To identify *T. gondii* antigens with source-attributing potential (proteins of interest, POIs)
- To explore serological methods that discriminate oocyst- from tissue cyst-driven infections
- To estimate the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in humans and animals

WP4 identifies novel antigens of *T. gondii* that have source-attributing potential and explores serological methods able to discriminate between oocyst- vs. tissue cyst-driven infections.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T1 Identification and production of *T. gondii* stage-specific antigens for source attribution

Task start month M25 - Task end month M48

Task Leader: Furio Spano, ISS; Deputy Task Leader: Frank Seeber, RKI

Task Participants: ISS, RKI, FLI

WP4-T1 takes place over the first and the second year of the project. In Y4, additional POIs will be produced, and the work on an antibody profiling method will be continued.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T2 Development of a novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections

Task start month M29 - Task end month M48

Task Leader: Gema Álvarez-García, UCM; Deputy Task Leader: Luis Ortega Mora, UCM

Task Participants: UCM, ANSES, VRI, PIWET, RIVM

WP4-T2 takes place over the first and the second year of the project. Work continues, and additional POIs from WP4T1 are assessed using the step-by-step validation process.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T2-sT1 Standardization of a POI-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and/or bradyzoite driven *T. gondii* infections using reference pig sera

Sub-Task Leader: Gema Álvarez-García, UCM

Sub-Task Participants: ANSES, VRI, PIWET

Work continues; sera from experimentally infected pigs are screened by two source attribution approaches (sporozoite antigen-based ELISA or bradyzoite antibody profiling).

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T2-sT2 Validation of a novel stage-specific antigen based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and/or bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections using reference sera from several relevant host species including humans

Sub-Task Leader: Luis Ortega Mora, UCM

Sub-Task Participants: ANSES, RIVM, SSI

Work continues; reference sera from animals and humans are tested.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T3 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-derived *T. gondii* infections in animals and in humans

Task start month M40 - Task end month M54

Task Leader: Rebecca Davidson, NVI; Task Co-Leader: Radu Blaga, ANSES

Task Participants: NVI, ANSES, PIWET, SSI, BRCT, RIVM, INIAV, WBVR, VRI, BIOR, INSA

WP4-T3 takes place over the second and third year of the project. Using the POI-ELISA validated in WP4-T2, an inter-laboratory ring trial is conducted, followed by pilot studies. The method will also be offered to other Consortium partners for testing existing collections of positive sera.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory validation of the POI-based ELISA

Sub-Task Leader: Rebecca Davidson, NVI

Sub-Task participants: NVI, ANSES, PIWET, SSI, RIVM, INSA, BRCT

POI-based ELISA will be adapted to the participating laboratories to obtain comparable results. Inter-laboratory reproducibility and analytical sensitivity will be evaluated using positive and negative reference sera (experimental *T. gondii* infection) identified in WP4-T2-sT1.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T3-sT2 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in domestic animals (pigs, small ruminants) and wildlife (wild-boar, wild ungulates) used for human consumption

Sub-Task Leader: Radu Blaga, ANSES

Sub-Task participants: ANSES, NVI, PIWET, INIAV, WBVR, VRI, BIOR, SSI

To reveal differences in the relative prevalence of oocyst-driven infections between animal species, regions and management systems, positive sera from naturally infected animals from different European regions will be tested using the POI-based ELISA.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4-T3-sT3 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in humans

Sub-Task Leader: Henrik Vedel Nielsen, SSI

Sub-Task participants: SSI, RIVM, INSA, BRCT/NRCT

Well-defined positive sera from *T. gondii*-infected humans available from different European regions will be tested using the POI-based ELISA from WP4-T2 by pilot studies: (i) 50-100 sera from congenitally-infected children aged <13 months and from older children >2 years; (ii) 200-500 sera from recently infected adults; (iii) sera from any suspected *T. gondii* outbreaks in Europe.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5 Novel *T. gondii* typing method to detect within-genotype variation

WP start month M25 - WP end month M54

WP Leader: Gereon Schares, FLI; Deputy WP Leader: Simone Caccio, ISS

WP participants ANSES, BIOR, FLI, ISS, NVI, PIWET, RIVM, SSI, UCM, VRI, SZÚ/NIPH, HZAU, JLU

WP5 takes place over the first, second and the third year of the project. Objectives of WP5:

- To develop a novel *T. gondii* typing method with the discriminatory power needed in Europe
- To apply the novel method in pilot studies

WP5 aims to identify highly polymorphic regions in genomes of very closely related *T. gondii* strains across Europe. Preliminary NGS data on European Type II *T. gondii*, obtained in EURLP/ISS-FLI collaboration revealed substantial variation between isolates and relative to reference strains. Using a panel of representative strains, regions in the genome with an optimal SNP density are identified and used to establish a novel high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST-typing method.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T1 Retrieval of relevant *T. gondii* isolates or NGS-quality DNAs for NGS and NGS-MST typing

Task start month M25 - Task end month M44

Task Leader: Gereon Schares, FLI; Deputy Task Leader: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI

Task Participants: ANSES, BIOR, FLI, ISS, NVI, PIWET, RIVM, SSI, UCM, VRI, SZÚ/NIPH, HZAU, JLU

WP5-1 takes place over the first and second year of the project. In addition to the *T. gondii* isolates or WGS-quality DNAs collected in Y3, further isolates are collected to establish a panel for inter-laboratory comparison and pilot studies (WP5-T3). For particular regions, we aim at a larger number of further isolates (about n=10) to show that resolution of typing is high enough to trace differences of local isolates. All DNAs in the panel are also characterised based on polymorphism of fewer markers using existing standard techniques (PCR-RFLP and microsatellite (MS) typing).

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T2 Novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method

Task start month M25 - Task end month M48

Task Leader: Simone Caccio, ISS; Deputy Task Leader: Pavlo Maksimov, FLI

Task Participants: ANSES, BIOR, FLI, ISS, NVI, PIWET, RIVM, SSI, UCM, VRI, SZÚ/NIPH, HZAU, JLU

WP5-T2 takes place over the first and second year of the project. Based on sequence information obtained by WP5-T1 a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST genotyping method is established and validated to separate closely related *T. gondii* strains.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T2-sT2 Establishment, validation and refinement of a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method

Sub-Task start month M31 - Sub-Task end month M44

Sub-Task Leader: Pavlo Maksimov, FLI; Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Simone Caccio, ISS

Sub-Task Participants: FLI, ISS

For validation, the novel NGS-MLST results are compared with results of conventional techniques (PCR-RFLP, MS typing) (i). Similarities and differences in the capability of the novel NGS-MLST method and the PCR-RFLP- and MS-based techniques for the *T. gondii* differentiation are established. (ii) The analytical sensitivity is determined using different sample matrices, spiked with different levels of parasites. Sample matrices included are intermediate host tissues, feline faeces and environmental samples. A standardized workflow for the collection and preliminary analysis of NGS-MLST data on *T. gondii* is established. Finally, the new technology is distributed to interested partners by a workshop at FLI prior to inter-laboratory comparison and pilot studies (WP5-T3).

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T3 Inter-laboratory comparison and NGS-MLST pilot studies

Task start month M41 - Task end month M54

Task Leader: Luis Ortega-Mora, UCM; Deputy Task Leader: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI

Task Participants: ANSES, BIOR, FLI, ISS, NVI, PIWET, RIVM, SSI, UCM, VRI, SZÚ/NIPH, HZAU, JLU

WP5-T3 takes place over the second and third year of the project. First, an inter-laboratory comparison of the established novel NGS-MLST genotyping method is performed. In Y5 the method will be applied on “real/unknown“ *T. gondii* positive samples from the field, i.e. samples from intermediate hosts (including humans), definitive hosts and environment, by 4-6 selected labs representing all four European regions. There will be altogether three pilot studies, designed in detail during M41-M48 based on availability of suitable isolates/DNAs/samples, collected in collaboration with WP5-T1, and the applicability of the method to different matrices, as tested in WP5-T2. Aim is to apply the method to samples from intermediate hosts, definitive hosts, and environment. A questionnaire among the interested partners revealed >100 positive DNA samples, suitable for this purpose and already available at this stage.

JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory comparison on the novel NGS-MLST method
Sub-Task start month M41 - Sub-Task end month M48
Sub-Task Leader: Pavlo Maksimov, FLI; Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Rafael Calero-Bernal, UCM
Sub-Task Participants: FLI, UCM

An inter-laboratory comparison of the established novel NGS-MLST genotyping method is performed: a defined set of samples is send out to 4-6 selected labs from all four European regions to confirm that typing results are in accord between different labs.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.3	Report on the ring trial of WP3	M40
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.1	Report on prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> infection in animals for human consumption and cats within Europe	M40
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.2	Report on quantitative exposure data from survey of WP2	M48
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.4	Report on literature review on the prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> oocysts in fresh produce and environment	M48
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.2	SOP for a novel source-attributing serological method	M48
D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1	SOP for a novel NGS-MLST genotyping method of WP5	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-09	Finalization of risk-based sampling strategy of WP3	M38
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-10	Country-specific estimates of prevalence in animals provided as input for QMRA	M38
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-11	Questionnaires for exposure survey ready to be rolled out by WP2	M38

M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-12	List of meat products for which processing parameters need to be collected is provided to WP2-T4	M40
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-13	Exposure data from survey are provided as input for QMRA	M43
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-14	Processing parameters for relevant meat products are provided as input for QMRA	M45
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-15	Country-specific estimates for prevalence of human <i>T. gondii</i> infection provided as input data for QMRA	M45
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-	Delivery of data summary on fresh produce consumption in EU from WP3 to WP2	M45
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-	Delivery of data summary on literature-based prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> oocysts in environment from WP3 to WP2	M45
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-	Antigens for serological assays	M48
M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-	Annual Meeting held by WP1	M48

2.4.2.1.23 JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ-SH 5: Determinants of the reversal of the decreasing trend in Salmonella incidence in humans and poultry in the EU								
Research Project Title		Assessing Determinants Of the Non decreasing Incidence of Salmonella								
Research Project Acronym		ADONIS								
Leading Organisation		P30-RIVM			Deputy Leading Organisation			P34-PIWET		
Project Leader		Eelco FRANZ			Deputy Project leader			Dariusz WASYL		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMIL	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	17,9	3,8	18,16							
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	15				13			20,4	8,52	1,25
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UOS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM					4,5			10,82	5,9	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM		9,5	9,35	26,35						
Objectives: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● to facilitate partners' cooperation and WP integration ● to guarantee timely delivery of periodic reports ● to accumulate, communicate and disseminate project outcomes 										
Description of work JPR26-WP1 Project management WP start month: 25 WP end month: 54 WP Leader: Eelco FRANZ (RIVM) Deputy WP Leader: Dariusz WASYL (PIWET) WP participants: ANSES, Sciensano, SSI, UCM, IP, RIVM, PIWET										

Description of the WP:

WP1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project. It is led by projects leaders supported by WPs leaders and deputies. It facilitates and cumulates all the efforts taken within other WPs, summarises and reports the outcomes to OHEJP management team, aligns and communicates to other OHEJP research and integrative activities, and disseminates the conclusions beyond OHEJP.

WP1 consists of two tasks ongoing throughout the project period. Since task 1 governs internal issues of the ADONIS consortium, task 2 is orientated to external partners and stakeholders.

JPR26-WP1-T1 Coordination

Task Leader: Eelco FRANZ (RIVM)

For fluent communication, planning and results sharing between partners and WPs three physical meetings and regular teleconferences are organised for the entire consortium, WPs leaders/deputies or given WP partners, depending on the issue.

Y4 Annual progress meeting, followed by teleconferences are organised in operational phase to follow, assess, and steer the achievements of the project.

JPR26-WP1-T2 Aligning and communication

Task Leader: Eelco FRANZ (RIVM)

T2 consists of two subtasks.

JPR26-WP1-T2-ST1 Reporting

Subtask Leader: Eelco FRANZ (RIVM)

ST1 is responsible for annual reporting to OHEJP coordinator.

Annual report for Y3 is prepared.

JPR26-WP1-T2-ST2 Alignment and communication

Subtask Leader: Dariusz WASYL (PIWET)

ST2 is responsible for alignment and communication with other OHEJP activities and stakeholders.

Aligning and communication with relevant OHEJP activities and stakeholders is continued and facilitated.

JPR26-WP2 *Salmonella* controls at the primary production level

WP start month 25

WP end month 54

WP Leader Michel-Yves MISTOU (ANSES)

Deputy WP Leader Julio ALVAREZ SANCHEZ (VISAVET-UCM)

WP participants ANSES, APHA, PIWET, VISAVET-UCM, WVBR

Description of the WP: continued from previous year

JPR26-WP2-T2.1 Comparative analysis of *Salmonella* controls and management measures at MSs level

Task start month 25

Task end month 48

Task Leader: Julio Alvarez Sanchez (VISAVET-UCM)

Deputy Task Leader: Jowita S. Niczyporuk Dariusz WASYL (PIWET)

Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, PIWET, VISAVET-UCM, WVBR

Description of the task: continued from previous year

JPR26-WP2-T2.2 Comparative analysis of *Salmonella* controls and management measures at farm level

Task start month 25

Task end month 48

Task Leader: Dariusz WASIL (PIWET)

Deputy Leader: Becky GOSLING (APHA)

Task Participants: ANSES, APHA, PIWET, VISAVET-UCM, WVBR

Description of the task: continued from previous year

JRP26-WP2-T2.2-ST1 Field studies during outbreaks and sensitivity testing

SubTask Leader: Sophie LEBOUQUIN-LENEVEU (ANSES)

SubTask Participants: ANSES, APHA, VWBR

Description of substak: continued from previous year

JRP26-WP2-T2.2-ST2 On farm surveys

SubTask Leader: Jowita S NICZYPORUK (PIWET)

SubTask Participants: PIWET, VISAVET-UCM, VWBR, ANSES, APHA

Description of substak: continued from previous year

JPR26-WP3 Surveillance, epidemiology and source attribution

WP start month: 25

WP end month: 48

WP Leader: Roan PIJNACKER (RIVM)

Deputy WP Leader: Nina VAN GOETHEM (Sciensano)

WP participants: RIVM, Sciensano, AGES, INIAV, INSA, ISS, Pasteur, VISAVET-UCM

JPR26-WP3-T1 Evaluation of surveillance systems in humans

WP start month: 26

WP end month: 48

Task Leader: Nina VAN GOETHEM (Sciensano)

Deputy Leader: Roan PIJNACKER (RIVM)

WP participants: RIVM, Sciensano, INSA, Pasteur, VISAVET-UCM, AGES

Description of the task: In the second year of the project, the surveillance systems of the three selected countries will be evaluated on several attributes, including validity (e.g. extent of correct information about the cases), completeness (i.e. stratified by internal and external completeness), sensitivity (i.e. the proportion of cases in the population that are notified through the surveillance system) and representativeness (i.e. the extent to which the cases captured by surveillance reflect the cases in the general population). These will be quantified using indicators that are associated with the attributes, such as proportion of cases complying with the case definitions (associated with validity), percentage of cases with no missing information (associated with completeness), proportion of cases in the general population reported to the surveillance system (associated with sensitivity), and proportion of the total population covered (associated with representativeness).

JPR26-WP3-T2 Assessment of changes in the epidemiology of human *S. Enteritidis* cases and other relevant serovars

WP start month: 29

WP end month: 48

Task Leader: Roan PIJNACKER (RIVM)
Deputy Leader: Angela PISTA (INSA)
WP participants: RIVM, INSA, INIAV, VISAVET-UCM

Description of the task: Continued from previous year.

JRP26-WP3-T3 Assessment of human exposure to *S. Enteritidis*

WP start month: 32
WP end month: 48
Deputy Leader: Eric EVERS (RIVM)
WP participants: RIVM, Piwet, WBVR

Description of the task: Continued from previous year.

JRP26-WP4 *Salmonella* Genomics

WP start month: 25
WP end month: 54
WP Leader: Eva Litrup (SSI)
Deputy WP Leader: Maria Pardos de La Gandara (IP)
WP participants: SSI, IP, RIVM, Piwet, Sciensano, WBVR, PHE, APHA, INSA, INIAV, ANSES, VISAVET, AGES, ISS
Description of the WP: continued from previous year

JRP26-WP4-T2 Population structure and comparative genomics

Task start month M25
Task end month M48
Task Leader: Eva Litrup (SSI)
Deputy Task Leader: Maria Pardos de La Gandara (IP)
Task Participants: SSI, IP, RIVM, Piwet, Sciensano, PHE, APHA, INSA, INIAV, ANSES, VISAVET, AGES, ISS
Description of the task: continued from previous year

JRP26-WP4-T3 Phylodynamics and Phylogeography

Task start month: 31
Task end month: 51
Task Leader: Eelco Franz (RIVM)
Deputy Task Leader:
Task Participants: SSI, IP, RIVM, Piwet, Sciensano, PHE, APHA, INSA, INIAV, ANSES, VISAVET
Description of the task: continued from previous year

JRP26-WP4-T4 Mutant creation and testing including GWAS studies

Task start month: 31
Task end month: 54
Task Leader: Eva Litrup (SSI)
Deputy Task Leader Michel-Yves Mistou (ANSES)
Task Participants: SSI, IP, Piwet, Sciensano, APHA, INSA, INIAV, ANSES, ISS
Description of the task: continued from previous year
Sub-Task GWAS studies
Sub-Task start month: 37
Sub-Task end month: 54

Sub-Task Leader: Nicolas Radomski (ANSES)
Sub-Task Participants: SSI, IP, Piwet, Sciensano, APHA, INSA, INIAV, ANSES, ISS

WP5: JRP26-WP5 MCDA model to support priority setting

WP start month 28

WP end month 52

WP Leader: Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)

Deputy WP Leader: Nina van Goethem (Sciensano)

WP participants: RIVM, Sciensano, WBVR

Description of the WP: Continued from previous year.

Task: JRP26FBZ-4-WP5-T1 Framework building

Task start month 28

Task end month 48

Task Leader: Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)

Deputy Task Leader: Nina van Goethem (Sciensano)

Task Participants: RIVM, Sciensano, WBVR

Description of the task: Continued from previous year.

Task: JRP26FBZ-4-WP5-T2 MCDA modelling

Task start month 36

Task end month 52

Task Leader: Lapo Mughini-Gras (RIVM)

Deputy Task Leader: Roan Pijnacker (RIVM)

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-JRP26-WP1.2	Y3 report delivered	39
D-JRP26-WP2.2	MS's specific analysis of temporal trend of Salmonella in poultry flocks	42
D-JRP26-WP2.3	MS's specific analysis of temporal trend of Salmonella in poultry flocks	43
D-JRP26-WP2.4	Recommendations for improving Salmonella surveillance in poultry flocks	48
D-JRP26-WP2.3	Recommendations for improving Salmonella controls in poultry flocks	48
D-JRP26-WP3.3	Report on the evaluation of the surveillance systems' attributes	48
D-JRP26-WP3.4	Extended the report on epidemiological characteristics with results from the rarefaction analysis the refined source attribution models, but also with data on food consumption patterns	45
D-JRP26-WP3.5	Report on human S. enteritidis exposure in different countries and time periods	42
D-JRP26-WP5.1	Final assessment framework of the MCDA	48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-JRP26-10	Annual meeting organised	40

M-JRP26-11	Outline of the assessment framework (transmission chain)	42
M-JRP26-12	Meeting on aligning epidemiological and QMRA approach	45
M-JRP26-13	List of candidate strains for phenotype testing	37
M-JRP26-14	Identification of the experts to participate in the weighting exercise of the MCDA	42
M-JRP26-15	Data finalized for manuscript on Population of Salmonella collection	48

2.4.2.1.24 JRP24-R2-FBZSH9-BeONE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)			FBZ-SH 9: Better tools for detection and investigation of foodborne outbreaks, including antimicrobial resistant pathogens, as well as economic assessments of potentially increased cluster detection through whole genome sequencing							
Research Project Title			Building integrative tools for OneHealth Surveillance							
Research Project Acronym			BeONE							
Leading Organisation			P13-SSI			Deputy Leading Organisation		P30-RIVM		
Project Leader			Kristoffer Kiil			Deputy Project leader		Claudia Coipan		
Project Start month			M25			Project End month		M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM							12	0,6	0,6	1,5
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	27								1,4	1
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM						2		10,67		0,96
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM	1,25	6		23,01						
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Establish method comparability M48 ● Integrated model for outbreak detection/delineation using genomic and epidemiological data M46 ● Guideline for cluster investigation using integrated data M48 ● Ontology based metadata standardization system M48 ● Ad-hoc data sharing system M48 ● Dashboard M48 ● Dashboard collaboration and analysis tool M48 										
Description of work										
WP1: Typing comparability and nomenclature										

WP start month: 25
WP end month: 48
WP Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA(36)
Deputy WP Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)
WP participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)
WP1 takes place over the first and second year of the project
Description of the WP: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP1-T3 Clustering congruence and thresholds

Task start month: 25
Task end month: 48
Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA (36)
Deputy Task Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)
Task Participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)
T1.3 takes place over the first year and the second year of the project.
Description of the task: continued from previous year

WP2: Joining molecular and epidemiological methods

WP start month: 25
WP end month: 48
WP Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)
Deputy WP Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA (36)
WP participants: RIVM (30), INSA (36), SSI (13), PHE (22), NVI (33), RKI (11), APHA (21), PIWET (34)
WP2 takes place over the first and the second year of the project.
Description of the WP: continued from previous year

Task BeONE-WP2-T2: Integrating genomics with epidemiology

Task start month 33
Task end month 46
Task Leader : Claudia Coipan, RIVM(30)
Deputy Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA (36)
Task Participants: RIVM(30), INSA(36), SSI(13), PHE(22), NVI(33), PIWET(34), APHA (21)
T2.2 takes place over the first and second year of the project.
Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task BeONE-WP2-T3: Definition of guidelines for cluster investigation

Task start month 41
Task end month 48
Task Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)
Deputy Task Leader : Vítor Borges, INSA (36)
Task Participants : RIVM(30), INSA(36)
T2.3 takes place over the second year of the project.
Description of the task:
Based on the results of WP1 and T2.2, a document will be drafted containing guidelines for implementation of the algorithm for outbreak detection and a final version of it will be prepared following feedback from the partners. A first version of procedural stepwise approach for improved cluster investigation for a target foodborne bacterium will be drafted by month 42, based on epidemiologic and genomic data. Following the feedback from the partners in WP5 that will test the

detection outbreak clustering algorithm making use of the draft guidelines, the guidelines will be refined to address potential shortcomings and unpredicted situations.

WP3: Storage, management, and sharing for meta- and molecular data

WP start month: 25

WP end month: 54

WP Leader: Carlus Deneke, BfR (09)

Deputy WP Leader: Kim Ng, SSI (13)

WP participants: SSI (13), NVI (33), IZSAM (28), FLI (10), RKI (11), BfR (09), DTU (12)

WP3 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Description of the WP: continued from previous year

Task: BeOne-WP3-T2: Metadata acquisition and standardisation

Task start month 25

Task end month 48

Task Leader: Simon Tausch, BfR (09)

Deputy Task Leader: Jörg Linde, FLI (10)

Task Participants: NVI (33), FLI (10)

T3.2 takes place over the first and second year of the project.

Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task: BeOne-WP3-T3: Database design and implementation

Task start month 25

Task end month 54

Task Leader: Kim Ng, SSI (13)

Deputy Task Leader: Simon Tausch, BfR (09)

Task Participants: SSI (13), BfR (09), IZSAM (28), NVI (33), DTU (12)

T3.3 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task: BeOne-WP3-T4: National data sharing pilot

Task start month 48

Task end month 54

Task Leader: Carlus Deneke, BfR (09)

Deputy Task Leader: Jörg Linde, FLI (10)

Task Participants: FLI (10), BfR (09), RKI (11)

T3.4 takes place over the second and the third year of the project.

Description of the task:

Building on the database system developed in WP3, a pilot on a national level will be tested spanning institutes with human, food and animal data. This task will make use of data from WP1-T2. Metadata and molecular data will be exchanged using the developed ontologies. Therefore, the implemented database structure will first be tested on institutional level. Next, using the database structure to share national data will be tested.

WP 4: Development of a user-oriented interface for analysis and sharing of epi and molecular data

WP start month: 25

WP end month: 54

WP Leader: Stefano Cardinale, SSI (13)

Deputy WP Leader: Rolf Sommer Kaas, DTU (12)

WP participants: BfR (09), SSI (13), DTU (12)
WP4 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.
Description of the WP: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP4-T1 Dashboard

Task start month: 25
Task end month: 42
Task Leader: Stefano Cardinale, SSI (13)
Deputy Task Leader: Simon Tausch, BfR (09)
Task Participants: BfR (09), SSI (13), DTU (12), RKI (11)
T4.1 takes place over the first and second year of the project.
Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP4-T3 Cluster analysis and collaboration tool

Task start month: 37
Task end month: 48
Task Leader: Stefano Cardinale, SSI (13)
Deputy Task Leader: Carlus Deneke, BfR (09)
Task Participants: BfR (09), SSI (13), DTU (13)
T4.3 takes place over the second year of the project.

Description of the task:
Building upon T4.1, implement a system for saving, naming, analysing and commenting on selected clusters of samples.

Task: BeONE-WP4-T4 Data sharing front end

Task start month: 29
Task end month: 54
Task Leader: Stefano Cardinale, SSI (13)
Deputy Task Leader: Simon Tausch, BfR (09)
Task Participants: BfR (09), SSI (13), DTU (12)
T4.4 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.
Description of the task: continued from previous year

WP5: Dissemination, Testing, Evaluation and Sustainability

WP start month: 25
WP end month: 54
WP Leader: Stefano Cardinale, SSI (13)
Deputy WP Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)
WP participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)
WP5 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.
Description of the WP: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP5-T1 Dissemination

Task start month: 25
Task end month: 54
Task Leader: Stefano Cardinale, SSI (13)
Deputy Task Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)

Task Participants: SSI (13), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)

T5.1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP5-T2 Continuous Testing and Feedback

Task start month: 25

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)

Deputy Task Leader: Stefano Cardinale, SSI (13)

Task Participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)

T5.2 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP5-T3 Final evaluation

Task start month: 48

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: Eva Litrup, SSI (13)

Deputy Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA (36)

Task Participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)

T5.3 takes place over the second and third year of the project.

Description of the task:

As a final evaluation of the dashboard it is tested with a simulated international outbreak. Here, all partners will participate and results will be summarized in a final report.

Task: BeONE-WP5-T4 Sustainability

Task start month: 25

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: Claudia Coipan, RIVM (30)

Deputy Task Leader: Eva Litrup, SSI (13)

Task Participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)

T5.4 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Description of the task: continued from previous year

WP6: Management

WP start month: 25

WP end month: 54

WP Leader: Kristoffer, Kiil, SSI (13)

Deputy WP Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA (36)

WP participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)

WP6 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.

Description of the WP: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP6-T1 Management

Task start month: 25

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: Kristoffer Kiil, SSI (13)
Deputy Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA (36)
Task Participants: SSI (13), INSA (36), RIVM (30), BfR (09), IZSAM (28), DTU (12), FLI (10), NVI (33)
T6.1 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.
Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP6-T2 Communication

Task start month: 25
Task end month: 54
Task Leader: Kristoffer Kiil, SSI (13)
Deputy Task Leader: Vítor Borges, INSA (36)
Task Participants: SSI (13), RKI (11), IZSAM (28), RIVM (30), Piwet (34), FLI (10), APHA (21), DTU (12), FHI (32), PHE (22), NVI (33), BfR (09), INSA (36)
T6.2 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.
Description of the task: continued from previous year

Task: BeONE-WP6-T3 Data Management

Task start month: 25
Task end month: 54
Task Leader: Kristoffer Kiil, SSI (13)
Deputy Task Leader: Carlus Deneke, BfR (09)
Task Participants: SSI (13), BfR (09)
T6.3 takes place over the first, the second and the third year of the project.
Description of the task: continued from previous year

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-BeOne.2.2	Final Outbreak detection algorithm	46
D-BeONE.1.3	Report with clustering congruence results	48
D-BeONE.2.3	Final Guidelines	48
D-BeONE.2.4	Draft manuscript on outbreak detection algorithm and guidelines	48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-BeONE.5.4	Overall evaluation at 2nd annual meeting (workshop)	40
M-BeONE.6.1	2nd annual meeting	40
M-BeONE.2.2	Outbreak detection algorithm -provisional version	42
M-BeONE.2.3	Guideline proposal	42
M-BeONE.3.7	Data porting from an existing pipeline	42
M-BeONE.4.6	Cluster analysis and collaboration tool ready for testing	42
M-BeONE.1.5	Clustering congruence analysis completed	48
M-BeONE.3.8	Application of the selected ontology system(s)	48
M-BeONE.3.9	Data porting from at least one further pipeline	48
M-BeONE.3.10	Expansion of the API for export functionality	48
M-BeONE.4.7	Import/Export front end for reference databases implemented	48
M-BeONE.4.8	Dashboard in workable condition for Final Evaluation workshop	48
M-BeONE.5.2	Yearly sustainability document	48

2.4.2.1.25 JIP01-R1-IA1.1-ORION

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)			IA 1.1: Interpretation of surveillance data - Standardised data formats and ontologies, common tools and procedures for data analyses, including interpretation of sequence data							
Integrative Project Title			One health surveillance Initiative on harmOnization of data collection and interpretation							
Integrative Project Acronym			ORION							
Leading Organisation			P9-BfR			Deputy Leading Organisation		P41-SVA		
Project Leader			Matthias Filter			Deputy Project leader		Fernanda Dórea		
Project Start month			M1			Project End month		M42		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M			5,5				30	16,85		9
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M	5								3,65	2,90
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAMI	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
P.M								5,72	0,81	10
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M	8,80							2	10,10	
Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Finalize OH pilot studies ● Revise “OHS CRAC”, including lessons learned from the OH pilots ● Revise “OH Knowledge Base – Epi”, including lessons learned from the OH pilots ● Revise “OH Knowledge Base –NGS”, including lessons learned from the OH pilots ● Revise “OH Knowledge Base – Integration”, including lessons learned from the OH pilots ● Revise “OH Harmonisation Infrastructure Hub”, including lessons learned from the OH pilots ● Revise “Sustainability Roadmap” ● Update “OHS Codex” populated with resources from WP1, WP2 and WP3 and lessons learned from pilots 										

- **Perform dissemination and training activities**

Description of work:

WP: **WP1 - "OH Surveillance Codex"**

WP1 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: 9-BfR

Deputy WP Leader: 38-SVA

WP participants: 3 -CODA-CERVA/WIV-ISP, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 21-PHE, 32-NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM, 38-SVA

Description of the WP:

This WP aims at the development of an integrated approach for harmonized description and categorisation of surveillance data covering all surveillance phases. The primary focus will be on the development of the first "OH Surveillance Codex", a document with harmonized descriptive guidelines. WP1 will also define requirements for data standards and software tools that should be developed to facilitate broad and easy adoption of the framework. Some of these new resources will be implemented by WP3. The OH pilot carried out by WP1 has the goal of demonstrating that the "OH Surveillance Codex" guidelines are practically applicable and generate the expected added value. It will also test and evaluate the supporting standards and tools developed by WP3. Based on the lessons learned from the OH pilot study this WP will make necessary adjustments to the "OH Surveillance Codex" document and provide feedback to the tool developers in WP3. Throughout the duration of the project WP1 will use workshops organized by WP4 to train other EJP projects and stakeholders and disseminate the "OH Surveillance Codex" and the underlying conceptual framework. WP1 will further support the development of the "Sustainability Roadmap" (Task 4.3) to secure future development and adoption of the "OH Surveillance Codex" by EJP partners and European veterinary and public health agencies.

Task T-1.3: **One Health pilot**

Task 1.3 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M7

Task end month: M39

Task Leader: 38-SVA

Deputy Task Leader: 9-BfR

Task Participants: 3 -CODA-CERVA/WIV-ISP, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 21-PHE, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM, 38-SVA

Description of the task:

The OH pilot aims at illustrating the practical applicability of the "OH Surveillance Codex" when applied to real world surveillance data.

Subtask3 (M19 – M39): Execution of the OH pilot - applying the "OH Surveillance Codex" guide.

Task T-1.4: **Evaluation and Recommendations**

Task 1.4 takes place over the third and fourth annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M31

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: 9-BfR

Deputy Task Leader: 38-SVA

Task Participants: 3 -CODA-CERVA/WIV-ISP, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 21-PHE, 32-NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM, 38-SVA

Description of the task:

The aim of this task is the generation of lessons-learned from the OH pilot project. Specifically, it will analyse:

1. where the proposed "OH Surveillance Codex" has to be improved or adapted
2. what improvements and recommendations should be given regarding software provided by WP3

3. which implications this OH pilot has for the overall “ORION OH surveillance data harmonization framework”.

WP4 will host a joint ORION Evaluation workshop in M39, where the results from all ORION OH pilots will be jointly discussed, analysed and critically evaluated. In addition, this task will generate presentations, documents and training material that can be integrated into the “OHS Knowledge Hub” (operated by WP4).

WP: **WP2-Epi**

WP2-Epi takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M42

WP Leader: 10-FLI

Deputy WP Leader: 9-BfR

WP participants: All ORION partner

Description of the WP:

Within this work package we will focus on general surveillance data. In the first task we will carry out a requirement analysis to specify the state of the art of surveillance systems. We will then create an inventory of existing components of surveillance systems and identify gaps. Based upon the results, we will contribute to the development of a “OH Surveillance Codex” (WP1) and an application tool for surveillance systems. These tools will be tested in OH pilot studies and the result will be presented to the OH surveillance community.

Based on a literature review and a questionnaire survey, we create inventories on both data sources and data analysis; The inventory generated in this WP2 (OH Knowledge Base Epi) also covers current best practice guidelines and recommendations on using available resources. We will identify gaps and missing resources for reaching the ORION OH integration and harmonization objective. Appropriate diseases to be included in the OH Knowledge Base Epi might be Salmonella, Toxoplasma, Listeria, Campylobacter, VTEC/EHEC, Cryptosporidium, as well as antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

In a joint ORION prioritization workshop (M13) an “OH surveillance resource development plan” will be defined. This plan will detail and synchronizes the work carried out in all WP2s during task 2. New or improved resources will be integrated into the OH Knowledge Base Epi. In the second task, data from EJP partners of selected diseases or AMR will be collected, collated and prepared in order to use them for the OH pilot studies. In the third task WP2 -Epi will carry out OH pilot studies to prove whether (i) the OH surveillance framework previously developed by WP1 is suitable for the available data and (ii) if the data meet the requirements of the framework. The results of the pilot studies will be used to identify gaps in data availability and to improve the framework. Where appropriate these OH pilots will support the evaluation of resources developed by other WPs, e.g. WP1 and WP3.

WP2-Epi will integrate generated resources into OH Knowledge Base Epi which then becomes part of the “OHS Knowledge Hub” operated by WP4. Throughout the duration of the project WP2-Epi will use workshops organized by WP4 to train other EJP projects and stakeholders and disseminate their knowledge.

Task T-2Epi.3: **Epi - OH pilot studies**

Task 2.3 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M7

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: 9-BfR

Deputy Task Leader: 10-FLI

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 20-APHA, 21-PHE, 30-WBVR/CVI, 31-RIVM, 32-NIPH, 33-NVI, 38-SVA,

Description of the task:

The OH pilots will validate and exemplify the improved knowledge database generated in this WP. Topics for OH pilots will be selected along the overarching OH surveillance harmonization objective considering

recommendations from EJP partners and other EJP sub-projects. Each of the OH pilots will be performed in a timely synchronized fashion:

Phase 1 (M7 - M12): Selection of the OH pilot study topic

Phase2 (M13 – M18): Planning and performing work necessary to prepare the execution of the OH pilot. This includes: specification of targets, definition of performance indicators, identification and collection of required data and software tools etc.

Phase3 (M19 – M42): Execution of the OH pilot - applying resources from “OH Knowledge Base Epi”

Sub-Task sT-2Epi.3.1 (M7-42) One Health Pilot 1: Toxoplasma gondii

In this pilot study, we will analyse currently available data on T. gondii surveillance from reports of the different sectors. This will be followed by a risk factor analysis for the infection with T. gondii in the relevant livestock species. With this pilot study, we will be able to test the inventory and show its practical applications. Additionally, we will be able to make a gap analysis and show opportunities and challenges for stakeholders.

Sub-Task sT-2Epi.3.2 (M7-42) One Health Pilot 2: Salmonella

A pilot study will be carried out by PHE and APHA on Salmonella surveillance using the OH surveillance framework. Within the study both partners will harmonise data transfer including data format, frequency, resolution and time. The partners will provide data to WP1 to be able to share data on early detection systems (EDS), methodology and application to salmonella datasets within the OH surveillance framework.

Sub-Task sT-2Epi.3.3 (M7-42) One Health Pilot 3: Hepatitis E

Within this subtask 30-WBVR/CVI and 31-RIVM will carry out a common pilot study. Data about hepatitis E surveillance done in different institutes belonging to different sectors are gathered and put in a country map. The country map consists of surveillance components or monitoring projects per sector and institute and data sharing among these sectors for a disease or pathogen. To make the country map broadly useable for others, an instruction of how to complete the map will be made. Following the results on our country map, the goal is to set up and enhance inter-sectoral (all identified institutes in the country map) collaboration for hepatitis E.

Sub-Task sT-2Epi.3.3 (M7-42) One Health Pilot 4 AMR (carried out by Sciensano, Belgium) (M7-M30):

The aim of this pilot project is to enlighten the network of collaboration between the authorities and the scientists in term of surveillance of antibioresistance in Belgium, in analysing the participation of scientists in national meetings where topics related to OH AMR surveillance or monitoring are discussed (focus : operations and communication).

Sub-Task sT-2Epi.3.3 (M7-42) One Health Pilot 5: Application of Rasch model on data collected in questionnaires

Based on the questionnaires describing the properties of surveillance projects a set of quality scores are planned to be calculated by the use of a Rasch model . By this application of a method developed and validated in JIP1-WP2-T2-ST2 - Data analysis and validation on data collected in JIP1-WP2-T2-ST1 - Data collection and integration we optimize the information gain and further examine the practical applicability of the method collection. With the results we provide a base for a ranking of surveillance systems and for the discussion of the properties of recent surveillance projects under the framework of one-health.

Task T-2Epi.4:

Evaluation and Recommendations Epi

Task 2Epi.4 takes place over the third and fourth annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M25
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 30-WBVR/CVI
Deputy Task Leader: 38-SVA AND 13-SSI
Task Participants: all ORION partners

Description of the task:

This task aims at the generation of lessons-learned from the OH pilot project. Specifically, it will be analysed

- 1. where the OH Knowledge Base - Epi has to be improved or adapted*
- 2. what improvements and recommendations can be given on the software provided by WP3*
- 3. which implications this OH pilot has to the overall "ORION OH surveillance harmonization framework".*

In order to facilitate this WP4 will host a joint ORION Evaluation workshop in M39. There the results from all ORION OH pilots will be jointly discussed, analysed and critically evaluated. In addition this task will generate presentations, documents and training material that can be integrated into the "OHS Knowledge Hub" (operated by WP4).

WP:

WP2 – NGS

WP2-NGS takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP

WP start month: M1
WP end month: M42
WP Leader: 33-NVI
Deputy WP Leader: 32- FHI/NIPH
WP participants: 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 21-PHE, 30-WBVR/CVI, 31-RIVM, 32- FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM/PHA

Description of the WP:

There are several methods available today for identifying bacterial species and strains. Sequencing based strategies are rapidly gaining popularity, but that is not the only novel technique available (examples are NMR and MALDI-TOF). However, these methods may not be appropriate or applicable to a surveillance setting. Within this work package we will first do a review of existing and novel methods and systems for bacterial identification to find which methods/systems that are applicable for surveillance purposes. Based on the result we will set up an analysis pipeline, which may be within an existing system, which will be tested out in One Health pilots. The results will then be reviewed, and recommendations regarding analysis methods will be made. The work within this WP will primarily focus on NGS based methods, to better align with the work being done in other EJP projects.

Specifically, the aim of this' WP is the creation of an "OH Knowledge base NGS" - a cross-domain inventory of currently available data/methods/algorithms/tools/systems linked to existing and novel NextGen bacterial identification (primarily NGS) analysis methods and provide best practice solutions that support integrated OH surveillance data generation, data analysis, modelling and decision support. To accomplish that WP2-NGS will as described in previous WPs conduct expert interviews and SWOT analysis to identify gaps and missing resources.

The generated OH Knowledge Base NGS will for several relevant zoonotic agents contain meta-information on:

- 1. existing and novel analysis data sources*
- 2. methods and algorithms for data management and integration*
- 3. methods and approaches for data analysis*

The analysis will also consider current experiences on practical issues such as data storage capacity, data exchange capacity, bioinformatics expertise, data exchange platforms, harmonised terminology etc.

WP2-NGS will participate in a joint ORION prioritization workshop (M13) as described in earlier WPs. WP2-NGS will also carry out OH pilots in a similar fashion as described in WP2-Epi, and will based on the results make

necessary adjustments to the “OH Knowledge base NGS” and update the “OH surveillance resource development plan”.

Task T-2Ngs.3: NGS OH pilot studies

Task 2Ngs.3 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M7
Task end month: M39
Task Leader: 33-NVI
Deputy Task Leader: 32- FHI/NIPH
Task Participants: 31-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI

Description of the task:

Based on the results of 2Ngs.2.3 we will design an NGS based One Health pilot study. Two pathogens will be chosen for the pilot, in order to distinguish between pathogen specific issues and methodological issues. The OH pilot will be performed in the same fashion as previously described for WP-EPI timely synchronized with other ORION OH studies:

- Phase1 (M7 - M12): Selection of the OH pilot study topic
- Phase2 (M13 – M18): Planning and performing work necessary to prepare the execution of the OH pilot. This includes: specification of targets, definition of performance indicators, identification and making available required data sources and software tools etc.
- Phase3 (M19 – M36): Execution of the OH pilot - applying resources from “OH Knowledge Base – NGS”

Task T-2Ngs.4: Evaluation and Recommendations NGS

Task 2Ngs.4 takes place over the third and fourth annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M25
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 31-RIVM
Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI, 33-NVI, 32- FHI/NIPH
Task Participants: 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 21-PHE, 30-WBVR/CVI, 31-RIVM, 32- FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM/PHA

Description of the task:

This task aims at the generation of lessons-learned from the OH pilot project. The task will be performed as previously described for WP-Epi, but with a focus on the areas examined in this WP. Specifically, it will be analysed

1. where the OH Knowledge Base - NGS has to be improved or adapted
 2. what improvements and recommendations can be given on the software provided by WP3
 3. which implications this OH pilot has to the overall “ORION OH surveillance harmonization framework”.
- In order to facilitate this WP4 will host a joint ORION Evaluation workshop in M39. There the results from all ORION OH pilots will be jointly discussed, analysed and critically evaluated. In addition this task will generate presentations, documents and training material that can be integrated into the “OHS Knowledge Hub” (operated by WP4).

WP: WP2 – Integration

WP2-Integration takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP
WP start month: M1
WP end month: M42
WP Leader: 12-DTU
Deputy WP Leader: 13-SSI
WP participants: 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM/PHA, 38-SVA

Description of the WP:

- This WP2 has two main aims:
- 1) to ensure integration of the knowledge and methods generated by the two subWP2s – Epi / NGS to avoid duplications and maximise benefits of the project;
 - 2) a pilot study to demonstrate integration of all disciplines.

Specifically, during the first year we will create an inventory on WP2-Integration on current integrated OH surveillance approaches in use in the EU. The inventory generated in this WP2 (OH Knowledge Base Integration) also covers current best practice guidelines and recommendations. To accomplish this WP2 will carry out jointly with the other ORION WPs expert interviews.

In a joint ORION prioritization workshop (M13) a “OH surveillance resource development plan” will be defined. This plan details and synchronizes the improvement work carried out in all WP2s. New or improved resources developed by this WP2 will be integrated into the OH Knowledge Base Integration.

In the third task this WP2 will carry out a pilot study that enhances OH surveillance on a specific topic. The pilot will not only integrate human, veterinary and food surveillance data, but also integrate the traditional disciplines with others. A specific objective of this OH pilot study is to ensure a robust approach to OH surveillance without losing the value of the historic data. The pilot study will try to use relevant outputs from all ORION WPs. WP2-Integration will further support the development of the “Sustainability Roadmap” (Task 4.3) in order to secure continued implementation and adoption of the “OH surveillance resource development plan” created by WP2 (M13).

Task T-2Int.3: Integration OH pilot studies

Task 2Int.3 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

Task start month: M7
Task end month: M39
Task Leader: 12-DTU
Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI
Task Participants: 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 33-NVI

Description of the task:

A multi-sector topic will be chosen, such as AMR, Listeria or VTEC/EHEC. This pilot will not only integrate human, veterinary and food surveillance, but also integrate the disciplines in WP2 – epidemiology and microbiology, to ensure robust OH surveillance without losing the value of the historic data.

Phase1 (M7 - M12): Selection of the OH pilot study topic
Phase2 (M13 – M18): Planning and performing work necessary to prepare the execution of the OH pilot. This includes: specification of targets, definition of performance indicators, identification and making available required data sources and software tools etc.
Phase3 (M19 – M30): Execution of the OH pilot - applying the resources from “OH Knowledge Base Integration”

Task T-2Int.4: Evaluation and Recommendations - Integration

Task 2Int.4 takes place over the third and fourth annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M25
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 12-DTU
Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI
Task Participants: 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI, 37-FOHM/PHA, 38-SVA

Description of the task:

This task aims at the generation of lessons-learned from the OH pilot project. Specifically, it will be analysed

1. where the “OH Knowledge Base Integration” has to be improved or adapted
2. which implications this OH pilot has to the overall “ORION OH surveillance harmonization framework”.

In order to facilitate this WP4 will host a joint ORION Evaluation workshop in M39. There the results from all ORION OH pilots will be jointly discussed, analysed and critically evaluated. In addition this task will generate presentations, documents and training material that can be integrated into the “OHS Knowledge Hub” (operated by WP4).

WP: WP3 - OH Surveillance Harmonisation Infrastructure

WP3 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP
WP start month: M1
WP end month: M42
WP Leader: 38-SVA

Deputy WP Leader: 37-FOHM/PHA
WP participants: 9-BfR; 10-FLI, 12-DTU; 13-SSI; 20-APHA; 21-PHE; 31-RIVM; 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI; 37-FOHM/PHA; 38-SVA

Description of the WP:

WP3 will focus on identifying infrastructural resources which can support the harmonization and integration of existing methods to collect and analyse surveillance data. These infrastructural resources include - among others - data standards, software libraries, ontologies, terminology mappings, semantic networks, software tools. The specific development tasks to be carried out by WP3 will be identified by requirements expressed from WP1 (in relation to the "OH Surveillance Codex"), WP2 (supporting their developments) and through interviews of domain experts from other EJP partners and projects. Through the close interaction with WP1 and WP2 in the requirement analysis phase, WP3 will identify existing resources along the full surveillance data lifecycle. WP3 will inventory and where possible / required improve these tools and resources. The decision on the specific WP3 developments to be carried out in task 3.2 will be taken together with WP1 and WP2 during the joint ORION prioritization workshop (M13). In contrast to the other ORION WPs, this WP will focus on specifications for necessary data standards along the full surveillance data lifecycle – from annotation of analytical data, documentation of analytical methods, applied data processing and modelling steps to visualization of results. These proposed data standards will exploit the "One-Health Surveillance Ontology" also generated by this WP.

One or more pilots will allow for testing how the improved infrastructural resources, and in particular the proposed data standards, support the goal of surveillance data harmonisation. Based on the lessons-learned from these OH pilot studies WP3 will make necessary adjustments to their developed resources and update the inventory of OH surveillance infrastructural resources that then becomes part of the "OHS Knowledge Hub" operated by WP4. Throughout the duration of the project WP3 will use workshops organized by WP4 to train other EJP projects and stakeholders and disseminate its knowledge. WP3 will further support the development of the "Sustainability Roadmap" (Task 4.3) in order to secure continued development of OH surveillance infrastructural resources.

Task T-3.4: Evaluation and Recommendations

Task 3.4 takes place over the third and fourth annual period of the EJP.

Task start month: M31
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 38-SVA
Deputy Task Leader: 37-FOHM/PHA
Task Participants: 9-BfR; 10-FLI, 12-DTU; 13-SSI; 20-APHA; 21-PHE; 31-RIVM; 32-FHI/NIPH, 33-NVI; 37-FOHM/PHA; 38-SVA

Description of the task:

This task aims at the generation of lessons-learned from the OH pilot project. Specifically, it will be analysed

1. where the improved infrastructural resources have to be further improved or adapted
2. which implications this OH pilot has to the overall "ORION OH surveillance data harmonization framework".

In other words, the lessons learned and resources generated with the pilot will be generalized into reusable frameworks that can be borrowed by other countries. The pilot will be evaluated, and the results made reusable and disseminated within this task. This task will also contribute to the training tasks planned in WP4.

WP: WP4-Coordination, Communication, Training and Sustainability

WP4 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP

WP start month: M1
WP end month: M42
WP Leader: 9-BfR
Deputy WP Leader: 38-SVA
WP participants: all ORION partners

Description of the WP:

This WP integrates all horizontal project activities including the coordination of internal and external communication, the set-up of shared technical resources (Wiki's, web-based OHS Knowledge Hub, software code repositories etc.), and the development of a "Sustainability Roadmap" paving the way to broad adoption of project results in future European surveillance practice. This WP will also organize all cross-WP workshops (M4, M13, M39) and promote wider group assessment / validation of findings at critical points in the project. The training and dissemination activities organized by this WP will promote knowledge exchange between project partners as well as other EJP partners and projects. Special focus will be given to the synchronization with the other(s) EJP Integrative action project(s), funded under IA-2. All external communication and knowledge transfer activities will be integrated into the overarching activities carried out by EJP WP5 "Science to Policy Translation". This includes promotion of knowledge transfer to responsible entities (e.g. EU reference laboratories, EFSA, ECDC) and international statutory bodies.

Task T-4.1: Internal project coordination

Task 4.1 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

*Task start month: M1
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 9-BfR
Deputy Task Leader: 38-SVA
Task Participants: all ORION partners*

Description of the task:

This task takes responsibility for and effective project coordination. This will be facilitated by hosting monthly full consortia conference calls / online meetings, one full consortia project meeting and dedicated cross-WP workshops in month 4, 13, and 39 to promote synchronized decision making and development within the ORION project. This task also disseminates duties to corresponding partners and keeps track of timely provisioning of partner's deliverables. Further it will manage the creation of yearly project reports.

Task T-4.2: External project integration (synchronized with EJP WPs)

Task 4.2 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

*Task start month: M1
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 38-SVA
Deputy Task Leader: 9-BfR
Task Participants: all ORION partners*

Description of the task:

This task will deal with the coordination of collaboration with other EJP initiatives, and also support other projects. We will support other funded EJP initiatives in two main ways: by including these projects in the phase of requirement analysis, for all WPs, so that they have a chance to contribute their views on current gaps and opportunities for OH integration; and by providing training (see specific training tasks below). The requirement analysis is also a point of close collaboration in the work to be carried out. We foresee that many projects may plan to conduct tasks similar to ORION's requirement analysis, and partner interviews. We suggest that integration with other projects will be needed to maximize resources, and avoid reducing the quality of survey responses due to an excessive number of questionnaires being mailed to EJP partners. Further, the results of this project should be closely tied to the Integrative Area 2, so that the accomplishments in integration of data collection and analysis can be in line with the issues of knowledge integration and decision making. In Year 4, in particular, this task will coordinate the passing of information generated in ORION to the second round of OHEJP integrative projects.

Task T-4.3: Sustainability roadmap

Task 4.3 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

*Task start month: M7
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 9-BfR
Deputy Task Leader: 38-SVA
Task Participants: all ORION partners*

Description of the task:

Sustainability issues will arise throughout the project, in all WPs, and in all tasks. For this reason, it has been assigned to the coordination to follow and document raised issues of sustainability, whether legal or technical. Budget has been planned for legal and technical consultation, where needed, in order to inform potential solutions to sustainability issues, and trace a road map of sustainability for the integration of data and methods in a OH surveillance context. The final "Sustainability Roadmap" document will be created based on the results of the joint ORION Evaluation workshop hold in M39. This document will give recommendations on how the "ORION OH surveillance data harmonization framework" with all its components should be consolidated by EJP partners and European veterinary and public health agencies in the future.

Task T-4.4: Training and Dissemination

Task 4.4 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual periods of the EJP.

*Task start month: M1
Task end month: M42
Task Leader: 38-SVA
Deputy Task Leader: 9-BfR
Task Participants: all ORION partners*

Description of the task:

This task will be concerned with planning and conducting, throughout the project, training that aims at sharing the knowledge already available within the consortium among all partners, training partners in the use of new tools produced/adopted, and disseminating results and training external partners in the adoption of tools and guidelines published by ORION. All partners have assigned a minimum of 2PM to training, so that they can take part in the activities listed below – receiving training, training others, or helping with dissemination activities.

Sub-Task sT-4.4.2 (M7 – M42): Knowledge integration (web portal, Wiki, curricula, tutorials, videos, sample data)

*Sub-Task Leader: 9-BfR
Sub-Task Participants: all ORION partners*

Description of the task:

All WPs have tangible outcomes that are meant to benefit the surveillance community - e.g. the OH Surveillance Codex from WP1, the OH surveillance data inventories with validated tools in WP2, the ontology generated in WP3. This task will oversee the production of dissemination means, while training will be provided in the following Sub-Task. Workshops and webinars to the overall public are planned for the entire project, and in particular during the last 12 months. Permanent dissemination means – such as videos and a wiki – will guarantee access to the project outcomes after the conclusion of the project. Particular emphasis is given to the "OHS Codex", which will be a repository of all the tools and guidelines produced in the project.

Sub-Task sT-4.4.3 (M7 - M42): Training and support for other EJP projects & partners

*Sub-Task Leader: 38-SVA
Sub-Task Participants: all ORION partners*

Description of the task:

Training on all the guidelines, framework, and tools produced as part of ORION will be provided to other interested EJP partners. A minimum of two dedicated training workshops for external OHEJP project members are planned for the last project year (last 12 months). When training can be carried online, we will make recordings permanently available in the OHS knowledge Hub (see task above).

2.4.2.1.26 JIP02-R1-IA1.2-COHESIVE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		IA 1.2: Common reporting and signalling procedures, joint platform for sharing surveillance data and their interpretation, incl. risk assessments								
Integrative Project Title		One Health Structure In Europe								
Integrative Project Acronym		COHESIVE								
Leading Organisation		P30-RIVM			Deputy Leading Organisation			P31-WbvR		
Project Leader		Kitty Maassen			Deputy Project leader			Wim van der Poel		
Project Start month		M1			Project End month			M42		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
P.M	1	2,53	5,5			2,5	15	1,1		0
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
P.M									1,6	0
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbvR	FHI
P.M						3,25	8,5	18,37	2,63	10
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAY	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
P.M	3,10						2	0	4,6	
Objectives:										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stimulating sustainable One Health approaches at the national level within EU countries, focussing on strengthening human-veterinary collaboration with respect to early signalling and assessing zoonotic threats. Roadmap towards an EU zoonoses risk-assessment or risk-analysis structure Design and test a common platform for the collection and analysis of surveillance and outbreak data on foodborne zoonoses. Capacity building within and between EU countries at several levels within the area of zoonotic diseases 										

Description of work

WP1 Coordination, communication and sustainability

WP start month: 1 WP end month: 42

WP Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy WP Leader: Wim van der Poel, WBVR

WP participants: Bfr, APHA, IZS AM, WBVR, RIVM, SVA: All actively involved in this WP. All other project partners will have a reactive role in this WP, such as attending annual meetings.

Description of the WP: WP1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. The objective of this WP is to coordinate the activities of the partners as described in the various WPs and ensure the smooth running of the project. This also includes overseeing the links between the WPs and assist with linking to other projects within the EJP and outside. The project is aiming at sustainable products (risk-analysis structures, collaborations, data platform). The steering group will stimulate partners and associate partners to reach for those goals. Within this WP also internal and external communication is coordinated.

Task: T-1.1 Coordination

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 42

Task Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: Wim van der Poel, WBVR

Task Participants: WP (deputy)leaders: Bfr, APHA, IZS AM, WBVR, RIVM,SVA

Description of the task: Task 1.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. The RIVM is project coordinator and responsible for the project management and leading the steering group. WBVR will be deputy task-leader to ensure a good follow-up and management of the task. WBVR will be also the first sparring partner of the coordinator to discuss upcoming problems with. A steering group is formed consisting of the WP-leaders and deputy WP-leaders. To ensure efficient progress within the WPs, regular communications moments are organized. Most of the times this is together with the task leaders. Normally, there will have at least one physical meeting per year, most likely coupled to the annual meeting, but due to COVID-19 this might not be possible in Y4. The steering group will ensure the completion of deliverables in time and reaching the milestones (in time). Complete and timely reporting to the EJP management team is a joined responsibility of the steering group with final responsibility lying with the project coordinator. The project coordinator will liaise with the overarching EJP management. Important is also to oversee possibilities to connect activities between different WPs, look for opportunities to involve external organisations and link to other (EU) projects. The steering group can stimulate and facilitate to act upon such opportunities. Also contacts with EFSA, ECDC, WHO and FAO have been established and will be maintained in order to inform them on our progress. For EFSA we try to fulfill their needs and build upon already existing databases, models etc. Contact with ECDC is reduced to a minimum due to reallocation of the contact person. Three new partners were added to the consortium (INIIV, ANSES and VRI). PHE left the consortium due to leave of key personnel.

Task: T1.2 Communication/dissemination

Task start month: 1

Task end month: 42

Task Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: Wim van der Poel, WBVR

Task Participants: WP (deputy)leaders: Bfr, APHA, IZS AM, WBVR, RIVM, SVA

Description of the task Task 1.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. Within this task internal project communication is coordinated in close collaboration with task T-1.1. Due to COVID-19 the annual meeting of the 3rd year will be online. Depending on the situation and need an annual meeting with all partners will or will not take place in 2021. . In the meeting general project issues will be discussed and progression in the WPs is shared and discussed. In view of efficiency, the steering group meetings most likely will be coupled to the annual meetings. In addition, there is also the possibility to combine it with workshops or other meetings organized within other WPs.

At the end of the project a closing symposium will be organized. It is one way to disseminate the various products obtained in the project and transfer knowledge. This symposium is open to all EJP partners and preferably to all EU countries, also those not involved in the EJP consortium. Depending on the COVID-19 situation this will be a physical or online meeting.

A general EJP One Health website has been developed. This website does have the possibilities for private groups. Three groups are set up. One group for (secure) exchange of information between members of the steering group, one to inform all Cohesive members and one to inform all interested EJP members. Via several websites different products will be disseminated. Targeted dissemination of information will be also defined, to address specific stakeholders with project progress and main results/deliverables.

Concerning sustainability, basic activities such website maintenance, networking with partners will be planned to continue after the end of the project. An example is the website with guidelines as product of WP2.1, this website will be linked to the MVNA website after OHEJP ends. The main tools and procedures developed will be disseminated not only among the project partners but also to other national/international institutions/organizations potentially interested in the activities, favoring the further development of the tools and the extended networking. Contacts are made to the Tripartite WHO, FAO, OIE. They might link to some of our products on there websites.

WP2 Integrated risk-analysis at the national level

WP start month: M1

WP end month:M42

WP Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM

Deputy WP Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA

WP participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, ISZ LER, ISZ AM, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA, FOHM/PHA, INIAV.

Description of the WP: WP2 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. The objective of this WP is to provide common procedures and tools that can be used to improve the human-veterinary collaboration in the area of (emerging) zoonosis or even implement a sustainable integrated One Health structure at the national level. Examples of best practice methods will be used to design common procedures and tools, but also differences between countries and barriers for efficient collaboration will be taken into account as well.

Importantly, the project will facilitate in the first step of creating support for a One Health structure by organizing local workshops with national stakeholders. In addition, a systematic way to select tools to help assess zoonotic threats will be developed to be used within the One Health structures.

Task: T-2.1 Development of guidelines for national One Health structures

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M40

Task Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, ISZ LER, ISZ AM, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WbvR, RIVM, SVA, FOHM/PHA, INIAV

Description of the Task: Task 2.1 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. First, an inventory was made of current practice of One Health risk analysis (structures) at the national level. For this purpose, a workshop was organized accessible to all project partners, EJP partners and EU countries outside the consortium. This workshop was focused on current practice on human-veterinary collaboration, risk analysis and good practice, but will also reveal barriers to good practice, such as technical, political barriers, legal issues, logistics, difference in interests (economic versus health), difference in terminology and privacy. In this workshop also national goals and ambitions to improve the integration of human-veterinary risk-analysis were inventoried. As in the second year, the plan was to have several dedicated workshops in the third year to discuss and progress towards possible solutions for the most important barriers as identified within the first workshop and to further provide input for the guidelines. However, due to COVID-19 probably no physical workshops will be held in Y3. Only one or two online workshops will be organized, with probably less output than would be gathered during a physical workshop. Hopefully, in 2021 one workshop can be held. If not, the quality of the website with the guidelines might be less than aimed for. The plan is to develop a short, printable interactive Pdf version in addition to the website. Whether this can be achieved will depend on the progression of the website, which is hampered by COVID-19 as stated above. This WP will be in close collaboration with WP3, because of similar issues arise on European level. All information gathered will be used to develop common procedures and guidelines for setting-up/improving a national One Health structure. The guidelines will also contain suggestions on how to incorporate and use the national information system and tracing framework to be developed in WP4. The products developed will be publicly available and will be used as input for task 3 of this WP and in WP3.

Task: T-2.3 Knowledge transfer and dissemination

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Kitty Maassen, RIVM Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, ISZ LER, ISZ AM, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA, FOHM/PHA, INIAV

Description of the Task: Task T-2.3 takes place over third and fourth annual period of the EJP. The common procedures and tools developed in Task T-2.1 and T-2.2 of this work package will be pilot-tested in partner and interested EJP-countries (upon request) via short-term missions by the consortium. The main goal is to create support in an interested country. It is known that it is difficult to get support for a structured collaboration when there is no crisis to show its importance. Therefore, we would like to organize short-term missions (pilots) in order to locally provide

information to all national stakeholders using experiences from others countries. Leading up to the meeting and during the meeting the developed common tools and procedures are tailored to the needs of the country and can be used for further implementation. During the project it became clear that the best way to approach is was by organizing pilots. In these pilots the first steps of the developed guidelines will be taken (priority setting, stakeholder analysis and systems mapping of the current situation to jointly, in a One Health fashion, find ways to improve the collaboration). Four countries showed interest in such a pilot, Italy, Norway, Portugal and Belgium. The short-term mission will be a systems mapping workshop led by a Swiss expert. However, due to COVID-19 the Belgium workshop that was planned in March 2019 had to be cancelled and also the other workshops were postponed several times, since they have to be physical meetings. Hopefully all 4 workshops can take place in 2021, but it is realistic that none of the workshops can be held. Since the workshops are at the beginning of the implementation process, also there is realistic risk that also the follow up steps cannot be monitored and used in improvement of the guidelines.

WP3 Towards an EU zoonoses structure

WP start month 1

WP end month 36

WP Leader: Elina Lahti, SVA

Deputy WP Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA

WP participants: BfR, APHA, FHI/NIPH, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WBVR, RIVM, SVA, AGES, INIAV.

Description of the WP: WP3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. The overall aim of the work package is to bring together existing risk analysis and epidemiological tools, skills and facilities that are required for a 'one-health' approach with respect to zoonotic diseases in Europe. One of the main tasks will be in assessing the barriers encountered by risk analysis experts including surveillance experts to collaborate across country borders and recommending changes to overcome them and ensure that surveillance experts have access to the tools and data (see WP4) that are needed to provide a comprehensive risk analysis and surveillance service. Identifying good practice throughout this area will require maintaining a knowledge base that is constantly curated by experts and subject to scrutiny both within and outside the project. The aims of workpackage 3 will be delivered via 5 tasks:

Task: 3.4 Pilot One-Health Early Warning System

Task start month: 25

Task end month: 42

Task Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA

Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: APHA, FHI/NIPH, FLI, SLV/NFA, PHE, ISS, NVI, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, WbVR, RIVM, SVA

Description of the task: Task T-3.4 takes place over third and fourth annual period of the EJP. This pilot One-Health early warning system should include the relevant partners involved in both tasks 3.1 and 3.3 to build on and extend the initial findings. This task includes how the exchange of signals can take place, for example in a formal meeting setting or an informal teleconference/video link. This pilot will also be an opportunity to trial some of the solutions to overcome barriers experienced in task 3.1. This task will also try to identify routes to escalate possible issues or possibly recommend

further data collection that should be undertaken. The group will look into the possibility to keep the activities of the group open and transparent to allow countries outside the task to learn from the project.

Task: 3.5 Development of tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis

Task start month: 25

Task end month: 42

Task Leader: Charlotte Cook, APHA Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: APHA, BfR, AGES, CODA-CERVA

Task T-3.5 takes place over the third and fourth annual period of the EJP. In this task we will review tools and models for conducting cost-benefit analysis throughout the farm-to-consumption food chain using systematic literature research of available publications. In reviewing these we will address the strengths and weaknesses of cost-benefit approaches, providing guidance on the optimal scenarios for each tool. The data used when reviewing the tools developed will be collected from research or surveillance projects both within and outside this EJP project. This will provide the basis for application of a decision support framework over these tools, with synergies to task 2.2.

Work will be developed in harmony with task 4.3 to ensure that all the tools developed in the project are produced in a similar framework to reduce the complexity for users. Using a common framework will also minimise the training required and ensure that dissemination activities can be unified across the work packages where possible.

Due to Covid-19, resource and logistical capacity to complete all of these objectives has been limited. Restrictions on movement have also reduced face-to-face engagements with other member states. As a result, there is a realistic risk that some of these goals may not be met.

WP4 Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

WP start month: M1

WP end month: M40

WP Leader: Armando Giovannini, IZS-AM Deputy WP Leader: Armin Weiser, BfR

WP participants: BfR, FLI, IZS, FHI/NIPH, NVI, NFA, PHE, IZSLER, ISS, WbvR, FOHM/PHA, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, AGES

WP4 takes place over the first, second, third and fourth annual period of the EJP. The aim of this platform is to provide IT tools and data that are quickly available, usable and helpful in outbreak situations and for risk assessments.

During the fourth year project, main activity of WP4 will be to finalize sub-tasks delayed, mainly for COVID 19 crisis, as well as integrate software realized by the Tasks 4.1, 4.2, 4.3. In particular, information from CIS - COHESIVE Information System (Task 4.1) will be available and compatible with FoodChainLab (Task 4.2) and RRisk (Task 4.3).

Additionally, the ORION COHESIVE joint activity related to ontologies integration on CIS will be finalized.

Task: T-4.2 Development of a platform-independent tracing framework

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M40

Task Leader: Marion Gottschald, BfR Deputy Task Leader: Birgit Lewicki, BfR

Task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, NVI, ISS, FOHM/PHA

Description of the task: Task 4.2 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. This task is going to combine and improve available tracing algorithms with analysis and visualization of WGS data into modern software integrating surveillance and outbreak data. Within this task a server system is provided freely offering all developed tools browser-ready and open source.

The server runs on a Linux machine and the framework used is a Node.js / Angular framework providing secure areas for sensitive data. The server is available worldwide for modern browsers, which mainly mean that only very old versions of common browsers are excluded, but the Internet Explorer is completely excluded.

Sub-Task sT4.2.3

Sub-Task start month M13

Sub-Task end month M38

Sub-task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, FHI/NIPH, IZSLER, FLI, FOHM/PHA, ISS

Sub-task T4.2.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the third annual period of the EJP. This subtask takes care of the integration of meaningful surveillance and outbreak data into the software platform for analysis. Further data sources from MED- and VET-side, like cases, sampling results and also analysis results based on WGS-data from WP4.1 are going to be implemented resulting in a new algorithm based on probabilities for the scoring of common sources of an outbreak. To some extent, case and sampling information are already included in the visualization of delivery networks in FCL Web. Year three and four now aim at implementing analysis results based on WGS-data from WP4.1.

This subtask does also take care of the synchronization with IA-1: ORION and WPs 2 and 3. Selected promising tools will be taken into account for integration into the software platform of WP4. Especially, Task5 from WP3 seems promising, and it may come out that Task3 also develops into a candidate for the platform.

The deliverable of this subtask is the ready-to-use tool with extended WGS-Epi module and a report on additionally needed tools.

Task: T-4.3 Development of a platform-independent risk modeling framework

Task start month: M1

Task end month: M30

Task Leader: Christin Wallstab, BfR

Deputy Task Leader: Christine Müller-Graf, BfR

Task Participants: BfR, FHI/NIPH, FLI, FOHM/PHA, NVI

Description of the task: Task 4.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the first, second and third annual period of the EJP. The risk modelling framework will provide a flexible support to conduct high-end statistical modelling and simulation (including two-dimensional Monte Carlo and Markov chain Monte Carlo techniques, uncertainty and sensitivity analysis) with automatic reporting

and model documentation, modular structure and options for using pre-defining templates for parts of the model. Risk scenarios defined in other task groups are considered as use cases.

The graphical user interface for risk modelling will be developed and implemented with shiny R package to build an interactive web app. The app will be hosted on BfR webpage and server. Moreover, all scientific code will be made available under open source license model.

Sub-Task sT4.3.3 Validation of the risk modelling framework

Sub-Task start month M19

Sub-Task end month M37

Sub-task T4.3.3 continues based upon what was achieved during the second annual period of the EJP.

- a. Defining testing scenarios for verification and validation for each programme module,
- b. Testing using testing scenarios and benchmarking (i.e. runtime),
- c. Comparison with external programmes when available.

Sub-Task sT4.3.4 Deployment of the risk modelling framework

Sub-Task start month M34

Sub-Task end month M40

Sub-task Participants: BfR, FLI, IZS, FHI/NIPH, NFA, PHE, IZSLER, ISS, WbvR, FOHM/PHA, CODA-CERVA, WIV-ISP, AGES

Sub-task T-4.3.4 takes place over the fourth annual period of the EJP.

Task: T-4.4 Dissemination Task start month: M25

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: Marion Gottschald, BfR Deputy Task Leader:

Task Participants: BfR, IZS-AM, NVI

Description of the task: Task T-4.4 takes place over the third and fourth annual period of the EJP. Dissemination via workshops and supporting of real/historical outbreak investigations (bilateral possible) was already done over the whole project duration and will be continued in year 4. A joint interactive workshop on WP4 tools and how they interact is envisioned. It will be open for the COHESIVE community and other interested users and could be conducted online if meetings in person cannot take place due to COVID-19. All tools developed in WP4 will have enduring support and interactive live online courses will be offered. The tools will also be used in pilots in WP2 and WP3.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-1.7	Closing symposium	M42
D-1.8	Annual report	M42
D-2.5	Development of common procedures and tools	M40
D-2.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	M42
D-3.6	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	M40
D-3.8	Tool for systematic cost-benefit analysis	M42

D-4.2.3	Integration and analysis of epi-data from 4.1 → WGS-Epi module and selected features from IA-1, WP2, WP3	M38
D-4.3.3	Final testing design elaborated Report section about testing results (internal standards) Report section about testing results using external comparative models) Final release (open access)	M40
D-4.4.1	each subtask conducts workshops, provides documentation and tutorials	M42
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.4	Closing symposium	M42
M-AI2.COHESIVE.1.5	Annual report	M42
M-AI2.COHESIVE.2.2	Development of common procedures and tools	M40
M-AI2.COHESIVE.2.3	Knowledge transfer and dissemination	M42
M-AI2.COHESIVE.3.3	Local dissemination	M42
M-A2. COHESIVE.4.10	Analysis of epi-data into tracing framework enclosed	M40
M-A2. COHESIVE.4.11	Final release of risk modeling framework	M40

2.4.2.1.27 JIP03-R2-IA2.3-CARE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		IA 2.3: Joint databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata.								
Integrative Project Title		Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union								
Integrative Project Acronym		CARE								
Leading Organisation		P12-DTU			Deputy Leading Organisation			P13-SSI		
Project Leader		Rene Hendriksen			Deputy Project leader			Mia Torpdahl		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	41									7,5
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	26				6		38,5	40	4,26	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM					11	12	31	6	4,4	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM		35				2,6	3,5	4,95		
WP: WP0 Project coordination										
Objectives										
To coordinate collaboration between the public health, food and animal health sectors participating in CARE										
Description of work										
WP start month: 25										
WP end month: 54										

WP Leader: Rene Hendriksen, DTU
Deputy WP Leader: Mia Torpdahl, SSI
WP participants: ANSES, DTU, SSI, UCM, INRAE, IP, APHA, ISS, IZSAM, IZSLER, RIVM, WbvR, PIWET, SLV, FOHM, SVA.
Description of the WP: JIP IA 2.1-WP0
The coordinator and coordinating institute, DTU will invest a large amount of time in the CARE project. The coordinator will maintain regular contacts between the 16 different partners and will be responsible for the efficient progress of the project. The coordinator will make sure that all deliverables and milestones are reached in the timeframe envisioned for the project. The coordinator will organize interactions between groups, and meetings (one annually meeting and quarterly telephonic conferences) to continuously monitor progress of the objectives and to discuss scientific advances and problems. The kick off meeting will take place at DTU, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark, the interim meeting at ANSES, Paris, France and the closing meeting at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark. All partners are aware that strict management and clear lines of communication are essential to the successful completion of the proposed work programme. All partners have previously been involved in EU, ECDC, EFSA or other large consortia and are familiar with working in multi-centre, multinational projects. The partners have collaborated in different constellations with each other before and have been chosen both for their scientific credentials and proven ability to deliver in such projects. Excellent lines of communication and working relationships between all the partners have already been established. Efficient communication between partners will be achieved using electronic mail, and frequent telephone and web meetings. Each partner will provide the coordinator with scientific and financial statements, from which the coordinator will prepare the reports (cost details, research results and technical advancements). Any problem related to the financial management of the project will be discussed.

Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP0-T1 Over-all project coordination
Task start month: M25
Task end month: M54
Task Leader: Rene Hendriksen; DTU
Deputy Task Leader: Mia Torpdahl, SSI
Task Participants: ANSES, DTU, SSI, UCM, INRAE, IP, APHA, ISS, IZSAM, IZSLER, RIVM, WbvR, PIWET, SLV, FOHM, SVA.
Description of the task: Maintain regular contacts between the 16 different partners and monitor progress of the project through tele-conferences every 2nd month. Thus, to ensure that all deliverables and milestones are reached in the timeframe envisioned for the project.

Sub-Task JIP IA 2.1-WP0-T1-ST1: Organize kick off meeting.
Sub-Task start month: M25
Sub-Task end month: M25
Sub-Task Leader: Rene Hendriksen, DTU
Deputy Sub-Task Leader: Mia Torpdahl, SSI
Sub-Task Participants: ANSES, DTU, SSI, UCM, INRAE, IP, APHA, ISS, IZSAM, IZSLER, RIVM, WbvR, PIWET, SLV, FOHM, SVA.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D.0.5	Minutes of the interim meeting - 2021	M38
Milestones		

Ref	Title	Due month
M.0.2	Interim meeting - 2021	M37
WP1		
Objectives		
To develop guidance for cross-sectoral proficiency testing, aimed at trialling the collaborative systems' ability to solve food-borne outbreaks and other trans-sectoral challenges.		
Objectives		
To develop guidance for cross-sectoral proficiency testing, aimed at trialling the collaborative systems' ability to solve food-borne outbreaks and other trans-sectoral challenges.		
Description of work		
Task: IA 2.1-WP1: Develop of cross-sectional PT's		
WP start month: 25		
WP end month: 54		
WP Leader: 13 SSI, Jeppe Boel		
Deputy WP Leader: 12 DTU, Rene Hendriksen		
<p>WP participants: DTU, SSI, UCM, PIWET, APHA, ISS, RIVM, WBVR, SLV, FOHM, SVA, ANSES.</p> <p>Proficiency testing- (PT) or external quality assurance (EQA) schemes is an integrated part of quality assurance management for laboratories within the field of human and animal medical microbiology. The aim of this WP is to develop guidance for proficiency testing schemes that can be used cross-sectorial. This will be done by mapping the currently available PT's and assess the usefulness of these schemes in a cross-sectorial context and by developing proposals for new PT schemes that can accommodate unmet and new needs.</p> <p>The rapid emergence of whole genome DNA sequencing (WGS) methodologies for characterization of pathogens including analytical approaches that can predict virulence factors, antimicrobial resistance, clonal relationship, and identify food- and water borne outbreaks is an area where there is a need for new cross-sectorial PT schemes. Likewise, in the area of molecular based methodologies, including WGS, for culture-free detection/identification of pathogens in complex sample material new PT schemes are needed.</p> <p>In order to facilitate the development of the new PT proposals the WP will include a number of well-designed pilot PT's that will be performed among the WP participants.</p> <p>The WP will be concluded by developing a final guidance document giving specific recommendations in relation to which PT's that should be prioritized and containing specific guidance on how to perform the proposed cross-sectorial PTs.</p> <p>The WP will be divided into three parts (tasks):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of existing PT's and proposals for new PT schemes (6 months, M25-30) • Pilot trials (organized as sub-tasks) and documentation of outcome (18 months, M31-48). • Development of guidance document and proposals for SOPs where appropriate with suggestions for design of future cross-sectorial PT schemes (6 months, 49-54). 		
Task: IA 2.1-WP1-T2 Pilot trials and documentation of outcome (18 months)		
Task start month: 31		
Task end month: 48		
Task Leader: SSI – for coordination		
Task Participants: WP participants: DTU, SSI, UCM, PIWET, APHA, ISS, RIVM, WBVR, SLV, FOHM, SVA		
Description of the task:		

Based on the outcome of **IA 2.1-WP1-T1** a number of well-designed pilot PT's will be organized to support the design of new cross-sectorial PT's. The PT's will be performed in accordance with the criteria stipulated in ISO17043:2010, "Conformity assessment - General requirements for proficiency testing"

The pilot PT's will include both wet and dry laboratory exercises, and include different approaches, including culture and non-culture based detection methods and characterization methods with special focus on WGS based methodologies. A novel component is to perform pilot PT schemes where the proficiency in the speed of response to an outbreak is assessed. The participating laboratories will both provide analytical results as well as information about the applied methods.

The activities in this task will be coordinated with JRP/FBC 2.5 "Better tools for detection and investigation of foodborne outbreaks, including antimicrobial resistant pathogens, as well as economic assessments of potentially increased cluster detection through whole genome sequencing". The precise activities within each sub-task will be determined and coordinated at the first meeting at the initiation of the CARE project.

All learnings from the pilot PTs will be used directly in development of the design of the future PT schemes

The pilot PT's will be performed as three subtasks and documented in reports that will be used in **IA 2.1-W1-T3**.

Sub-Task: IA 2.1-W1-T2-ST1 Pilot PT on isolation/detection and characterization of pathogens

Sub-Task start month: M31

Sub-Task end month: M48

Sub-Task Leader: SVA, Elina Lahti

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: FOHM, Cecilia Jernberg

Sub-Task Participants: DTU, SSI, UCM, APHA, ISS, RIVM, WBVR, SLV, FOHM, SVA, ANSES.

Description of the sub-task:

The work will be focused on the laboratories ability to detect one or several different pathogens in different matrices; food and caeca/fecal samples. The pilot PT will target pathogens that are likely to be present in foods and known to cause illness in humans. The pilot PT will include the detection/isolation methods that are used in the different sectors, including the possibility to use culture, molecular and metagenomics based methods. The pilot PT will be performed as a cross-sectorial exercise where different strains with a matrix will be distributed to veterinary and food laboratories and simultaneously a set of strains will be distributed to public health laboratories. This will be followed by comparison of the reported results on detection, isolation and level of characterization from the sectors.

The work will be finalized with a report (D.1.2.1) describing the outcome of the pilot PT and recommendations for a design of cross-sectorial PTs within this area.

Sub-Task: IA 2.1-W1-T2-ST3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data

Sub-Task start month: M31

Sub-Task end month: M48

Sub-Task Leader: SSI, Jeppe Boel

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: APHA, Nick Coldham

Sub-Task Participants: DTU, SSI, UCM, APHA, PIWET, ISS, RIVM, WBVR, SLV, FOHM, SVA, ANSES.

Description of the sub-task:

Typically, for proficiency testing a turnaround time of up to three weeks would be expected. However, this might be too slow where a rapid response is required in an outbreak situation and member states need to introduce control measures.

In silico pilot PT trials will be launched to assess the laboratories ability to identify the source of foodborne outbreaks. The pilot PTs will include a scenario exercise, where laboratories shall identify

an outbreak based on simulated data that will be provided to the laboratories in real-time. The exercise will test the laboratories ability to analyse, interpret and communicate data in real time, and test overall collaborative performance of the systems in place for outbreak detection. Additionally, an important element of the pilot PT will be to evaluate the speed of the response. Standard techniques for phylogenetic comparison of bacterial strains will be evaluated, as this information may be essential for discovering new emerging pathogenic strains, tracing outbreaks, and introducing appropriate control measures across countries. Common target species such as *Salmonella* and *E. coli* will be included and the pilot PT might also include testing for AMR genes as this is a generic end point for many laboratories. The work will be finalized with a report (D.1.2.3) describing the outcome of the pilot PT and recommendations for a design of future cross-sectoral PTs within this area.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D.1.2.1	WP1-T2-ST1: Report - Pilot Isolation/detection of pathogens	M48
D.1.2.2	WP1-T2-ST2: Report - Pilot on typing/characterization including WGS	M48
D.1.2.3	WP1-T2-ST3 Pilot on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M.1.2	Review of task 1 and description of relevant pilot PTs	M35

WP: JIP IA 2.1-WP2 – Creation of EUROpanelOH, Objectives

- To make an inventory of current use and existence of bacterial reference materials across CARE OHEJP partner institutes, for selected, prioritised foodborne pathogens and antimicrobial resistance collections.
- To conduct a gap analysis with respect to accessibility, quality, characteristics and usefulness of existing and needed reference materials from a One Health perspective.
- To develop an approach for enrichment and adding values to the holdings.

Description of work

WP: JIP IA 2.1-WP2 – Creation of EUROpanelOH, a reference database of strains and genomes for effective quality control analysis in food safety and public health protection across sectors

WP start month: 25

WP end month: 52

WP Leader: Olivier Chesneau, IP

Deputy WP Leader: Stefano Morabito, ISS

WP participants: ANSES, DTU, UCM, INRAE, IP, ISS, IZSAM, IZSLER, SSI, WBVR, SLV, FOHM, PIWET, SVA.

Description of the WP: Bacterial reference materials (RM) are dispersed in Europe. Control strains are regularly distributed for EURLs PTs, PulseNet surveillance programs and EQAs organized by ECDC, but completeness and harmonization in providing RM for the application development and validation of analytical methods in a One Health perspective is still scanty. The need of certified RM is crucial in detail for the validation of novel methods, which is currently an active area of development, especially in the field of methods capable to identify and characterize bacterial strains on the basis of whole

genome sequence (WGS) analyses. Valuable on-line resources to infer virulence and identify genetic features associated to antimicrobial resistance from WGS data are already available through several bioinformatics suites of programs, either commercially available or distributed through open web portals, such as services provided by the Center for Genomic Epidemiology at DTU (<http://www.genomicepidemiology.org>) or ARIES webserver hosted by EURL VTEC (<https://www.iss.it/site/aries>). Nevertheless, novel tools are being developed continuously for bioinformatics analysis of WGS data and there is a necessity of certified RM for their benchmarking and validation in laboratories.

The first objective of WP2 will consist of making an inventory of current use and existence of RM among CARE partners and other voluntary OH-EJP partners with a balance of leading sources according to the sector(s) of the partner: Animal, Food, Human (JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T1). Type specimens will be listed from pathotypes to phylotypes among prioritised pathogens, with a special effort made in the field of antimicrobial resistance to cover all mechanisms and track major allelic variants. Attention will be made to associate reference isolates with the corresponding genomic sequences. Redundancy will be avoided, phenotypes and genotypes will be reported, and there will be an assortment of clinically important resistance mechanisms outside the zoonotic foodborne potential, contributing to the One-Health perspective. A systematic process of gathering information that is appropriate and sufficient to develop an effective database (strains and genomes) will address the groups' needs and wants (JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T2). The database with epidemiological, phenotypic and genomic information will be organized for each selected bacterial species. A sub-database will be dedicated specifically to antimicrobial resistance mechanisms. Each CARE partner will be asked to contribute for enriching the databases by fill in the gaps through better characterization of selected isolates that will be shown of interest (JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3). At the end of CARE and for next future developments, the EUROpanelOH will be a curated repository of certified RM that will serve as a centralized source of challenge sets for surveillance and advancing basic science research.

Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T2 **Gap analysis** with respect to accessibility, quality and usefulness of existing and potential new reference materials from a One-Health perspective.

Task start month: 36 (duration 7 months)

Task end month: 42

Task Leader: Olivier Chesneau, IP

Deputy Task Leader: INRAE, Sophie Roussel

Task Participants: SSI, DTU, ISS, SSI, WBVR, SVA, UCM, ANSES, IP, PIWET, INRAE.

Description of the task: Following the results of the survey conducted in JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T1 and the construction of the database listing the available RM (i.e. what we have), a need assessment will be conducted in JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T2 and will require consultation with partners in CARE, in OH-EJP and among a broader scientific audience to identify gaps related to the desirable RM (i.e. what we should have). These could include emerging threats or reference strains for additional features of already represented species, including reference isolates with unknown or elusive mechanisms of resistance, due to novel horizontally acquired genes or novel mutations arisen in the genomes. In addition, this gap analysis will be a key insight to stress the need of reference genomic sequences for many of the identified RM which will be identified and listed in this task. Such a need assessment will contribute to feed the JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3. The mass-spectrometry (MS) data of at least some representative RM for the pathogens included in the list could be also desirable in order to compile spectra which could serve the needs of laboratories working in food safety. The whole process of JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T2 will aim to determine what should be done in the enrichment and characterization of RM for the benefit of the laboratories that develop or validate methods for pathogen detection and antimicrobial resistance prediction.

Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3 Production of **additional RM** to fill in gaps and/or improve characterization if needed

Task start month: 43 (duration 10 months)

Task end month: 52

Task Leader: WBVR, Kees Valdman

Deputy Tasks Leaders: ISS, Stefano Morabito and INRAE, Sophie Roussel

Task Participants: SVA, UCM, DTU, SSI, IZSLER, IZSAM, PIWET, WBVR, IP, ANSES

Description of the task: The objective of this task will consist of coordinating the needed actions to fill the gaps identified in JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T2. In detail, identified RM could still need to be better characterized in terms of additional phenotypic traits (e.g. serologic assessment, biochemical characterization, MS spectrum, antibiotic susceptibility, cytotoxicity), or access to genome information. The sequencing approaches will depend on what is possible to do for each RM provider but high-coverage short-read data will be favoured to avoid potential complications due to errors in gene sequences that could misinterpret a serovar or a susceptibility profile. The minimum requirement for sequencing data is that the generated raw reads and assemblies be deposited in ENA Sequence Read Archive (SRA). In these archives, the information relating to experimental workflows are captured and displayed. The availability of raw reads and assemblies will provide a pathway to re-analyse, if required, the data as newer technologies emerge. The ENA works closely together with NCBI and DDBJ as partners in the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration. The policy of INSDC is to provide free and unrestricted permanent access to all archived nucleotide data. All primary data in the INSDC belongs to the submitters and can only be updated with submitter consent. Moreover, novel RM will be added *ex novo* in the list, following the identification of their lack in the database created in JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T1 and the gaps noted in JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T2. These novel RM will need to be retrieved and fully characterized, including by WGS and mass spectrometry (MS) analyses that will constitute subtasks JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3-ST1 and JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3-ST2, respectively. Each participant of the JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3 will work to fill the identified gaps. WGS data will facilitate a more complete understanding of the mechanisms of resistance and virulence, including the correlation between genotypes and phenotypes. MS data will give protein mass fingerprints of bacterial hazards useful for their detection in food and clinical microbiology. All these molecular characterization results will provide necessary passports for inclusion of needed RM in EUROpanelOH, thus feeding WP3 in a way stable over time.

Sub-Task JIP IA 2.1-WP2- T3-ST1 : WGS characterization

Sub-Task start month: 43

Sub-Task end month: 52

Sub-Task Leader: ISS, Stefano Morabito

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: DTU, Rene Hendriksen

Sub-Task Participants: SVA, UCM, SSI, IZSLER, IZSAM, PIWET, INRAE, IP, ISS, WBVR, ANSES, ISS, DTU.

Whole genome sequencing will be applied to a selection of reference bacterial strains for which genome data will still be lacking, as identified during the gap analysis for RM needed as part of JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T2. A minimum set of basic criteria for evaluating the quality of the sequencing data produced will be applied (e.g. minimum coverage, N50 of the assembly, total base paired assembled). In detail, this sub-task will be conducted according to the recommendations and guidelines provided by EFSA program ENGAGE whose outcomes for WGS are now available (<http://www.engage-europe.eu/>; <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/it/supporting/pub/en-1431>). The raw sequencing files and the corresponding genome assemblies produced will be deposited at ENA (D2.4) and the corresponding accession numbers made available for inclusion in the RM database.

Sub-Task JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3-ST2 : MALDI-TOF characterization

Sub-Task start month: 43

Sub-Task end month: 52

Sub-Task Leader: INRAE, Sophie Roussel

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: PIWET, Małgorzata Olejnik

Sub-Task Participants: IP, ANSES, UCM, WBVR, INRAE, PIWET, SVA

MALDI-TOF Mass spectrometry is now commonly used for bacterial identification and can also be used to find specific biomarkers. As large variations can be seen in MALDI-TOF mass spectra obtained under different conditions, the sub-task JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3-ST2 will first consist in standardizing the way of producing reference MALDI-TOF/MS spectra by defining a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) to ensure repeatability and reproducibility of analysis. Sub-task JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3-ST2 participants will then produce reference spectra for the bacteria on which the project is focused. The objective is to build a database containing the reference mass spectra obtained 1) for the Reference strains defined and characterized by the project 2) for a number of other strains in the same species or, depending of the relevancy, in the same pathotype or serotype for example. The number of these supplementary strains will be adjusted depending of the number of reference spectra already existing in the commercial databases. This work will contribute to the fine characterization of the RM. The accumulation of standardized spectra for each bacteria of interest will also generate data, which will be useful in further studies aiming at the identification of biomarkers.

Sub-Task JIP IA 2.1-WP2-T3-ST3 : Completing metadata and phenotypic data

Sub-Task start month: 43

Sub-Task end month: 52

Sub-Task Leader: WBVR, Kees Veldman

Deputy Sub-Task Leader: IP, Olivier Chesneau

Sub-Task Participants: ISS, ANSES, INRAE, SVA, UCM, DTU, SSI, IZSLER, IZSAM, IP, WBVR.

This final part of the WP2 is intended to ensure the completion of a predefined dataset of the identified RM including metadata as well as phenotypic traits (e.g. serovar, biochemical characterization, antibiotic susceptibility).

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D.2.3	A need assessment document stating what RM we should have	M40
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M.2.2	Consensual list of identified gaps	M42

WP: WP3 - Access and sustainability of well-defined microbial reference materials (RM)

Objectives

- To identify existing systems (software, databases) in place to record and query collections of biological materials held by OHEJP partners, for routine diagnostic and research needs.
- To ensure the long-term availability and sustainability of the reference material collection.
- To develop an approach for making such collections more widely accessible, within defined limits.

Description of work

WP: WP3 - Access and sustainability of well-defined microbial reference materials (RM)

WP start month: **25**

WP end month: **54**

WP Leader: Michel-Yves Mistou (INRAEE)

Deputy WP Leader: Anne Brisabois (ANSES)

WP participants: ANSES, INRAE, IP, PIWET, IZSAM, SVA, SSI, WBVR, IZSLER, SLV.

Description of the WP:

This WP seeks to make visible, accessible and sustainable the reference material well-identified and characterized in WP2 with the complete data panel associated. The second objective of this WP is to make visible the microbial collections of CARE partners. Firstly, from existing portal data infrastructures, an information system will be developed including a web site and a searchable electronic collection catalogue (JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T1). This information system will facilitate the open access to reference strains and data for the scientific community use. Reference strains identified in WP2 will be maintained and stored in microbial collections considered as “sustainable” (JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T2). This work should enable us to ensure the long-term availability of RM in order to contribute the needs of the European research. Moreover, we plan a training session dedicated to the management of microbial collections (JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T2). This training should enable CARE partners to update and manage their microbial collections. In a third task (T3.3), we will ensure wide dissemination and accessibility of the RM. We aim to connect the CARE information system with data portals of existing international and solid infrastructures, to ensure the long-term availability of the CARE information system.

Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T1 Development of an information system for making RM more widely accessible and visible

Task start month: M25 (Duration : 11 months)

Task end month: M46

Task Leader: INRAEE, Michel-Yves Mistou

Deputy Task Leader: IZSAM, Giuseppe Aprea, PIWET Magdalena Zajac

Task Participants: INRAEE, IP, DTU, PIWET, IZSLER, SSI, IZSAM, SLV, SVA, WBVR.

Description of the task: The Task JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T1 relies on an informatic approach. Beforehand, existing systems to record and query collections held by OHEJP partners will be listed. An information system (IS) will be developed to enable users evidence, query, and access of reference material. It will consist a minima of (i) a searchable electronic catalogue containing a maximum of information and data on the reference strains preserved and where they are stored (ii) a website. In addition, the IS will contain IT tools to support the curators and to provide users information in a structured way. A plan management data will also be established. Data will be of different types including mandatory- and -not mandatory data: “passport” data, sequencing and phenotyping data, and “regulation” data for easy access in compliance with applicable legislation (Nagoya Protocol).

The CARE catalogue will be connected to a broad range of European and National databases of microbial collection (including databases of CARE partners). We will follow recommendations established by the scientific community such as for instance the US AgBiodata consortium (Harper et al., 2018). The CARE IS will embrace the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles established by stakeholders from the scientific, publishing and library communities (Wilkinson et al., 2016, 2019). The IS must be regularly updated, upgraded and curated. The CARE IS will link established databases and bridge the gaps between biodiversity repositories, sequence databases and characterization data obtained in WP2 (outputs WP2D2.1 ; WP2D2.6). The data portal infrastructure will be comparable and compatible to (i) this already existing of the Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) (Droege et al., 2013) and (ii) the future one that will be developed within the European Research Infrastructure MIRRI (Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure) (Casaregola et al., 2016).

This portal will make reference strains available for the European research, be it public or private. Data associated with strains will be freely available through IS. This portal will be a key tool as it will allow users to access strains and relevant information *via* one entry point, avoiding time-consuming

searches for necessary information on specific strains. Through CARE, a new level of interoperability between strains, metadata and databases will be obtained and should boost the European research.

Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T2 Ensure the long-term sustainability of Reference Material collections

Task start month: 37 (Duration 15 months)

Task end month: 51

Task Leader: INRAEE, Florence Valence, Michel-Yves Mistou

Deputy Task Leader: PIWET, Magdalena Zajac, IP (Dominique Clermont)

Task Participants: INRAEE, PIWET, IP, ANSES, IZSLER, UCM, IZSAM.

Description of the task:

The task JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T2 relies on microbiological work. Strains identified as reference strains (output WP2 D2.1 and D2.6) will be entered, maintained and preserved within the microbial collections considered as sustainable. These collections are collections certified according to high quality criteria. The entry of RM in collections relies on isolation, identification and conservation work, done under high standard of quality. In CARE, microbial collections of at least three partners (IZSLER, IP-CP, INRAE-CIRM) are certified according to ISO9001 or/and NF S 96-900 and are satisfying OECD best practices guidelines.

Two partners, INRAE-CIRM and IP-CIP, are public microbial Biological Resource Centers (mBRCs), members of World Federation for Culture Collections (WFCC) and European Culture Collections Organisation (ECCO). They are operating under quality certified procedures for the accession, the authentication, the preservation and the distribution of microorganisms. MBRCs are repositories whose role is to preserve the microorganisms in order to provide them to the scientific community. They offer the guarantee of accessibility and sustainability of microbial resources hosted (Janssens et al., 2010). The Task will benefit from expertise of the two mBRCs in the management of microbial collections. These two mBRCs will train CARE partners to update their own microbial collection, to have it certified according to quality standards and render it sustainable. This will enrich microbial collections available for routine and reference activities across OHEJP participants (including its usage in PTs organized in WP1) and will provide them an added and sustainable value.

Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T3 Ensuring the long-term accessibility of the RM collection and its existence

Task start month: 45 (10 months)

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: Mery Piña (IP)

Deputy Task Leader: Maria Beatrice Boniotti (IZSLER), Michel-Yves Mistou (INRAEE)

Task Participants: ANSES, INRAEE, IP, IZSLER, UCM.

Description of the task: This task relies in strengthening ongoing collaborations of CARE partners with international stakeholders such as the OIE (World Organization for Animal Health), the WDCM (World Data Center for Microorganisms), MIRRI and other described below to increase the visibility and ensure the sustainability of the portal developed in task JIP IA 2.1-WP3-T1. The signature of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoUs) with the organizations listed below will guarantee the long-term accessibility of the RM collection.

The OIE is developing the Virtual Biobank portal (release planned for 2021), which will consist of a website where users can search for biological materials produced and distributed worldwide by the OIE Reference Laboratories as part of their commitment in the standardization and harmonization of diagnostic methods. Many CARE partners (ANSES, APHA, IZSAM, IZSLER, NVRI, VISAVET) are OIE Reference Laboratories and IZSLER, who leads the OIE project, is the Collaborating Centre for Veterinary Biologicals Biobank. All these CARE partners will ensure the appropriate coordination and the optimal synergy between the two projects.

The WDCM, is the data center for the WFCC, which manages several databases, including the Global Catalogue of Microorganisms (GCM). Launched in 2013, the GCM is a robust, reliable and user-friendly

system to help culture collections to manage, disseminate and share the information related to their holdings. The GCM 2.0 is an international community-led project towards full genome sequencing and data annotation of microbial type strains, IP is currently a partner in this project.

In the European level, the CARE database is intended to be linked to data portals of European Research infrastructures (RI) such as MIRRI (<http://mirri.org>), EMBRC (<http://www.embrc.eu/>), BBMRI (<http://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>) and ELIXIR (www.elixir-europe.org), in particular with the H2020 EOSC-Life project (<https://www.elixir-europe.org/news/eosc-life-start>). INRAE, IP and IZLER are currently working in the development of MIRRI and the conception of its “Collaborative Working Environment” to which the CARE IS could be linked.

Glossary

- ECCO: European Culture Collections Organisation
- ELIXIR: brings life science resource from across Europe. These resources include databases, software tools, training material, cloud storage and super computers.
- EMBRC: European Marine Biological Resource Centre
- EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
- ESFRI: European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
- MIRRI: Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure
- OECD: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
- OIE: World Organization for Animal Health
- WFCC: World Federation for Culture Collections

References

- Casaregola S, Vasilenko A, Romano P, et al (2016) An Information System for European culture collections: the wayforward. Springerplus. 5:772.
- Droege G, Barker K, Astrin JJ et al (2013). The global genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) Data Portal. Nucleic Acid Research, 42607-612.
- Harper L, Campbell J, Cannon EKS et al., (2018). AgBioData consortium recommendations for sustainable genomics and genetics databases for agriculture. Database 1-32
- Janssens D, Arahall DR, Bizet C et al (2010). The role of public biological resources centers in providing a basic infrastructure for microbial research. Research in Microbiology 161, 422-429
- Wilkinson MD et al., 2016. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific data.
- Wilkinson MD et al., 2019. Addendum. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Scientific data.

WP: WP4

Objectives

- The aim of WP4 is to investigate and benchmark the availability and quality of the existing (meta-)data (in close collaboration with WP2) among the OHJPE members relevant for risk assessment.
- WP4 also aims, for higher comparability, to harmonise data and to increase the accessibility of the data by all OHEJP members.
- To avoid duplication and limited comparability with existing EU data collections and initiatives the CARE consortium aims to collaborate with ECDC and EFSA.
- To promote national participation in initiatives from EU authorities that serve to make high quality (meta-)data more readily available for risk assessments.

Deliverables		
Ref	Title	Due month
D.3.1.1	Database Structure for RM catalog	32
D 3.1.2	Synthesis Documents after questionnaire processing 1/ partners expectations 2/ list of existing softwares 3/ technical choice	35
D 3.1.3	Searchable online RMs catalogue	46
D3.2.1	Deposit of RMs within mBRCs and collections considered as "reference collections"	51
D3.3.1	Signing of an MoU to ensure the sustainability of the CARE IS	54
Ref	Title	Due month
M.3.1.1	Define list of fields for the RM database	31
M3.1.2	Building questionnaire on expectations of CARE partners for the RM online catalog	31
M3.2.1	Training session on microbial collection management	43
M3.2.1	Training session completed	43
M3.3.1	Drafting MoU to be done and circulated among partners	47
M3.3.2	Launching event of the CARE portal where stakeholders will be invited to sign the MoU	50
<p>Description of work WP: WP4 WP start month: 25 WP end month: 54 WP Leader: Laurent Guillier, ANSES Deputy WP Leader: Henk Aarts, RIVM WP participants: ANSES, RIVM, IZSAM, DTU. WP4 will result in an assessment and benchmarking of the availability, relevance and quality of the existing (meta-)data, that is currently used among the OHJPE members for risk assessment. WP4 will also result in a high level of harmonised datasets and an increased accessibility of the data by all OHEJP members. Furthermore, in order to avoid duplication and limited comparability with existing EU data collections and initiatives the CARE consortium aims to collaborate with ECDC and EFSA. WP4 will not create its own database but will utilize an existing web platform to make the surveillance data accessible for simple visualizations, comparisons with other open sources of data, and download in a single place. The first activity of WP4 is to conduct a survey among the OHJPE members regarding the available data for risk assessment. Based on the outcome of this survey a roadmap will be developed in how to collaborate with (reporting) initiatives (like the SIGMA project, RAKIP etc.) and existing databases maintained by EU authorities to prevent limited comparability and duplication. Furthermore, a dissemination plan for encouraging the national authorities in charge to put emphasis on the collection and reporting of the above identified data to enable readily availability and an increasing amount of data for risk-assessments.</p> <p>Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP4-T1 Task start month: 25 Task end month: 40 Task Leader: Henk Aarts, RIVM</p>		

Deputy Task Leader: Laurent Guillier, ANSES

Task Participants: ANSES, RIVM, IZSAM.

Description of the task:

This task will develop and launch a survey among OHEJP members to identify which data/databases (and associated metadata) is currently used in risk assessment. Three subtasks have been defined for Task 1.

T1.1 A survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment

First, the targeted institutes (EJP members broad sense, external bodies through EFSA network, others) will be defined (M.4.1.1). In order to design the survey, a short review of types of risk assessment (M.4.1.2) and criteria data quality and availability (M.4.1.3) will be established. The CARE consortium will use for this objective the controlled vocabularies and the harmonized model annotation for risk assessments models proposed in ANSES/BFR/DTU RAKIP model (Haberbeck et al. 2018). The CARE Consortium will also benefit from JIP ORION, which aims at establishing and strengthening inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in the area of health data integration. A specific question on ontologies related to data quality will be addressed to JIP ORION leader.

Based on these elements, a survey template will be developed and tested to small panel of colleagues from RIVM and ANSES (M.4.1.4). Once validated, the survey will be sent out to all targeted users (D.4.1).

T1.2 Connection of this CARE activity with the databases and initiatives already in place

Several initiatives are being conducted in the field of risk assessment in order transparency and availability of data and models. The leaders of these initiatives will be conducted in order to gather from them the relevant information for the CARE project (M.4.1.5.). The CARE's objective will presented as well. To avoid duplication and limited comparability with the already reported data, develop a roadmap for collaboration with (reporting) initiatives (like the SIGMA project, RAKIP etc.) and existing databases maintained by EU authorities (ECDC and EFSA), a specific meeting (M.4.1.6) will be held.

This will provide the deliverable (D.4.1.2): that is the establishment of connection of this CARE activity with the databases and initiatives already in place.

T.1.3 Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility

WP4 members will first analyze the outcome of the survey. Descriptive statistics of the items of the survey will be provided (M.4.1.7). This will be the basis for writing the analysis report. Partners will review the report (M.4.1.8)

Deliverable 4.1.3 Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility

Task: JIP IA 2.1-WP4-T2 Metadata web platform

Task start month: 34

Task end month: 52

Task Leader: Jolene Lee Masters Pedersen, DTU

Deputy Task Leader: Rene Hendriksen, DTU

Task Participants: ANSES, RIVM, IZSAM, DTU

Description of the task:

Based on the survey a user guide (D.4.2.1) will be developed describing how to access the available data and furthermore to develop a strategy to raise awareness by EU authorities of collecting relevant and high quality data for risk-assessment and implement this strategy (D.4.2.2). WP4 will incorporate the surveillance data into a web platform (D.4.2.3) that aims to facilitate the exploration of antimicrobial resistance and infectious disease data together with publically available predictors of

these factors. It will be possible to get a visual overview of available surveillance materials, test simple correlations with other important factors and download the data directly. Antimicrobial resistance and infectious disease data together with publically available predictors of these factors will be used as a case study of data connection, analysis and visualization.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D.4.1.1	A survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment	31
D.4.1.2	The establishment of connection of this CARE activity with the databases and initiatives already in place	35
D.4.1.3	Report on analyzed survey data regarding the quality and accessibility	42
D.4.2.1	User Guide for accessing relevant data for risk-assessment	42
D.4.2.2	Implementation of developed strategy to raise awareness by EU authorities	45
D.4.2.3	Web based exchange platform including antimicrobial resistance surveillance data.	48
D.4.3	Executed dissemination plan	54

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M.4.1.1	Define the list of targeted institutes to who the survey will be addressed	27
M.4.1.2	Definition of criteria to assess the data quality and accessibility	28
M.4.1.3	Definition of types of risk assessment and associated metadata	28
M.4.1.4	Test the draft questionnaire of a small panel of risk assessors	30
M.4.1.5	Letter to take contact with JIP/EJP project (Harmony, Matrix, RADAR,...) and other projects (SIGMA, EFSA Knowledge Junction, RAKIP...)	34
M.4.1.6	Teleconference of the different partners of these project to check for synergy and to avoid duplication of the work	35
M.4.2	Data typology and description methodology	38
	Data gaps and accessibility analysis	40
	Inventory of existing data visualization tools	45

2.4.2.1.28 JIP04-R2-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		IA 2.2: Harmonised protocols and common best practice								
Integrative Project Title		One Health Harmonisation of Protocols for the Detection of Foodborne Pathogens and AMR Determinants								
Integrative Project Acronym		OH-Harmony Cap								
Leading Organisation		P13-SSI			Deputy Leading Organisation			P13-SSI		
Project Leader		Nadia Boisen			Deputy Project leader			Flemming Scheutz		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	6,1						6			
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	35,3								15,3	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbvR	FHI
PM				2,4	18			3,8		3,31
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
PM	2	5,5	5,42	17,5		0,7	4	9,5		
Objectives (for WP1-5) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and test of an adjusted OHLabCap survey for primary diagnostic sector • Level of methods used for characterisation of model organisms • Ranking and choice of harmonised protocols 										
WP1: Project Coordination <i>This WP takes place over the first, second, and third annual period of the project. All the tasks run concurrently</i>										

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 13-SSI

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA

Description of WP1: Description of WP1: This WP will focus on effective project management subdivided between internal coordination, external engagement, and knowledge building. The purpose is to enabling collective activities, and ensure cohesiveness, efficacy, and sustainability. The intent is not only to enable seamless coordination between 5 WPs, 11 countries, and 15 institutions but also to be flexible and address unforeseen problems as they arise. Further this WP ensures that roles and responsibilities are clearly defined.

Task WP1-T1: Internal coordination

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA

Description of the task: This task is centred on SSI's long track record of coordinating complex health activities across multiple EU countries. With 15 participating institutions, the aim is to move the project forward, keeping staff on budget, meet deadlines, ensure quality deliverables, and realise the full impact of the project. Intra-project exchanges will be focused on effective communication strategy, i.e. conference calls, five face-to-face meetings, and automated data collection such as surveys. This task also ensures that the "model organism" tracks will be carried out into the WP-specific work.

Task WP1-T2: External coordination, outreach and engagement

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA

Description of the task: External engagement will be important to find synergies with other projects, obtain important and timely feedback from external partners, and effectively disseminate our own results. The aim is then to stay connected with external stakeholders. Particular attention will be paid to collaboration with other EJP initiatives, particular MATRIX and CARE, so they have a chance to contribute their views on current gaps, which will, benefit OH integration. Practically, this will be achieved by workshops described in WP5.

Task WP1-T3: Data management

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA

Description of task: This task will continuously track, monitor, analyse, and store data in order to ensure progress throughout the project. The outcome then is a data asset that will be readily

available for all our purposes, as well as those that may need this data in the future, also contributing to the sustainability of the project. The specific deliverable will be a preliminary data management plan, which can be adjusted, as the project progresses.

Task WP1-T4: Sustainability

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 30-RIVM, 26-Teagasc, 41-SVA

Description of task: Sustainability is an important cross-theme to all WPs, with considerations before, during, and after the project. The intent is that others find value in this work and build upon it once the project has concluded. Mechanism includes, but are not limited to, dissemination in peer reviewed publications, participations in external events, data sharing, and future collaborations across the OneHealth interface.

WP2: Development of the OHLabCap

WP2 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy WP Leader: 30-RIVM

WP participants: All OH-Harmony-Cap participants

Description of WP2: The aim of WP2 is to develop a benchmarking tool "OHLabCap", by surveying OneHealth laboratory interoperability, capacity and performance across EU. The focus will be on the detection and typing of selected priority foodborne pathogens, AMR determinants, and priority parasites across each sector (AH, PH, and FS). The main deliverable will result in the establishment of an OHLabCap that is repeatable and sustainable at both an EU and National level. An efficient tool *must* support harmonised data collection and validation, and encourage cross-sectoral communication and assist competent authorities in establishing and strengthen National networks. This requires identifying and characterising OneHealth laboratory interoperability, capacity and performance in each step within the system (e.g. coordination, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and dissemination of data). The tool will produce country-scale profiles of laboratory interoperability and identify gaps in capability and capacity. This tool will make use of the existing EULabCap without repeating existing surveys and incorporate AH and FS. The surveys will define targets across three dimensions: 1. primary diagnostic testing (e.g. regulation, guidelines, USE, and AST), 2. NRL services (e.g. regulation, reference material, typing, and AMR markers), and 3. laboratory-based interoperability and communication (e.g. national networks, participation in EQAs, communication on OH levels). To ensure this, two surveys will be developed a pilot survey at the NRL level and an adjusted survey in collaboration with the NRLs of the primary sector, and four tasks will be undertaken. The four tasks will run consecutively.

Task WP2-T3: Development and testing of an adjusted survey (Primary sector)

Task WP2-T3 takes place during the second year of the project

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Task Participants: All OH-Harmony-Cap participants

Description of the task: Development and testing of an adjusted survey at the primary diagnostic level, i.e. non NRL, based on the results of the pilot survey (WP2-T1 and WP2-T2). The adjusted survey will include a list of indicator, modifications, and organised, through the respective NRLs, and include inventories of diagnostic methods for the chosen foodborne pathogens at local/regional laboratories to map which pathogens are analysed and how detection, and isolation, are carried out to identify methodological gaps that would lead to skewed OneHealth disease surveillance. Three subtasks will be undertaken. The technical report from WP2-T1-S3 (D-2.1-3) will determine which targets, indicators and pathogens from the WP2-T1-2 subtasks can be included. The survey population will be the primary diagnostic laboratories as identified in the first survey and the tools will be electronic questionnaires (D-2.3).

Subtask WP2-T3-S1 (M37-M39): Compilation of indicators from the primary sector and national microbiology reference laboratory services

Subtask WP2-T3-S2 (M39-41): Creation of a beta version questionnaire in the chosen software. Usability test of beta version among a smaller group of primary diagnostic laboratories selected by the WP2 OH-Harmony-Cap participants and the NRLs.

Subtask WP2-T3-S3 (M42): Finalise the adjusted survey questionnaire and circulate to the survey population

Task WP2-T4: **Scoring of collected data and chosen indicators (Primary sector)**

Task WP2-T4 takes place during the second and third year of the project

Task start month: M43

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Task Participants: All OH-Harmony-Cap participants

Description of the task: The aim of task WP2-T4 is to evaluate, assess, and score the collected data and chosen indicators using scoring options similar to those used in the OHLabCap pilot survey (WP2-T1 and WP2-T2). Two subtasks will be undertaken

Subtask WP2-T4-S1 (M43-M48): Analyses including identification of gaps and challenges of the adjusted survey results.

Subtask WP2-T4-S2 (M48-52): Prepare the One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability for the primary diagnostic laboratories in each of the EU/EEA countries and dissemination.

The overall outcome of WP2-T3 and WP2-T4 will be an integrated One Health map of the levels of system capability/capacity/interoperability for each of chosen organisms for the primary diagnostic laboratories in the EU/EEA countries. This tool will not include an evaluation of surveillance capacities and capabilities (EUEpiCap), which is included in MATRIX, however, collaboration is planned, including a joint workshop, between OH-Harmony-Cap and MATRIX if both projects are funded (WP5-T3).

WP3: One Health Laboratory interoperability guidance

WP3 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project

WP start month: M26

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 26-Teagasc

Deputy WP Leader: 36-INSA

WP3 participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 26-Teagasc, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Description of WP3: The overall aim of this WP is to map the existing knowledge gaps and propose new studies and/or methods that are needed to fill them. The main deliverable will be guidance (in a series of summary reports), for the chosen model organism(s), for systematic methodological improvement with respect to One Health laboratory interoperability. This includes developing a modern harmonised system for food, feed, animal and human sampling and testing in Europe. Three tasks will be undertaken; Sampling and Testing, Characterisation, and Data management. This WP does *not* include analysis of specific the protocols. Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* have been pre-selected for the project's purposes.

Task WP3-T2: **Characterisation of methods**

Task WP3-T2 takes place during the second year of the project

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: 21-APHA

Deputy Task Leader: 36-INSA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 26-Teagasc, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: The aim of this task is to attempt harmonised strain characterisation including typing and virulence gene testing in Europe.

Sub-task WP3-T2-ST1 (M37-M42): The responses to the questionnaire (WP3-T1-S1) will be used to establish current practice in Europe.

Sub-task WP3-T2-ST2 (M42-M48): A systematic review of the scientific and other relevant literature will be used to identify currently available methods for strain characterisation. Moreover, the recommendations contained in relevant EFSA Opinions, FAO reports, etc. on the specific strain information required to underpin future food safety regulation/policy will be used to inform the deliverable.

The deliverable will be a summary report describing; [1] current routine strain characterisation in Europe; [2] gaps in strain characterisation that are inhibiting food safety regulation/policy in the EU; [3] recommendations on what typing methods, AMR and virulence gene testing, etc. should be undertaken as part of a future harmonised approach to strain characterisation and [4] recommendations on how this harmonised strategy should be implemented (D-3.2).

Task WP3-T3: **Data management of harmonised reporting**

Task WP3-T3 takes place during the second and third year of the project

Task start month: M44

Task end month: 54

Task Leader: 26-Teagasc

Deputy Task Leader: 36-INSA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 26-Teagasc, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: This task aims at describing harmonised reporting including foodborne pathogen data management within individual MSs and data transfer to EFSA and ECDC.

Sub-task WP3-T3-ST1 (M44-M50): The responses to the questionnaire (sub-task WP3.T1.S1) will be used to establish current data management practices with individual MSs and how this data is communicated to EFSA and ECDC.

Sub-task WP3-T3-ST2 (M47-54): Experts from Information and communications technology (ICT) companies will be invited to present their data management systems to a panel of personnel (with relevant experience) from within the project and external experts (eg. personnel in EFSA and ECDC who collate and analyse this data). Recommendations on best practice used to form the basis for a harmonised system for recording, storing and transferring data with the EU.

The deliverable will be a summary report (drafted by the WG but reviewed by all project participants) describing; [1] current used data management systems in Europe; [2] a harmonised data management system for the future and [3] recommendations on how this system should be implemented (hard ware, software, motivating MSs, etc.).

WP4: Harmonisation of protocols

WP4 takes place during the first, second, and third year of the project

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M48

WP Leader: 27-ISS

Deputy WP Leader: 1-ANSES

WP4 participants: 1-ANSES, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 32-NIPH, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Description of WP4: The aim of WP4 is to produce recommendations and protocols to harmonise the methodology for the detection and typing of the model pathogens. These pathogens will be selected as example for the project's purposes, and identified candidates include Shiga Toxin producing *E. coli* (STEC), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), Cryptosporidium, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*. This would allow us to take advantage of the experience of the EURL for *E. coli* and the EURL for Parasites, hosted by ISS and involved in the WP, who are continuously making efforts in the harmonisation of methods applied by Veterinary Laboratories through the coordination of the National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) networks. The strategy and the approaches adopted in the framework of WP4 activities can be, if needed, transferred to other pathogens, enabling harmonisation of methodologies in use in the EU/EEA Laboratories. During the first year of the project, information on the methodologies and protocols in place for the detection of the selected pathogens in Laboratories working in the different sectors will be collected.

Task WP4-T2: Evaluation of the collected laboratory protocols

Task WP4-T2 takes place in the first and second year of the project

Task start month: M31

Task end month: M39

Task Leader: 41-SVA

Deputy Task Leader: 1-ANSES

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 32-NIPH, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of selected foodborne pathogens, including STEC, ETEC, *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR for *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, in use in the laboratories operating in public health and veterinary sectors. The information about the methodologies applied in the EU/EEA laboratories will be circulated among the WP4 participants and will be assessed with the purpose of identifying differences and similarities in the methodological approaches applied in the different laboratories. This will be the basis for the definition of Harmonised protocols. Three subtasks will be undertaken and they will run concurrently. Three working groups (WG) of 4-6 relevant participants, with required expertise and experience in STEC/ETEC, *Cryptosporidium*, and AMR, to undertake Task WP4-T2.

WP4-T2-S1(M31-M39): Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing STEC/ETEC

WP4-T2-S2 (M31-M39): Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing for AMR *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*

WP4-T2-S3(M31-M39): Evaluation of the laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of *Cryptosporidium*

Task WP4-T3: **Ranking and choice of the harmonised laboratory protocols**

Task WP4-T3 takes place during the second year of the project

Task start month: M39

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: 34-PIWet

Deputy Task Leader: 1-ANSES

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 32-NIPH, 30-RIVM, 33-NVI, 34-PIWet, 35-INIAV, 36-INSA, 39-SLV, 40-FOHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: WP4 participants will be enrolled in the preparation of the protocols according to their area of expertise. They will rank and evaluate the harmonised laboratory protocols for the detection and typing of "model organisms". The protocols will be distributed to the Medical and Veterinary Laboratories participating in the WP4 and those who participated in the collection of the protocols (WP4 T1). Medical, food, and veterinary laboratories examine the presence of pathogens in specimens: clinical, food, or animal samples, can employ unique protocols making it difficult to harmonise therefore the deployment of a unique procedure is not conceivable. Food and Vet laboratories are required to use ISO protocols, when in place, such as ISO13136 for the detection of STEC in foods. Nevertheless, the collection of the protocols in use will help in defining common approaches and protocols, to be applied, in the different fields of investigation, with a special focus on the public Health laboratories (D-4.3).

WP5: Training sessions on harmonised protocols

WP5 will take during the second and third year of the project

WP start month: M40

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 27-ISS

Deputy WP Leader: 13-SSI

WP participants: All OH-Harmony-Cap participants

Description of WP5: The aim of this WP consist in increasing EU capacity to deal with foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats across the OneHealth interface through partner-to-partner delivery of training. The training will provide opportunities for better communication, knowledge exchange, and knowledge integration within the OneHealth interface, and not just for the OH-Harmony-Cap participants. As such, two workshops will be held during the final meeting in Copenhagen. Copenhagen was chosen for two reasons; 1) joint meeting with MATRIX and CARE, and 2) logistically, Copenhagen is easily accessible, for most participants, thus ensuring a high attendance. Finally, practical workshops and e-learning activities dedicated to the application of the harmonised protocols developed in WP4 on a set of foodborne pathogens will be organised.

Task WP5-T1: Facilitation and communication of the OHLabCap

Task WP5-T1 will take place during the second and third year of this project

Task start month: M40

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: All OH-Harmony-Cap participants

Description of the task: A workshop for communicating and discussing the outcome of the OHLabCAP survey conducted in the framework of WP2 will be organized and planned in Y4 and the dissemination will take place, in Copenhagen, during the final annual meeting in Y5. The workshop will be a combination of presentations and workgroup discussions where sessions will be split into predetermined topics based on the outcome of WP2. The aim is to establish and suggest guidelines to increase the interoperability, capacity and performance of harmonised data collection and validation, and encourage cross-sectoral communication and assist competent authorities in establishing and strengthen National networks.

Task WP5-T2: Joint workshop between CARE, OH-Harmony-Cap, and MATRIX

Task WP5-T2 will take place during the second and third year of this project

Task start month: M40

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: All participants from CARE, OH-Harmony-Cap, and MATRIX

Description of the task: The three integrated projects, CARE (IA2.1), OH-Harmony-Cap (IA2.2), and MATRIX (IA2.3) propose a joint workshop, if funded, where the outcomes of CARE, OHLabCap, and EUEpiCap (WP4, MATRIX) will be presented. The aim is to strengthen the OneHealth interface by facilitating dissemination between NRLs and epidemiologists. The main focus of the workshop will be the description of gaps and challenges in the communication between laboratories and epidemiologists, and discuss recommendations to ultimately improve One Health surveillance and outbreak detections. The workshop will consist of presentations, held by CARE, OH-Harmony-Cap,

and MATRIX, which will provide the background for workgroup discussions. Sessions will be split into predetermined topics decided by CARE, MATRIX and OH-Harmony-Cap (D-5.2)

Task WP5-T3: Training sessions in harmonised protocols

Task WP5-T3 will take place during the second and third year of this project

Task start month: M40

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 27-ISS

Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 13-SSI, 27-ISS, 35-INIAV

Description of the task: Practical workshops and e-learning activities dedicated to the application of the harmonised protocols developed in WP4 on a set of foodborne pathogens will be organised.

WP5-T3-ST1 (M40-M53) Practical workshops: Ad hoc training programs will be developed for the benefit of the project's participants operating either in the veterinary or medical areas expressing the interest of participating in such hands-on workshops. These practical training sessions will be pivotal for the assessment of the protocols deployed and to implement the harmonisation between the different sectors. The trainings will consist of three days of laboratory activities on the application of the harmonised protocols developed. Three practical workshops, focusing on the model organisms considered in this project, will be held at ISS and SSI. Training for STEC/EPEC and parasites will be held at ISS and training for AMR will be held at SSI. Three different rounds (STEC/EPEC, Cryptosporidium, and AMR) will be foreseen, in order to allocate maximum four scientists in the laboratory (for a total of 8 scientists visiting ISS and SSI).

WP5-T3-ST2 (M40-M54) E-learning: Dissemination of the application of the harmonised protocols through e-learning. Besides the practical workshops, training sessions on the Harmonised protocols will be deployed also through the use of several e-learning tools, including webinars and distance learning e-modules. This would enable a high level of dissemination of the project's achievements. The participating institutes have distance learning facilities and experience on the development of webinars and e-learning courses. All the training delivered will have a final step of assessment of the achievement of the learning objectives.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.2.3	Adjusted survey	M42
D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.3.2	List of methods used to characterised pathogens	M48
D-IA.2.2.OH-Harmony-Cap.4.3	A technical report of Harmonised protocols including; 1) detection of selected pathogens, and 2) characterisation (e.g. virulence genes asset) and typing of pathogens.	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-IA2.2. OH-Harmony-Cap.5	WP3-T2 completed	M46
M-IA2.2. OH-Harmony-Cap.6	Assessing protocols for detection and typing of the selected foodborne pathogens	M39

2.4.2.1.29 JIP05-R2-IA2.1-MATRIX

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		IA 2.1: Common frameworks for design and methods to assess equivalence between surveillance and control activities								
Integrative Project Title		MATRIX: Connecting dimensions in One-Health surveillance								
Integrative Project Acronym		MATRIX								
Leading Organisation		P13-SSI			Deputy Leading Organisation			P41-SVA		
Project Leader		Diana Connor			Deputy Project leader			Fernanda Dórea		
Project Start month		M25			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	20,8						19,85	8,4		6,5
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM	24			15	17				7,4	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	Uos	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	8,4				5	26,5		8,5	3	16,52
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM	3,88	14,2		16,6			8	23		
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate a sector based (e.g. animal health (AH), public health (PH), & food safety (FS)) inventory of existing frameworks for surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards, and review existing methods for evaluating these frameworks • Bring forward a map of the surveillance chain considering all sectors for each of the hazard-tracks • Identify cross-sectorial surveillance chain linkages, focusing on outputs and sharing • Propose best-practice guidelines and effective strategies for data collection, analysis, and dissemination aimed at multi-sectorial One-Health (OH) OH collaboration, for each specific hazard-track • Inventory of past work and current practice 										

- Identification of operational partners and stakeholders
- Perform a requirement analysis for national One-Health surveillance (OHS) roadmaps
- Create a Knowledge Integration Platform
- Training and dissemination
- Country-based Identification of existing cross-sectorial OHS activities
- Define the content needs for cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards

WPO: Coordination

This WP takes place over the third, fourth, and fifth annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy WP Leader: 41-SVA

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, UCPH, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 31-WBVR, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the WP: Description of the WP: This is a “housekeeping” collection of activities, to ensure project cohesiveness, efficacy, and sustainability.

Task: WPO-T1: Internal coordination

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, UCPH, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 31-WBVR, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Regular meetings to coordinate the work across WPs and weave the work of tracks into the WP-specific work.

Task: WPO-T2: External coordination and communication

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, UCPH, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 31-WBVR, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: continuous work to publish project progress updates and stay connected with other OHEJP projects (from the first and second phases), as well as external projects of relevance. Continued communication with stakeholders.

Task: WPO-T3: Data management

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 28-IZSAM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Development of a data management plan and continuous update until the end of the project.

Task: WPO-T4: Sustainability

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54
Task Leader: 13-SSI
Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA
Task Participants: 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 28-IZSAM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 41-SVA
Description of the task: Continuous identification and documentation of sustainability challenges and opportunities to address them. Sustainability here refers specifically to the maintenance of project outputs after its conclusion.

WP1: Existing frameworks and OH capacity

This WP takes place over the third, fourth, and fifth annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 10-FLI

Deputy WP Leader: 13-SSI

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 31-WBVR, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA.

Description of the WP: The aim of WP1 is to provide guidelines for adapting existing AH, PH, and FS surveillance frameworks into systems that can support sectorial surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards. This WP will therefore focus on existing relevant surveillance frameworks found within each of the three individual sectors and how these frameworks can be adapted and improved to support One- Health Surveillance (OHS) of inter-sectorial hazards. Furthermore, this WP will continue and build upon the work already undertaken in COHESIVE and ORION, as well as previous and current initiatives, such as RISKSUR, HOTLINE, STOC-FREE, SIGMA, COMPARE, and EFFORT (Illustrated in Figure 1 in the Annex). WP1 will revise frameworks within each sector, and provide input for the cross-sectorial work carried out in all other WPs.

Task: WP1-T2: Generate suggestions for adaptation of existing frameworks into a common sectorial framework (AH, PH, FS) which can support surveillance of inter-sectorial hazards (OHS)

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: 10-FLI

Deputy Task Leader: SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 31-WBVR, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA.

Description of the task:

This task is concerned specifically with providing guidelines for the adaptation/improvement of surveillance in each individual sector, but addressing specifically surveillance targeting inter-sectorial hazards (foodborne pathogens, AMR, and emerging threats). Participants of the consortium will provide their input in requirements for such a framework. Stakeholders involved in the project will be able to participate in this step and help in the development such framework for sectorial support to OHS.

WP2: Best-practices and multi-sectorial collaboration

This WP takes place over the third, fourth, and fifth annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 28-IZSAM

Deputy WP Leader: 13-SSI

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the WP: WP2 aims to provide a common framework across sectors with best-practices for data collection, analysis, and dissemination of surveillance results, and facilitate OH

collaboration across sectors. The dissemination of results, in particular, has been extensively addressed in the first round of OHEJP projects (ORION and COHESIVE), therefore MATRIX will focus more on the other steps of the surveillance continuum, and how the results brought forward by ORION and COHESIVE can be brought into surveillance practice, connecting surveillance practice to outputs dissemination.

While WP1 focuses on strengthening surveillance within each sector, to support OHS, WP2 is concerned with cross-sectorial collaboration and the operationalization of OHS surveillance as a multi-sectorial activity. The outcome is to add more value to existing surveillance related processes, with a focus on loops of feedback among sector agencies in order to inform decision making, while simultaneously avoiding duplication and overlapping processes with systems already in place. Using information generated by individual agencies to inform surveillance decision across sectors is highly dependent on effective collaboration. Therefore, the development of best-practices will be strongly supported by the development of guidelines and compilation of effective strategies for multi-sectorial collaboration. This WP is linked to WP1 and will utilise the outputs of WP1 to identify cross-sectorial linkages in order to define a common framework for OHS of inter-sectorial hazards. This information will further be utilised by WP5 and WP6.

Task: WP2-T1: Mapping of the surveillance chain across all sectors for each hazard-track

Task start month: M30

Task end month: M35

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy Task Leader: 32-FHI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Some of this work is already planned within the first round of OHEJP projects - NOVA for instance plans to deliver such a mapping for a few specific hazards and countries. It is likely that these mappings will not cover all the hazards in the MATRIX "hazard tracks", or relate to the same countries, but we will learn from their work, and complement where needed following their experience, in order to provide a full map of the surveillance chain for the hazard tracks for at least one country per hazard-track.

Task: WP2-T2: Identify cross-sectorial surveillance chain linkages, particularly, which outputs should be shared and how they should be shared for OH orientated decision making

Task start month: M36

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: 41-SVA

Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Once we have a full map of the surveillance chain for each sector, we will start identifying chain linkages e.g. which outputs of one surveillance sector could serve as inputs for decision making in another sector. The sectorial mapping of the surveillance activities will also provide a base for discussion on how sharing of information could be operationalised - timelines and mode of operation. This task will provide the input for discussions in the following task.

Task: WP2-T3: Propose best-practice guidelines and effective strategies for data collection, analysis and dissemination aimed at multi-sectorial OH collaboration, for each specific track.

Task start month: M33

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: 28-IZSAM

Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the task: This task will be concerned with developing best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration to operationalize OHS. These will address data sharing, dealing with data sharing limitations, data analysis, and interpretation and dissemination of outputs. The work in this task will be hazard specific (hazard tracks). This work will gather the conclusions from the first round of OHEJP projects, in particular the integrative ones and NOVA (focused on surveillance), and consolidate them into a suggested framework of OHS surveillance. These will cover both the aspects of collaboration among people, as well as the technical aspects for implementation. In other words, a practical guide for concrete implementation of the results of previous projects, advancing OHS practice.

Task: WP2-T4: Identify commonalities across the tracks, to propose a common OHS framework when applicable.

Task start month: M46

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Deputy Task Leader: 13-SSI

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 16-INIA, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the task: The work in the previous track will be hazard-specific. This task will be concerned with identifying the similarities among tracks, and producing a common OHS framework, which can serve as the basic foundation of OHS implementation.

WP3: Output-based surveillance evaluation

This WP takes place over the third, fourth, and fifth annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 21-APHA

Deputy WP Leader: 34-PIWET

WP participants: 12-DTU, UCPH, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 31-WBVR, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the WP: The aim of WP3 is to develop guidelines for the design, implementation, and evaluation of official controls within the food sector using output-based standards. Although legislation already allows for countries to take an output-based standards approach to surveillance, previous work within the RISKSUR project identified that few countries are currently implementing this approach, with most of the surveillance, control and monitoring programmes relying on input-based standards instead. In this context, WP3 will assess the suitability of using output-based standards for OHS using several different worked examples from the hazard specific tracks included in MATRIX. WP3 is linked with the food sector part of WP1 and WP2. The output of this WP will, where possible, be streamlined to correlate with the roles and messages of national risk managers and standard setting bodies.

Task: WP3-T2: Identification of operational partners and stakeholders

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: *Not yet replaced*

Deputy Task Leader: 34-PIWET

Task Participants: 21-APHA, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA

Description of the task: Each participating country will select the appropriate members of AH, PH and FS competent authorities as required to reflect the heterogeneity in governance of official

controls within different countries. Makeup of the operational partners will include stakeholders from design and implementation of 'official control' schemes. As the identification of operational partners is important to designing schemes suitable for the specific environment, this deliverable starts from the beginning of the project and is constantly reviewed through the life of the project.

Task: WP3-T3: Selection of appropriate output-based surveillance systems

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: 21-APHA

Deputy Task Leader: 31-WBVR

Task Participants: 12-DTU, UCPH, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 31-WBVR, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Key to the effectiveness of surveillance systems is selection of appropriate methodologies to achieve the objectives of the surveillance system. While this work is part of a wider project that is focused on One-Health activities, there may be situations where specific industry focused efforts are most effective and efficient. Each of the partners involved will select a surveillance pathogen or contaminant that is relevant to their specific situation. In some cases there may not be a single target, but a suitable system such as new and emerging diseases. Selection of an appropriate output-based methodology to suit the objectives of the surveillance system will be made by each participating country

- Surveillance sensitivity approaches
- Probability of freedom (subject to suitable models)
- Expected cost of error (novel application) with examples

Task: WP3-T4: Development of evaluation strategies for surveillance systems based on output-based metrics

Task start month: M40

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 34-PIWET & 28-IZSAM

Deputy Task Leader: 21-APHA

Task Participants: 12-DTU, UCPH, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 31-WBVR, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Having decided on the most suitable approach for a surveillance system there are a number of different parameters that require defining, for example the metric(s) to be measured, the thresholds and boundaries for the metric(s), and the frequency of evaluation. The metrics that are used within a surveillance system will directly influence how the system may be evaluated. RISKSUR has already produced a very comprehensive design tool for surveillance systems, but tailoring it for output-based surveillance will require revision and addition of modules. Operational partners within each participating country will need to agree the most appropriate output metrics that are to be used in the development of a standard. Although each country is following the same guidance, the diversity in production type and systems across the partner institutes will require an individualised approach from each partner to identifying the thresholds and boundaries of the metrics and the frequency of evaluation.

WP4: EUEpiCap

This WP takes place over the third, fourth, and fifth annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 1-ANSES

Deputy WP Leader: 23-UoS

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 10-FLI, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 16-INIA, 23-UoS, 34-PIWET

Description of the WP: The objective of WP4 is to develop a benchmarking tool "EUEpiCap" to support performance monitoring and evaluation of OH surveillance activities across MS, by sector. In practice, OHS comprises the shared collection, collation, analysis and collaborative interpretation of information produced for and by surveillance systems from diverse sectors. A truly efficient OHS would ensure that surveillance inputs (data and resources) and outputs from systems that may vary widely in scope, objectives and methods/activities are accessible, comparable and easy-to-use by other sectors. This requires identifying and characterising the processes across AH, PH and FS sectors regarding practices and resources at each step of the surveillance system (e.g. governance and coordination, data collection, collation, analysis, interpretation and dissemination of data) in order to identify barriers and best-practices towards the implementation of OH surveillance. WP4 aims to develop a generic benchmarking tool, EUEpiCap, for characterizing, monitoring and evaluating surveillance capacity and capabilities within each sector (AH, PH, FS) that supports OHS. The tool will produce country-scale profiles of surveillance interoperability between sectors and highlight needs in surveillance capabilities and capacity. Comparison of results among systems and MS will allow identification of best-practices and making recommendations to facilitate the development and implementation of OHS approaches and improve existing OHS frameworks by providing targeted advice. This tool will not include an evaluation of laboratory capacities and capabilities, which are targeted by the existing EULabCap survey tool. Close collaboration is planned, including a common workshop, between MATRIX and the proposed OH-HARMONY-CAP for laboratory capacities if both projects are funded.

Task: WP4-T1. Review of existing methods for surveillance systems evaluation

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M36

Subtask Leader: 1-ANSES

Deputy Task Leader: 23-UoS

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 16-INIA, 23-UoS, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET

Description of the task: The work will identify existing methods for surveillance systems evaluation from previous reviews (e.g. RISKSUR project for AH and PH sectors), international policy documents and standards, and other literature sources. We will also ask partners to provide results of any such evaluations previously applied in their countries. Previous reviews have identified up to 49 evaluation criteria. We will use different approaches to reduce this number of criteria to a manageable set while delivering a fair snapshot of OHS capabilities.

Task: WP4-T2. Development of the surveillance capacity benchmarking tool

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: 23-UoS

Deputy Task Leader: 1-ANSES

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 10-FLI, 16-INIA, 23-UoS, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET

Description of the task: In the development of the evaluation tool, we will deploy an array of evaluation methods ranging from semi-quantitative to quantitative. Multicriteria analyses will be implemented to derive quantitative value functions for the selected set of criteria in Task WP4-T1; critical elements of the multicriteria approaches (e.g. criteria weights) will be determined by expert-driven (e.g. multi-attribute-value models) and data-driven approaches (e.g. conjoint analysis or probabilistic inversion). In more detail, different scenarios (e.g. reflecting different hazards, levels of risk, and varying health capacities and vulnerabilities) will be presented to groups of stakeholders to derive scenario-specific weights for the criteria, thus increasing the applicability of the tool. Likewise, the suggested array of semi-quantitative and quantitative approaches will allow

comparisons between the models' outputs and provide some form of validation of our approaches. We will also develop a user-friendly interface to record data for each criterion included in the assessment. The interface will automatically generate synthetic country profile reports to facilitate diffusion of results. A tutorial will explain how to use the tool.

WP5: Outreach and roadmap

This WP takes place over the third, fourth, and fifth annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 9-BfR

Deputy WP Leader: 41-SVA

WP participants: 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the WP: The objective of WP5 is to create a roadmap for future development of national OH surveillance activities, specifically targeted at different levels of infrastructural and economic capacities. This OHS roadmap template will take into consideration: the heterogeneity of OHS capacities, resources, and developments across MS, as well as the OHS frameworks and solutions identified by WP1, WP2, WP3, and WP4. A high-level strategy that addresses opportunities for better communication, knowledge exchange and knowledge integration between OHS domains will be outlined in this WP. WP5 will set up a technical platform supporting knowledge exchange between the different MATRIX partners with close connection to the overarching EJP platform.

Task: WP5-T1: Perform a requirement analysis for national OH surveillance roadmaps

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M45

Task Leader: 13-SSI

Deputy Task Leader: 30-RIVM

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: The objective of this task is to assess the national barriers (e.g. in OHS capacity, resources and developments) preventing efficient OHS integration in the different EU Member States (MS).

Task: WP5-T2: Develop a national OH surveillance roadmap template

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 41-SVA

Deputy Task Leader: 9-BfR

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 12-DTU, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: This task entails the creation of the actual OHS roadmap template on the basis of the requirements and findings outlined in Task WP5-T1. This OHS roadmap is a high-level strategic guide (similar to a checklist), which outlines a set of key-elements needed for (future) national development of cross-sectorial and trans-disciplinary surveillance capacity. The development process of the OHS roadmap (road mapping) will be supported by four 2-3 day (physical) meetings/workshops, where experts and stakeholders from different sectors/disciplines are brought together to 1) create a common understanding of the outcomes and opportunities of the OHS roadmap template, 2) identify and align key-elements (e.g. activities, approaches, developments) needed for future OHS developments, 3) create a strategic guide, including an approach for sustainability, and 4) re-evaluate and update the strategic guide based on scenarios from the different project tasks.

Task: WP5-T3: Knowledge-Integration Platform

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 9-BfR

Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 41-SVA

Description of the task: The objective of this task is to establish a web-based Knowledge-Integration Platform to facilitate and enhance interaction/collaboration between the OHS stakeholders (e.g. EFSA and ECDC) and project members (from different disciplines, institutions and countries).

Task: WP5-T4: Training and dissemination

Task start month: M25

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 9-BfR

Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA

Task Participants: 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 32-FHI, 34-PIWET, 36-INSA, 41-SVA

Description of the task: This task will be concerned with knowledge dissemination and training.

WP6: Decision and collaboration dashboards

This WP takes place over the third, fourth, and fifth annual period of the EJP

WP start month: M25

WP end month: M54

WP Leader: 41-SVA

Deputy WP Leader: 32-FHI

WP participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 10-FLI, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the WP: WP6 will focus on visualisation of OHS inputs and outputs for the use of surveillance officials in PH, AH and FS. This will be achieved by the creation of dashboards, an information centre for collaboration and decision making in surveillance for specific hazards. The dashboards will include surveillance data from all three sectors to the extent that data accessibility agreements allow (timelines, level of aggregation and level of details). This WP will not build a data sharing platform, it will work on converting already available data into actionable information.

The ORION project has identified data sources that are already public or shared across sectors. The NOVA project is building automated routines for data analyses and visualization when trend monitoring is possible. The MATRIX project will build on these results to create an information centre where all data/information shared will have rich contextual meta-data/meta-information, allowing explicit consideration of possible pitfalls and biases when OH data is co-analysed, which is crucial for the right decision-making. Trend monitoring and signal detection will be performed and visualised jointly across sectors for specific hazards. The issue of multi-sectorial data analysis will be addressed specifically. The dashboards will include not only data and statistical outputs, but also all important surveillance information for specific zoonoses such as contact persons, workflow, and regulations, as such depicting the full OHS structure for that hazard.

Task: WP6-T2: Defining the content needs for cross-sectorial decision and collaboration dashboards

Task start month: M34

Task end month: M45

Task Leader: 41-SVA

Deputy Task Leader: 40-FOHM

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: Each participating country (at least 2) will choose one or more zoonotic pathogens from the “hazard tracks” to serve as the “case study” for dashboard construction. Surveillance officials in the sectors of AH, PH, and FS will be invited to workshops to present the dashboard concept, and spark inter-agency discussions on the possibilities and problems that can be addressed with joint analyses and/or visualization of data. Design of the dashboards will be driven from the end user perspective, that is, what information does a surveillance official need on their everyday work, and in case of emergency? What kind of data can provide that information? This will lead to a specific discussion on what kind of contextual information must be presented with the data, so that the data can lead to right conclusions even across domains/agencies. Information gaps and methodological limitations, in particular, will be documented to allow the information presented to be correctly interpreted, from their original collection context, into the OH surveillance context. Technical and legal barriers associated with data sharing across sectors will be documented. Within the timeframe of MATRIX, it is not expected that new data agreements will be put into place. Rather, we will document current possibilities and constraints, and build upon achievements from the previous integrative projects.

Task: WP6-T3: Technical implementation and testing of dashboards

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M54

Task Leader: 32-FHI

Deputy Task Leader: 41-SVA

Task Participants: 1-ANSES, 9-BfR, 13-SSI, 21-APHA, 28-IZSAM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 41-SVA

Description of the task: This task is concerned specifically with the technical implementation of the dashboards, following the vision set by task WP6-T2. Dashboards will be coded using open source tools only, and all codes made available through the deliverable. The agencies involved will share codes, and progress in parallel through regular teleconference meetings. Through collaboration with WP5 (outreach), we will ensure that the results of this WP can be available and implementable by other interested MS. The dashboards will be tested by surveillance officials from AH, PH, and FS in each country individually, and joint workshops will be organized to get feedback on user friendliness, and features to strengthen. The issue of sustainability will be addressed, documenting potential issues and suggested actions to ensure that the dashboards can remain a tool to support decision-making after the implementation phase and as cycles of surveillance continue.

Deliverables and Milestones Year 4

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-WP1.2	Description of a common framework for OH surveillance	M48
D-WP2.1	Mapping of the surveillance chain for all hazard tracks, and cross-sectorial linkages	M42
D-WP2.2	Suggested best-practices for multi-sectorial collaboration in order to achieve OHS, hazard-specific (hazard tracks)	M48
D-WP3.1	Report on the output-based surveillance system selection methodology for each country and as many of the approaches as possible	M48
D-WP4.1	Report on the selected set of criteria for evaluation of epidemiological capacities.	M39
D-WP4.2	EUEpiCap tool and tutorial	M51
D-WP5.1	Report on requirement analysis for “OHS roadmap template”	M45

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
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M-WP5.1	Knowledge-platform operational	M42
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2.4.2.1.30 JIP06- SARS-CoV2 Research Integration and Preparednes-COVRIN

The framework of this new integrative action is still under discussion with the REA and the AWP Y4 is not finalised yet.

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		IA 3.1 Response to COVID-19 pandemic								
Integrative Project Title		SARS-CoV2 Research Integration & Preparedness: Drivers for Emergence and Spread, and Risk Assessment of SARS-CoV2								
Integrative Project Acronym		COVRIN								
Leading Organisation		P31-WBVR			Deputy Leading Organisation			P23-UoS		
Project Leader		Wim van der Poel			Deputy Project leader			Dan Horton		
Project Start month		M37			Project End month			M54		
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	TBD	TBD	TBD			TBD	TBD	TBD		
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM					TBD		TBD		TBD	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	TBD				TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
PM	TBD	TBD	TBD					TBD		
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV2 To generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV2 										
WPO Coordination and communication										

T0.1: Internal project organisation:

Management of information flows; Meetings organisation,
Organisation of data sharing.

T0.2: Communication and reporting

Periodical reports; internal and external communication

T0.3: Meetings and stakeholder connection

Kick-off-, midterm- and final meeting; Interactions with stakeholders

Scoping exercise to avoid overlap with other EU funded COVID-19 activities

WP1: Detection of SARS-CoV2 in animal reservoirs and hosts, and the environment

T1.1: SARS-CoV2 spread in livestock, wildlife and pets

T1.2: Optimization and harmonization of RNA detection methods for SARS-CoV-2 detection in wildlife and environmental samples

T1.3: Definition of bioavailability of virus in fomites, water, and the environment

WP2: SARS-CoV2 characterization

T2.1: Genome analyses

Next generation sequencing

T2.2: in vitro and ex vivo biological characterization of SARS-CoV2

T2.3: Development, optimization and harmonization of animal models for SARS-CoV2 characterization

T2.4: Analyses of virus traits related to zoonotic and/or reverse zoonotic transmission

WP3: SARS-CoV2 risk assessment

T3.1: Integration of surveillance activities

wildlife, food producing animals, pets, environment incl. sewage

T3.2: Mapping of surveillance data

wildlife, food producing animals, pets, environment incl. sewage

T3.3: Risk factors for virus transmission

Wildlife reservoirs, food producing animals, environment

T3.4: Models for transmission routes and risk assessment in a One health perspective

WP4: SARS-CoV2 preparedness

T4.1: Virus –host interactions

Evolution; host adaptation

T4.2: Drivers of virus emergence

Phylodynamics; cross-species interactions, focus on zoonotic and reverse zoonotic aspects and adaptations

T4.3: Virus emergence risk modelling		
WP5:		
Deliverables - TBD		
Ref	Title	Due month
Milestones - TBD		
Ref	Title	Due month

2.4.2.1.31 Phd01-R1-AMR2-ECO-HEN

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	AMR 2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR									
PhD Project Title	Investigate the gaps in the transmission dynamics of AMR <i>E. coli</i> in commercial laying hen production									
PhD Project Acronym	ECO-HEN									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P17-UCM			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation				P12-DTU		
PhD Supervisor	Miguel A. Moreno			Deputy PhD Supervisor				Valeria Bortolaia		
PhD Start month	M14			Project End month				M49		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies (Y2, Y3, Y4, Y5)								Y4 - 2021		
Participant number	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Acronym of participant	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NCIPD	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI
PersonXmonths ¹ per participant:										
Participant number	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Acronym of participant	DTU	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA
PersonXmonths per participant:						15				
Participant number	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Acronym of participant	PHE	UoS	OKI	NIJG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr
PersonXmonths per participant:										
Participant number	32	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	
Acronym of participant	FHI	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PersonXmonths per participant										
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reveal to what extend the table egg production system represents a risk for spread of AMR to humans and the environment. • Effect of reduced antimicrobial use in the production animals on the AMR bacteria initially present in one-day chicks. 										
Description of work										

WP: WP8. Flow of AMR isolates from animals to egg shells.

WP start month: M38

WP end month: M40

WP Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy WP Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

WP participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the WP: WP8 continues based upon what was achieved during the second annual period of the OHEJP and is devoted to analyse relationships between AMR bacteria of laying hens and eggs.

Task: T8.1. Bioinformatic analysis of the WGS.

Task start month: M38

Task end month: M42

Task Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: new sequenced isolates will be examined using the same bioinformatic analysis that the previous isolates.

Task: T8.2. Data analysis and scientific manuscript preparation.

Task start month: M37

Task end month: M41

Task Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy Task Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

Task Participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the task: this task is devoted to analysis of data and preparation of a manuscript.

WP: WP9. Writing of PhD thesis.

WP start month: M42

WP end month: M48

WP Leader: M.A. Moreno (UCM)

Deputy WP Leader: V. Bortolaia (DTU)

WP participants: UCM, DTU

Description of the WP: This WP is devoted of the preparation of the doctoral thesis dissertation.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-E14-8.1.	Manuscript	M41
D-E14-9.1.	Doctoral thesis draft	M48

2.4.2.1.32 PhD02-R1-AMR2/3/6-LIN-RES

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	AMR 2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR AMR 3: Risk Assessment AMR AMR 6: Metagenomics and bioinformatics for detection and surveillance of AMR pathogens and determinants									
PhD Project Title	Investigation of the molecular basis, origin, transferability and risk factors associated with linezolid-resistance emergence in Gram-positive bacteria of human and animal origin.									
PhD Project Acronym	LIN-RES									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P4-Sciensano			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation				P4-Sciensano		
PhD Supervisor	Dr. Cécile Boland			Deputy PhD Supervisor				Dr. David Fretin		
PhD Start month	M13			Project End month				M48		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies										Y4-2021
Participant number	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Acronym of participant	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NCPD	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI
PersonXmonths per participant:			12							
Participant number	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Acronym of participant	DTU	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA
PersonXmonths per participant:										
Participant number	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Acronym of participant	PHE	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WBVR
PersonXmonths per participant:										
Participant number	32	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	
Acronym of participant	FHI	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PersonXmonths per participant										
Objectives										
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigate the molecular basis, origin, transferability and risk factors associated with linezolid-resistance emergence in Gram-positive bacteria of human and animal origin 										
Description of work										

Description of the WP:

Mention introductory: WP4 continues based upon what was achieved during the second year of the PhD (OHEJP Y3).

This WP4 aims to investigate the risk factors associated with cfr/poxxA/opxA occurrence at farm level (i.e. mainly antimicrobial consumption history, contacts with other farms).

Task: T4.1 risk factors associated with cfr/poxxA/opxA occurrence investigation at farm level

Task start month: M33

Task end month: M48

Task Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland

Deputy Task Leader: Dr. David Fretin

Task Participants: Sciensano, BfR and ANSES

Description of the task: collection of antimicrobial consumption history of farms with previous observation of linezolid resistant bacteria.

WP: WP5- Synthesis and reporting

WP start month: M45

WP end month: M48

WP Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland

Deputy WP Leader: Dr. David Fretin

WP participants

Description of the WP: Synthesis and reporting of the results of the entire LIN-RES project.

Task: T5.1 Synthesis and reporting

Task start month M45

Task end month m48

Task Leader: Dr. Cécile Boland

Deputy Task Leader: Dr. David Fretin

Task Participants:

Description of the task: Synthesis and reporting of the results of the entire LIN-RES project.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-E27-3.3	Results of laboratory experiments to demonstrate transferability of linezolid resistance genes	M48
D-E27-4.1	Summarize of the risk factors analysis (epidemiological and consumption data)	M48
D-E27-5.1	Final synthesis and reporting	M48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-E27-5	Final synthesis and reporting	M48

2.4.2.1.33 PhD03-R2-AMR2.1-HME-AMR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		AMR2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread								
PhD Project Title		Investigating the role of heavy metals in the environment as a selective pressure for the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance								
PhD Project Acronym		HME-AMR								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P26-TEAGASC			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P25-NUIG		
PhD Supervisor		Kaye Burgess			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Dearbháile Morris		
PhD Start month		M33			PhD End month			M66		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4 -2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM				12						
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM										
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The objective for this work period is to compare the resistome in low and high metal containing soils using culture dependent and independent analyses. <p>Description of work:</p>										

Selective pressures drive bacterial populations to evolve and may promote the dissemination of AMR genes, in the human and animal gut, or in the environment. However, there is limited information about the impact of selective pressures in the agri-food environment on HGT between microorganisms. One of the factors which can act as a selective pressure and can influence this HGT is the presence of heavy metals. Heavy metals occur ubiquitously in the agri-food environment and sometimes in high concentrations in soil. Very limited information is available regarding the impact of selective pressures such as heavy metals which may be present in the environment on the mobilisation of antimicrobial resistance and its potential transfer into the food chain.

Culture based analysis will screen for the presence of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase producing *Enterobacteriaceae*, fluoroquinolone resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* and carbapenemase producing *Enterobacteriaceae* on selective agars, using methodologies in place. Isolates will be identified by MALDI-TOF and screened for resistance to a panel of antimicrobials and heavy metals. A representative sample set from each study will be utilised in a shotgun metagenomic study to characterise the wider resistome.

Sampling sites will be determined by collaboration with Geological Survey Ireland and with an ongoing research project which is investigating the impact of land application of zinc on sites for production of food crops. This will ensure an expedited sampling process.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
	Report on AMR bacteria present in soils of differing heavy metal content	M46

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
	SOP in place for sampling culture based analysis	M38
	Sequences of sufficient quality obtained from metagenomic analysis	M46

2.4.2.1.34 PhD04-R2-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		AMR 2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread								
PhD Project Title		Exploring the evolutionary success of the antibiotic resistant Salmonella Kentucky ST198								
PhD Supervising Organisation		KENTUCKY								
PhD Supervisor		P4-Sciensano			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P19-INRAE		
PhD Coordinator person name		Ceyssens			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Doublet		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M57		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies		Y4-2021								
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM			12							
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
PM						39	40	41		

Objectives:

Salmonella enterica serovar Kentucky (*S. Kentucky*) is a common causative agent of gastroenteritis in humans. It is one of most notorious *Salmonella* serotypes, as it is strongly associated with antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

In this project, we will investigate (i) what explains the evolutionary success of the multidrug resistant *S. Kentucky* ST198 clone, (ii) what is the mechanisms of the integration (and potential further transfer) of the ESBL gene in its chromosome, and (iii) Are there genetic determinants of different human-animal host ranges in epidemic *S. Kentucky* ST198 and ST152?

Description of work:

In the second year of the PhD project (Y4), the candidate will explore more subtle variations which might contribute to epidemic success based on Differential Gene Expression experiments. We will expose the four strains to conditions that simulate the intestinal tract (low pH, anaerobic shock, anaerobic growth, osmotic shock, iron limitation) and mimic stresses endured during intracellular growth (e.g. in macrophages) by administering oxidative stress, nitrogen shock, phosphate limitation and magnesium limitation. Total RNA will be isolated and sequenced, followed by statistical quantitative analysis using EdgeR. This will be done at Sciensano (BE).

Moreover, he/she will finalize the study of epidemically successful associations between identified MGEs and *S. Kentucky* will be in vitro investigated by analysing conjugative efficiencies, cell biology transfer dynamics, maintenance (addiction systems), incompatibility/exclusion, cooperation (i.e. conjugative mobilization) and fitness in the different genetic backgrounds. This part will be performed at INRAE (FR).

In the meantime and based on these results, a selection of full length (active) prophages and plasmids as well as their individual ORFan genes (on inducible expression vectors) will be transferred to a prophage- and plasmid-cured *S. enterica* host strain in order to systematically study their elicited interactions and phenotypes. This will be done at the laboratory of Prof. Aertsen (KU Leuven, BE).

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D5	Peer-reviewed paper: Genetic variation within the MDR <i>S. Kentucky</i> ST198 lineage	48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M4	Finalization of characterization of MGEs and selection of elements for further study at KULeuven	46

2.4.2.1.35 Phd05-R2-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		AMR 2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animal populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR AMR 6.1: Development of NGS-based tools for surveillance of AMR in Enterobacteriaceae in animals, humans and the environment ET 5: Ecology of emerging pathogens								
PhD Project Title		Metagenomics and genomic approaches for the prevention of the spread of plazomicin resistance in humans, animals and the environment								
PhD Project Acronym		METAPRO								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P17-UCM			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P23-UoS		
PhD Supervisor		Bruno Gonzalez Zorn			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Roberto La Ragione		
PhD Start month		M22			PhD End month			M60		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4-2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM					14					
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM										

Objectives:

- Metagenomic analysis of the samples from the first sampling
- Isolation and genomic analysis of Enterobacteria harbouring plazomicin resistance determinants from the first sampling
- Design and execution of a second sampling and proceed with the sequencing

Description of work:

Sequencing of the metagenome of the different samples will be performed and the prevalence of plazomicin resistance determinants will be assessed. Further analysis of the metagenomic data obtained will be carried out. Simultaneously, isolation of enterobacteria in plazomicin selective media will be undertaken. Up to ten enterobacteria from each site will be subjected to MALDI-TOF for their identification and to antimicrobial resistance profiling. Bacteria differing in either characteristic will be subjected to Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) using a hybrid long read-short read approach. Data obtained from both studies will be bioinformatically analysed.

Additionally, a second sampling will be designed and executed, and by the end of the year is intended to have the sequencing of both the metagenome and the enterobacteria completed.

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS	Metagenome sequencing of the first sampling	M39
MS	Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the first sampling	M39
MS	Design of the second sampling	M42
MS	Second sampling execution	M45
MS	Metagenome sequencing of the second sampling	M48
MS	Enterobacteria isolation and WGS from the second sampling	M48
MS	Analysis of the genomic and metagenomic data from the first sampling	M48

2.4.2.1.36 PhD06-R1-ET5-PEMbo

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	ET 5: Ecology of emerging pathogens									
PhD Project Title	From genotype to phenotype: patho-evolution of French strains of <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i>.									
PhD Project Acronym	PEMbo									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P1-ANSES			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation				N/A		
PhD Supervisor	Boschioli Maria Laura			Deputy PhD Supervisor				N/A		
PhD Start month	M22			Project End month				M58		
Y4-2021										
Participant number	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Acronym of participant	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NCIPD	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI
PersonXmonths ¹ per participant :	12									
Participant number	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Acronym of participant	DTU	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA
PersonXmonths per participant:										
Participant number	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Acronym of participant	PHE	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAMI	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR
PersonXmonths per participant:										
Participant number	32	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	
Acronym of participant	FHI	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PersonXmonths per participant										
Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obtaining reference sequences by Illumina / PacBio sequencing of strains belonging to main clonal groups • Identification of genomic events (insertion / deletion or broad sequence polymorphism (LSP)) by comparison study of genetic variation: analysis focused on the study of 182 virulence genes, genes involved in envelope biosynthesis and the study of excreted antigens. • Study of the antigenic variation: biochemical and lipidomic analyses of the strains 										
Description of work										

WP2: Genome sequence analysis

WP2 start month: M9

WP2 end month: M24

WP2 Leader: Boschiroli Maria Laura

Deputy WP2 Leader : Lorraine Michelet

WP2 participants: PhD student

Description of the WP2: The genomic data (87 genomes) already available at the NRL will be supplemented by sequencing (Illumina) additional strains in order to extend the panel of isolated strains from various hosts, from different foci of different locations but also of "modern" versus "old" strains. An overall analysis will be performed by comparing these data with the new reference sequences generated in WP1 to identify variants (SNPs) as well as other genetic events (deletion, insertions and LSPs). A genome-wide analysis will be also carried out focusing on the selection of 182 virulence genes. Strains showing interesting profiles or particular mutations profiles in those genes will be selected to for further *in vitro* analysis (WP3).

Task-2.2: Genomic markers analysis

Task-2.2 start month: M13

Task-2.2 end month: M24

Task-2.2 Participants: PhD student

Description of the task-2.2: Potential SNPs and insertion/deletion (in/del), which differentiate the selected strains will be identified. SNP will be screened and sorting using information in the whole genome including intergenic, synonymous and non-synonymous mutations. The total number of nonsynonymous and synonymous sites in the SNP-affected genes will be determined and sorted using Bionumerics software 7.0 and command line. Values of dN/dS will be calculated according to the formula $(N/n)/(S/s)$, in which N = the number of nonsynonymous SNPs, n = the number of nonsynonymous sites, S = the number of synonymous SNPs, and s = the number of synonymous sites. A dN/dS calculation will be used to compare selection pressures at an individual isolate level. Concatenated SNPs will be used to create a maximum likelihood phylogenetic tree using MEGA 4.1 software. A selection of 182 virulence genes, involved in envelope biosynthesis and excreted antigen (targeted genes: lipoprotein (lppO, lppT, lppG, lppM, lppA and rpfA), genes involved in host tropism (PE-PGRS genes and PPE genes), the ESAT-6 family of secreted antigens (Mb3919c and Mb3935c), the genes involved in the variability of parietal lipids, polyketide synthases (pks) and transporter (mmpSL)) will be deeply analysed. SNPs identified in these genes will be criteria for the selection of strains which will be further characterized in WP3.

WP3: Analysis of the antigenic variability: biochemical and lipidomic studies

WP3 start month: M21

WP3 end month: M30

WP3 Leader: Biet Franck

Deputy WP3 Leader: Boschiroli Maria Laura

WP3 participants: PhD student, Thierry Cochard

Description of the WP3: The strains selected according to their potential for antigenic variation (WP2) and their epidemiological characteristics will be analysed by biochemical approaches.

Task-3.1: Protein profiles determination

Task-3.1 start month: M21

Task-3.1 end month: M30

Task-3.1 Participants: PhD student, Thierry Cochard

Description of the task-3.1: analysis of protein profiles by SDS PAGE Western blot using a collection of sera from animals of different infectious status

Task-3.2: Lipidomic analyses

Task-3.2 start month: M21

Task-3.2 end month: M30

Task-3.2 Participants: PhD student, Thierry Cochard

Description of the task-3.2: lipid analyses by thin layer chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry analyses.

WP4: Valorisation and dissemination of results

WP4 start month: M17

WP4 end month: M36

WP4 Leader: Boschiroli Maria Laura

Deputy WP4 Leader: Lorraine Michelet

WP4 participants: PhD student

Description of the WP4: This WP is dedicated to the dissemination of all the results obtained in the other WPs to the scientific community, either by the publication of articles in international open access journals or by the participation at international scientific meetings. Writing of the PhD manuscript is the final step of the project.

Task-4.1: Publication of results

Task-4.1 start month: M21

Task-4.1 end month: M36

Task-4.1 Participants: PhD student

Description of the task-4.1: writing of scientific papers for publication in international open access journals and publication of genomic data in international databases.

Task-4.2: Communication

Task-4.2 start month: M17

Task-4.2 end month: M34

Task-4.2 Participants: PhD student

Description of the task-4.2: Participation at international scientific meetings to present the results of the different WP.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-E5-2	Second steering committee report	M38
D-E5-3	Oral communication at a congress	M38
D-E5-4	Publication in an international journal (in prep or submitted)	M44

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-E5-5	Strain selection for WP3	M40
M-E5-6	SNP matrix	M44
M-E5-7	List of SNP in virulence genes	M44

2.4.2.1.37 PhD07-R2-ET2.1-MACE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		ET 2.1: Evaluation of early detection methods for emerging threats								
PhD Project Title		Mathematical models and economic evaluation for cystic echinococcosis control and elimination								
PhD Project Acronym		MACE								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P23-UoS			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P27-ISS		
PhD Supervisor		Joaquin Prada			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Adriano Casulli		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M57		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4-2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	NVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM	13									
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA		
PM										
<p>Objectives:</p> <p>1) Assess surveillance streams to monitor impact of control measures towards CE control and elimination.</p> <p>2) Adapt the model to Albanian setting.</p> <p>Description of work:</p>										

The model outcomes from the previous year will be fine-scale risk maps of CE. The framework will be used to better understand surveillance needs and assess different control strategies, allowing for accurate and effective quantitative risk analysis to be performed. It will be extended for robust economic analysis and cost effectiveness of the different surveillance and control alternatives.

We anticipate some of the data from the survey in Albania will be available during this period for analysis and the model could be adapted to this setting.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
MACE.Y4.1	Final draft of publication with the control scenarios	M40
MACE.Y4.2	Draft of economic analysis	M44
MACE.Y4.3	Model of CE extended to include economic aspects	M44

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MACE.Y4.A	Fitted model of CE with economic evaluation	M44
MACE.Y4.B	Exploration of Albanian data	M40

2.4.2.1.38 PhD08-R2-ET5.1/4.1/FBZSH3-DESIRE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		ET 5.1: The role of wildlife in the ecology of potentially zoonotic emerging threats ET 4.1: Host factors associated with increased susceptibility to infection and disease of emerging threats with undefined routes of transmission FBZ-SH 3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance considering also the environment and non-livestock reservoirs (e.g. pets and wildlife) as sources								
PhD Project Title		Developing Evidence-based Surveillance for emerging Rat-borne zoonoses in changing Environments								
PhD Supervising Organisation		DESIRE (Developing Evidence-based Surveillance for emerging Rat-borne zoonoses in changing Environments)								
PhD Supervisor		P30-RIVM			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P31-Wbvr		
PhD Coordinator person name		Miriam Maas			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Wim van der Poel		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M68		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies								Y4-2021		
Partici pant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM*										
Partici pant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Partici pant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UOS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM								3		
Partici pant	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41		
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISpV	SLV	FOHM	SVA		
PM										

Objectives:

This year the field study will continue (two years in total), which will deliver samples for both hypothesis 2 and 4. The collection of monitoring data by app is continued.

Description of work:

1) Continuation of activities in Y2, further collection of data with the mobile application.
2) Field study to test rats from various urban environments. Brown and black rats will be captured in collaboration with professional rat control agencies from contrasting populations and study areas in cities and rural environments. Using both NGS and non-NGS methods, the pathobiome will be described and compared for these different populations.

Visit to collaborating partners to test samples and to learn additional techniques.

3) Development of the risk-analysis model, and further collection of data before analysis is finalised
4) A comparative study between cities and neighbourhoods within cities will be performed. The PhD candidate will trap rats in areas that range widely in the amount of greenness/blueness, and in the level of rat trapping/control. Questions addressed include the following: Do neighbourhoods with more greenspace and water have higher rat populations? What differences are seen between various types of green areas? How do human activities (work, residential and recreational) affect rat activity in a particular area? Which adaptations are needed to prevent rat population outbreaks? Do areas with rat trapping/control have lower pathogen occurrence and prevalence?

The PhD candidate will join the Wageningen University International graduate school for Agricultural Sciences (WIAS) for courses and training.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D2	Comparative study between cities and neighbourhoods for rat and rat-borne diseases.	M45
D5	An international, peer reviewed publication about the effect of city greening on rat populations and related public health risks.	M45

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M3	Visit laboratories of partner institutes WBVR and FLI	June (M42)

2.4.2.1.39 PhD09-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ-SH 3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance considering also the environment and non-livestock reservoirs (e.g. pets and wildlife) as sources. AMR2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer in humans, animals and the environment, including epidemiology of resistant microorganisms and antimicrobials in the environment and their (environment-mediated) spread								
PhD Project Title		Understanding the development of fluoroquinolone (FQ) resistance in <i>Campylobacter</i> present in broilers and the risks of FQ resistance persisting through the food-chain to cause disease in people								
PhD Project Acronym		UDoFRiC								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P21-APHA			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P1-ANSES		
PhD Supervisor		John Rodgers			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Isabelle Kempf/Katell Rivoal		
PhD Start month		M27			PhD End month			M62		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4-2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM									12	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM										

Objectives:

- 1) MIC determination for *Campylobacter* to fill data gaps for phenotypic characterisation.
- 2) WGS sequence of *Campylobacter* and predicted resistance determination to complete data gaps.
- 3) Description of the diversity of FQ resistance and acquisition of resistance variants over time.
- 4) Describe relationship between WGS and phenotype for FQ resistance.
- 5) Genome Wide Association Studies (GWAS) to assess if FQ resistant *Campylobacter* isolates in broilers are linked to disease in people.
- 6) Assess the fitness of FQ resistant variants of *Campylobacter* from broiler using *in vitro* growth models.

Description of work:

1) MIC determination for *Campylobacter* to fill data gaps in phenotypic characterisation. Competence in bacterial culture and MIC testing methodology will be acquired. Isolates identified for phenotyping will be MIC tested.

2) WGS sequence of *Campylobacter* and predicted resistance determination to complete data gaps. Competence in WGS methodology including sample preparation, processing and data handling and analysis will be acquired. Isolates identified for WGS will be processed and analysed.

3) Description of the diversity of FQ resistance and acquisition of resistance variants over time. A full description of resistance genes present for FQ in the collated dataset will be undertaken, this report will examine the temporal trends in the acquisition of these resistance genes. The diversity of resistance genes present in *Campylobacter* from difference locations or sources will also be described.

4) The relationship between WGS and phenotype for FQ resistance. Using the available WGS and phenotyping data, the relationship between WGS and MIC phenotype will be explored. This will examine the performance of resistance predicting pipelines, relationship between MIC and WGS may be examined.

5) GWAS to assess if FQ resistant *Campylobacter* isolates in broilers are linked to disease in people. GWAS will be constructed using WGS data from *Campylobacter* isolates from broiler sources and from clinical cases to assess if particular resistance variants are linked to disease in people.

6) Assess the fitness of FQ resistant variants of *Campylobacter* from broilers using *in vitro* growth models.

Resistance variants that are identified as persisting in broilers when there is less selective pressure through FQ use (temporal trends post 2014) and/or variants that are associated with disease in people (GWAS) will be assessed in fitness model experiments. Fitness will initially assessed using an *in vitro* growth models before proceeding to survival and colonisation models in the next year of the project.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
3	Annual review	Feb 2021
4	Description of the diversity of FQ resistance and acquisition of resistance variants over time.	May 2021
5	Report on the relationship between WGS and phenotype.	June 2021
6	9 month review	Sept 2021

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
6	PhD Annual Review	Feb 2021

7	Completion of phenotypic and WGS data generation to fill data-gaps	March 2021
8	Description of the diversity of FQ resistance and acquisition of resistance variants over time.	May 2021
9	Report on the relationship between WGS and phenotype.	June 2021
10	9 month review	Sept 2021
11	GWAS	Sept 2021
12	Growth trials	Dec 2021

2.4.2.1.40 Phd10-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ-SH 3: Source attribution of bacterial foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance. AMR 2.1: Dynamics of AMR selection, clonal spread and horizontal gene transfer.								
PhD Project Title		Contribution of wild birds to AMR in the environment and on farm.								
PhD Project Acronym		WILBR								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P21-APHA			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P41-SVA		
PhD Supervisor		Muna Anjum			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Stefan Borjesson		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M57		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4-2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM									14,9	
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PM										
Objectives for Y2 of PhD: 1) Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study Collection of faecal samples from pigs and gulls will provide insight into each species microbiome as we can isolate bacteria from the samples and carry out phenotypic and genotypic testing to identify levels of AMR in the populations. 2) Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance										

Molecular analysis of isolates will allow bacterial species to be identified and any resistance profiles to be established. Comparisons can then be drawn between isolates from pigs, and isolates from gulls.

3) Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR.

Further characterisation will make it possible to identify if any of the antimicrobial resistance genes are mobile, and if so which mobile genetic elements (MGE) they are located on. Carrying out this analysis on pig and gull isolates would allow us to see if any MGEs are being found in both populations, inferring a transfer of resistance.

Description of work:

1) Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study

The farms successfully recruited for the longitudinal study will be visited twice and an as of yet undecided number of pig faecal samples will be collected. In collaboration with the wildlife team based at Sand Hutton (York) gull faeces will be identified from the environment and collected.

2) Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance.

Enterobacteriaceae will be isolated from faecal samples collected using selective media. Isolates will undergo short-read sequencing and analysed using several bioinformatics programmes and pipelines to identify species and the presence of AMR determinants.

3) Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR.

Further bioinformatics analysis will help identify any MGEs. Long-read sequencing of any isolates harbouring resistance to critically important antibiotics on MGEs or multi-drug resistant MGEs can undergo long-read sequencing in order to circularise any plasmids.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
1	Completion of 9 month review	M45
2	Completion of 12 month review	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
1	Collection of microbiological samples for longitudinal study	M48
2	Molecular analysis of bacterial isolates and antimicrobial resistance	M48
3	Characterisation of mobile elements transmitting/proliferating AMR	M48
4	Completion of 9 month review	M45
5	Completion of 12 month review	M48

2.4.2.1.41 PhD11-R1-FBZ4/5- EnvDis

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)	FBZ 4: Source attribution and transmission routes FBZ 5: Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics									
PhD Project Title	Environment and Foodborne Zoonosis: Linking Mechanism and Phenomenology									
PhD Project Acronym	EnvDis									
PhD Supervising Organisation	P23-UoS			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation				P23-UoS		
PhD Supervisor	Giovanni (Gianni) Lo Iacono			Deputy PhD Supervisor				Alasdair (Alex) Cook		
PhD Start month	M24			Project End month				M57		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies (Y2, Y3, Y4, Y5)	Y4-2021									
Participant number	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Acronym of participant	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NCIPD	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI
PersonXmonths ¹ per participant:										
Participant number	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Acronym of participant	DTU	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA
PersonXmonths per participant:										
Participant number	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Acronym of participant	PHE	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR
PersonXmonths per participant:		12								
Participant number	32	33	34	35	36	37	39	40	41	
Acronym of participant	FHI	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PersonXmonths per participant										
Objectives (for all years)										
<p>01. Can we identify and access “big data” – existing information that can be interrogated to yield new evidence for decision-making in One Health? The generation of new analytical approaches would provide tools that could then be adapted to specific animal or human health issues where environment plays a key role in aetiology.</p> <p>02. Can we identify the key environmental processes triggering and propagating zoonoses?</p> <p>03. Can we disentangle the role of animal, human (including socio-economic factors) and environmental factors in zoonoses?</p>										

- 04.** Can we identify the delay between variations in the environment (e.g. increase in the temperature or behavioural change) and the occurrence of a foodborne outbreak?
- 05.** How can we quantify their impact on Animal and Public Health?

Description of work

WP1

WP start month: January 2019 (13M)

WP end month: December 2021 (48M)

WP Leader Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy WP Leader: Alex Cook

WP participants: PhD Student

Description of the WP:

To develop a general tool to assess the risk of infectious diseases (in particular zoonosis) when we have information of relevant environmental factors.

Task: ii) Test and discuss findings of the model for Salmonellosis; Complete the same tasks for Leptospirosis; write up thesis.

Task start month: 36M

Task end month: 48M

Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: PhD Student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Description of the task:

Sub-Task: Test and discuss findings of the model for Salmonellosis

Sub-Task start month: 36M

Sub-Task end month: 40M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: PhD Student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Sub-Task Complete the same tasks for Leptospirosis

Sub-Task start month: 40M

Sub-Task end month: 44M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: PhD Student, Alex Cook, Gianni Lo Iacono

Sub-Task: Write up thesis

Sub-Task start month: 36M

Sub-Task end month: 48M

Sub-Task Leader: Gianni Lo Iacono

Deputy Task Leader: Alex Cook

Task Participants: PhD Student

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-6.7	Presentation of findings (e.g. conferences, internal school seminars)	48

D-6.8	End of Year Confirmation Report	48
D-6.9	Completion/Submission of thesis	48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-6.8	Test and discuss findings of the model for Salmonellosis	40
M-6.9	Complete the same tasks for Leptospirosis	44
M-6.10	Write up thesis	48

2.4.2.1.42 PhD12-R2-FBZSH9-AptaTrich

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ-SH 9: Better tools for detection and investigation of foodborne outbreaks, including antimicrobial resistant pathogens, as well as economic assessments of potentially increased cluster detection through whole genome sequencing								
PhD Project Title		Development of an aptamer-based test for <i>Trichinella</i> detection								
PhD Project Acronym		AptaTrich								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P1-Anses			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P9-BfR		
PhD Supervisor		Gregory Karadjian			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Anne Mayer-Scholl		
PhD Start month		M22			PhD End month			M57		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4 - 2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Agcs	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	12									
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM										
<p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To select aptamers on <i>T. spiralis</i> whole larvae - To produce stage specific proteins and apply protein-SELEX <p>Description of work:</p> <p>In year 3, all the work will be done at Anses laboratory of Maisons-Alfort. Selection of a DNA-based aptamers set specific for <i>Trichinella spiralis</i> (<i>T. spiralis</i>) whole Muscle Larvae (ML) will be performed using a DNA library by SELEX method (Systematic Evolution of Ligands</p>										

by Enrichment) at ANSES. Intact *T. spiralis* whole ML will be incubated with the DNA library for multiple rounds (>10) with a progressive decrease in ML number and interaction time at each round. Negative selection will be performed to avoid cross-reactivity using larvae from related organisms (i.e. *Toxocara* spp., *Strongyloides stercoralis*, ...).

As it is very important to select aptamers against early and late *T. spiralis* expressed proteins, recombinant stage specific proteins will be expressed and protein-SELEX method will be applied on these recombinant proteins.

At each round of the two SELEX methods, the quantity of the different aptamers selected will be evaluated by qPCR, using the number of melting peaks to quantify. The number of cycles to obtain less than ten aptamers by selection will be defined.

During each cycle round, a PCR step will allow to amplify the aptamers in each set including a FAM staining. At the fifth cycle, the capacity of the aptamers to bind *Trichinella* larvae will be assayed by contact and looked at confocal microscope.

Objectives:

- To identify the aptamers selected in Year 3
- To identify the best aptamer binding to *Trichinella spiralis* ML or protein (super-aptamer(s))
- Redaction of a scientific article on the selection, identification of the super-aptamer (s)
- To select and prepare a protocol for the diagnostic test development

Description of work:

The aptamers identification will be performed by Next-Generation-Sequencing at Mc Gill University (extra EJP partner).

Then, at Anses, the different aptamers identified will be ordered individually, modified with FAM label to allow staining larvae with the different FAM-aptamers. The aptamers (s) with the highest affinity for their target (super-aptamer (s)) will be selected for the development of the future application in the diagnostic test.

An article on the selection and identification of *T. spiralis* aptamers will be submitted to a peer-review journal.

BfR partner will select the best test to develop (ELONA, ELASA, ...) according to the number and nature of the selected aptamers (s).

The super-aptamer (s) will be ordered with and without a biotin label, and a protocol for use in serological assays will be developed.

Deliverables	Title	Due month
Ref	Title	Due month
D-4	<i>T. spiralis</i> super-aptamers are identified	42
D-5	Article submitted to peer-review journal	46
Milestones	Title	Due month
Ref	Title	Due month
M-4	Aptamers in the set are identified	39
M-5	Selection and development of a protocol for test development	48

2.4.2.1.43 Phd13-R2-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 8: Model Systems (in vitro and in vivo) to study host/food – microbe interactions AMR 2: Epidemiological studies into the dynamics of AMR in human and animals populations and the environment including horizontal gene transfer and selection of AMR								
PhD Project Title		<i>In Vitro</i> and <i>In Vivo</i> analyses and MODulation of the chicken GUT microbiome to combat AMR.								
PhD Project Acronym		VIMOGUT-AMR								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P31-WbvR			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P21-APHA		
PhD Supervisor		Michael Brouwer			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Muna Anjum		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M68		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4-2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RVM	WbvR	FHI
PM									9,82	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PM										

Objectives:

- Perform 16S sequencing and analysis of caecal samples from OH-EJP VIMOGUT.
- Carry out experiments in the *in vitro* model to test ESBL *E. coli* colonisation intervention strategies.
- Carry out experiments in the *in vitro* model to test the transfer range of ESBL plasmids within the microbiome.

Description of work:

During this year, the microbiome analysis will be performed, analysed and written into a manuscript, describing more in-depth how the relationship is between the developing chicken gut microbiome and colonisation by ESBL *E. coli*. Samples that were collected from different broiler farms and flocks during VIMOGUT-AMR in year 3 are analysed.

The *in vitro* chicken gut model will be completely operational by this time. Based on the literature study that was performed, the most promising intervention strategies to prevent ESBL *E. coli* colonisation in the chicken gut model will be tested. Furthermore, the model will be used to analyse the transfer of ESBL plasmids through the *in vitro* microbiome to study the transfer range of different plasmid types.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D2	Manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.	48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M8	Perform 16S sequencing and analysis of caecal samples from OH-EJP VIMOGUT.	42
M9	Write manuscript on relationship between chicken gut microbiome maturation and ESBL colonisation over several farms.	48

2.4.2.1.44 PhD14-R2-FBZ4-ToxSauQMRA

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 4: Source attribution and transmission routes								
PhD Project Title		Study of the tropism and persistence of Toxoplasma gondii: from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham, a quantitative risk assessment								
PhD Project Acronym		ToxSauQMRA								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P1-ANSES			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P30-RIVM		
PhD Supervisor		Pascal BOIREAU			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Joke VAN DER GIESSEN		
PhD Start month		M22			PhD End month			M57		
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4-2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM	8,36									
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INI/AV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHM	SVA	
PM										

Objectives:

“What is the attributable part of the traditional raw pork products in the human Toxoplasma infection? “

Following the scientific question, the present research project aims to respond, based on three main areas of study consisting of (i) a thorough investigation of *T.gondii* predilection sites in experimentally infested pig carcasses with two different stages (tissue-cyst versus oocyst) (WP1); (ii) evaluate the impact of the manufacturing process (including different incorporation rates of nitrites and NaCl) and the conservation of dry sausage on the viability of *T. gondii* (WP2); (iii) a quantitative microbiological risk assessment analysis to be conducted for the various raw pork products (dry sausage, dry ham, etc) (WP3).

Description of work:

The work is organized into 3 work packages (WPs) with tasks (T). The 3-year project spans over four Annual Periods (Y2-Y5) and is described in four Work Plans.

WP2 - Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii* during the production and storage of dry sausages and dry ham

WP start month M26 - WP end month M42

WP participants ANSES, Institut du Porc, Université de Champagne-Ardennes, INRAE Corte

WP2-T2: Assessment of the persistence of *T. gondii*

Task start month M27 - Task end month M42

WP2-T2 takes place over the third and the fourth year of the project. During Y4, the main focus is the analyse of the dry ham for the detection and quantification of *T. gondii* by quantitative PCR, Magnetic Capture PCR and mouse bioassay.

WP3 - Quantitative microbiological risk assessment

WP start month M37 - WP end month M57

WP participants ANSES, RIVM

WP3-T1 Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* in various dry pork delicatessen

Task start month M37 - Task end month M42

WP3-T1 takes place over the fourth and the fifth year of the project. During Y4, the main focus is the review of the prevalence data of *T.gondii* in pork delicatessen. Therefore data from various studies involving long-last processing pork delicatessen (Jambon de Parme; Jambon Serrano, etc) will be collated, building on the systematic reviews performed for EFSA and EJP Toxosources. Data will be analysed by Bayesian hierarchical modelling to estimate the prevalence by speciality and technical parameters.

WP3-T2 QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections

Task start month M43 - Task end month M57

WP3-T2 takes place over the fourth and the fifth year of the project. During Y4, the main focus is building the QMRA model and running it. The existing meatborne QMRA model will be adapted to include various pork delicatessens/various tissues and fit to consumption data that is specifically collected for this purpose within WP2-T3 of the EJP Toxosources. In addition, sensitivity analyses (to identify the most influential input parameters) and scenario analyses (in case of large uncertainty regarding input parameters) will be initiated.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-WP2.2	Final report on the <i>T.gondii</i> detection in collected tissues after processing	M46
D-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-WP3.1	Report on prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> in various dry pork delicatessen	M46
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-01	Data on quantitative PCR, Magnetic-capture PCR and mouse bioassay on tested tissues after processing to be collected	M46
M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-02	Prevalence of <i>T.gondii</i> in relevant meat products to be collected	M46
M-PhD-ToxSauQMRA-03	Prevalence of <i>T.gondii</i> in relevant meat products is provided as input to QMRA	M51

2.4.2.1.45 Phd15-R2-FBZ5-TRACE

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 5: Epidemiological studies: risk factors and dynamics								
PhD Project Title		Tracking the public health hazard of foodborne Hepatitis E								
PhD Project Acronym		TRACE (TRacking publiC health risk of hepatisE)								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P30-RIVM			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation			P31-Wbvr		
PhD Supervisor		Eelco Franz			Deputy PhD Supervisor			Wim van der Poel		
PhD Start month		M21			PhD End month			M66		
Indicate for which annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM										
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	Wbvr	FHI
PM								1,58	3,29	
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PM										
<p>Objectives: Identification of virulence genes and elucidation of the relationship between quasispecies and changing virulence of circulating HEV strains</p> <p>Description of work:</p>										

We will use genome-wide association procedures to identify genomic regions associated with HEV virulence and HEV infectivity by linking genomic data to available epidemiological data: population incidence of patients with acute hepatitis, and asymptomatic RNA positivity among blood donors, clinical data (i.e. presence/absence of symptoms, disease severity) and veterinary data.

If we want to know on which point a certain mutation is introduced in the virus we need to look for quasispecies of the virus and not only at het consensus sequences. Such can play an important role in the changing virulence of the virus. Unchanging consensus sequences do not mean absence of mutation rate, but a continuous replacement of the mutation pool with an identical consensus. When the equilibrium of the consensus pool will change, the consensus sequence will change. The cloud of quasispecies sequences can change during selective forces (immune response, antiviral agents, environment, etc.). By looking into the quasispecies of the sequences we aim find the underlying non dominant sequences which can play an important role in the change of virulence of the virus. HEV quasispecies evolution will also be analyzed during experimental infection using deep sequencing methods (related PhD project at ANSES, supervisor Dr. Nicole Pavio) and the results from this work will be compared with the data from natural clinical samples.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D3	Publication on identification of virulence genes and elucidation of the relationship between quasispecies and changing virulence of circulating HEV strains	48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
N/A		

2.4.2.1.46 PhD16-R2-FB22/AMR6.1-Codes4strains

Reference to the Strategic Research Agenda (please refer to D2.7)		FBZ 2: Development and harmonisation of NGS-based methods for detection and tracing of FBZ agents, emerging threats and AMR determinants AMR 6.1: Development of NGS-based tools for surveillance of AMR in Enterobacteriaceae in animals, humans and the environment								
PhD Project Title		Tracking bacterial pathogens through sources, geography and time using stable phylogenetically-informative genome codes								
PhD Project Acronym		Codes4strains								
PhD Supervising Organisation		P20-IP			Deputy PhD Supervising Organisation				N/A	
PhD Supervisor		Sylvain Brisse			Deputy PhD Supervisor				N/A	
PhD Start month		M22			PhD End month				M57	
Annual period of the OHEJP the PhD work plan applies									Y4 - 2021	
Participant	1	2	4	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BFR	FLI	RKI	DTU
PM										
Participant	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	PHE
PM								12		
Participant	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
	UoS	OKI	NIJG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	FHI
PM										
Participant	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PM										

Objectives:

Simulate genomic evolution and use the three approaches to encode resulting evolved genomes; compare resulting codes with expectations

Write publication on LINcodes concept and implementation with comparison with cgMLST and SNAperDB approaches

Description of work:

After having analysed large real datasets in previous quarters, we will use simulated evolved genomes to test the ability of the three coding methods to recover the right phylogenetic relationships.

We will then write up the publication on LINcodes approach based on real and simulated genomic data.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D4.1	Simulated dataset analysed	M42
D4.2	Publication on LINcode approach and comparison with cgMLST and SNP address approaches	M48
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
M4.1	Simulations completed	M42
M4.2	Publication submitted	M48

2.4.2.1.47 Summer School 2021

Summer School Title	Summer School 2021 'Environmental issues in One Health: from risk assessment to surveillance'										
Summer School Acronym	SS2021Env										
Summer School Organising Institute	P27-ISS			Deputy Summer School Organising Institute				N/A			
Summer School Coordinator	Umberto Agrimi			Deputy Summer School Coordinator				N/A			
Summer School Start Month	M31			Summer School End Month				M34			
Participant number	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
Acronym of participant	Anses	Ages	Sciensano	NCIPD	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI	
PersonXmonths per participant:											
Participant number	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	
Acronym of participant	DTU	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA	
PersonXmonths per participant:											
Participant number	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	
Acronym of participant	PHE	UoS	OKI	NIJG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR	
PersonXmonths per participant:						0					
Participant number	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	
Acronym of participant	FHI	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA	
PersonXmonths per participant											
Objectives											
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build-up the first training initiative of the OHEJP entirely devoted to environmental issues. • Bring together different domains/disciplines within and between countries on environmental aspects of OH • Supporting OHEJP sustainability by supporting global view and multidisciplinary 											
Description of work											
WP1: Planning the programme of SSS2021Env WP start month: M31 WP end month: M48 WP Leader Umberto Agrimi Deputy WP Leader Alberto Mantovani WP participants: University of Surrey; other OHEJP partners											

Description of the WP: SS2021Env

The workshop:

What: Environment is one pillar of OH. **SS2021Env** is the first training initiative of the OHEJP entirely devoted to environmental issues. Environmental issues will be illustrated and discussed in their multi-faceted aspects: risk assessment, role of ecosystem-related factors, role of human-made factors, the farm as environmental modifier, and the issue of sustainability.

Who: Early career researchers (post-doc, PhD, junior staff members) throughout the EU and from neighbouring areas involved in all aspects of OH including biological as well as environmental hazards, coming from all EU countries as well as neighbouring areas, are the target audience of the SS2021Env. If a selection has to be done, priority will be given to i) scientists interested in SS2021 from a research point of view wanting to set up a OH initiative/project ii) scientists aiming at the development of systems thinking in their workplace; iii) scientists coming from EU countries where OH still needs implementation.

The SS2021Env involves an ad hoc MoU between the ISS and the CeRSAG (Regional Centre for Global Health). The CeRSAG will contribute to the SS2021Env implementation by committing its resources and facilities: indeed, ISS has a time-honored history of co-operation with CeRSAG on international training initiatives taking place in Orvieto.

The faculty will involve experts in all areas of risk analysis (assessment as well as management and communication) relevant to the environmental pillar of OH: ecology of AMR.vectors and infections, wildlife biology and ecology, epidemiology, eco/toxicology, exposure assessment, food security, sustainability of agrifood systems, governance and policy making.

Maximum number of participants: around 30

When and where: a 10-day event occurring in 2021 on the 2nd half of July (or if not feasible, last week of August-1st week of September); locations will be Orvieto and Roma (Italy)

Time: In general start 9am – 17 pm. Adjustments may be needed on occasional days.

Program: The SS2021Env will be led by Umberto Agrimi (chair), Alberto Mantovani (co-chair), Francesco Cubadda, Stefano Morabito, Gaia Scavia (vice-chairs).

The program will consist of five days in Orvieto (lectures plus Working groups): Day 1) Vision and challenges; (day 2) Factors related to the natural environment (ecosystem, wildlife) in zoonoses and AMR; (day 3) Factors related to the human-made environment in zoonoses and AMR; (day 4) The environment-farm-environment interface; (day 5) Way forward: from bench to field and society (day 6-7) week-end pause with social event; (day 8) transfer to Rome: workshop at FAO on OH and sustainability; (day 9) workshop on OH case study at the Istituto Zooprofilattico of Lazio and Toscana; (day 10) Wrap-up day at ISS

Information/materials (E-learning): Background information as well as in depth scientific information will be made available as well as the tools used during the workshop as well as additional tools

Task: T1-1 Preparation of the program

Task start month: M31

Task end month: M44

Task Leader: Umberto Agrimi

Deputy Task Leader: Alberto Mantovani

Task Participants: University of Surrey, OHEJP PMT

Description of the task: In this task we will prepare the final program for SS2021Env, including the identification/preparation of material and resources to be used before, during and after the workshop

Task: T-1.2 Defining the logistics and advertising for SS2021Env

Task start month: M31

Task end month: M44
Task Leader: Umberto Agrimi
Deputy Task Leader: Alberto Mantovani
Task Participants: University of Surrey, OHEJP PMT, other partners TBC
Description of the task: In this task all practical issues around SS2021Env will be organised. This includes: MoU with CeRSAG; organizing accommodation and transportation schedules, organizing social events, spreading the events notice at scientific meetings and networks and in the social networks milieu, sending a save the date, making promotion materials, aligning with other dates of the OHEJP, etc.

Task: T-1.3 SS2021Env follow-up
Task start month: M41
Task end month: M48
Task Leader: Umberto Agrimi
Deputy Task Leader: Alberto Mantovani
Task Participants: University of Surrey
Description of the task: The ISS team will contact the attendees after the event in order to understand -through a standardized structured questionnaire with the help of WP6- the impact of SS2021Env on their activity

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-WS-1.1	Timeline with activities around the program	M34
D-WS-1.2	Timeline with logistics and communication activities	M34
D-WS-1.3	Finalized program and assignment	M40
D-WS-1.4	SS in Orvieto and Rome	M44
D-WS-1.5	SS2021 ENV follow-up	M48

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
M-WS-1	MoU with CeRSAG	M34
M-WS-2	SS in Orvieto and Roma	M44
M-WS-3	SS2021Env follow-up	M48

2.4.2.1.48 CPD module 2020

CPD Title	Training on innovative digital software solutions supporting risk assessment, zoonotic outbreak investigations and data interoperability									
CPD Acronyme	Digital innovations for One Health practitioners									
CPD Organising Institute	9 - BfR			Deputy Leader institute						
CPD Coordinator	Matthias Filter			Project Deputy Leader person name			Marion Gottschald			
CPD start month	M33				CPD end month				M39	
Participant number Acronym of participant	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
	Anses	Ages	NO SCIENSA	NCIPD	NDRVMII	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI
PM								0		
Participant	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
	DTU	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA
PM										
Participant	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
	PHE	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR
PM										
Participant	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41
	FHI	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FoHM	SVA
PM										
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Provide an overview and introduction on best practice software tools used in the domain of food safety risk assessment, emerging risk identification and linked open data (LOD). 2) Provide an overview on best practice software tools supporting foodborne disease outbreak investigations and zoonotic disease modelling 3) Provide hands-on training on specific software solutions that were extended within the OHEJP projects ORION, COHESIVE & RADAR 										
<p>Description of work</p> <p>This CPD module aims at providing early career researchers and PhD students from the domains of food safety, animal health and public health with a comprehensive training in best-practice innovative software solutions that can be used in the area of zoonotic disease modelling, food safety risk assessment and foodborne disease outbreak investigations. Specifically it is planned to provide training on the tracing software FoodChain-Lab, the modelling platform RAKIP and the ORION-LOD tools available via the FoodRisk-Labs portal (https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fr/). The CPD module</p>										

itself will be composed of two synergistic components: 1) an online e-learning course for the named software resources and 2) a physical workshop with up to 25 participants hosted at the BfR (Berlin) in February 2021. The work plan outlined below accounts for these two components, as each of it has to be prepared on a specific schedule.

WP1: Development of e-learning course

WP start month: 33
WP end month: 39
WP Leader: BfR
WP Participants: OHEJP WP6
WP1 takes place over the third and the fourth annual period of the OHEJP

Description of the WP:

This WP aims at developing a first e-learning course for the innovative software solutions developed under the FoodRisk-Labs suite of software tools to provide an easy and user-friendly way of getting started with the software. E-learning courses will also contribute to the sustainability of the software solutions after the end of the OHEJP projects. Another important aspect of this WP is to acquire knowledge on how to create e-learning courses and share this knowledge with other OHEJP partners, OHEJP projects and within BfR itself.

Task: 1.2 E-learning course development

Task start month: 34
Task end month: 37
Task Leader: BfR
Task 1.2 takes place over the third and the fourth annual period of the OHEJP

Description of the task:

Within this task the e-learning course designer implements the course concepts, i.e. the necessary course materials (video tutorials, presentations, wiki pages, exercises, solutions etc.) will be created. The developed course will be tested by at least five research scientists that provide feedback for further improvements.

Task: 1.3 Knowledge dissemination

Task start month: 37
Task end month: 39
Task Leader: BfR
Task Participants: OHEJP WP6

Description of the task:

This task is dedicated towards the promotion of the e-learning concept within OHEJP, OHEJP projects and within BfR. It includes the generation of a dedicated contribution to the “Forward hand-over pack”, a presentation within a BfR seminar and the generation of a recorded webinar.

WP2: Workshop planning and implementation

WP start month: 33
WP end month: 39
WP Leader: BfR
WP participants: OHEJP Communication, invited experts from SVA, DTU, ANSES, EFSA, RKI, Pensoft
WP2 takes place over the third and the fourth annual period of the OHEJP

Description of the WP:

This work package covers all activities related to the planning, implementation and evaluation of the physical workshop event in February 2021.

Task: 2.1 Event organisation

Task start month: 33

Task end month: 38

Task Leader: BfR (BfR Academy)

Task 2.1 takes place over the third and the fourth annual period of the OHEJP

Description of the task:

In this task all activities are carried out that are needed to assure a smooth and successful physical CPD workshop. Specifically Task 2.1 will be responsible for all activities related to the venue, catering, travel & accommodation, social events, invitation of speakers and participants, registration and online evaluation & feedback. It also organizes on-site organisational support during the workshop days and takes care on workshop accreditation by German veterinary and public health associations.

Task: 2.2 Marketing and promotion

Task start month: 34

Task end month: 38

Task Leader: BfR (BfR Academy)

Task Participants: OHEJP Communication

Task 2.2 takes place over the third and the fourth annual period of the OHEJP

Description of the task:

In this task all marketing and promotion activities are planned and implemented in close collaboration with the OHEJP Communication Team. Specifically it is planned to implement a promotional campaign using the BfR and OHEJP communication channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, BfR and OHEJP websites, BfR & OHEJP newsletters). Also required printing materials for the courses will be generated.

Task: 2.3 Workshop implementation and post-event activities

Task start month: 37

Task end month: 39

Task Leader: BfR

Task Participants: invited experts from SVA, DTU, ANSES, EFSA, RKI, Pensoft

Description of the task:

In this task all content-related workshop activities are performed. This includes preparation of power-point presentations, preparation of exercises for the hands-on practical sessions, preparation of software installation guidelines (were necessary) and USB-sticks with pre-installed software tools, update of software documentation, performance tests (assuring that the heavy load during the workshop does not lead to infrastructure failure), preparation of online event evaluation questionnaires etc. In addition this task also covers the execution of the hands-on training workshop days with support of sufficient tutors (a tutor-participant ratio of 1:5 is planned). Finally this task creates the CPD module report (including the results from the online event evaluation questionnaires) and the "Forward hand-over pack".

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
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D-CPD2020-1.2	E-Learning courses developed and online for two software tools	37
D-CPD2020-2.3a	CPD2020 on-site workshop	38
D-CPD2020-2.3b	CPD2020 module report	39
D-CPD2020-2.3c	CPD2020 Forward hand-over pack	39
Milestones		
Ref	Title	Due month
none		

2.4.2.1.49 Short Term Missions 2021

STM Title	Short Term Missions 2021									
STM Acronym	STM 2021									
STM Beneficiaries	P23-UoS P25-NUIG P30-RIVM P32-FHI			Deputy STM Beneficiaries				N/A		
STM Coordinator	N/A			Deputy STM Coordinator				N/A		
T&E Start month	M37			Project End month				M48		
Participant number	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Acronym of participant	Anses	Agés	Sciensano	NCIPD	NDRVMI	SZU	VRI	BfR	FLI	RKI
PersonXmonths per participant:										
Participant number	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Acronym of participant	DTU	SSI	UT	VFL	INIA	UCM	MVNA	INRAE	IP	APHA
PersonXmonths per participant:						0				
Participant number	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Acronym of participant	PHE	UoS	OKI	NUIG	TEAGASC	ISS	IZSAM	IZSLER	RIVM	WbVR
PersonXmonths per participant:		0		0,8					0	
Participant number	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41
Acronym of participant	FHI	NVI	PIWET	INIAV	INSA	IISPV	IC	SLV	FOHMI	SVA
PersonXmonths per participant		0,4								
Objectives										
To complete the four short term missions described below to share scientific expertise, knowledge, facilities and methodologies to harmonise approaches in the area of Foodborne Zoonoses (FBZ), Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR), and Emerging Threats (ET). Reports for each of these short term missions will be provided, and summaries and testimonials from each of these missions will be made available on the One Health EJP website.										
Description of work										
Task: T1.1 STM 2021_1: Startup of an efficient sequencing facility										
Expected date: Winter or spring 2021 (the pandemic situation will affect the time of the visit)										
Task Participants: Cathrine Arnason Bøe (The Norwegian Veterinary Institute, Norway)										

Place to visit: Statens Serum Institute, Denmark

Research Domain: Foodborne Zoonoses, AMR and Emerging threats

OH Thematic Area: Skills development missions (e.g. genomics, bioinformatics, big data epidemiology)

Description of the task:

SSI has a weekly routine (see figure indicating routine workflow below Monday through Friday) handling library preparation and high-throughput sequencing (HTS) of up to 300 samples per week. Their sequencing service resembles the platform SEQ-TECH is establishing.

Typical workflow for one week at SSI will look like this:

The STM should last a week to monitor the workflow of a regular week. During that time, the applicant will acquire knowledge regarding:

- How to organise the sequencing service efficiently
- Routine workflow: from sample submission to sequencing of up to 300 samples each week
- Operating/handling the Hamilton NGS robot
- Operating/handling the NextSeq sequencer
- 16S amplicon-sequencing in the weekly routine (if SSI has that service up and running by then);
- exchange experiences regarding:
- DNA/RNA extraction for HTS
- Sequencing of virus

Task: T1.2 STM 2021_2: Developing the TELE-Vir bioinformatics toolkit for rapid characterization of emerging threats: an intersectoral exchange

Expected date: Approx. 4 weeks in spring 2021 (travel restrictions permitting)

Task Participant: Carlijn Bogaardt (University of Surrey, UK)

Place to visit: Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), Spain

Research Domain: Emerging threats

OH Thematic Area: Skills development missions (e.g. genomics, bioinformatics, big data epidemiology) Integration of microbiological, risk assessment and surveillance activities

INSA and University of Surrey are the two partner institutes leading JRP TELE-Vir WP2, which involves the development of a bioinformatics toolkit that integrates genetic, phenotypic and epidemiological data with the aim of rapidly characterising emerging viral threats. The two institutes have complementary expertise (public health, and veterinary medicine), and the planned STM thus offers an opportunity to augment planned activities and undertake training and knowledge exchange.

The goals of my planned visit to INSA are:

- (i) to exchange ideas about the needs of different stakeholders who might use the toolkit, with my hosts and me coming from different perspectives (public health and academic research, respectively);
- (ii) to share expertise in viral sequence detection and characterisation, and align approaches with regards to expansion of the existing INSaFLU pipeline, developed by my hosts;
- (iii) to enhance my skills in software development, especially where it concerns writing “open source” software, web design, and taking into account the needs of other users;

to consolidate the collaboration between our teams, with the hope that increased engagement of myself/University of Surrey as external, academic partner in the expansion of INSaFLU may (1) enhance the tool’s longevity and support maintenance when staff at public health institutes are overstretched, and (2) foster future, similar collaborations

A detailed plan of activities will depend on progress made towards TELE-Vir tasks in the time until the STM. However, proposed activities include:

Week 1 - Induction, introductions of host team, presentation of my background

Week 2 - Understanding “historical” need for & current use of INSaFLU in surveillance of influenza, COVID-19; discussions with users around functionality requests & interface

Week 3 – Learning about the role of bioinformatics in public health

Week 4 – Further work on user interface; discussions with other potential users, e.g. in animal health, food safety, other public health surveillance programmes

Task: T1.3 STM 2021_3: Tracking endemic carbapenemase plasmids in human, animal and environmental isolates.

Expected date: July or August 2021

Task Participant: Liam Burke (NUI Galway, Ireland)

Place to visit: VISAVET-UCM, Spain

Research Domain: AMR

OH Thematic Area: One Health Missions- Veterinary, Medical, Environmental research, Skills development missions (e.g. genomics, bioinformatics, big data epidemiology), Harmonization of diagnostics tests, platforms and research

Background

WGS is usually done via generation of high throughput next-generation-sequencing (NGS) reads, (e.g. Illumina MiSeq) which are typically short (<300 bp) but accurate (>98%). However mobile resistance genes residing within plasmids are often carried on transposable elements, repeated sequences that can be thousands of base pairs in length, which can cause problems during assembly. Resolving these repeats can be accomplished using longer, third-generation sequencing reads, such as those obtained using the Oxford Nanopore MinION sequencer, which are long

enough to span most repeated regions. Recent advances in the reproducibility and accuracy of long-read sequencing, combined with reduced costs, have enabled more widespread use of this technology. Hybrid assembly (assembly of long and short reads simultaneously), although still not economically viable for routine use in the reference laboratory, enables the accurate reconstruction of complete resistance plasmid sequences. This strategy has great potential for the investigation of resistance plasmid epidemiology, including from a One Health perspective (1). Furthermore, once resolved by hybrid assembly, plasmid MLST schema can be designed to identify locally endemic resistance plasmids using NGS reads alone (2).

NGS data is available for environmental CPE isolates collected by our research group since 2016 from Irish sewage, wastewaters and natural waters including rivers, lakes and coastal seas. Environmental isolates producing NDM-7 (fresh water stream, sewage, seawaters) NDM-5 (seawaters, lakes), OXA-48 (seawaters, estuary, rivers, sewage, wastewaters) and KPC-2 (seawaters, sewage) have been identified (3, 4, 5). NGS data is also available for every CPE isolate collected in Irish hospitals since 2018 and many prior to this. This data demonstrates frequent detection of the above CPE markers in clinical samples and screening samples from inpatient faecal swabs and hospital environments. Dr Burke is involved in ongoing projects (see above) which will in the near future gather NGS data for faecal isolates collected from regular recreational users of Irish rivers, lakes and seas and from the general public, as well as from wild animals.

Aim:

This mission aims to characterise and compare similar carbapenemase plasmids of interest from these sources in order to infer possible dissemination routes, investigate plasmid evolution over time and to create a spatiotemporal One Health map of important carbapenemase plasmids.

Outcome:

The data will contribute to bridging the knowledge gaps that exist in our understanding of the role of the environment and wildlife in the persistence, evolution and transmission of AMR plasmids and the propensity for carbapenemase plasmid transfer between different bacterial species and strains in distinct hosts and ecological niches. It may also identify emerging AMR threats from a One Health perspective.

Work plan

Preparation for mission

Training in genomics data science analysis methods is currently ongoing, including programming in R and Python, and will be completed prior to this mission. A collection of *Klebsiella* spp. and *Escherichia coli* isolates with **identical carbapenemase markers** from different ecological niches or host species, and from different temporal periods, will be carefully selected for hybrid sequence analysis. CPE isolates will be selected from clinical samples; screening samples from hospital inpatients and the hospital environment; hospital sewage; municipal wastewater; rivers, lakes and seas; faecal samples from frequent recreational users of these waters and the general public; and faecal samples from wild animals associated with urban/peri-urban water bodies including swans, gulls and bats. This will facilitate investigation of the epidemiology of Irish carbapenemase plasmids from a one health perspective and may provide insights on their evolution over time. The isolate collection will be subcultured to agar stabs for transport. Sequence reads, genome assemblies and metadata on the collection will be curated in our BIGSdb genome database.

Week 1 and 2:

Culture of isolate collection. Isolation of pure genomic DNA for sequencing from all strains. DNA concentration normalisation via Qubit fluorometric quantitation (Invitrogen). S1-PFGE plasmid profiling and carbapenemase gene hybridization by Southern blot. Preparation of sequencing

libraries using the Rapid Sequencing kit (Oxford Nanopore). Sequencing (for approximately 16 hours) using the flow-MIN106 R9 flow cell.

Week 3 and 4:

Hybrid genome assembly using Unicycler (6). Assembly polishing using Pilon (7). Representation of resistance plasmids using CLC Genomics Workbench 9.5.2. Comparison and visualisation of human-animal-environmental resistance plasmids in BLAST ring image generator (BRIG).

References

- (1) Orlek A, et al. (2017) *Front. Microbiol.* <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.00182>
- (2) Brehony C, et al. (2019) *J Antimicrob Chemother*, 74(7): 1856–1862, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkz136>
- (3) Mahon BM, et al. (2017) *Euro Surveill.* 22(15):pii=30513. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2017.22.15.30513>
- (4) Mahon BM et al. (2019) *Sci Total Env* 609; 1-6, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.480>
- (5) Cahill N, et al. (2019) *Sci Total Env* 672; 618–624
- (6) Wick RR, et al. (2017) *PLOS Comput. Biol.* 13(6): e1005595. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005595>
- (7) Walker BJ, et al. (2014) *PLOS ONE* 9(11): e112963. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0112963>

Task: T1.4 STM 2021_4: Zoonotic pathogen detection in rats

Expected date: October and November 2021

Task Participant: Marieke de Cock (RIVM, the Netherlands)

Place to visit: Friedrich-Loeffler-Institut (FLI), Germany

Research Domain: Emerging Threats

OH Thematic Area: One Health Missions- Veterinary, Food, Medical and or Environmental research, Harmonization of diagnostics tests, platforms and research

During the short-term mission, samples of wild rats (± 300) collected by the RIVM in 2020 and 2021 will be brought to FLI to be tested. We want to test the wild rats for a list of pathogens (see the table below). Most of these pathogens will be tested at the RIVM laboratory, but at the RIVM diagnostics are not available for all pathogens, such as cowpox virus. Therefore some pathogens will be tested at other partner institutes (see the table below for an overview), for example testing for cowpox will be performed at FLI. Next to that, comparative diagnostics will be performed for Seoul orthohantavirus and hepatitis E virus at FLI and RIVM/WBVR. For various antibiotic resistant bacteria, such as extended spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) producing bacteria, testing can be performed at one of FLI's close collaborators (e.g. Greifswald University).

Pathogens	Organ/tissue	Detection method	Institute
Seoul orthohantavirus	Lung	Real-time RT-PCR + ELISA (Ayril <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Maas <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	RIVM and FLI
<i>Leptospira</i> spp.	Kidney/urine	Real-time PCR + culture (Himsworth, Bidulka, <i>et al.</i> , 2013; Ayril <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Lee <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Maas <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	RIVM

Cowpox/orthopox virus	Nasal septum	PCR (Jeske <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	FLI
<i>Bartonella</i> spp	Spleen	Real-time PCR (Morick <i>et al.</i> , 2009; Obiegala <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	RIVM
<i>Streptobacillus moniliformis</i>	Saliva swab	PCR (Kimura <i>et al.</i> , 2008)	FLI collaborator
<i>Rickettsia</i> spp.	Skin (ear)	PCR (Schex <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Obiegala <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	RIVM
<i>Borrelia</i> spp.	Skin (ear)	PCR (Obiegala <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	RIVM
<i>Anaplasma</i> spp.	Spleen	PCR (Obiegala <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	RIVM
Resistant <i>Campylobacter</i> spp.	Intestines (feces)	PCR, culture (Nkogwe <i>et al.</i> , 2011)	RIVM
ESBL/AmpC-producing <i>Enterobacteriaceae</i> (including <i>E. coli</i> and <i>Salmonella</i> spp.)	Intestines (feces)	PCR, culture (Nkogwe <i>et al.</i> , 2011; Burt <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	FLI collaborator
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (including MRSA)	Oropharyngeal swab	PCR + latex agglutination test (Himsworth, Miller, <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	RIVM
Resistant <i>Clostridium difficile</i>	Intestines (feces)	PCR, culture (Himsworth, Patrick, <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Burt <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Krijger <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	FLI collaborator
Hepatitis E virus	Liver	PCR (Ayril <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ryll <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	Wageningen Bio-veterinary Research (WBVR) and FLI

At FLI, there is currently research ongoing focusing on polyomavirus in rats from different European countries. This visit will also provide opportunity to include our Dutch wild rats in this polyomavirus investigation. In this way, the applicant will get acquainted with yet another pathogen detection method, and the captured wild rats can be used for detection of an additional pathogen.

Also, by the time this short-term mission takes place, the applicant will have performed NGS analysis on bacterial DNA from rats at RIVM. At FLI, there is unused NGS data available about viruses found in rats. If time allows, the applicant will try to generate contigs/complete genomes with these data for some rat-specific viruses that have not been characterized yet.

Planning

- In the first week, the applicant will be shown around in the institute and the laboratories of the collaborators and will get acquainted with the laboratory. Also, the applicant will give a presentation about her PhD research.
- Week 2-5 are needed to learn and perform several specific pathogen detection techniques (for Seoul orthohantavirus, hepatitis E virus, cowpox virus and some of the antibiotic resistant bacteria) on the rat samples.
- Week 6 and 7 will be used to collaborate in the ongoing polyomavirus investigation by testing the Dutch rat samples for polyomavirus. If time allows, the applicant will also work on (or start with

analysing) NGS virus data.

- Week 8 will be used to finalise the experiments, discuss results and discuss possible new collaboration opportunities between FLI and RIVM.

This whole short-term mission will be used to strengthen the collaboration between RIVM and FLI and to exchange best practices.

Deliverables

Ref	Title	Due month
D-STM-1.1	STM 2021_1_Mission	M41
D-STM-1.2	STM 2021_2_Mission	M41
D-STM-1.3	STM 2021_3_Mission	M44
D-STM-1.4	STM 2021_4_Mission	M47

Milestones

Ref	Title	Due month
MS-STM-1	STM 2020_1_Report and Testimonial	M42
MS-STM-2	STM 2020_2_Report and Testimonial	M42
MS-STM-3	STM 2020_3_Report and Testimonial	M45
MS-STM-4	STM 2020_4_Report and Testimonials	M48

2.4.2.2 List of programmed activities

Activity	Lead Beneficiary N°	Acronym lead beneficiary	PM	Start Month	End Month
WP1	1	Anses	97,1	37	48
WP2	30	RIVM	4,5	37	48
WP3	4	Sciensano	15,5	37	48
WP4	41	SVA	15,57	37	48
WP5	9	BfR	25,33	37	48
WP6	23	UoS	39,5	37	48
WP7	27	ISS	13	37	48
JRP02-R1-AMR2-ARDIG	21	APHA	34,58	37	42
JRP12-R2-AMRSH5-FARMED	21	APHA	92,9	37	48
JRP13-R2-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	25	NUIG	123,5	37	48
JRP14-R2-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	04	Sciensano	116,23	37	48
JRP15-R2-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	02	Ages	154,76	37	48
JRP16-R2-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	13	SSI	120,87	37	48
JRP17-R2-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	01	Anses	123,84	37	48
JRP05-R1-ET1-TOXdetect	01	Anses	38,44	37	48
JRP18-R2-ET1.1-MEmE	27	ISS	135,26	37	48
JRP19-R2-ET1.1-PARADISE	27	ISS	95,51	37	48
JRP06-R1-FBZ1-NOVA	41	SVA	92,27	37	42
JRP10-R1-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	19	INRAE	51,72	37	42
JRP20-R2-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	12	DTU	144,94	37	48
JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	09	BfR	205,24	37	48

Activity	Lead Beneficiary N°	Acronym lead beneficiary	PM	Start Month	End Month
JRP22-R2-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	13	SSI	149,49	37	48
JRP23-R2-FBZSH5-ADONIS	30	RIVM	164,45	37	48
JRP24-R2-FBZSH9-BeONE	13	SSI	87,99	37	48
JIP01-R1-IA1.1-ORION	09	BfR	110,33	37	42
JIP02-R1-IA1.2-COHESIVE	30	RIVM	82,24	37	42
JIP03-R2-IA2.3-CARE	12	DTU	273,71	37	48
JIP04-R2-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	13	SSI	134,83	37	48
JIP05-R2-IA2.1-MATRIX	13	SSI	252,55	37	48
PhD01-R1-AMR2-ECO-HEN	17	UCM	15	37	48
PhD02-R1-AMR2/3/6-LIN-RES	04	Sciensano	12	37	48
PhD03-R2-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	26	TEAGASC	12	37	48
PhD04-R2-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY	04	Sciensano	12	37	48
PhD05-R2-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO	17	UCM	14	37	48
PhD06-R1-ET5-PEMbo	01	Anses	12	37	48
PhD07-R2-ET2.1-MACE	23	UoS	13	37	48
PhD08-R2-ET5.1/4.1/FBZSH3-DESIRE	30	RIVM	3	37	48
PhD09-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC	21	APHA	12	37	48
PhD10-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR	21	APHA	14,9	37	48
PhD11-R1-FBZ4/5- EnvDis	23	UoS	12	37	48
PhD12-R2-FBZSH9-AptaTrich	01	Anses	12	37	48
PhD13-R2-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR	31	WbvR	9,82	37	48

Activity	Lead Beneficiary N°	Acronym lead beneficiary	PM	Start Month	End Month
PhD14-R2-FBZ4-ToxSauQMRA	01	Anses	8,36	37	48
PhD15-R2-FBZ5-TRACE	30	RIVM	4,87	37	48
PhD16-R2-FBZ2/AMR6.1-Codes4strains	20	IP	12	37	48
Short Term Missions 2021	NUIG-UoS-RIVM-NVI		1,2	37	48

2.4.2.3 Annual Deliverables List

Deliverable N°	Deliverable name	WP N°	Acronym of lead beneficiary	Dissemination level	Est. Del. Date
D1.12	Annual report on the internal and external newsletter produced during the second year	1	Anses	PU	M37
D1.13	Complete version of annual report for stakeholders n°2	1	Anses	PU	M41
D1.14	Summary progress report year 3	1	Anses	PU	M45
D1.15	Annual work plan for the fourth year	1	Anses	PU	M45
D1.25	Ethical review report for Y2	1	Anses	CO	M38
D2.8	Report on scientific developments	2	RIVM	PU	M42

Deliverable N°	Deliverable name	WP N°	Acronym of lead beneficiary	Dissemination level	Est. Del. Date
D2.9	Report on strategic links established and strategic developments	2	RIVM	PU	M42
D3.15	3rd periodic report on JRP	3	Sciensano	PU	M39
D3.16	Abstract book for 3rd Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM)	3	Sciensano	PU	M41
D3.17	Report n°2 on evaluation of finalised JRP	3	Sciensano	PU	M48
D4.21	Report from thematic meeting III	4	SVA	PU	M42
D4.22	3rd periodic report on JIPs	4	SVA	PU	M39
D4.23	Report from 7th cogwheel workshop	4	SVA	PU	M42
D4.24	Report on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 1st round	4	SVA	PU	M48
D4.25	Report from 8th cogwheel workshop	4	SVA	PU	M48
D5.9	Fourth annual report on dissemination activities to international stakeholders	5	BfR	PU	M48

Deliverable N°	Deliverable name	WP N°	Acronym of lead beneficiary	Dissemination level	Est. Del. Date
D6.9	Report of the second CPD module in one health	6	Surrey	PU	M40
D6.10	Report n°2 of the annual short term missions completed also uploaded onto the EJP webpage.	6	Surrey	PU	M38
D6.11	Report n°3 on one workshop per year associated with ASM (with WP1,3,4 and 5)	6	Surrey	PU	M48
D6.12	Report of the third One health summer school	6	Surrey	PU	M48
D6.13	Report of the third CPD module in one health	6	Surrey	PU	M48
D7.2	One Health SRIA 2021-2030.	7	ISS	PU	M40
D7.3	Document on governance model and related financial plan for a sustainable Partnership based on the SRIA 2021-2030	7	ISS	PU	M42

2.5 Participation in Annual Work Plan activities

Beneficiaries concerned : P04-SCIENSANO, P06-NDRVMI, P07-SZU, P08-VRI, P09-BfR, P10-FLI, P11-RKI, P12-DTU, P14-UTARTU, P15-VFL, P16-INIA, P17-UCM, P18-MVNA, P20-IP, P22-PHE, P23-UoS, P24-OKI, P25-NUIG, P23-ISS, P27-IZSAM, P28-IZSLER, P32-FHI, P33-NVI, P34-PIWET, P35-INIAV, P36-INSA, P37-IISPV, P39-SLV, P40-FoHM	
Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contribution provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.5.1 P01-Anses

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the project should not be sub-contracted)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work is performed by linked third parties	Y
<p><u>WP3 Joint research projects</u></p> <p>Description of the Third Party: Santé publique France was created on 27 April 2016 as the French National Public Health agency, resulting from the merging of the French Institute for Public Health Surveillance (InVS), the French Institute for Health Promotion and Health Education (Inpes) and the Establishment for Public Health Emergency Preparedness and Response (Eprus). Santé publique France will serve the population in all aspects of public health based on scientific knowledge, data, and information.</p> <p>It will support the government and society in improving the health and well-being of the population. It will apply a population-based approach with the objective of reducing social health inequalities in all areas of public health: Infectious diseases; Non-infectious diseases; Environmental health; Occupational health. The agency is present throughout the national territory with regional units, including oversea territories, and works hand to hand with the Regional Health Agencies (ARS).</p> <p>Link of the participant to the third party: Renewable Partnership Framework Agreement Anses/InVS (ANSP) over the period 01/03/2016 to 28/03/2018, (ref: Anses CC572B)</p> <p>Description and justification of the foreseen tasks to be performed by the third party:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity: JRP06-R1-FBZ1-NOVA <p>The collaborative project strives to develop new surveillance tools and methods and to harmonize and optimize the use of existing surveillance system data. The project group consists of a network of 19 Med and Vet institutions from 10 European countries. The project is scheduled to run for three years and is divided into five scientific work packages (WPs) plus an administrative WP. Three of the five scientific WPs concern the development of targeted surveillance tools, whereas the remaining two concern integrative measures. Each WP consists of a series of individual projects conducted under a common research umbrella.</p>	
Does the participant envisage the use of contributions in kind provided by third parties (Articles 11 and 12 of the General Model Grant Agreement)	Y

WP6 / Task 6.4 Doctoral Training Programme

Anses will use in-kind contribution for the following activities under Article 11:

- **Activity PhD06-R1-ET5-PEMbo:** Anses will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD-E5-PEMbo activities in Anses premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the Université Paris-Est Créteil (UPEC). This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by UPEC and working for Anses. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment.

The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.

- **Activity PhD12-R2-FBZSH9-AptaTrich:** Anses will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD12 AptaTrich activities in Anses premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the Université Paris-Est Créteil (UPEC). This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by UPEC and working for Anses. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment.

The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.

- **PhD14-R2-FBZ4-ToxSauQMRA:** Anses will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD14 ToxSauQMRA activities in Anses premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the Ecole Nationale Veterinaire d'Alfort – ENVA. This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by ENVA and working for Anses. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment.

The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.

Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N
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2.5.2 P02-AGES

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y

WP3 Joint research projects

AGES will use of the in-kind contribution, provided by the following third party under Article 12 of the GA:

- **Activity JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE:** University of Veterinary Medicine Vienna (Vetmeduni Vienna - VMU) will provide personnel having specific skills to implement the following tasks:
 - WP2 (1 PM): VMU will contribute to the development and application of the biosecurity protocol, where input from recent work completed will be given and data from the recent study will be used.
 - WP4 (1 PM): VMU will provide the information to be collected within WP2 for the economic assessment, to be conducted in Y2 and Y3.
 - WP5 (1 PM): VMU will contribute to the data integration from WP2 and 4 into the catalogue of biosecurity measures. This builds on previous work which has been done at Vetmeduni Vienna.

In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises

Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N
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2.5.3 P13-SSI

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP3, T3.4: 2021 Annual Scientific Meeting organisation: P13-SSI will organise and host the 2021-ASM. In order to ensure a very well organised meeting it will hire a Professional Conference Organiser (PCO). Justification: There is a considerable resource effort needed to organise a major professional congress (250 international delegates expected). At the host institute there are no in-house staff with the resource time available or the necessary experience in this type of event organisation, therefore the host will hire a Professional Conference Organiser (PCO) to undertake the organising and administration of the congress. Their role will be to set up and manage the website, set up and manage registration, marketing and promotion, attract sponsorship, delegate queries, finances and budget, production of conference materials, running of event at the venue and the social programme. The process to recruit the PCO is fully in line with national procurement rules. The PCO fee structure will be set out in a contract with the host organisation</p>	
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP4 Joint integrative projects SSI will use of the in-kind contribution, provided by the following third party under Articles 11 of the GA: Activity JIP05-R2-IA2.1-MATRIX: University of Copenhagen will provide personnel having specific knowledge on output-based surveillance evaluation as also outline in the MATRIX work plan. University of Copenhagen (UCPH) will play an important role in the development of guidelines for the design, implementation, and evaluation of official controls within the food sector using output-based standards (WP3). UCPH and SSI collaborate closely on a regularly basis as both institutions jointly are responsible for the Danish Veterinary Preparedness. Profs Liza Rosenbaum Nielsen and Hans Houe will be in charge of overseeing the work carried out by UCPH. Both Prof. Nielsen and Prof. Houe have extensive experience with output-based surveillance systems. In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises</p>	
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.5.4 P19-INRAE

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N

Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP3 Joint research projects INRAE will use of the in-kind contribution, provided by the following third party under Articles 11 of the GA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity JRP07-R1-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: University of Burgundy will provide personnel having specific skills to implement the tasks related to the project. • Activity JRP11-R1-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: University of Burgundy will provide personnel having specific skills to implement the tasks related to the project. <p>The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity JRP07-R1-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Institut National Supérieur des Agronomiques de l'alimentation et de l'environnement (AgroSup Dijon) will provide personnel having specific skills to implement the tasks related to the project. • Activity JRP11-R1-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Institut National Supérieur des Agronomiques de l'alimentation et de l'environnement (AgroSup Dijon) will provide personnel having specific skills to implement the tasks related to the project. <p>The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.</p> <p>Justification: To carry out this project it was necessary to mobilize some research assistant professors from the University of Burgundy and Agrosup. Pascal Piveteau (University of Burgundy) is a specialist on <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> biology and ecology, he previously coordinated an ETN: ListMaps program dedicated to the adaptation of <i>Listeria</i> to various environments. Dominique Garmyn (University of Burgundy) is an expert in bacterial genetics with special skills in <i>Listeria</i> genetics. He was recruited on this project to produce genetically constructed strains and mutants to decipher the role of certain genes of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in its adaptation to environmental conditions. Laurent Gal (Agrosup Dijon) has particular skills in microbial ecology and microbial physiology on <i>Listeria</i> and <i>Klebsiella</i> models. Sebastien Solanas is a technical assistant with skills in molecular methods for detecting these bacteria. All together, these persons from the University of Burgundy and Agrosup Dijon are contributing to the successful achievement of the two projects.</p>	
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.5.5 P21-APHA

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP6 / Task 6.4 Doctoral Training Programme: APHA is not an academic institution and as such is not in position to hire PhD student. Consequently, APFA will use Article 11 of the GA to support the following PhDs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity PhD09-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC: APHA will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD09- UDOFRIC activities in APHA premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the University of Warwick. This person will therefore be a seconded 	

<p>employee paid by University of Warwick and working for APHA. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment. The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.</p> <p>Activity PhD10-R2-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR: APHA will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD10-WILBR activities in APHA premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the University of Exeter. This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by University of Exeter and working for APHA. His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment. The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.</p>	
<p>Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)</p>	<p>N</p>

2.5.6 P30-RIVM

<p>Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)</p>	<p>N</p>
<p>Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)</p>	<p>N</p>
<p>Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)</p>	<p>Y</p>
<p>WP3 /Joint research projects RIVM and UMCU are active in One Health research together with other leading parties to forge an open innovation network named Netherlands Centre for One Health (NCOH). In this centre Dutch One Health knowledge is brought together with the goal to create added value by centralizing the specific knowledge of the partners (http://ncoh.nl/). As previously agreed between the REA and RIVM in course of 2018, RIVM envisages the use of the following in-kind contributions, provided by the following third parties under Articles 11 and 12 of the GA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity JRP03-R1-AMR3-RADAR: University Medical Centre Utrecht (UMCU) will provide personnel having specific knowledge of AMR. Involved in several WPs of the project, UMCU, provides particular support to the second WP of the project, dealing with transmission models, as WP deputy leader. Within this WP, the university will be particularly involved in the communication of results, and this work will form part of a PhD project within NCOH. • Activity JRP11-R1-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: University Medical Centre Utrecht (UMCU) will provide personnel having specific knowledge of Klebsiella. The university, through the NCOH network, will be particularly involved in WP3 – Genomics and Modeling – on activities related to the analyses and genomic sequences <p>In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises</p>	
<p>Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)</p>	<p>N</p>

2.5.7 P31-WbVR

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p><u>WP6 / Task 6.4 Doctoral Training Programme:</u> WbVR will use in-kind contribution for the following activity under Article 11:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity PhD13-R2-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR: WbVR will use the services provided by a PhD student to carry out PhD13 WIMOGUT-AMR activities in WbVR premises. This PhD student will be employed and paid by the Wageningen University & Research (WUR). This person will therefore be a seconded employee paid by WUR and working for WbVR . His salary will be supported by the OHEJP under Article 11 of the GA: in-kind contribution provided by third parties against payment. The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises <p><u>WP3 /Joint research projects</u> WbvR, UU, EMC and WU are active in One Health research together with other leading parties to forge an open innovation network named Netherlands Centre for One Health (NCOH). In this centre Dutch One Health knowledge is brought together with the goal to create added value by centralizing the specific knowledge of the partners (http://ncoh.nl/). As previously agreed between the REA and WbvR in course of 2018, WbvR envisages the use of the following in-kind contributions, provided by the following third parties under Articles 11 and 12 of the GA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JRP01-R1-AMR1-IMPART: University Utrecht (UU), Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, will provide strains resulted from sample material from its diagnostic microbiology laboratory for small animal, research results obtained with these strains and small animal microbiology expert knowledge. These activities are centred around the diagnostic apparatus of the veterinary microbiology diagnostic centre of the faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Utrecht. In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises. • Activity JRP08-R1-FBZ2-METASTAVA: Erasmus Medical Centre (EMC) will provide personnel having specific expertise in metagenome analysis. These analyses will be carried out in EMC's equipped with adequate materiel and qualified personnel for the performance of the tasks related to the project. In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises • Activity JRP10-R1-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC: Wageningen University & Research (WUR) will provide personnel that is able to do the WUR part of the research. The WUR, which is particularly involved in WP3 of the project, carrying out the modelling activities, will provide the project with human resources as well as material resources. In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises <p>In addition, WbvR envisages the use of the following in-kind contributions, provided by the following third parties under Articles 11 of the GA.</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity JRP14-R2-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE: University Utrecht (UU) will contribute to the project with the provision of human resources. The scientists involved in the project are specialised in infectious diseases and animal health. <p>In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity JRP20-R2-FBZSH3-DISCOVeR: University Utrecht (UU) will provide personnel having specific expertise, with a focus on analysis of bacterial (meta-) genomes for comparative genomics, molecular epidemiology and linking bacterial genotype to phenotype. <p>In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity JRP21-R2-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE: University Utrecht (UU) will provide personnel having specific expertise in and capabilities for designing pig farm audits and performing pig farm visits for auditing of biosecurity and pig health as well as potential hazards for animal and public health. In addition UU has considerable expertise in handling the data of these audits for further analyses. <p>The work will be carried out on beneficiary's premises.</p>	
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.5.8 P41-SVA

Does the participant plan to subcontract certain tasks (please note that core tasks of the programme should not be subcontracted) (article 13 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage that part of its work will be performed by linked third parties (article 14 of MGA)	N
Does the participant envisage the use of in-kind contributions provided by third parties (articles 11 and 12 of MGA)	Y
<p>WP7/ T7.4: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable</p> <p>SVA will use Article 11 of the GA to carry out the T7.4: Making the bridges between EJP's beneficiaries and stakeholders sustainable.</p> <p>The task of drafting of a detailed plan for an EU-wide analysis of current work processes, shared infrastructures, reference documents and guidelines across the multifaceted OH interface (environmental health-animal health-public health) will be conducted partly in the form of a PhD project in collaboration with Roskilde University (DK), Department of Social Sciences and Business. The contribution from Roskilde University will be to cover a part of PhD salary and tuition fees. The work will be carried out on Roskilde University's premises.</p> <p>In-kind contributions not used on beneficiary's premises.</p>	
Does the participant envisage the provision of financial support to third parties (article 15 of MGA)	N

2.6 Resources to be committed

2.6.1 Summary Effort Table

2.6.1.1 Overarching activities

Organisation	WP1-Coordination	WP2-SRA	WP3-JRPs management	WP4-JIPs management	WP5-Science to Policy translation	WP6-T&E management	WP7-Sustainability	Total
P01-Anses	47.00							47.00
P02-Ages	0.50							0.50
P04-Sciensano	6.50		14.00	1.25				21.75
P06-NDRVMI	0.50							0.50
P07-SZU	0.50							0.50
P08-VRI	0.50							0.50
P09-BfR	0.50				13.33			13.83
P10-FLI	0.50							0.50
P11-RKI	0.50							0.50
P12-DTU	0.50							0.50
P13-SSI	0.50		1.50		12.00			14.00
P14-UT	0.50							0.50
P15-VFL	0.50							0.50
P16-INIA	0.50							0.50
P17-UCM	0.50	2.25						2.75
P18-MVNA				0.00				0.00
P19-INRA	0.50							0.50
P20-IP	0.50						1.50	2.00

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Organisation	WP1-Coordination	WP2-SRA	WP3-JRPs management	WP4-JIPs management	WP5-Science to Policy translation	WP6-T&E management	WP7-Sustainability	Total
P21-APHA	0.50							0.50
P22-PHE	0.50							0.50
P23-UoS	26.60					38.00		64.60
P24-OKI	0.50							0.50
P25-NUIG	0.50							0.50
P26-TEAGASC	0.50							0.50
P27-ISS	0.50						4.50	5.00
P28-IZS AM	0.50							0.50
P29-IZS LER	0.50							0.50
P30-RIVM	0.50	2.25						2.75
P31-WbvR	0.50					1.50		2.00
P32-FHI	0.50							0.50
P33-NVI	0.50			1.00				1.50
P34-PIWET	0.50							0.50
P35-INIAV	0.50							0.50
P36-INSA	0.50			3.90				4.40
P37-IISPV	0.50							0.50
P39-SLV	0.50							0.50
P40-FoHM	0.50							0.50
P41-SVA	0.50			9.42			7.00	16.92
TOTAL	97.10	4.50	15.50	15.57	25.33	39.50	13.00	210.50

2.6.1.2 Training and Education activities

Organisation	CPD-2021	PhD01-AMR2-ECO-HEN	PhD02-AMR2/3/6-PhD LIN-RES	PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	PhD04-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY	PhD05-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO	PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	PhD07-ET2.1-MACE	PhD08-ET5.1/4.1/FBZSH3-DESIRE	PhD09-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC	PhD10-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR	PhD11-FBZ4/5- EnvDis	PhD12-FBZSH9-AptaTrich	PhD13-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR	PhD14-FBZ4-ToxSauQMRA	PhD15-FBZ5-TRACE	PhD16-FBZ2/AMR6.1-Codes4strains	STM-2021	TOTAL
P01-Anses							12.00						12.00		8.36				32.36
P04-Sciensano			12.00		12.00														24.00
P17-UCM		15.00				14.00													29.00
P20-IP																	12.00		12.00
P21-APHA									12.00	14.90									26.90
P23-UoS								13.00				12.00							25.00
P25-NUIG																		0.80	0.80
P26-TEAGASC				12.00															12.00
P27-ISS																			0.00
P30-RIVM									3.00								1.58		4.58
P31-WbvR														9.82		3.29			13.11
P33-NVI																		0.40	0.40
TOTAL		15.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	14.00	12.00	13.00	3.00	12.00	14.90	12.00	12.00	9.82	8.36	4.87	12.00	1.20	180.15

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2.6.1.3 Joint Research Projects/ Joint Integrative Projects

Organisation	JIP01- IA1.1- ORION	JIP02- IA1.2- COHESI VE	JIP03- IA2.3- CARE	JIP04- IA2.2- OH- HARMO NY CAP	JIP05- IA2.1- MATRIX	JRP02- AMR2- ARDIG	JRP05- ET1- TOXdet ect	JRP06- FBZ1- NOVA	JRP10- FBZ3- MoMIR- PPC	JRP12- AMRSH 5- FARME D	JRP13- AMRSH 5- WORLD COM	JRP14- AMR2.1- FULL- FORCE	JRP15- AMR2.1- FED- AMR	JRP16- ET2.2- TELE- Vir	JRP17- ET2.2- IDEMBR U	JRP18- ET1.1- MEEme	JRP19- ET1.1- PARADI SE	JRP20- FBZSH3- DISCoV er	JRP21- FBZ3.1- BIOPIG EE	JRP22- FBZ4.1- TOXOS OURCE S	JRP23- FBZSH5- ADONIS	JRP24- FBZSH9- BeONE	TOTAL
P01-Anses		1.00	41.00	6.10	20.80	2.50	11.60	11.74	0.85			8.00		13.00	30.30	29.50	6.50	12.50	6.00	11.20	17.90		230.49
P02-Ages		2.53											13.95						15.50		3.80		35.78
P04-Sciensano	5.50	5.50					9.27	8.67		17.10		12.19		5.50							18.16		81.89
P06-NDRVMI									8.00						19.00				32.00				59.00
P07-SZU													1.13							6.60			7.73
P08-VRI		2.50							3.85					0.00			4.10	16.00	11.00	11.00			48.45
P09-BfR	30.00	15.00		6.00	19.85	3.00	3.00	3.50		6.50		7.50	2.75		10.30		2.30	9.00	26.00	7.60		12.00	164.30
P10-FLI	16.85	1.10			8.40						19.20		8.40		8.40	9.00				9.00		0.60	80.95
P11-RKI						6.00		5.50									11.00		13.00	6.05		0.60	42.15
P12-DTU	9.00	0.00	7.50		6.50			3.50		5.00		7.05						8.00		1.05		1.50	49.10
P13-SSI	5.00		26.00	35.30	24.00			7.00		12.00		3.75	8.00	29.00		7.30	6.70	7.00		15.95	15.00	27.00	229.00
P14-UT											15.00		14.00			15.50							44.50
P15-VFL																2.00			7.90				9.90
P16-INIA					15.00			6.50				6.05		3.70									31.25
P17-UCM			6.00		17.00	4.00		2.00	1.00	20.00	21.70							16.00		11.40	13.00		112.10
P19-INRA			38.50				4.60		5.50			6.50											55.10
P20-IP			40.00			4.18	6.77						1.25								20.40		72.60
P21-APHA	3.65	1.60	4.26	15.30	7.40	7.10		3.32		11.13		6.13			10.99			8.78	22.10		8.52	1.40	111.68
P22-PHE	2.90					2.20		0.53										1.25			1.25	1.00	9.13
P23-UoS					8.40	0.00			0.00		12.80		12.96	9.70			5.15			3.25			52.26
P24-OKI																	2.00						2.00
P25-NUIG											28.80		18.00										46.80
P26-TEAGASC				2.40														2.28					4.68
P27-ISS		0.00	11.00	18.00	5.00				4.25	3.10		8.30				32.50	27.50	13.00	13.00	36.30	4.50		176.45
P28-IZS AM		3.25	12.00		26.50			3.42		12.80				18.50	13.90					16.00		2.00	108.37
P29-IZS LER		8.50	31.00						19.91					0.50					5.85				65.76
P30-RIVM	5.72	18.37	6.00	3.80	8.50			0.64				3.69				2.46	3.34	7.73	0.62	8.86	10.82	10.67	91.22
P31-WbvR	0.81	2.63	4.40		3.00	0.00			1.46	5.27		12.38			6.15			5.30	7.02	0.15	5.90		54.47
P32-FHI	10.00	10.00		3.31	16.52			16.00	6.90									2.42		1.55		0.96	67.66
P33-NVI	8.80	3.10		2.00	3.88	5.60	3.20	0.50				2.97	2.72	1.66		6.80	0.80	3.03	7.50	2.88		1.25	56.69
P34-PIWET			35.00	5.50	14.20							9.28	9.30	7.00		9.20	4.10	5.25	12.25	7.55	9.50	6.00	134.13
P35-INIAV		0.56		5.42											14.30	7.00	2.92	9.90		6.10	9.35		55.55
P36-INSA				17.50	16.60						26.00	10.75	62.30	26.31	10.50	5.00		13.50		2.00	26.35	23.01	239.82
P39-SLV		2.00	2.60	0.70													1.10			1.00			7.40
P40-FoHM	2.00		3.50	4.00	8.00			4.45				4.19					1.00						27.14
P41-SVA	10.10	4.60	4.95	9.50	23.00			15.00				7.50		6.00		9.00	17.00	4.00	9.50	0.00			120.15
TOTAL	110.33	82.24	273.71	134.83	252.55	34.58	38.44	92.27	51.72	92.90	123.50	116.23	154.76	120.87	123.84	135.26	95.51	144.94	205.24	149.49	164.45	87.99	2785.65

2.6.2 Other major cost items (equipment, goods and services, travel & subsistence, meetings organisation)

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
P01.5-ANSP	0.00		0.00		600.00		0.00	
WP3	0.00		0.00		600.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
P01-Anses	7 600.00		334 822.00		197 196.00		57 620.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		5 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		5 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP3	7 600.00		225 348.00		27 044.00		1 700.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		9 000.00	1 FOC delegate, 3 VIP - PMT, 8 VIP - ESAB, 3 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		10 000.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP05-ET1-TOXdetect	0.00		13 000.00	Reagents and consumables for interlab tests, shipment of samples to participants. (WP5), APC, Reagent for molecular biology (e.g. PCR and RT-PC kits ...) (WP2)	0.00		0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		4 300.00	APC - Article Publication Charges	1 600.00	NOVA meeting	0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		9 934.00	Serums analysis task 1.1	750.00	Final meeting	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		26 600.00	Publication costs, Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing, Lab reagents for MGE investigation	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		16 444.00	utensiles, Other reagents and enzymes, library preparation kits (6 kits)(Oxford Nanopore), MinIT (Oxford Nanopore), MinION starter pack (advanced)(Oxford Nanopore)	974.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting, January 2021, Sciensano, Belgium	0.00	

JRP17-ET2.2- IDEMBRU	7 600.00	Data server--> cost 25 000 €, 5 years of depreciation, 80 % of use for EJP (project of 2.5 years) --> eligible costs = $(25000 * 12 / 60) * 0,80$ =4000, Microscop 20 000 €, 5 years of depreciation, 90 % of use for EJP (project of 2.5 years) --> eligible costs = $(20000 * 12 / 60) * 0,9 =$ 3600	45 000.00	Consumables for sampling and direct testing (PCR, biotyping), Consumables for sampling and direct testing (Elisa Kit), Transport of ADN (UN 3373) , consumables for sequencing, Consumables for phenotyping, Consumables for antibioresistance testing, Transport of strains (UN 2814) , Consumables for immune and virulence analyses (ELISA and RT qPCR), Consumables for in vivo infection models, Consumables for toolkit, Consumables for data management, cloud rental, Consumables for coordination	2 800.00	Annual workshop (Intermediate meeting, 2021, Portugal, 2 participants, 2 days, 2 nights)	0.00	
JRP18-ET1.1- MEEmE	0.00		37 970.00	Foxes (n=14) , Reagents, Shipment cost, Publication fees	2 100.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		32 600.00	Molecular biology reagents and Kits for NGS, Consumables : Kits for cysts extraction, DNA or protein purification, Consumables for Molecular biology, Cloning and sequencing, Shipment of samples to partners	1 400.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		10 000.00	Wgs	0.00		1 700.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		0.00		1 700.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting	0.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		9 500.00	Publication and dissemination costs , Consumables	2 200.00	Annual meeting, to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM, WP5 Workshop	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		10 000.00	Bacteriology, Molecular biology (MLVA, WGS)	3 960.00	ADONIS meeting, Farm visits, Meetings	0.00	
WP4	0.00		86 671.00		163 382.00		55 920.00	
Integrative missions	0.00		77 687.00		150 000.00		48 000.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		8 984.00	consummable, OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES	6 775.00	training course, WP3, 2nd part 2021, Rennes, France, 2 days, 2 nights ; meeting: CARE information system, 2nd 2021, Côme, Italie, 2 nights ; Interim meeting, all WPs, First part 2021, Paris, France, 1,5 days, 2 nights	7 920.00	Interim meeting, Paris, First part 2021, 1,5 days
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		5 207.00	annual meeting (Rome), data analysis (Rome), annual meeting (Dublin)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		1 400.00	Consortium meeting, Consortium meeting	0.00	
WP6	0.00		22 803.00		1 770.00		0.00	
PhD06-ET5-PEMbo	0.00		3 000.00	APC - Article Publication Charges	0.00		0.00	
PhD09-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC	0.00		14 307.00	Consumables, Consumables course for animal experiment	1 470.00	Travel and acomodation for animal experiment Phd	0.00	
PhD12-FBZSH9-AptaTrich	0.00		5 496.00	Consumables for Molecular biology (NGS libraries preparation, PCR kits), Tagged probes, Aptamers processing (Magnetic beads...)	300.00	Round trip between Paris and Berlin for development of applications based on the aptamers selected	0.00	
PhD14-FBZ4-ToxSauQMRA								
P02-Ages	0.00		77 000.00		6 600.00		4 575.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		4 575.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	4 575.00	SSB meeting 2021 at Ages M38
WP3	0.00		77 000.00		5 600.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		67 500.00	Cultivation, DNA isolation (Standard-kits and special procedure for free DNA isolation), 16S amplicon sequencing, Shot gun sequencing, Gene enrichment, gene capture probes ; qPCR; qPCR arrays, Sequencing (WGS and/or Sanger), Samples collection, transport ; Antibiotics quantification, Soil microcosm, competence regulons: gene expression, RNA isolation, RT PCR ; Consumables	2 100.00	Interim meeting	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		0.00		1 200.00	Mid-term meeting, WP4-meeting	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		9 500.00	WGS	1 700.00	meeting year 1	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP4	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
P04-Sciensano	0.00		125 101.00		17 800.00		3 815.00	
WP1	0.00		4 500.00		1 000.00		900.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		4 500.00	Ethic Reviewers service Y1	1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	900.00	PMT meeting 1, PMT meeting 2, PMT meeting 3, PMT meeting 4
WP3	0.00		115 851.00		14 700.00		2 915.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		3 000.00	1 FOC delegate, 2 VIP - PMT, 2 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP05-ET1-TOXdetect	0.00		18 143.00	Consumables, Article publication charges	2 000.00	Final meeting	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		6 000.00	OTHER GOODS AND SERVICES	3 600.00	Annual meetings, Closing meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		8 000.00	Lab consumables sequencing	0.00		990.00	Annual Meeting
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		40 186.00	Administraton (incl. organization workshop), Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing (incl. Proficiency test), Lab reagents for MGE investigation, ENA database costs	1 950.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		13 772.00	sequencing kits (2 kits)(Oxford Nanopore), Flowcells (12 pieces)(Oxford Nanopore), Other reagents and enzymes	0.00		625.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting, January 2021, Sciensano, Belgium
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		24 750.00	Administration (publications, posters, ...), Lab reagents for WGS sequencing , Lab reagents for typing	1 400.00	Annual meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP3-JRPs management	0.00		5 000.00	Reviewers fee	2 750.00	travel to JRPs	1 300.00	annual JRPs/JIP meeting
WP4	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
WP4-JIPs management	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Workshop organisation	0.00	
WP6	0.00		4 750.00		1 100.00		0.00	
PhD02-AMR2/3/6-PhD LIN-RES	0.00		4 750.00	Next generation sequencing, Laboratory experiments to assess transferability	0.00		0.00	
PhD04-AMR2.1-KENTUCKY	0.00		0.00		1 100.00	Travel to INRA	0.00	
PO6-NDRVMI	0.00		23 000.00		24 400.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		23 000.00		23 400.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		6 000.00	Consumables for laboratory study; reagents; feed and feed production; animal experiments; publication	1 800.00	Travel to one pig farms where we will do the experiments.	0.00	
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	0.00		7 000.00	Consumables for sampling and laboratory analyses, Transport of strains (UN 2814), Transport of strains (UN 2814)	11 400.00	Annual workshop (intermediate meeting, 2021, Portugal, 2 participants, 2 days, 2 nights), Collection of samples on field (gasoline, transport of samples to the lab, 40 days of travelling)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		10 000.00	Reagents-consumables and materials for Bacteriology-Feed- feed preparation-Animal experiment-Publication ;	9 600.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting, Travel to 32 pig farms or slaughterhouses where we will do the experiments or collect information.	0.00	
P07-SZU	0.00		11 800.00		4 000.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		11 800.00		3 000.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		0.00		1 400.00	midterm meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		11 800.00	Diagnostic kits and materials-antigens, antibodies, conjugates, pipettes, plastics... ; PCR kits and chemicals, primers, pipettes, laboratory animals, sequencing costs...	1 000.00	Annual meeting, to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
P08-VRI	0.00		73 757.00		13 250.00		4 575.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		4 575.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	4 575.00	SSB meeting 2021 at VRI (CZ)
WP3	0.00		68 407.00		12 250.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		12 563.00	popis	300.00	data analysis-project meetings	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		12 444.00	MinIT (Oxford Nanopore), MinION starter pack (advanced)(Oxford Nanopore), utensiles, Other reagents and enzymes, library preparation kits (6 kits)(Oxford Nanopore)	350.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting, January 2021, Sciensano, Belgium	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		5 600.00	Purchase of target organisms for preparation of spiked RTE foodstuff, Reagents for PCR and sequencing, Reagents for testing enrichment methods	2 150.00	Annual meeting Year2, Technical workshop	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		10 000.00	Laboratory consumables (chemical reagents, isolation kits, plastics etc.) ; Laboratory consumables- data analysis-administrative consumables	3 600.00	annual meeting, WP2 meeting, WP4 meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		10 000.00	Administrative and laboratory consumables (laboratory plastic, sample collection, culture media etc.) ; Farm visits, Slaughterhouse visits	3 750.00	Annual meeting, WP2-meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		17 800.00	Multicenter QMRA for T. gondii, Testing of methods for the detection of T. gondii on fresh produce, Supply of T. gondii oocysts	1 500.00	2. year meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		5 350.00		0.00		0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		5 350.00	laboratory equipment, reagents, media, dequencing	0.00		0.00	
P09-BfR	0.00		121 537.00		44 660.00		16 425.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		4 675.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	4 675.00	PMC meeting 1-2021 at BfR (DE) M45
WP3	0.00		110 437.00		18 710.00		7 975.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		6 600.00	1 FOC delegate, 2 VIP - PMT, 8 VIP - STC	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP05-ET1-TOXdetect	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		32 000.00	y2 Minlon Sequencing, y2 Illumina shotgun sequencing, y2 Hi-C sequencing	1 100.00	Annual Meeting	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		22 500.00	Lab reagents for WGS sequencing, Lab reagents for MGE investigation	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		8 100.00	Lab consumables (NGS), Lab consumables (others), conference registration costs	900.00	scientific conference (y2)	0.00	
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	0.00		15 000.00	Lab reagents, Lab reagents, Sequencing (DNA; RNASeq), Lab reagents, Shipment of strains	1 400.00	Annual workshop (Intermediate meeting, 2021, Portugal, 2 participants, 2 days, 2 nights)	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		10 000.00	consumables and reagents for implementation of MLST SOP and preparation of ring trial (plastic ware, PCR reagents, DNA clean up kit, sequencing)	2 100.00	Annual meeting, technical workshop WP2	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		0.00		450.00	Intermediate meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		12 450.00	Conference registration, Publication cost, Consumables, HEV Sample extraction and realtime PCR (300 samples), Consumables (tubes, packaging, shipping)	2 800.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting, Conference participation	7 975.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting, Workshop 2

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		10 387.00	Publication and dissemination costs ; consumables for participation in ring test such as plastic ware, elution buffers, DNA extraction kit, PCR reagents ; consumables for analysis of field samples including plastic ware, elution buffers, DNA extraction kit, PCR reagents ; transport of field samples including dry ice	1 700.00	Annual meeting, to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM ; Workshop WP5	0.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		1 100.00	2nd Annual meeting- Apr 2021- Portugal-20 participants- 2 days- 1 night	0.00	
WP4	0.00		11 100.00		7 550.00		3 775.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		5 100.00	Open Access publication costs	1 650.00	ORION consortium meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		6 000.00	APC	0.00		0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		1 400.00	Y4 first meeting , Y4 second meeting	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		4 500.00	Full consortium meeting 4 , WP5 workshop 1	3 775.00	
WP5	0.00		0.00		17 400.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP5-Science to Policy translation	0.00		0.00		17 400.00	5.2.3 Consolidation of results 1 meeting, 5.3.2 Scientific support to enhance exploitation of results , 2 SC meetings , Dissemination/collaboration activity , Dissemination/collaboration activity , reimbursement of T&S costs of SC members	0.00	
P10-FLI	0.00		114 786.00		46 150.00		10 850.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		95 286.00		17 400.00		10 850.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	0.00		20 286.00	FLI Consumables , FLI Publication costs , FLI Participation fees	3 750.00	Annual Scientific Meeting , FLI Interlaboratory exchange meeting , FLI Participation in scientific conference	0.00	
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		11 800.00	FLI Consumables ,Conference participation fees, Publication costs	4 500.00	Annual meeting, Interlaboratory exchange,Participation in scientific conference	0.00	
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	0.00		9 200.00	Consumables for sampling and direct testing,Consumables for sequencing, Consumables for RNAseq and antibioresistance , Shipment of samples/strains (UN2814 and/or UN3373)	1 800.00	Annual workshop (Intermediate meeting, 2021, Portugal, 2 participants, 2 days, 2 nights)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		31 600.00	FLI Consumables, FLI Publication costs, FLI Participation fees	3 200.00	FLI Interlaboratory exchange, FLI Conference costs	8 900.00	Interim annual meeting
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		22 400.00	FLI Consumables	2 900.00	Annual meeting, to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM, FLI Interlaboratory exchange	1 950.00	FLI Workshop
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		650.00		0.00	
WP4	0.00		19 500.00		27 750.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		13 000.00	Lab material, Publication	11 250.00	WP meeting , ORION Meeting, international meeting	0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		3 000.00	Publication	8 600.00	Project meeting, WP meeting, International meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		3 500.00	FLI Publication costs, FLI Participation fee costs	7 900.00	Annual meeting, Biannual meeting, FLI Participation in Scientific conference, FLI Interlaboratory exchange meeting	0.00	
P11-RKI	0.00		56 900.00		7 400.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		56 900.00		6 400.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		28 500.00	Typing marker selection/development, Nanobody development	600.00	1 meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		4 900.00	Labotaratory disposibles e.g. culture media, tuber and micrtiter plates - disinfectants for testing	1 400.00	Mid term meeting, WP3 meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		23 500.00	Publication and dissemination costs , oligonucleotides, PCR reagents, cloning reagents, growth media, sequencing, plastic material, antibodies, purification reagents, shipping reagents to partners	500.00	Annual meeting-to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		3 300.00	2nd Annual meeting, Apr 2021, Portugal, 20 participants, 2 days, 1 night ; Ad hoc meetings;Ad hoc meetings;Ad hoc meetings	0.00	
P12-DTU	0.00		61 572.00		16 310.00		500.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		58 500.00		8 485.00		0.00	
ASM org-2021	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		2 400.00	1 FOC delegate, 3 VIP - LOC	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		0.00		1 500.00	project meeting 2021	0.00	
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		27 000.00	Minlon Sequencing, Illumina Sequencing	1 400.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		31 500.00	Administraton (incl. Publication costs), Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing (incl. Proficiency test), Lab reagents for MGE investigation, Computing for MGE investigations	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		0.00		1 575.00	Second annual project meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		0.00		500.00	Annual meeting-to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		550.00	2nd Annual meeting-Apr 2021-Portugal-20 participants-2 days-1 night	0.00	
WP4	0.00		3 072.00		6 825.00		500.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		2 500.00	publication	2 200.00	1 Orion workshop/meeting, ORION evaluation WS	500.00	WP2 Integration workshop
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		572.00		375.00		0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		0.00		2 050.00	Interim meeting-Paris, Training course- Rennes-France	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		2 200.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
P13-SSI	0.00		178 519.00		46 910.00		900.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		148 519.00		26 660.00		900.00	
ASM org-2021	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		3 600.00	1 FOC delegate, 2 VIP - PMT, 3 VIP - LOC	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		3 000.00	Publication and/or IT costs	0.00		0.00	
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		26 000.00	Reagents and consumables for sample preparation, culturing, spiking, DNA purification, MinION and Illumina sequencing ; Reagents and consumables for sample preparation, Voltrax, DNA purification, MinION sequencing	1 400.00	Annual meeting 2	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		16 769.00	Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		35 000.00	Lab consumables, Lab costs for sequencing	1 400.00	Interim-Portugal	0.00	
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		15 000.00	library preparation kits (12 kits)(Oxford Nanopore), Flowcells (12 pieces)(Oxford Nanopore)	700.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting-January 2021-Sciensano-Belgium	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		7 000.00	Laboratory consumables	9 250.00	Training (exchange of key staff members), Interim meeting Y4 (Germany), Scandinavian-Baltic Society for Parasitology's congress (Lithuania 2021), European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases (ECCMID) (2021), European Congress on Tropical Medicine and International Health (ECTMIH) (2021)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		9 600.00	Laboratory consumables, Reagents , Shipment	550.00	Annual Meeting	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCOVeR	0.00		10 000.00	Genome sequencing of isolates, Lab consumables for sampling-culturing	1 650.00	Mid-term-May 2021-ANSES-2 days-3 persons from SSI	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		9 150.00	Publication and dissemination costs , Laboratory consumables-serology, Laboratory consumables-genotyping	3 400.00	Annual meeting-to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM, Workshop	900.00	Annual meeting
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		17 000.00	Genome sequencing of isolates,Lab consumables for mutants and in vitro assays	1 400.00	Mid-term meeting-2 persons	0.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		2 750.00	2nd Annual meeting-Apr 2021- Portugal-20 participants-2 days-1 night	0.00	
WP3-JRPs management								

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP4	0.00		30 000.00		15 850.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		5 000.00	Sequencing of Campylobacter strains-lab consumables	0.00		0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		10 000.00	Consumables (WGS, shipping, media etc)	2 800.00	Interrim meeting-Paris, Training course-Rennes	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		13 000.00	Laboratory Consumables, Communication and publication	8 400.00	3rd meeting (Rome), 4th meeting (Dublin),EJP annual scientific meeting	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		2 000.00	Publication fees	4 650.00	Biannual meeting (no. 3), Biannual meeting (no. 4), WP5 meeting, WP1 meeting, WP2 meeting	0.00	
WP5	0.00		0.00		3 400.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP5-Science to Policy translation	0.00		0.00		3 400.00	2 SC meetings, Dissemination/collaboration activity, Dissemination/collaboration activity	0.00	
P14-UT	0.00		45 200.00		10 900.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		45 200.00		9 900.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	0.00		6 000.00	Lab plastic, Enzymes-molecular biology kits-lab chemicals-minor lab equipment (e.g. pipettes) etc	2 300.00	Trip 3	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		17 100.00	Consumables, Consumables, Conference participation fees	4 350.00	Interlaboratory exchange, Interlaboratory exchange, Participation in scientific conference	0.00	
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		22 100.00	Consumables for molecular studies	2 650.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany), Scandinavian-Baltic Society for Parasitology's congress (Lithuania 2021), Training 2 (exchange of key staff members)	0.00	
P15-VFL	0.00		12 500.00		5 550.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		12 500.00		4 550.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		5 000.00	Reagents and consumables	2 550.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany), Training 1 (exchange of key staff members)	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		7 500.00	Materials directly for performance of analyses-reagents, culture media, consumables, gloves, disinfectants etc ; Materials directly for performance of analyses-reagents, culture media, consumables, gloves, disinfectants etc ; Local transportation	1 400.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting	0.00	
P16-INIA	0.00		44 534.00		9 160.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP3	0.00		42 534.00		5 660.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		7 000.00	costs of stationery and computer science-program licences-scientific and technical publications and videos-cibercloud...	1 860.00	NOVA meeting	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		19 300.00	Reactives for SMRT, Reactives for plasmid DNA isolation, Others: plastics and buffers, Publication costs	2 700.00	Annual FULLFORCE meeting 2021, Annual EJP meeting 2021	0.00	
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		16 234.00	Consumables, Other reagents and enzymes, library preparation kits (6 kits)(Oxford Nanopore)	500.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting-January 2021-Sciensano-Belgium	0.00	
WP4	0.00		2 000.00		2 500.00		0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		2 000.00	costs of cibercloud-scientific publications	2 500.00	Annual MATRIX meeting, Annual EJP meetin	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
P17-UCM	0.00		112 800.00		17 500.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP2	0.00		0.00		2 500.00		0.00	
WP2-SRA	0.00		0.00		2 500.00		0.00	
WP3	0.00		99 300.00		9 350.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		3 000.00	1 FOC delegate, 2 VIP - PMT, 2 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		20 000.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		6 000.00	Sequencing material for Minlon-Illumina Sequencing and Lab material for molecular Biology, Sampling and onsite testing	1 000.00	Annual meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	0.00		14 000.00	Sample collection-laboratory testing, On-site testing-laboratory control material-molecular biology	1 050.00	OHEJP annual scientific meeting	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		9 700.00	Reagents-consumables and material for WP2-WGS-Publication	1 100.00	Mid-term meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		40 600.00	Consumables for WP2 needed for surveys and collect data , Consumables needed for WP3 (DNA extraction,PCR, package delivery),Consumables for Task 4.2. Development of a novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA to diagnose oocysts and/or bradyzoite driven infections. And task 4.3 (interlaboratory trial) , Consumables needed for WP5 (Whole genome sequencing)	2 100.00	Annual meeting WP, Workshop WP5 to transfer technology of novel standardized high-throughput direct NGS-MLST genotyping method prior to pilot studies	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		9 000.00	Reagents-consumables and material for Salmonella analysis-WGS-Publication	1 100.00	Interim meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		6 900.00		4 650.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		6 900.00	Reagents-consumables and material for PT-material for RM-WGS-Publication	2 450.00	Interim meeting, Training course	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		2 200.00	Biannual meeting 3 (BfR), 2 people, 2 days, 1 night ; Biannual meeting 4 (NIPH), 2 people, 2 days, 1 night	0.00	
WP6	0.00		6 600.00		0.00		0.00	
PhD01-AMR2-ECO-HEN	0.00		4 000.00	Laboratory consumables	0.00		0.00	
PhD05-AMR2/6.1/ET5-METAPRO	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
STM-2021	0.00		2 600.00	Long read sequencing costs	0.00		0.00	
P18-MVNA	0.00		15 450.00		1 600.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP3	0.00		0.00		600.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
WP4	0.00		15 450.00		0.00		0.00	
WP4-JIPs management	0.00		15 450.00	website building (2nd payment - 50% as agreed with the service provider)	0.00		0.00	
P19-INRA	0.00		72 047.00		4 660.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		50 008.00		1 160.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP05-ET1-TOXdetect	0.00		10 000.00	Culture media, Laboratory glasswares and chemicals for microbiology and proteomic, small equipments (chromatography columns...) (WP3, WP5), yyy... (INRA PIMs), Molecular biology and small equipment (WP4, WP5), xxx... (INRA PIMS), APC	0.00		0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		26 408.00	1282 reagents for bacterial, serological and molecular analysis ... , 1282 Article Publication Charges (ACP), 1282 to be transferred from ANSES to INRAE (for R. Drumo' research), Books-Publication fees	0.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		13 600.00	Consumables for SMRT sequencing, Consumables for functional characterization of MGE , Genome studies (hardware, software for bioinformatic)	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	
WP4	0.00		22 039.00		2 500.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		22 039.00	Software-data storage-online surveys , Consumables for strain characterization analysis (Bacteriology, Mass Spectrometry, Molecular biology) and sequencing services , Consumables for integrating strains in collection (Bacteriology, Mass Spectrometry, Molecular biology, sequencing services and preservation). Consumables for training , Consumables for IT development, data storage costs (in data center or in house)	2 500.00	Interim meeting Paris (1½ days) during first semester 2021-4 persons-1 night-1,5 days ; IT meeting with MIRRI/EOSC in one european country-year 2-1 person-1 night-1 day ; IT meeting with MIRRI/EOSC in one european country-year 2-1 person-1 night-1 day	0.00	
P20-IP	0.00		122 906.00		6 700.00		7 000.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		50 906.00		3 200.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		1 200.00	1 FOC delegate , 1 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		19 125.00	Sequencing kits (Illumina), Microbiology media, Molecular biology (enzymes, primers, Q-PCR), Antibiotics and reactif for susceptibility determination, Pastics (tups, tubes, plaques), antibodies, publication, APC	1 000.00	Participation to a scientific meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP05-ET1-TOXdetect	0.00		14 480.00	reagents and consumables for bacteriology-molecular biology-toxin detection kit , reagents and consumables for bacteriology-molecular biology, Reagents and consumables for mass spectrometry (columns, solvents)-softwares	0.00		0.00	
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		6 805.00	Lab consumables, Lab costs for culturing-sequencing-AMR	300.00	Kickoff meeting	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		10 496.00	DNA preparation and High Throughput Sequencing, Sequencing Analysis, Phenotypic experiments	700.00	ADONIS Y2 Meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		72 000.00		300.00		7 000.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		72 000.00	Sequencing and characterization	300.00	Interim meeting	7 000.00	Lauching event of CARE IS (Milestone 3.3)
WP6	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
PhD16-FBZ2/AMR6.1-Codes4strains	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
WP7	0.00		0.00		2 200.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP7-Sustainability	0.00		0.00		2 200.00	WP 7 coordination activity meeting will be held in Paris and in Rome, meeting with other WPs leaders for specific sustainability issues-in particular with WP4 leader, WP5 leader, Attendance at the 2019 Stakeholders meeting to start introducing sustainability strategies to the stakeholders	0.00	
P21-APHA	0.00		201 619.00		39 116.00		2 210.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP3	0.00		151 776.00		20 397.00		2 210.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		1 800.00	1 FOC delegate, 2 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		5 867.00	cost for culture media-molecular biology kit-WGS	2 000.00	to travel to meetings and conferences	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		6 700.00	Cloud computing	920.00	Travel for projet leader to Weybridge/London for meetings (based remotely)	0.00	
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		34 387.00	Consumables, Nanopore Flow Cell (R9.4.1) (12x), Nanopore Rapid Barcoding Kit (5 kits), Agencore ampure beads, Cloud Storage, Seq consumables, Admin	4 480.00	Project Update meeting	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		24 480.00	Consumables, Nanopore Flow Cell (R9.4.1) (12x), Nanopore Rapid Barcoding Kit (5 kits), Cloud Storage, Admin	1 440.00	Y4-1 meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	0.00		26 243.00	DNA extraction kits, Molecular typing reagents, WGS reagents, RNAseq reagents, Cloud computing, Transport of strains (UN2814)	1 400.00	Annual workshop (Intermediate meeting, 2021, Portugal, 2 participants, 2 days, 2 nights)	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		21 592.00	Consumables Farm (VTEC), Consumables Lab (VTEC), Consumable extract (VTEC), Consumables Seq (CSU), Cloud storage, Consumables Salmonella	2 347.00	Project meeting Salm, Project meeting Salm2, Project meeting VTEC, Project meeting Model	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		2 347.00	consumables	2 960.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting, travel to farms/ abattoirs	2 210.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		28 160.00	Consumable (sequen), Cloud, Consumable media	1 950.00	Project meeting yr2, Project meeting yr2, Project meeting yr2	0.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		2 000.00	Cloud computing	1 100.00	2nd Annual meeting-Apr 2021- Portugal-20 participants-2 days-1 night	0.00	
WP4	0.00		46 043.00		14 499.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		4 000.00	Budget for procuring specialist IT solutions such as cloud computing-online code repositories and online collaboration sites, APC	2 250.00	ORION consortium meeting	0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		2 250.00	Wash up meeting	0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE			7 802.00	Consumables (standard laboratory supplies including buffers, sequencing reagents)	879.00	Year 2 meeting	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		30 741.00	Consumables, Seq consumables, Seq consumables, Dynabeads (ThermoFisher scientific), Cloud storage	5 820.00	Y4-1 meeting, Y4-2 meeting	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		3 500.00	Specialist IT e.g. cloud computing and storage	3 300.00	Biannual_meeting 3, Biannual_meeting 4, WP Planning meeting	0.00	
WP6	0.00		3 800.00		3 220.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
PhD09-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-UDOFRIC	0.00		2 500.00	Consumables	350.00	Meeting	0.00	
PhD10-FBZSH3/AMR2.1-WILBR	0.00		1 300.00	Lab Consumables/annum, PhD student fees at UoE	2 870.00	Sampling Phd, Sampling wildlife, Colaboration Phd	0.00	
P22-PHE	0.00		4 681.00		5 560.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		4 681.00		3 900.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		4 681.00	Molecular Test Kits, Other Laboratory Consumables, Postage, Printing and Publishing	0.00		0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		0.00		1 100.00	Annual Meeting	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		0.00		1 100.00	Annual Meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		1 100.00	Annual Meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		0.00		660.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		0.00		660.00	WP2 pilot meeting	0.00	
P23-UoS	0.00		78 100.00		80 500.00		153 240.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		3 000.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	3 000.00	
WP3	0.00		68 600.00		11 350.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		4 200.00	1 FOC delegate, 4 VIP - PMT, 2 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	0.00		20 000.00	Consumables - General laboratory consumables	3 000.00	Project meeting, National conferenece	0.00	
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		18 000.00	Consumables	1 400.00	Project launch meeting in Vienna	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		8 800.00	Consumables, Access	1 500.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting-January 2021-Sciensano-Belgium	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		20 300.00	Consumables for developing and testing typing schemes	750.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		1 500.00	Consumables for sample collection and oocyst recovery	500.00	Annual meeting-to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
WP4	0.00		0.00		3 500.00		3 240.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		3 500.00	Consortium meeting 1, Consortium meeting 2, WP-5 meeting	3 240.00	WP4 meeting
WP6	0.00		9 500.00		64 650.00		147 000.00	
CPD-2021							70 000.00	
PhD07-ET2.1-MACE	0.00		0.00		2 800.00	Meeting, Meeting, Meeting, Meeting	0.00	

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PhD11-FBZ4/5-EnvDis	0.00		9 500.00	Registration fees 3st year; Other consumables: e.g. books-subscriptions to relevant services (e.g. data service such as https://knoema.com/)- printing material (posters for meeting, leaflets for stakeholders and partners as Zoetis); Open access publication fees for two publications	3 800.00	Annual International Conference/meeting (budgeted as € 700 for registration, € 700 for economy airfare, travel from and to airports €150, €150 for daily accommodation/s ubsistence and €40 for catering. Registration fees is included in the unit travel cost) ; Annual National Conference/meeting (budget as €500 for registration, €175 for economy train fare, €150 for daily accommodation/s ubsistence and €40 for catering. Registration fees included in the unit travel cost)	0.00	
SS-2021							62 000.00	
STM-2021	0.00		0.00		55 350.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP6-T&E management	0.00		0.00		2 700.00	Attendance at meetings relating to management of WP6-PMT and SSB.	0.00	
WS-2021							15 000.00	
P24-OKI	0.00		1 300.00		1 600.00		2 965.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		1 300.00		600.00		2 965.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		1 300.00	Reagents (including sequencing), Shipment costs	0.00		2 965.00	
P25-NUIG	0.00		25 400.00		5 050.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		25 400.00		2 800.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	0.00		18 500.00	Research consumables	1 500.00	Month 42 Project meeting - Brussels	0.00	
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		6 900.00	Gene enrichment probes for 16 reactions , Molecular biology reagents	700.00	Interim meeting (Portugal)	0.00	
WP6	0.00		0.00		1 250.00		0.00	
STM-2021	0.00		0.00		1 250.00	Liam Burke accomodation,Liam Burke flights subsistence	0.00	
P26-TEAGASC	0.00		12 436.00		6 620.00		4 880.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		0.00		2 900.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		1 200.00	1 FOC delegate, 1 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		0.00		1 700.00	Progress meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		0.00		920.00		4 880.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		920.00	Project Meeting 1 (yr 2), Project Meeting 2 (yr 2)	4 880.00	Teagasc will host the second meeting in Year 4
WP6	0.00		12 436.00		1 800.00		0.00	
PhD03-AMR2.1-HME-AMR	0.00		12 436.00	Sequencing costs and lab consumables	1 800.00	Travel and subsistence costs-project meetings-sample collection-OHEJP meetings-national conference	0.00	
P27-ISS	0.00		346 954.00		29 785.00		2 100.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		243 354.00		15 310.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		1 200.00	1 FOC delegate, 1 VIP - PMT	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		26 570.00	Reagents-consumables and materials for Bacteriology-molecular Biology -Cell Biology - Immunology-Animal experiment-Publication , APC	0.00		0.00	
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		9 000.00	Reagents and consumables for metagenomics and sample preparation, Reagents and consumables for Resfinder-"like" experiments, Reagents and consumables for benchmarking experiments , Reagents and consumables for on-site experiments	1 400.00	Intermediate meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		24 990.00	Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing ,Lab reagents for MGE investigation,Administration (task lead)	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		30 500.00	Consumables, International courier, Publication fees	5 700.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany), Scandinavian-Baltic Society for Parasitology's congress (Lithuania 2021), European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases (ECCMID) (2021), European Congress on Tropical Medicine and International Health (ECTMIH) (2021), Training 2 (exchange of key staff members)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		60 000.00	Shipment (International courier)	1 100.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		5 000.00	Sequencing of STEC stains	1 050.00	Mid-Project meeting	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		22 550.00	Plasticware-personal protection equipment (PPE)-reagents for molecular biology and sequencing (RT-PCR, Realtime-RT-PCR)-ELISA screening kit-commercial antibodies.	1 400.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		52 319.00	Consumables, International courier	1 500.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		12 425.00	Lab reagents and services for WGS sequencing	1 400.00	First Meeting (NL)	0.00	
WP4	0.00		51 000.00		9 075.00		2 100.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		7 000.00	software for data analysis and visualization, cost for publication	2 400.00	annual meeting, Task meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		39 000.00	Sequencing reagents for pilot PTs, Molecular biology reagents for pilot PTs, Media and reagents for microbiological tests in pilot PTs	525.00	Interim meeting	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		5 000.00	Materials for the organization of the training sessions on pathogenic E. coli and parasites	3 750.00	Fourth meeting, Meeting for the dissemination of the results of OHLabCap	2 100.00	Third meeting
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		2 400.00	Berlin (BfR), SVA, NIPH	0.00	
WP6	0.00		49 600.00		0.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
SS-2021	0.00		49 600.00	Registration fee reimbursement to consortium members,Transport costs and Delegate travel,Participant Certificates of attendance,Preparation of a OHEJP Summer School course handbook,One Health EJP Merchandise,Marketing (advertising, webpage, social media, phographer),Accreditation	0.00		0.00	
WP7	0.00		3 000.00		4 400.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP7-Sustainability	0.00		3 000.00	tool for on line surveys and interviews. This will be used to contact and solicit different stakeholder groups and experts to collect information and opinions that will be translated in sustainability strategies	4 400.00	WP 7 coordination activity meeting will be held in Paris and in Rome, meeting with other WPs leaders for specific sustainability issues-in particular with WP4 leader-WP5 leader, Attendance at the 2019 Stakeholders meeting to start introducing sustainabi	0.00	
P28-IZS AM	0.00		63 080.00		24 350.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		57 780.00		9 200.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		6 000.00	APC	4 200.00	Annual meeting, Project meeting, ASM, Final Meeting	0.00	
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		12 000.00	Minlon Sequencing, Illumina Sequencing	1 400.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		10 140.00	MinION starter pack (advanced)(Oxford Nanopore), MinIT (Oxford Nanopore), Other reagents and enzymes	500.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting-January 2021-Sciensano-Belgium	0.00	
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	0.00		14 640.00	Material and reagents for Bacteriological experiments, Material and reagents for WGS and molecular biology, Material and reagents for in vitro infection studies	1 400.00	Annual workshop (intermediate meeting, 2021, Portugal, 2 participants, 2 days, 2 nights)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		15 000.00	Plastic,PCR reagents,Culture media&reagents,Biological reference materials	0.00		0.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		1 100.00	2nd Annual meeting-Apr 2021-Portugal-20 participants-2 days-1 night	0.00	
WP4	0.00		5 300.00		14 150.00		0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		7 400.00	Project meeting,Final meeting,ASM	0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		5 300.00	Plastic,PCR reagents,Culture media&reagents,Biological reference materials	2 100.00	Interim-meeting,Training course	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		4 650.00		0.00	
P29-IZS LER	0.00		91 160.00		9 500.00		1 300.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		60 672.00		3 500.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		44 228.00	Reagents-consumables and materials for Bacteriology-Sample analysis by standard diagnostic PCRs-Animal experiment-Other reagents and enzymes- Cell Biology & Immunology Shipments (on dry ice) , Publication costs	0.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		16 444.00	MinIT (Oxford Nanopore), MinION starter pack (advanced)(Oxford Nanopore), utensiles, Other reagents and enzymes, library preparation kits (6 kits)(Oxford Nanopore)	1 500.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting-January 2021-Sciensano-Belgium	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		0.00		1 400.00	Mid-term meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		30 488.00		5 000.00		1 300.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		488.00	APC	2 250.00	Annual meeting (2 persons, 2 nights), Thematic workshop (2 persons, 2 nights)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		30 000.00	Reagents for strain purification and characterization-including genotyping or whole genome sequencing,Reagents for quality test of batches	2 750.00	Interim meeting,Training microbial collection	1 300.00	
P30-RIVM	0.00		114 384.00		82 130.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP2	0.00		0.00		2 500.00		0.00	
WP2-SRA	0.00		0.00		2 500.00		0.00	
WP3	0.00		45 201.00		38 183.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		2 400.00	1 FOC delegate,1 VIP - PMT,2 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		0.00		17 500.00	NOVA general meetings and working visits	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		16 667.00	Sequencing costs	1 500.00	Projectmeetings	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		2 000.00	Consumables	2 250.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany), Training 1 (exchange of key staff members)	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		3 200.00	interlaboratory validation of the new markers	1 400.00	Annual meeting	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		0.00		3 333.00	Projectmeetings	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		0.00		2 000.00	Annual meeting-to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM, WP meeting	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		16 667.00	Sequencing costs	2 800.00	Projectmeetings	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		6 667.00	Sequencing costs	5 000.00	2nd Annual meeting-Apr 2021-Portugal-20 participants-2 days-1 night	0.00	
WP4	0.00		50 183.00		37 300.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		33 183.00	Consumables	1 100.00	Projetmeeting	0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		15 000.00	Reserved for EJP consortium partners not already part of the COHESIVE consortium	27 000.00	Annual Meeting and Workshop,Reserved for EJP consortium partners not already part of the Consortium	0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		2 000.00	chemicals	1 050.00	Interim meetings	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		3 600.00	Biannual meeting ISS-Rome,Biannual meeting TEAGSCA-Dublin	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		4 550.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP6	0.00		19 000.00		3 147.00		0.00	
PhD08-ET5.1/4.1/FBZSH3-DESIRE	0.00		19 000.00	Bench fee (Lab material),Sequencing costs,Education WIAS	0.00		0.00	
PhD15-FBZ5-TRACE	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
STM-2021	0.00		0.00		3 147.00	Short term mission- stay at FLI	0.00	
P31-WbvR	0.00		158 343.00		22 200.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		137 425.00		15 950.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		1 800.00	1 FOC delegate,1 VIP - PMT,1 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		11 875.00	Consumables budget	0.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED	0.00		25 450.00	Reagents and consumables for sample preparation-culturing-spiking-DNA purification- MinION and Illumina sequencing, Reagents and consumables for sample preparation-Voltrax-DNA purification- MinION sequencing	550.00	Annualmeeting2	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		30 000.00	Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing (incl. Proficiency test),Lab reagents for MGE investigation,Other lab materials and publication costs	500.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP17-ET2.2- IDEMBRU	0.00		55 000.00	Acquisition of animal and human derived macrophages ,Consumables for in vitro experiments,Acquisition of primers and reagents for RT-qPCR,Transport of strains	1 400.00	Annual workshop (Intermediate meeting, 2021, Portugal, 2 participants, 2 days, 2 nights)	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3- DISCoVeR	0.00		1 500.00	Materials for sequencing	2 800.00	Annual meeting, WP meeting	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1- BIOPIGEE	0.00		3 600.00	consumables for sampling,post costs for sending samples to lab,traveling to farms,unforeseen,Consumables virus culture (WBVR)	7 000.00	Kick-off meeting,Mid-term meeting,Final meeting,WP3-meeting,WP4-meeting,WP6-meeting,WP2-work visits (1),WP2- work visits (2),WP3-meeting (WBVR),Mid-term meeting (WBVR)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		0.00		500.00	Annual meeting to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		10 000.00	Salmonella isolates sequencing-sampling on farms	1 400.00	WP meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		20 918.00		3 550.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		500.00	Intersector meetings-coordination Pilot (WBVR-RIVM). Travell cost-etc	0.00		0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		14 718.00	MATERIALS	1 000.00	Final meeting	0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		4 700.00	Labmaterials	1 050.00	Interim meeting	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		1 000.00	Disposables and consumables laboraotry	1 500.00	Meetingyear2	0.00	
WP6	0.00		0.00		1 700.00		0.00	
PhD13-FBZ8/AMR2-VIMOGUT-AMR	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
PhD15-FBZ5-TRACE	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
WP6-T&E management	0.00		0.00		1 700.00	Participatino of Wim to summer school 2019	0.00	
P32-FHI	0.00		41 000.00		16 350.00		9 663.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		29 000.00		4 350.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		2 000.00	APC	0.00		0.00	
JRP10-FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC	0.00		24 000.00	Microbiome sequencing,Postage - microbiome samples to sequece centre on ice tur/retur,APC	0.00		0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		0.00		2 600.00	travelling	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		3 000.00	Publication and dissemination costs	500.00	Annual meeting to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		650.00	2nd Annual meeting-Apr 2021-Portugal-20 participants-2 days-1 night	0.00	
WP4	0.00		12 000.00		11 000.00		9 663.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		10 000.00	consumables to perform laboratory work	0.00		0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		2 000.00	APC	0.00		0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		3 600.00	ISS-Rome,TEAGSCA-Dublin	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		7 400.00	biannual_meeting 3-BfR-Germany,WP meeting	9 663.00	
P33-NVI	0.00		125 210.00		37 167.00		810.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		116 210.00		19 520.00		810.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JRP05-ET1-TOXdetect	0.00		4 500.00	growth media-consumeables, publication and conference fees, Shipping of strains to partners in PT trials	1 200.00	Project meeting, conferences	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		1 800.00	Publication fees open access	1 800.00	Final meeting	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		17 190.00	Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing	770.00	ECCMID	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		22 900.00	Amplicon sequencing-up to 96 samples,Shot-gun sequencing-four samples,WGS of selected isolates,Quantification of antimicrobials,Article publication costs,Administration cost	1 700.00	Midterm meeting	0.00	
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		12 444.00	utensiles,Other reagents and enzymes,library preparation kits (6 kits)(Oxford Nanopore),MinIT (Oxford Nanopore),MiniON starter pack (advanced)(Oxford Nanopore)	2 000.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting-January 2021- Sciensano-Belgium	0.00	
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		14 750.00	Consumables	2 950.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany),Training 2 (exchange of key staff members)	810.00	Training (exchange of key staff members)

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		3 400.00	Shipment of samples, Reagents for inter-laboratory assay	1 400.00	Interim meeting Y4	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCOVeR	0.00		16 046.00	Reagents and consumables for WGS, Reagents and consumables for metagenomics, WP3 (Task2)	3 500.00	Mid-term meeting	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		6 380.00	Laboratory disposables e.g. culture media- tubes and micrtiter plates- disinfectants for testing	700.00	kickoff meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		16 800.00	Consumables, Consumables, Consumables	1 500.00	Annual meeting to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		1 400.00	2nd Annual meeting-Apr 2021-Portugal-20 participants-2 days-1 night	0.00	
WP4	0.00		9 000.00		14 997.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		0.00		2 250.00	Pilot meeting, Final meeting	0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		9 000.00	Workshop WP2.3 Norwegian pilot system mapping of OH structure,Publication costs direct access	1 800.00	Final meeting	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		3 047.00	Third project meeting-Rome, Fourth project meeting-Dublin	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		7 900.00	plenary meeting,WP meeting,plenary meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP4-JIPs management	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
WP6	0.00		0.00		1 650.00		0.00	
STM-2021	0.00		0.00		1 650.00		0.00	
P34-PIWET	0.00		150 494.00		26 550.00		5 170.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		121 194.00		15 400.00		3 650.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		10 050.00	Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing,disposables (i.e. plastics),services	1 000.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		13 000.00	Chemical reagents and analytical standards of antibiotics, Services of equipment required for samples analysis, LC-MS/MS analytical columns and consumables for LC-MS/MS system	1 100.00	annual meeting 2	0.00	
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		17 444.00	MinIT (Oxford Nanopore), MinION starter pack (advanced) (Oxford Nanopore), utensils, Other reagents and enzymes, library preparation kits (6 kits) (Oxford Nanopore), disposables (i.e. plastics)	1 000.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting-January 2021- Sciensano-Belgium	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1- MEEmE	0.00		12 650.00	analytical test reagents and kits,disposables (i.e. plastics),services (i.e. sampling, shipment)	1 550.00	Interim annual meeting 2021 (Germany),attending international meeting	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1- PARADISE	0.00		3 400.00	analytical test reagents and kits,disposables (i.e. plastics),services (i.e. sampling, shipment)	1 850.00	Annual meeting, Technical Workshop	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3- DISCoVeR	0.00		7 150.00	reagents,disposables,ser vices,sequencing reaents	4 800.00	annual meeting (second annual meeting, May 2021, France (ANSES))	0.00	
JRP21-FBZ3.1- BIOPIGEE	0.00		16 500.00	analytical test reagents and kits,disposables (i.e. plastics),services (i.e. sampling, shipment)	1 400.00	Mid-term meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1- TOXOSOURCES	0.00		23 500.00	analytical test reagents and kits,disposables (i.e. plastics),services (i.e. sampling, shipment)	1 000.00	Annual meeting to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		17 500.00	analitical test reagents and kits,disposables (i.e. plastics),services (i.e. sampling, shipment)	0.00		3 650.00	
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		1 100.00	2nd Annual meeting(Apr 2021, Portugal, 20 participants, 2 days, 1 night)	0.00	
WP4	0.00		29 300.00		10 150.00		1 520.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		29 300.00	analitical test reagents and kits,disposables (i.e. plastics),services (i.e. sampling, shipment)	2 050.00	Interim meeting (1½ days, in Paris, 2021),Training course (2 days, Rennes, 2021)	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		3 000.00	Annual meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		5 100.00	Interim meeting Y4 ,Training 1 (exchange of key staff members),Training 2 (exchange of key staff members)	1 520.00	
P35-INIAV	0.00		66 450.00		14 710.00		3 450.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP3	0.00		53 950.00		9 810.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	0.00		7 000.00	Reagents and consumables for AMR analysis (antibiotics, Etests, MEDIA),Development of the Toolkit	0.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		15 350.00	Reagents and consumables	2 250.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany), Training 1 (exchange of key staff members)	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		4 000.00	Reagents and Consumables	2 600.00	Second year meeting, Technical Workshop	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		13 100.00	Reagents and consumables for WGS, Reagents and consumables for metagenomics, WP3 (Task2)	1 760.00	Mid-term meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		4 200.00	Consumables for sampling and oocyst recovery, Consumables for pilot study	1 000.00	Annual meeting to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		10 300.00	Reagents and consumables for WGS, Reagents and consumables for metagenomics, WP3 (Task2)	1 600.00	Mid-term meeting	0.00	
WP4	0.00		12 500.00		3 900.00		3 450.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		900.00	COHESIVE task 2.1 Work Session Development of guidelines for national One Health structures (Netherlands?)	3 450.00	Lisbon Meeting
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		12 500.00	Goods and services	3 000.00	Meeting Dublin-EAGASC, Meeting Rome-ISS- Italy	0.00	
P36-INSA	0.00		137 649.00		27 760.00		9 308.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		117 949.00		11 835.00		9 308.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		1 200.00	1 FOC delegate,1 VIP - PMT	0.00	
JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM	0.00		16 149.00	Lab reagents for multiplex,Lab reagents feasibility testing	1 500.00	Annual scientific meeting 2021	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		22 000.00	Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing ,Lab reagents for MGE investigation	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	0.00		24 900.00	Lab consumables,Lab costs for sequencing,Lab reagents for metagenomics and WGS	0.00		4 450.00	Interim meeting
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		5 000.00	MagNA Pure LC Total Nucleic Acid Isolation Kit (Roche),Other reagents and enzymes,library preparation kits (3 kits)(Oxford Nanopore),Flow cells (3)	1 000.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting (Jan 2021)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU	0.00		23 000.00	Reagents and consumables for molecular diagnosis, Reagents and consumables for bacteriological diagnosis, Reagents and consumables for molecular typing, Reagents and consumables for whole genome sequencing, Reagents and consumables for AMR analysis (antibiotics, Etests, MEDIA), Development of the Toolkit, Reagents and consumables for whole genome sequencing, Reagents and consumables for MLVA and MLST	0.00		3 738.00	Annual workshop (Intermedia te meeting, 2021, Portugal, 27 participants , 2 days, 2 nights)

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		3 500.00	Consumables,Publication fee	3 650.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany),Training 1 (exchange of key staff members),Conference meetings	0.00	
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		7 500.00	Lab costs for sequencing	2 025.00	second anual meeting	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		2 400.00	Laboratory consumables	500.00	Annual meeting to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	0.00		13 500.00	Consumables-DNA extraction and quantification , WGS,Consumables for phenotypic-stress response and fitness tests	1 400.00	Annual meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE	0.00		0.00		0.00		1 120.00	2nd Annual meeting,(A pr 2021, Portugal, 20 participants , 2 days, 1 night)
WP4	0.00		19 700.00		14 925.00		0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		12 000.00	Communication with national partners,Dissemination of project findings in external meetings,Training (consumables)	5 325.00	Y4 biannual meeting,Y4 biannual meeting,EJP annual meeting	0.00	

JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		7 700.00	Contacts with national partners,Actions to the project progress updates at AMR level,Actions to provide guidelines for the adaptation/improvement of surveillance in each individual sector-mainly at AMR level,Actions to the development of practical guidelines and strategies for data collection- analysis and dissemination-and to identify commonalities across the tracks: mainly at AMR level,Actions to select a surveillance pathogen or contaminant that is relevant to the specific situation of the country/partner; and to identifying the thresholds and boundaries of the metrics and the frequency of evaluation for the country/partner	8 100.00	Bi-annual meeting,Bi-annual meeting,WP meeting,WP meeting,Bi-annual meeting 3 (at bFR) (INSA_AMR),Bi-annual meeting 4 (at bFR) (INSA_AMR)	0.00	
WP4-JIPs management	0.00		0.00		1 500.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
P37-IISPV	0.00		0.00		1 600.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		0.00		600.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
P39-SLV	0.00		10 013.00		8 225.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		4 113.00		1 775.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		4 113.00	Reagents-primers/probes etc, Consumables (plastics, gloves etc)	675.00	Meeting 2021	0.00	
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		0.00		500.00	Annual meeting to be held in connection to OHEJP ASM	0.00	
WP4	0.00		5 900.00		5 450.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		1 400.00	Final meeting of the Cohesive project, Workshop WP 2	0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		5 900.00	delivery services, consumables, substrates and reagents, consumables, reagents	1 050.00	interim meeting (2 days, 1 night)	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		3 000.00	Meeting 2 night, Meeting 2 night	0.00	
P40-FoHM	0.00		33 280.00		9 510.00		0.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		27 380.00		3 260.00		0.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		600.00	1 FOC delegate	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		2 000.00	APC	1 400.00	Attending project meetings	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		21 980.00	Administration (incl. Task leaders for T2.3), Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing	560.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID 2021	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		3 400.00	Reagents, Shipping, Reagents	700.00	Annual meeting 2	0.00	
WP4	0.00		5 900.00		5 250.00		0.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		5 900.00	delivery services, consumables, substrates and reagents, consumables, reagents	1 050.00	interim meeting(2 days, 1 night)	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		1 800.00	Annual meeting 1, Annual meeting 2	0.00	
JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		0.00		2 400.00	Annual meeting 1, Annual meeting 2	0.00	
P41-SVA	0.00		140 094.00		70 440.00		7 883.00	
WP1	0.00		0.00		1 000.00		0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
WP1-Coordination	0.00		0.00		1 000.00	Governing meetings 2021	0.00	
WP3	0.00		119 436.00		17 400.00		1 850.00	
ASM T&S-2021	0.00		0.00		3 000.00	1 FOC delegate,3 VIP - PMT,1 VIP - PhD	0.00	
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA	0.00		5 236.00	Conference fees,Annual assembly,Costs for mandatory revision,APC	5 000.00	Conference attendance,Annual assembly	0.00	
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	0.00		21 750.00	Lab reagents for SMRT sequencing (incl. Proficiency test)	1 500.00	Annual meeting at ECCMID	0.00	
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir	0.00		18 000.00	library preparation kits (12 kits)(Oxford Nanopore),Flowcells (12 pieces)(Oxford Nanopore),utensiles,Other reagents and enzymes	1 500.00	1st TELE-Vir meeting (January 2021, Sciansano, Belgium)	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	0.00		9 750.00	Plastics-reagents and consumables,Plastics-reagents and consumables,Plastics-reagents and consumables	1 250.00	Interim meeting Y4 (Germany),Training (exchange of key staff members)	0.00	
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	0.00		58 500.00	Reagents for MLST scheme development-DNA extraction-PCR and Sanger seq etc,Shipping of samples to other main laboratories in T3.2,Reagents for development of hybridization capture probes,Reagents for inter-laboratory testing-DNA extraction-PCR and Sanger seq etc	1 400.00	Annual meeting 2	800.00	Technical WS
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	0.00		0.00		1 650.00	Reagents for isolation and sequencing	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	0.00		6 200.00	Computer for Beth Young, Expenses for 20 farm visits including reimbursement for farmers, Publication costs	2 100.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting	1 050.00	Kick-off meeting, Mid-term meeting, Final meeting, WP3-meeting, WP4-meeting, WP6-meeting
JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	0.00		0.00		0.00		0.00	
WP4	0.00		20 658.00		49 640.00		6 033.00	
JIP01-IA1.1-ORION	0.00		10 000.00	Adobe connect license, Training materials, Workshop organization (local, food, etc), APC	7 440.00	Consortium meeting, Workshop	0.00	
JIP02-IA1.2-COHESIVE	0.00		0.00		2 700.00	Project meeting	0.00	

Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
JIP03-IA2.3-CARE	0.00		6 000.00	Laboratory consumables, Delivery costs, Sequencing and MALDI-TOF	3 200.00	Interim meeting, EJP annual meeting	0.00	
JIP04-IA2.2-OH-HARMONY CAP	0.00		0.00		4 500.00	Annual meeting, Annual meeting	4 920.00	Y3 meeting 2

JIP05-IA2.1-MATRIX	0.00		3 158.00	Adobe Connect license	5 800.00	THIRD full consortium meeting-Spring 2021-location TBA- 1.5 days of work-2 nights-2.5 subsistence days (traveling the night before, coming home the evening of the 2nd meeting day) , FOURTH full consortium meeting-Fall 2021- location TBA-1.5 days of work- 2 nights- 2.5 subsistence days (traveling the night before, coming home the evening of the 2nd meeting day), WP meeting or EJP meeting (budget assigned to attend eventual scientific consortium meetings, or physical meetings	1 113.00	WP5 meeting
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Organisation	Equipment costs	Justification	Other goods and services costs	Justification	Travel and subsistence costs	Justification	Meeting organisation costs	Justification
						needed by the WPs)		
WP4-JIPs management	0.00		1 500.00	License Adobe Connect	26 000.00	PhD	0.00	
WP7	0.00		0.00		2 400.00		0.00	
WP7-Sustainability	0.00		0.00		2 400.00	PhD	0.00	

3 Planned activities for the fifth year

3.1 WP1

Task 1.1: Management of EC contractual obligations

The CT will supervise the preparation and submission of the deliverables due from M49 to M60 to the REA. At the beginning of the period, the CT will carry out the annual technical and financial reporting. Also, the CT will coordinate the preparation, compilation and submission to the EC of the Summary Progress Report (SPR) for year 5. The CT will also coordinate and manage the Final Report. All the above activities will be carried out in liaison with the REA project officers.

Task 1.2 Project management

The CT members will exchange on a weekly basis via teleconferences to ensure that administrative, financial and contractual requirements are met. The CT and the PMT will have monthly teleconference to ensure a smooth management and coordination of the WP activities. The CT will regularly liaise with the REA project officers and report any issue that may arise.

Task 1.3: Organisation of EJP management and governance meetings

The Support Team (ST) will ensure the organisation of all the project governance bodies meetings in regards to the identified planning. There will be 2 SSB, 3 PMT, 1 POC and 1 PMC meetings organised.

Task 1.4: Communication tools

Subtask 1.4.0: Communication Groups:

In the fifth year, the CCP network will have a significant role in disseminating OHEJP outcomes within their institutes as the programme comes to an end. This will contribute to the sustainability of the OHEJP. The CCP network will have a strong relationship with the Communications Team and another meeting will be organised with the CCPs at the beginning of the fifth year to ensure that each member of the network is well supported in the required activities.

Subtask 1.4.1: Website: The website will continue to be developed throughout the lifetime of the OHEJP to meet the needs of the consortium and the OHEJP stakeholders. Content for all of the pages will be updated on a regular basis. In particular the Education and Training, news and events and Joint Research and Joint Integrative pages will be closely monitored to ensure that the content is up to date and clearly showcases the events throughout the OHEJP. In the fifth year, the OHEJP projects will end and therefore it is imperative that all of the project (JIP, JRP and PhD) pages, deliverables page and publications page are up to date to contribute to the sustainability of the OHEJP.

Subtask 1.4.2: Internal communications: Newsletters: Consortium newsletters will be disseminated every three months in February, May, August and November 2022, with a final newsletter in December 2022 to summarise the last five years. These newsletters will provide updates regarding events, meetings, JIP/JRP progress, PhD project progress, funding opportunities and any other information that the consortium requests the Communications Officers disseminate. These newsletters will continue to be sent using MailChimp which allows the Communications Officers to monitor the success of each newsletter. Additionally, this service facilitates the monitoring of mailing lists. The external newsletters will be disseminated every six months (June and December 2022). This newsletter will be sent to the consortium, in addition to the external mailing list generated on the OHEJP website. These newsletters will be targeted to a wider audience, including the general public. The final December 2022 newsletter will be a summary of the 5 year project.

Subtask 1.4.3: External Communications: Press Releases: Press releases for the One Health EJP ASM will be published each year (these are the responsibility of the local organisers). This press release will also be published on the One Health EJP website and advertised on social media platforms. If press releases for other events, such as WP6 events are appropriate, these will also be the responsibility of the local organisers and will be advertised by the Communications Officer on the OHEJP website and social media platforms. There will be a final press release and summary of the OHEJP which also be widely distributed to all OHEJP audiences.

Subtask 1.4.4: External Communications: Professional social networks: The OHEJP social media platforms and the OHEJP website will continue to grow in popularity and are continuously monitored to ensure that this success continues to increase. The key objectives of the social media platforms are to increase the number of followers, engagements and impressions from the content posted. Advertising and live tweeting of One Health EJP events such as the ASM, meetings, events and funding opportunities will raise the profile of the One Health EJP and encourage engagement online. A key focus will be to raise the profile of the OHEJP events and encourage participants of events, WP6 activities, the ASM etc to actively tweet and engage on social media during events. Furthermore, to use Twitter and LinkedIn to post about their experiences of these events. Active social media posts in the final year will be of the utmost importance OHEJP projects come to an end and the Communications Team will have the opportunity to highlight all the successes in real time.

Subtask 1.4.6: External Communications: Merchandise and Branding: The Communications Officers will continue to increase the visibility of the OHEJP brand, which is essential in the final year as this contributes to the sustainability of the OHEJP. This will be achieved through close communication with JIP/JRP project leaders, PhD supervisors, PMT and the consortium to ensure that the branding of any outputs meets the needs of the OHEJP. Merchandise will continue to be sent to our partner institutes and the ASM and other OHEJP events will be excellent platforms to share our merchandise. Merchandise should also be offered at the OHEJP Summer School, CPD workshop, ASM Satellite workshop, ASM and all meetings across the consortium.

Subtask 1.4.7: Annual and final report: The annual report for Year 4 (May 2022) and Year 5 (December 2022) will be completed in this period, in addition to a special issue on One Health-Zoonoses for a scientific journal.

The Communications Team will continue to adjust our messages and method of engaging our audiences as our audience grows and the OHEJP progresses.

3.2 WP2

In the fifth year, the activities of WP2 will be directed at providing input for the development of the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) in WP7.

3.3 WP3

WP3 will monitor ongoing JRP through 9M and 12M reports and organise the fourth Annual Scientific Meeting, ASM2022.

3.4 WP4

During the fifth year, the WP4 commits to the following:

- To continue supervision of implementation and progress of JIPs, and evaluation of the merit of ongoing JIPs from second call of the EJP, following previously elaborated guidelines for evaluation of JIPs.

- To arrange for the final evaluation of JIPs in agreement with D4.19.
- To continue facilitation of internal integration of the resources developed, and support alignment with other similar activities in EC member states in collaboration with WP2, WP5 and WP6. To avoid redundancies and make use of previous and ongoing developments.
- To maintain integration of JIP output among EJP beneficiaries, namely those who are not primary participants in the respective JIP.
- To continue the support of implementation of data management plans developed in each JIP project. To assure that the final DMPs are uploaded on Zenodo.
- To continue support function for integration of additional partners in ongoing JIPs, through additional integrative missions.
- To realize and evaluate the simulation exercise
- To organize the 5th thematic integrative meeting between JRPs and/or JIPs, to facilitate integration across domains, within themes.
- To contribute to the organization of the annual ASM.
- To produce and deliver the 4th periodic report on JIPs (M51)
- To organize and report on the 5th thematic meeting (M51)
- To report on evaluation of finalised JIPs, 2nd round (M60)
- To produce and deliver the 5th periodic report on JIPs (M60)

3.5 WP5

During year 5, WP5 will continue the close interaction with the European, national and international stakeholders. Focus will be given to the dissemination of results, and in facilitating that these results are considered in national and international policies. The fifth year will see the Stakeholder Conference, which will focus on disseminating, in an appropriate way, the outcomes of the consortium to decision and policy makers. Sustainability will be discussed with WP7. Input for the SRIA will be given from the work performed on stakeholders needs.

3.6 WP6

During the fifth year, WP6 will co-ordinate the following activities:

Work Package 6 will continue to support and monitor the progress and reporting of the 16 PhD studentships. As this will be the final year of the OHEJP (2022), all PhD projects still in progress will produce a Final Thesis Report which will inform Deliverable 6.18. Each Final Thesis Report will include a general introduction, summaries of each chapter (including materials and methods), all results collected for each chapter, along with a detailed discussion and conclusion. This will be completed using the validated template which will be provided by WP6. This deliverable will be submitted to the REA by the OHEJP Support Team by 31 Dec 2022 as a final output of the Doctoral Programme.

PhDs that finish by June 2022 should produce a completed draft thesis as a final output instead of the final thesis report. This will be added as an annex in the final annual report.

Throughout the final year, WP6 will continue to liaise with the Principal Investigators (PIs) and their respective PhD students to ensure WP6 receives the relevant project progress updates, and any dissemination activities are reported on our website and are also reported to the coordination team

via the Internal Events Survey. PhDs will showcase their projects at the ASM through the Three Minute Thesis (3MT) PhD competition, and an oral presentation session dedicated to the PhDs, which will be unique to final ASM. Students will continue to interact with the OHEJP social media channels to raise the profiles of the PhD student cohort, the OHEJP and their achievements. The PhD students will also be actively encouraged to join delegates attending or participating in the remaining WP6 activities to build the next generation of 'One Health' researchers. This new consortium or alumni will play an important role in the sustainability of the OHEJP outcomes.

- WP6 will also monitor the progress of the STMs selected in Y4. These missions will take place throughout Y5, and once the missions are completed, individual reports will be produced. These reports will be used to inform the content for both Deliverable 6.20 and the webpage dedicated for STMs in 2022. WP6 will work with the Communications Team to communicate this on the website through visually attractive and OHEJP-branded case studies.
- WP6 will support and monitor the planning and organisation of the fourth ASM Satellite Workshop, Summer school and CPD module, which will all be held in the final year. The local organisers will be selected in Y4 through the validated process coordinated and managed by WP6. All selected local organisers will be informed of the roles of the local organising team, WP6 team and Communications Team to market and deliver the event successfully through a guidance document prepared by WP6.
- In the final year, WP6 will produce the deliverable reports for D6.14, D6.15, D6.16, D6.17, D6.18, D6.19 and D6.20.

3.7 WP7

On the 5th year WP7 will finalize a up-to-date and feasible proposal for the long-term OHEJP sustainability, which will include a) the follow-up of OHEJP activities in one or more new Partnerships of HorizonEurope (with special interest to the partnerships implementing a OH vision of Animal Health and AMR); this will also include a.1) the extension of the OHEJP fields of activities in order to include the suggestions and requestes of stakeholders (e.g., more attention to environmental issues and global health).; b) the new role of MedVetNet as a cross-cutting link between the components of OHEJP that will participate to different partnershps.

In addition, WP7 will co-operate with other WPs in order to ensure that research and integrative activities really show the added value of interdisciplinary integration, as this has been identified as a key value for the OHEJP long-term sustainability.

The activities are foreseen to be developed with the continuous support of feedbacks from PMT, SSB, ESAB and EU authorities: a physical workshop is foreseen at around month 50.

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